

DOCTORAL THESIS IN INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING

XXXVII Cycle

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: A Pathway to Alternative Hydrogen Storage Solutions

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Academic Year 2024/2025

Declaration of Authorship

I, Federica GUARNACCIA, declare that this thesis titled, "Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: A Pathway to Alternative Hydrogen Storage Solutions" and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This work was done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a research degree at this University.
- Where any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
- Where the thesis is based on work done by myself jointly with others, I have made clear exactly what was done by others and what I have contributed myself.

- While not explicitly stated, every chapter of this work has been done under the supervision of Professor M. Manno, Professor M. Gambini, and Professor M. Vellini, while Professor M.L. Di Vona and Professor S. Mazzoni have given me valuable input for chapter three and nine respectively.

Signed: _____

Date: _____

03/02/2025

“What’s the use of a fine house if you haven’t got a tolerable planet to put it on?”

Henry David Thoreau

Abstract

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs) represent a promising technology for hydrogen storage and transport, offering an alternative to traditional methods such as compressed or liquid hydrogen. LOHCs, which are organic compounds that can absorb and release hydrogen through chemical reactions, allow hydrogen to be stored in a liquid form at ambient conditions. The technology involves two key processes: hydrogenation, where hydrogen is chemically bonded to the carrier, and dehydrogenation, where hydrogen is released for use. Advantages of LOHCs include high volumetric hydrogen density, safety in handling, and compatibility with existing fuel infrastructure. However, commercialization faces challenges related to energy efficiency, carrier stability, recyclability, and the need for effective catalysts.

Due to the limited documentation available and the similar thermodynamic behavior of these systems, significant initial work was conducted on modeling metal hydrides, which are much better known and studied. This foundational work provided a basis for subsequent research. An overview of the work done on metal hydrides and the relevant literature is therefore presented in Appendix A, followed by Appendices B and C, which contain more technical details on the modeling of LOHCs.

Chapter 1 and Chapter 2 provide a literature review on hydrogen systems and LOHCs, highlighting existing knowledge and gaps. Chapter 3 focuses on the kinetic characterization of N-ethyl Carbazole (NEC), discussing modelling methods for hydrogen release and uptake. The proposed model makes use of a simplified approach, where the multi-step reaction is condensed into an equivalent reaction between the fully saturated and unsaturated compounds. This assumption carries over the following chapters.

Chapter 4 addresses thermodynamic modeling, advocating for simplified models due to the limited experimental data and early stage of LOHC technology. It suggests using a lumped parameter approach for batch reactors, justified by their simplicity and suitability for initial applications. The chapter highlights the importance of maintaining constant temperature and efficient stirring to ensure accurate modeling and safety. Coupling of the reaction heat and possible local temperature variability over the reaction rate makes the lumped parameter approach still relevant despite the typical system Biot number.

Chapter 5 compares plug flow reactors (PFRs) and batch reactors, emphasizing that PFRs, despite their complexity, offer higher efficiency and are better suited for large-scale applications. It discusses reactor design and the integration of storage tanks, aiming to enhance control over reaction conditions and improve overall system performance. A novel reactor layout is proposed through the introduction of two vessels, cyclically acting as either the LOHC source or buffer.

Chapter 6 evaluates various control strategies, including temperature, pressure, and mass flow rate controls, for managing LOHC reactions. Temperature control is identified as the most effective, maintaining high efficiency across different loads, while pressure control and mass flow rate control are less effective, particularly at high demands. Both the batch and plug flow reactor configurations are tested, and controllability results are evaluated under a constant demand. Performances are returned by normalizing the hydrogen demand so that it can be used to guide the LOHC sizing when coupling it with the end-users demand.

Chapter 7 explores the integration of LOHC systems with solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs), which eliminates the need for an external heat source for dehydrogenation. It compares pressure and temperature control strategies, finding temperature control to be superior, especially under high power factors. The chapter emphasizes the importance of maintaining controllability and exploring more complex controllers for future improvements. A detailed model of the SOFC waste heat is introduced and validated with experimental results found in the literature.

Chapter 8 assesses LOHC systems for marine fuel applications, comparing them with ammonia. An additional control strategy in the form of LOHC mass flow rate control is introduced and acts as the main control variable. Despite LOHCs' ability to adapt to changing demands, they require larger volumes and masses compared to ammonia, which offers better energy density and efficiency. The study concludes that ammonia is likely a more viable solution for large-scale marine applications due to its superior energy metrics and lower dehydrogenation heat requirements.

Chapter 9 presents a static modeling approach for LOHC systems, focusing on steady-state conditions rather than transient dynamics. By defining the state of LOHC subsystems through parameters like degree of hydrogenation, temperature, and pressure, this approach simplifies control strategies and enhances predictability of system behavior. This representation may provide a useful input to assess the potential benefits of the introduction of LOHC modules in more complex energy systems.

Chapter 10 evaluates the efficacy of simplified equivalent reactions versus multi-step models for LOHC kinetics, specifically for NEC and dibenzyl toluene (DBT). While the equivalent reaction model is effective for NEC, it faces limitations for DBT due to data scarcity and reaction heterogeneity, suggesting the need for alternative modeling approaches.

The work presented in this thesis has led to the publication of six articles ^{1,2,3,4,5,6}. Despite the lack of experimental data, the research has significantly contributed to the understanding of LOHC systems. By utilizing available data, it has highlighted critical issues that are often overlooked, including reactor sizing and reaction kinetics. In light of the results obtained, it is evident that the most promising application for LOHCs appears to be in energy transportation.

¹*Liquid organic hydrogen carriers: Development of a thermodynamic and kinetic model for the assessment of hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes*, International Journal of Hydrogen [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.06.120], Marco Gambini, Federica Guarnaccia, Maria Luisa Di Vona, Michele Manno, and Michela Vellini.

²*Feasibility study of LOHC-SOFC systems under dynamic behavior for cargo ships compared to ammonia alternatives*, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.07.224], Marco Gambini, Federica Guarnaccia, Michele Manno, and Michela Vellini.

³*Hydrogen flow rate control in a liquid organic hydrogen carrier batch reactor for hydrogen storage*, International Journal of Hydrogen [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.05.153], Marco Gambini, Federica Guarnaccia, Michele Manno, and Michela Vellini.

⁴*Thermal design and heat transfer optimisation of a liquid organic hydrogen carrier batch reactor for hydrogen storage*, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.08.200], Marco Gambini, Federica Guarnaccia, Michele Manno, and Michela Vellini.

⁵*Flow rate control in a plug-flow reactor for liquid organic hydrogen carriers dehydrogenation*, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy [DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.03.082], Marco Gambini, Federica Guarnaccia, Michele Manno, and Michela Vellini.

⁶*Ragone plots of material-based hydrogen storage systems*, Journal of Energy Storage [DOI: 10.1016/j.est.2023.109815], Marco Gambini, Federica Guarnaccia, Michele Manno, and Michela Vellini.

Acknowledgements

I'd like to thank my wonderful friends, family and professors for all their help and support along the way. I don't usually do long, formal acknowledgements, but I'd like to give a special (and long-overdue!) thank you to Michele.

Nomenclature

The next list describes several symbols and acronyms that were used in the body of this document. Acronyms list is comprehensive of every acronym mentioned, while the list of symbols focuses on the main parameters that have been used. As such, parameters that have only been used in a limited context are omitted from this list to avoid clutter and limit repetition. A description of said parameters is still provided when necessary in the chapters. Possible ambiguities have been limited by selecting a mostly unambiguous symbology, with very few exceptions which are explicitly stated below.

List of Symbols:

A	Surface
a_x	DoH to mass conversion factor
b	Pressure coefficient
Bi	Biot number
C	Heat capacity
c	Specific heat coefficient
D	Diffusivity
d	Diameter
E	Energy or electric potential if referring to SOFC
e	Specific energy
E_a	Activation energy
F	Faraday constant
f	Friction factor
f_r	Reactor's volume factor
Fr	Froude number
g	Gravitational Acceleration
Ge	Entrance correction
H	Height
h	Specific enthalpy
I	Current
j	Current density
k	Frequency factor
k_B	Boltzmann constant
K_{eq}	Equilibrium constant
L	Length
M	Molar weight
m	Mass
N	Number
n	Reaction order or moles if with subscript referring to a compound
Nu	Nussel number
p	Pressure
P	Power
p_v	Vapore pressure
Pr	Prandtl number
Q	Heat
R	Gas constant
r	Kinetic rate
r	Radius
Re	Reynolds number
R_u	Universal gas constant
S	Entropy
T	Temperature
t	Time
U	Overall heat transfer coefficient
V	Volume, or voltage if referring to SOFC

v	Velocity
W	Work
w	Gravimetric capacity of storable hydrogen

Greek:

α	Convective heat transfer coefficient
ΔG	Gibbs free energy
ΔH	Reaction enthalpy
δ	Thickness
ϵ	Heat transfer effectiveness
ζ	Reaction coordinate
η	Efficiency
λ	Thermal conductivity
μ	Dynamic viscosity
ρ	Density
σ	Electric conductivity
τ	Release time
χ	Molar fraction
ω	Rotational speed

Acronyms:

AR	Aspect Ratio
BR	Batch Reactor
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCUS	Carbon Capture Usage and Storage
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
DBT	Di Benzyl Toluene
DEC	Decalin
DME	Di-Methyl Ether
DMFC	Direct Methanol Fuel Cell
DNEC	Dodecahydro N-Ethyl Carbazole
DOE	Department of Energy (USA)
DoH	Degree of Hydrogenation
FA	Formic Acid
FC	Fuel Cell
FCTO	Fuel Cell Technologies Office
HHV	Higher Heating Value
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
HTR	Heat Transfer Ratio
LCOH	Levelized Cost Of Hydrogen
LH2	Liquid Hydrogen
LHV	Lower Heating Value
LOHC	Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MH	Metal Hydride
MHC	Metil Cyclo Hexane
MTH	Methanol-To-Hydrocarbon
NEC	N-Ethyl Carbazole
NTU	Number of Transfer Units
ODE	Ordinary Differential Equations
PDBT	Perhydro Di Benzyl Toluene
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane (Fuel Cell)
PFR	Plug Flow Rate
PI	Proportional Integral (controller)

PID	Proportional Integral Derivative (controller)
PNEC	Perhydro N-Ethyl Carbazole
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuel
SCR	Selective Catalytic Reduction
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
SNG	Synthetic Natural Gas
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
TOF	Turn Over Frequency
TOL	Toluene
TPI	Toxicity Potential Indicator
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WGS	Water Gas Shift Reaction

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Chapter 1

Hydrogen

1.1 Hydrogen Overview

1.1.1 Future Role

Unlike conventional fuels, the combustion of hydrogen does not produce CO₂ and results in minimal environmental impact¹. Hydrogen can be used as a feedstock, as a fuel or for energy storage and transport: its potential applications are in industry, transport, power generation and the tertiary sector (Tzimas et al., 2003; Commission, 2022). Hydrogen can replace fossil fuels in several carbon-intensive industrial processes, such as steel production or the chemical industry, reducing their greenhouse gas emissions and increasing their competitiveness (Bassano and Deiana, 2020). Areas of interest may include refineries, ammonia and methanol production.

In the transport sector, hydrogen could be a promising option, especially for applications where electrification is more complicated, such as city buses and heavy-duty road vehicles and fuel cell trains (Agency, 2023; energy.gov, 2022a). It could also be used for short sea shipping or inland waterways. In the longer term, it may be possible to decarbonise the maritime and aviation sectors (Cells and Undertaking, 2020), for example by producing kerosene or other synthetic fuels, or by developing fuel cell-powered aircraft designs or hydrogen jets. It is estimated that hydrogen combustion could reduce the environmental impact of flying by 50-70 %, while the development of FC aircraft could lead to reductions of 75-90 %. These properties mean that hydrogen could play a key role in achieving the EU's target of carbon neutrality by 2050, as well as supporting the goals set out in the Paris Agreement (Commission, 2018). To date, hydrogen represents only a tiny fraction of the European and global energy mix, and its production is still closely linked to fossil fuels, with annual CO₂ production in the UE estimated at 70-100 million tonnes. However, in the Strategic Vision for a Climate Neutral UE published in 2018 (Commission, 2018), the share of hydrogen energy produced at UE level is projected to increase from less than 2 % to 13-14 % by 2050. Investment in hydrogen will go hand in hand with sustainable growth objectives and the creation of new jobs, which remain crucial to recovery from the COVID-19 crisis (Europe, 2020).

Hydrogen can be produced by a number of different processes, each characterised by very different emissions (Administration, 2023):

- Electricity-based hydrogen: produced by electrolysis of water, regardless of the source of electricity. From IEA reports, with the UE and global electricity mix there are 14 and 26 kg_{CO_{2,eq}}/kg_{H₂} well-to-gate (IEA, 2021).
- Renewable hydrogen: produced by an electrolyser using electricity generated from renewable sources, with near-zero life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions. Hydrogen produced by biogas reforming or biochemical conversion of biomass (at a cost of ≈2.5-5.5 €/kg) also falls into this category.
- Fossil-based hydrogen: produced by a variety of processes using fossil fuels as feedstock, mainly by natural gas reforming and coal gasification. For natural gas reforming, it is estimated that 9 kg_{CO_{2,eq}}/kg_{H₂} well to gate (≈1.5 €/kg) (IEA, 2021).

¹At high temperatures, with air as oxidant, thermal NO_x formation also occurs Capurso et al., 2023.

- Low carbon hydrogen: includes both electricity-based hydrogen and fossil-based hydrogen when accompanied by CO₂ capture. For the latter, the emission values depend on the capture efficiency; at 90 % and 56 % efficiencies there are 1 and 4 kg_{CO_{2,eq}}/kg_{H₂} well to gate (≈ 2.0 €/kg) respectively (IEA, 2021).
- Hydrogen-derived synthetic fuels: liquid or gaseous fuels based on carbon and hydrogen, defined as renewable if the latter is derived from renewable sources. GHG impacts vary widely depending on the process and feedstock.

To date, most hydrogen has been produced from fossil fuels (Martino et al., 2021): natural gas reforming processes rely on abundant, low-cost feedstocks and use well-established processes. However, the use of renewable feedstocks and energy to support production processes is key to achieving carbon neutrality, although the intermittent nature of many energy supplies poses a challenge. Increasing the competitiveness of renewable and low-carbon hydrogen will require significant investment, the establishment of a regulatory framework, continued research and innovation, and cooperation between countries. To support these investments, the European Clean Hydrogen Alliance has been established and will play a crucial role in facilitating and implementing the actions defined in the European Hydrogen Strategy, as well as supporting future investments (Alliance, 2023). With clean energy investment cycles of around 25 years, the time to act is now.

However, efforts will be needed on several fronts (Ahad et al., 2023):

- Production: development of more efficient, economically competitive and larger (GW) electrolyzers, while promoting alternative technologies such as hydrogen production from algae or direct solar water splitting.
- Infrastructure: to distribute and store large quantities of hydrogen. In the future it may be possible to use the existing infrastructure for natural gas.
- End-uses: especially in the chemical, petrochemical and steel industries and in transport. At the same time, the development of a regulatory framework and the establishment of harmonised standards and safety regulations will be necessary.

Other critical issues include social and market impacts, public acceptance, and the need to secure raw material supplies while considering the possibility of reducing their volumes, as well as substitution, reuse and recycling. Although challenging, overcoming these issues will stimulate economic growth and create new job opportunities. This transition is the natural conclusion of the turnover of energy sources, where there has been a shift from solid to liquid to gaseous sources (Fig. 1.1). Only through further research will it be possible to make hydrogen competitive with today's major energy sources.

1.1.2 General Properties

Hydrogen was discovered by Cavendish in 1766 (RinconEducativo, 2023) and is the lightest of the elements (atomic weight 1.007 94 Da) with unitary atomic number. It is the ninth most abundant element in the Earth's crust (1400 mg/kg), while it is the second most abundant in the oceans after oxygen (1.08×10^5 mg/L). Under normal conditions² It is colourless, odourless, tasteless, non-toxic and flammable (Fukai, 2010). Elemental hydrogen exists in several forms: as a monoatomic gas at low densities, as diatomic molecules, as a metallic conductor at high pressures, and as an ionised plasma at high temperatures; all these states exist in the Solar System, but on Earth elemental hydrogen exists only in molecules. Tab. 1.1 summarises some properties for hydrogen, including its isotopes deuterium and tritium (Fukai, 2010).

The hydrogen molecule consists of two hydrogen atoms and exists as ortho-hydrogen and para-hydrogen, in which the two atoms occur with the same or different spin, and which under normal conditions make up 75 % and 25 % of the total, respectively; this equilibrium composition is called normal hydrogen. However, as the temperature decreases, ortho-hydrogen transforms into para-hydrogen and in the liquid state is almost exclusively in the para state (Riaz et al., 2023). This transformation results in a heat release which, at

²Defined as 20 °C and 1.00 atm.

FIGURE 1.1: Global energy transition over time from 1850 to 2150 forecast.

	H	D	T
Nucleus			
Mass (Da)	1.008	1.998	2.993
Spin	1/2	1	1/2
Magnetic Moment (μ B)	2.7928	0.8574	2.9788
Atom			
Ionization energy (eV)	13.5989	13.6025	13.6038
Molecule			
Binding Energy (eV)	4.748	4.748	-
Dissociation Energy (eV)	4.478	4.556	4.590
Vibrational Energy (eV)	0.516	0.3712	0.3402
Rotational Energy (eV)	7.32×10^{-3}	3.70×10^{-3}	-
Gas - Liquid (normal)			
Critical Temperature (K)	32.98	38.34	40.44
Critical Pressure (MPa)	1.298	1.649	1.906
Boiling Temperature at 1 bar (K)	20.41	23.67	25.04
Latent Boiling Heat at 1 bar (J/mol)	913	1235	1394
Triple Point			
Temperature (K)	13.96	18.73	20.62
Pressure (kPa)	7.20	17.15	21.60

TABLE 1.1: Hydrogen properties distinguishing between its isotopes.

Pressure (MPa)	1.013×10^{-1}	5	10	20	30	35	40	50	70	100
Z	1	1.032	1.065	1.132	1.201	1.246	1.272	1.344	1.489	1.702

TABLE 1.2: Compressibility factor values for an increasing pressure level.

FIGURE 1.2: Hydrogen density with respect to pressure evaluated using Eq. 1.1 and Eq. 1.2, compared to real data.

20 K, is 703 J/g, with an energy required for the same transformation under normal conditions instead of 527-670 J/g. The effects of this conversion are manifested in the storage of liquefied hydrogen, as it is accompanied by a release of energy greater than the heat of evaporation (445.6 J/g), leading to boil-off losses.

Under normal conditions hydrogen is in the gaseous state and at atmospheric pressure it has a condensation point at -252.87°C and solidifies at -259.34°C . (energy.gov, 2001). The boiling point increases with increasing pressure to a critical point at -240.0°C and 13 atm, beyond which the increase in pressure has no significant effect on the boiling point. Its density is very low in both the liquid and gaseous states; under normal conditions in the gaseous state it has a density of 0.09 kg/m^3 , 70.80 kg/m^3 in the liquid state. In contrast, methane and gasoline have densities of $4.40\text{--}700.00\text{ kg/m}^3$ under the same thermodynamic conditions.

Although at pressures below 100 atm the perfect gas model accurately describes the behaviour of hydrogen, in general the highly polarised nature of the molecule causes attractive forces to be generated as pressure changes, manifesting as a compressive effect. Referring to the van der Waals equation of state (Eq. 1.1), a first model is:

$$\left(p + \frac{an^2}{V^2}\right)(V - nb) = nR_u T \quad (1.1)$$

where R_u is the universal gas constant, and the constants $a = 0.02476\text{ J m}^3/\text{mol}^2$ of dipole interaction and $b = 0.02661 \times 10^{-3}\text{ m}^3/\text{mol}$ volume occupied by molecules are empirically defined. Eq. 1.2 on the other hand accounts for the compressibility factor (Z) as well:

$$pV = nZR_u T \quad (1.2)$$

with Z assuming values in Tab. 1.2 for different pressure levels (Makridis, 2016).

The two models give results that are compatible with experimental values up to pressures of about 400 bar, but for higher pressures it would be necessary to develop a suitable model consisting of an equation of state relating T, p, V defined exclusively for hydrogen and an equation relating the change in internal energy to T, p, V (Walker, 2008). A comparison between experimental data and the two proposed analytical approaches is given in Fig. 1.2.

When hydrogen reacts with oxygen, water is formed and energy is released. The heating value is defined as the energy released during combustion per unit mass of hydrogen

	MJ/kg	MJ m ³ /N	MJ m ³ /N, H ₂ (l)
LHV	120.00	10.80	8.495×10^3
HHV	141.86	12.75	10.040×10^3

TABLE 1.3: Lower and higher heating values for hydrogen.

FIGURE 1.3: Lower heating values of different fuels compared in terms of gravimetric and volumetric density.

burned. Specifically, the heating value is lower when the water is in the vapour phase (LHV) and higher when it is in the liquid state (HHV), the values of which are given in Tab. 1.3, although these values may vary depending on the source, especially at high pressures. Note how the low density causes the energy density per unit volume to be very low, while per unit mass it is very high compared to other fuels (Fig. 1.3). The HHV is almost 15% higher than the LHV if the heat of condensation of water is included. In most applications, the energy actually available for conversion to work is LHV, but there are applications, such as PEMs, where water is produced in liquid form and for which HHV is more appropriate.

As an element, hydrogen has several unique properties, including a marked reactivity with many different elements, even at low temperatures. These are related to three main aspects (Fukai, 2010):

- Average electronegativity value (Web, 2023): The electronegativity represents the ease or difficulty with which an electron can be captured or released from an atom, and allows one to predict the type of bond that will form between two elements. If the electronegativity (χ) is such that $\chi_A < \chi_B$ the electron will be transferred from A to B to form A^+B^- , but if instead $\chi_A \approx \chi_B$ a covalent or metallic bond will be formed with no charge transfer. The average electronegativity value allows hydrogen to form different types of bonds.

- **Small size:** Actually the size of hydrogen depends on its state. As an atom its size is defined by Bohr's radius $a_B = 0.529 \text{ \AA}$, as an anion H^- has a relatively large size 2.1 \AA , while as a cation hydrogen has an ionic radius of $-(0.18 - 0.38) \text{ \AA}$, where the minus sign indicates that in the presence of the proton there is a contraction of the neighbouring bonds, with the value depending on the number of surrounding anions. The small size of hydrogen allows it to fit easily into the narrow interstitial sites in metal lattices, partly due to the flexibility of the surrounding electronic states.
- **Low nuclear mass:** In M–H alloys with large mass differences, the frequency distribution of the vibrational systems can be separated into a low frequency component (acoustic modes) similar to that of the parent metal, and a high frequency component (vibration per optical mode) related to interstitial hydrogens, with energies of 50-200 meV higher, which affect the phase stability and the nature of the interstitials and are comparable to thermal energies at ordinary temperatures. The peculiarities of the nuclear mass in the hydrogen wave function also mean that it is possible for hydrogen tunneling effects to occur between interstitial sites. Evidence for tunneling in bcc metals (with tetrahedral site spacing on the order of 1 \AA) has been recorded.

Another particular property of hydrogen is its tendency to degrade the mechanical behaviour of metallic materials and their subsequent fatigue failure, which poses a challenge to the construction of its infrastructure when present in atomic form. In structural materials such as aluminium and steel, it is possible for atomic hydrogen to be in solid solution in the crystal lattice (Peisl, 1978), facilitating fracture. Structures that have undergone welding are particularly susceptible to hydrogen embrittlement. For some materials it appears that the severity of the process also depends on the presence of other species. For example, the presence of hydrogen sulphide is particularly detrimental, and for aluminium alloys it appears that the presence of water vapour facilitates embrittlement (Fukai, 2010). The causes of hydrogen embrittlement are still debated scientifically (Murakami, 2019); it is believed that hydrogen atoms solute in metals tend to concentrate in defects in the crystal lattice, inhibiting the movement of dislocations and preventing plastic creep of the material so reducing its ductility. The effect of temperature does not follow a general trend for all metals; for example, ferritic steels exhibit greater vulnerability at low temperatures, and austenitic steels show a peak susceptibility around 200 K and then decrease with temperature (Yang et al., 2023). Additional embrittlement mechanisms may be related to the concentration of hydrogen at grain boundaries in molecular form and the possible formation of hydrides. Cracking conditions may also occur in the presence of hydrogen due to corrosive stresses and related to the onset of stresses in corrosive hydrogen atmospheres.

At elevated temperatures other degradation phenomena can occur; in steels this is known as hydrogen attack, caused by chemical reactions between atomic hydrogen and carbon leading to the formation of methane gas; in other materials, exposure to hydrogen at elevated temperatures can lead to internal precipitation of high pressure hydrogen gas as the temperature is lowered as solubility decreases. In both cases, the formation of high pressure gas in internal cracks can lead to fracture (Fukai, 2010). In this context, it is necessary to evaluate the mechanisms of hydrogen permeation in metals and non-metals.

In metals, diatomic hydrogen is adsorbed on the surface, dissociates into atomic hydrogen and then diffuses under a force related to the pressure gradient, producing a flux (J , $\text{m}^3/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s})$) which is a function of the wall thickness (δ) and the permeability ($P_{M,H}$, $\text{m}^3/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s Pa}^{0.5})$) as in Eq. 1.3. Hydrogen transport is very fast for metals such as palladium or its alloys at temperatures above 450 K, so one might consider using composite membranes with a thin active layer on a porous substrate for the purpose of cleaning hydrogen from reformers.

$$J = \frac{P_{M,H} (p_{high}^{0.5} - p_{low}^{0.5})}{\delta} \quad (1.3)$$

In nonmetallic materials, hydrogen permeation instead follows Fick's law, whereby in relation to permeability ($P_{H,NM}$, Eq. 1.4):

$$J = \frac{P_{M,H} (p_{high} - p_{low})}{\delta} \quad (1.4)$$

where permeability increases with temperature; this means that permeability only becomes a relevant issue in some temperature ranges, with negligible contributions for liquid hydrogen, for example.

1.2 Hydrogen Chain

1.2.1 Hydrogen Production

The different ways in which hydrogen can be produced are usually summarised by symbolically assigning colours to them (Europe, 2018):

- Grey: produced from fossil sources, mainly natural gas, without capturing the CO₂ produced.
- Green: produced by electrolysers using energy from renewable sources.
- Blue: produced from fossil sources, mainly natural gas, but with subsequent CCUS processes.
- Purple: produced using electricity from nuclear power stations.

There are other less common classifications (EWE, 2022). Hydrogen produced by gasification is sometimes referred to as brown or black, depending on whether the coal used is lignite or bituminous. White hydrogen is defined as hydrogen that for some reason already occurs naturally in rare underground deposits or is a by-product of an industrial process. Turquoise hydrogen, on the other hand, is produced by the pyrolysis of methane, a technology still at the experimental stage, which involves decomposition at high temperatures and the production of a solid coal. Finally, yellow hydrogen refers to hydrogen produced electrolytically using solar energy combined with electricity from a mix of sources depending on solar availability. To date, most of the demand for hydrogen is met by technologies that require the consumption of fossil fuels (Godula-Jopek, Jehle, and Wellnitz, 2012), with about 95% going to grey hydrogen (IEA, 2019). The most common is the conversion of methane and steam to hydrogen and carbon dioxide in a high-temperature catalytic reactor, but methane could also be replaced in reforming by biogas or other fuels such as ethanol or propane.

The overall reaction and the two reactions that actually take place in steam methane reforming are shown below:

Steam methane reforming is an endothermic reaction that requires water vapour as an oxidant. Although not currently widely used, there are variants of the traditional process (Tindall and Crews, 1995): partial oxidation, where the process uses oxygen or air as the oxidant and is exothermic, and autothermal reforming, a combination of the traditional mechanism and partial oxidation, where a mixture of air and steam is used in a ratio that does not require heat to be added or removed. High temperature steam (700-1000 °C) reacts with methane at pressures typically between 3-25 bar, producing CO and a small amount of carbon dioxide (energy.gov, 2019a). This initial reaction is endothermic and is followed by the water-gas shift reaction, which leads to the formation of carbon dioxide from carbon monoxide and an additional hydrogen molecule. This reaction is slightly exothermic. The remaining vapour is separated from the mixture by condensation, while the hydrogen is separated by pressure swing adsorption processes after removal of CO₂ and other impurities. In partial oxidation, natural gas reacts with a sub-stoichiometric amount of oxygen to produce a mixture with a composition consisting mainly of hydrogen and CO (and nitrogen if in air). A water-gas shift reaction is then induced; the reaction is exothermic and typically faster than SMR. However,

FIGURE 1.4: Production costs of hydrogen with and without CCUS in different regions of the world.

the hydrogen yield is lower.

In any case, hydrogen production by reforming involves the formation of carbon dioxide, the capture and storage of which would inevitably increase the cost of production. Fig. 1.4 sums up the costs in dollars per unit mass associated with hydrogen production, differentiated by region and related to the cost of natural gas in the relevant reference regions in 2018 (Europe, 2018).

From an environmental point of view, however, the most promising method of producing hydrogen is the electrolysis of water, in which electricity is used to split the water molecule into hydrogen and hydroxyl ions OH^- . The latter can move in the electrolyte from the cathode to the anode, where electrons are absorbed and OH^- is oxidised to water and oxygen. The mixing of oxygen and hydrogen is prevented by a permeable hydroxyl membrane. Ideally, the electricity would come from renewable sources and the hydrogen could be directed to fuel cells, in which case green hydrogen would be produced. At present, only small amounts of hydrogen can be produced conveniently by electrolysis. An electrolyzer consists of a number of modular cells and a central unit, and they are classified according to temperature and the type of electrolyte used (Dincer and AlZahrani, 2018): at low temperatures there are alkaline, proton exchange and anion exchange electrolytes; at high temperatures there are mainly solid oxide electrolytes, but these are still experimental technologies. Developments in the latter electrolytes could increase the efficiency of the conversion, making it possible to produce a synthesis gas directly from a stream of steam and CO_2 .

Hydrogen can also be produced as a result of some industrial electrochemical processes, such as the production of caustic soda and chlorine (Kumar, Du, and Lienhard, 2021). The process involves passing an electric current through a brine (an aqueous salt solution of sodium chloride), which dissociates and recombines through an exchange of electrons to form chlorine gas and caustic soda and hydrogen dissolved in water. The reaction produces 1.1 and 0.03 kg/kgCl of caustic soda and hydrogen, which must be separated. Other processes could be (Megia et al., 2021):

- Partial oxidation of heavy hydrocarbons: requires pure oxygen, and although it is now being developed on a commercial scale, it is inefficient and also involves CO_2 emissions.
- Coal gasification: not economically viable at present, but it is estimated that it could become the main source of hydrogen in the future, partly because of the large availability of the fuel.
- Biomass conversion: by gasification or pyrolysis, oils can be obtained from matrix decomposition for reforming; costs are very sensitive to transport and feedstock costs.

FIGURE 1.5: Schematic representation of the main hydrogen storage solutions available, sorted into physical and material - based storage solutions. Image courtesy of energy.gov (energy.gov, 2019b).

- Biological processes: could provide a solution for long-term sustainable hydrogen production with minimal environmental impact, but are currently at the research stage. However, it is possible to use photosynthetic bacteria to release pure hydrogen from the decomposition of organic material, or through electrolysis processes in which microbial species break down biomass using an electrical input.
- From aluminium: Of interest for micro-fuel cells, hydrogen can be produced by oxidation of aluminium in reactions such as

As highlighted by (Megía et al., 2021), biomass-based technologies in particular could have similar hydrogen yields to water-based technologies, but with higher energy efficiency and lower operating costs. Inconveniently, the hydrogen yield could be subject to seasonal availability depending on the type of biomass, but this problem is solved if waste is used.

1.2.2 Storage Technologies

Hydrogen storage is a key aspect of the development and deployment of hydrogen-based technologies and many alternatives for energy storage are available making use of different principles, see Fig. 1.5 (Walker, 2008; Godula-Jopek, Jehle, and Wellnitz, 2012).

To date, several agencies are focusing their attention on the development of advanced technologies and materials to overcome the major critical issues that exist (Preuster, Alekseev, and Wasserscheid, 2017), the first of which is the low energy density resulting from the very low calorific value per unit volume (Tzimas et al., 2003; Andersson and Grönkvist, 2019). This is particularly important for mobile applications, as discussed in Sec. 1.2.4. To address these challenges, the Fuel Cell Technologies Office (FCTO), for example, has defined two strategic paths: in the short term, a focus on compressed gas storage using advanced (fibre-reinforced composite) tanks capable of withstanding pressures of 700 bar; and in the long term, a focus on both cryogenic and material-based systems development (USDRIVE, 2017). Other approaches have also been defined: for example, an innovative device for the

storage of compressed hydrogen has been realised based on a honeycomb capillary glass structure (Zhevago, Denisov, and Glebov, 2010) with diameters of about 100 μm , capable of withstanding pressures of more than 1000 bar, and at least at the micro scale (volume of 8.5 cm^3) the device would appear to have volumetric and gravimetric capacities exceeding even the DOE's (energy.gov, 2019b) targets. In any case, the storage of molecular hydrogen in pure form on a significant scale is currently achieved exclusively by physical storage. Specific applications include liquid hydrogen storage in space applications and storage in large underground salt formations in the US and UK (Europe, 2019).

Compressed Hydrogen

These systems consist of two main elements: a compression system and a storage system. Operating costs and material strength requirements are such that large quantities of hydrogen are not stored at pressures above 100 and 200 bar for storage or (Burheim, 2017) for underground storage. The low densities associated with these pressures (at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, about 7.8 kg/m^3) lead to very high specific storage volumes and hence high investment costs. Conversely, higher pressures would require higher energy consumption, thus increasing operating costs. Polytropic and isentropic compression work are expressed in Eq. 1.5-1.6, with the adiabatic index (γ) defined in Eq. 1.7.

$$W_{pol} = \frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1} RT_1 \left[\beta^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right] \quad (1.5)$$

$$W_{ise} = c_p T_1 \left(\beta^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right) \quad (1.6)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{c_p}{c_v} \quad (1.7)$$

It should be noted that the compression of hydrogen gas is an energy consuming process (Langmi et al., 2022). Considering the isentropic compression of hydrogen under normal conditions to a pressure of 200 atm, with an assumed c_p equal to 14.65 $\text{kJ}/(\text{kg K})$, a specific work of 15 011 kJ/kg is obtained, about ten times the work required to compress methane under the same thermodynamic conditions. Investment costs for underground applications are much lower on a large scale. Salt caverns (Hydrogen, 2021) are the most attractive alternative because of low construction costs, low leakage, rapid injection and withdrawal rates, minimal risk of hydrogen contamination, and the minimal amount of cushion gas required (gas permanently stored to maintain sufficient pressure for a good injection and withdrawal rate). Aquifers and depleted oil or gas wells are viable alternatives in regions where there are no saline formations. However, underground storage can alter the quality of the hydrogen; depending on the geological formation, there may be water vapour impurities, hydrogen sulphide or other hydrogenation products of the rock components, requiring the presence of treatment units to remove the water and purify the feed prior to injection into the pipeline.

Another alternative is storage in tanks (Cheng et al., 2023), which are typically metal containers that can guarantee the purity of the stored hydrogen, but at a higher investment cost. For larger tanks, however, it may be appropriate to bury them a few metres below ground level to reduce land occupation, protect them from impacts and weathering, and provide an insulating effect. However, this makes inspection more difficult and increases susceptibility to corrosion. The choice of carbon fibre tanks for storage at 700 bar was made for early fuel cell vehicles; for stationary applications much larger volumes are required and the system costs would become prohibitive. Although there is little experience of storing large quantities of hydrogen in metal tanks, the same systems used for natural gas could be used. The most promising solution appears to be pipeline storage, where pressures of 100 bar can be achieved, making them the most compact solution (Commission, 2021; Cristello et al., 2023). From a construction point of view, they do not present great difficulties; the total length of the pipeline, made up of several relatively short modular elements, can be several kilometres and is usually laid a few metres underground. Using the pressure and diameter of pipelines currently used for methane, it is estimated that about 12 t/km of hydrogen could be stored. However, these would be more expensive than their counterparts for natural gas, mainly because of hydrogen embrittlement.

FIGURE 1.6: Plant scheme for liquid hydrogen production using a Joule - Brayton refrigeration cycle.

To date, compression is mainly achieved by using reciprocating positive displacement compressors or diaphragm compressors, but rotary compressors such as scroll and screw compressors could theoretically also be used. Dynamic compressors are not yet available and further research is needed to design them. Other commercially available solutions are ionic compressors, which are reciprocating compressors with a liquid piston where the dead volume is minimised. Efficiency is very high and each compression stage can be controlled individually, making it a versatile device. As the compression is almost isothermal, the outlet temperature from each stage is very low (130-150 °C with $T_{in} = 50$ °C and $\beta = 3$). One of the most important issues in compression is the need to lubricate the compressor, but mineral oils cannot be used as they can hydrogenate, so the two possible alternatives are either dry compression or the use of a chemically inert lubricant.

Liquid Hydrogen

Liquefaction allows relatively high hydrogen densities even at low pressures, although liquid hydrogen has primarily been studied as a distribution medium (Aziz, 2021). Hydrogen liquefaction is an energy-intensive process because the low boiling temperatures must be reached, and because hydrogen does not cool by isenthalpic expansion (Joule-Thomson effect) above -73 °C, it requires pre-cooling, which often involves the evaporation of liquid nitrogen. Fig. 1.6 shows a typical scheme of hydrogen production using a Joule - Brayton refrigeration cycle. In any case, it is an established technology with specific consumption currently around 10-13 kWh/kg of electrical energy, but it is estimated that in the future it could be reduced to below 6 kWh/kg in larger plants; in contrast, Peschka estimated a theoretical consumption for liquefaction of 3.9 kWh/kg (Peschka, 2012).

However, the capital cost remains a large proportion of the total cost, estimated at around 40-50% of the specific cost for new 100 t/d plants (Connelly et al., 2019). In fact, its main current application is in aerospace, where high costs are not a barrier. The main liquefaction process uses the Linde cycle, in which the compressed gas, cooled in an exchanger, is isentropically expanded through a throttle valve. Some of the cold gas condenses and is separated as a liquid, while the remaining gas is used to cool the compressed gas. This process is not suitable for hydrogen, because to cool after expansion the temperature must be well below room temperature (inversion temperature of 51 K at 100 kPa). An alternative would

then be the Linde-Sankey process with pre-cooling in liquid nitrogen (Macinko, Chelton, and Dean, 1960). In the Collins process, the pre-cooled liquid is compressed and then isentropically expanded. As the pressure drops, part of the fluid liquefies, while the gaseous part circulates in the opposite direction. To ensure that the temperature is low enough, it is necessary to use several heat exchangers and two expanders at different temperatures. In general, liquefaction occurs through three steps:

- Compression of pure, dry hydrogen to a pressure greater than the critical pressure.
- Cooling in two steps: a first pre-cooling step from room temperature to $T = 80 \pm 15$ K temperatures defined as "liquid nitrogen temperature level". In the second step the temperature is lowered to 22-45 K.
- Expansion to a pressure slightly above ambient pressure, typically through a throttling valve. Some of the cooled hydrogen liquefies, and the liquid hydrogen is separated in the phase separator from its vapor. The latter fraction is referred to as flash-gas and can be heated to temperatures about room temperature to cool the hydrogen supply, then being reinjected into the cycle.

Another method of liquefaction is magnetic liquefaction (Matsumoto et al., 2009), which exploits the magneto-heat effect, in which a reversible temperature change is caused by exposure to a varying magnetic field. The refrigeration cycle is similar to a Carnot cycle in which a magnetic material is added to the working fluid and consists of several stages of magnetisation and demagnetisation. The efficiencies that can be achieved appear to be higher than those achievable with other processes.

One of the main complexities in the design of these processes is the calculation of the equilibrium properties of hydrogen and its mixtures (equilibrium, normal, ortho and para), for which data are currently only available for normal hydrogen (pure ortho hydrogen) and pure para hydrogen (Zhang et al., 2021). The current integration of the ortho-para conversion process is not yet possible.

Once liquefied, the hydrogen must be stored in such a way as to minimise its evaporation, a phenomenon which results in a loss of both energy and hydrogen itself, since the hydrogen must be evacuated to prevent critical pressures from building up in the tank (Morales-Ospino, Celzard, and Fierro, 2023). The terms boil-off and boil-off rate therefore refer to the percentage of stored hydrogen lost on a daily basis; a reduction can be achieved by containing the heat exchanged with the environment using spherical tanks (minimum surface/volume ratio) and advanced insulation techniques. In addition to the heat exchange with the environment, boil-off is also related to the energy released in the ortho-para conversion in relation to the duration of storage and other phenomena such as:

- Thermal stratification: Inside the container, the hotter hydrogen will tend to float, being less dense, and position itself at the liquid-vapour interface, and it is this layer of liquid, at a higher temperature than the stored bulk hydrogen, that determines the vapour pressure, which is higher than the otherwise equilibrium pressure. The stratification is stable because hydrogen has a low thermal conductivity.
- Thermal overfill: In a tank overfilled with a relatively hot liquid, the liquid will rise to the temperature corresponding to the working pressure of the tank. If the surface layer is disturbed, the liquid below can be quickly brought to equilibrium with rapid boiling.
- Sloshing: related to the acceleration and deceleration motion of liquid hydrogen, where part of the energy is converted into heat energy.
- Flashing: due to transfer to a lower pressure container, where some of the hydrogen evaporates.

Boil-off is a critical factor mainly in applications where the storage and liquefaction plant are distant; in fact, if this is not the case, it is still possible to reinject the evaporated hydrogen into the line, with little additional cost given the temperature of the same. Typically, therefore, the vessels (cryostats) have two walls separated by a cavity which minimises convective

and conductive exchange, while radiative exchange is reduced by, for example, aluminium particles, silicates, perlite, or layers of glass fibre or alumina-coated polyester. These arrangements result in boil-off rates of less than 0.1 % in the largest vessels. At present, the largest tanks hold 230-270 t of hydrogen, but it is estimated that capacities in excess of 900 t can be achieved, and at a specific cost (per kg of hydrogen) which, on a large scale, is less than that expected for compressed hydrogen systems (Demaco-cryogenics, 2021).

Slush Hydrogen

This is a mixture of liquid and solid hydrogen characterised by a higher density (16 %) and heat capacity (18 %) than liquid hydrogen at boiling point (McNelis et al., 1995). These properties make it an attractive process for space, automotive and aerospace applications, but it requires special manufacturing processes (Ohira, 2016). At typical concentrations of 50 %_m solid fraction there is an increase in density and heat capacity of 15.5 % and 18.3 % respectively, evaluated at the boiling point, with an increased energy requirement of 12.0 % at best (Sherif, Gursu, and Veziroglu, 2014). The main existing production methods are then reported.

- Freeze-thaw method: the latent heat of vaporisation is used to solidify hydrogen (Sherif, Gursu, and Veziroglu, 2014). By removing the hydrogen gas at the triple point, a porous solid layer can be formed at the interface with the liquid. After mixing the solid with the liquid, this process can be repeated several times. However, this is a batch process, and since the pressure at the triple point is 6.95 kPa, even without considering the energy costs, there is a possibility of infiltration, which poses safety risks in relation to the formation of mixtures with oxygen.
- Auger exchanger: by a continuous process using a tube cooled with liquid helium, on the walls of which hydrogen solidifies. This is continuously removed by a screw inside the exchanger (Sherif, Gursu, and Veziroglu, 2014). From an energy point of view, it has a lower consumption.
- Slush Gun: Liquid hydrogen is pre-cooled by gaseous helium and injected through a nozzle into a tank containing cold gaseous helium, which solidifies the hydrogen in a continuous process (Brunnhofer et al., n.d.).

Physical adsorption

Adsorption storage exploits the physical van der Waals bonds between hydrogen and high surface area materials. As the bonds are weak, significant densities can only be achieved at high pressures and low temperatures, requiring a refrigerant such as liquid nitrogen, while hydrogen pressures can vary between 10-100 bar depending on the adsorbent and application (Samantaray, Putnam, and Stadie, 2021). Increasing the pressure has beneficial effects up to a threshold, beyond which the storage capacity would be greater as a compressed gas due to the bulkiness of the adsorbent itself (Murialdo et al., 2019). Although there are few applications of this technology to date, mainly on a laboratory scale, several materials could be used: porous carbon-based matrices, zeolites, porous polymeric materials and metallorganic structures (Lee et al., 2022). Among carbon compounds, curved structures such as carbon nanotubes have the advantage of interacting more with hydrogen molecules and having higher attractive forces than planar structures, but this discrepancy tends to decrease with increasing temperature (Petrushenko and Petrushenko, 2019). In general, carbon nanostructures are promising for this storage system. The potential of boron nitride based nanotubes is also being investigated. However, progress in this field has stalled over the last two decades. Several studies have focused on identifying correlations between hydrogen adsorption and the structure and composition of various metallorganic compounds (Bastos-Neto et al., 2012). Examples of these correlations are the relationship between the heat of adsorption and pore size, due to higher van der Waals forces, or that between the presence of an open site and adsorption capacity, related to the polarisation of hydrogen molecules (Park and Park, 2020).

The low density of these materials and the need to add additives to improve their thermal conductivity penalise their volumetric storage density. However, the most critical aspect remains the control of the heat generated during adsorption (exothermic), which is typically of the order of 3-10 kJ mol_{H₂}. So, assuming an adsorption enthalpy of 4 kJ mol_{H₂}, or 0.56 kWh/kg, and nitrogen as a refrigerant with a heat of vaporisation of 0.056 kWh/kg, about 10 kg of liquid nitrogen is required to remove the heat of adsorption of 1 kg of hydrogen. With an electricity consumption of 0.5 kWh/kg_{N₂} for large air separation systems, this already implies only 5.0 kWh/kg_{H₂} for system cooling alone, without considering heat exchange with the environment and assuming that desorption occurs only by pressure swing (Peng et al., 2022). Therefore, the overall efficiency of these systems remains low even for short storage periods and large applications, despite the ability to store hydrogen safely and flexibly and to operate at lower pressures than compressed hydrogen systems. Other possible advantages are related to fast kinetics and full reversibility, hence the possibility of reduced charging times and long cycle life. It is also reiterated that current technologies are far from commercialisation, with studies generally applied to small samples (less than 100 g). Another problem with this technology is related to the difficulties of accuracy and reproducibility of measurements.

Metal Hydrides

In this case hydrogen is chemically bonded, so stronger bonds are involved (Fukai, 2010). This results in a higher reaction ΔH , but on the other hand it is possible to store hydrogen at high density even at ambient conditions. A particular advantage of using metal hydrides is that, in the event of an accident, there is no fire hazard associated with the release of hydrogen as it remains contained within the metal structure. Hydrogen can be released either by thermolysis in the solid state by the supply of heat (endotherm) or by hydrolysis by reaction with water in solution (exotherm); while thermolysis may be reversible, hydrolysis is irreversible (Fukai, 2010; Usman, 2022).

Fig. 1.7 shows the standard classification of metal hydrides based on their chemical nature. The only hydride with hydrophilic release that might be promising at present is sodium boron hydride (NaBH₄), typically dissolved in alkaline solutions (e.g. 20%_m NaBH₄, 10%_m NaOH, 70%_m H₂O) (Lototskyy and Yartys, 2015). The concentration of NaBH₄ must remain low to avoid precipitation of the hydrolysis products and subsequent poisoning of the catalyst (cobalt or, for better performance, the more expensive ruthenium) by clogging of the active sites.

De-hydrogenation by hydrolysis is characterised by good kinetics even at room temperature and is strongly exothermic (in this case 240 kJ/mol_{H₂}), good start-up rate and relatively easy control of hydrogen release. However, the hydrolysis products are very stable, so hydride regeneration is complex and very energy intensive (Hirscher et al., 2020). Alternatively, it is possible to release the stored hydrogen by reducing the system pressure below an ideal plateau equilibrium pressure, which increases with temperature (Suda, Kobayashi, and Yoshida, 1980). In this way it is possible to induce the decomposition of a stable hydride under certain pressure and temperature conditions by increasing the latter so that the equilibrium pressure exceeds the system pressure, as shown in Fig. 1.8.

Most metallic elements can form binary compounds with hydrogen, but generally these simple compounds have very poor thermodynamic properties and/or storage capacity. In fact, the hydrides available for pressures around 1 bar and low temperatures (<80 °C) are based on heavy transition metals such as LaNi₅ and TiFe, and have low storage capacities. Because of this limitation, there has also been a strong interest in elemental hydrides; the most interesting for large-scale applications are magnesium hydride and aluminium hydride (Klopčič et al., 2023). Magnesium hydrides have two very attractive properties for storage: the high theoretical storage capacity (7.6%_m) and the combination of low cost and good availability of magnesium. Thermodynamically, however, the bond between magnesium and hydrogen is strong, causing the reaction ΔH to be 75 kJ/mol_{H₂}; in addition, the kinetics

FIGURE 1.7: Schematic classification of different metal hydrides for hydrogen storage.

FIGURE 1.8: Transition to the α to the β phase in a metal hydride.

FIGURE 1.9: Octahedral (O) and tetrahedral (T) interstitial sites for different crystal lattices.

of both sorption and release are very slow, due to both the dissociation of molecular hydrogen at the magnesium surface and the diffusion of hydrogen into the hydride (Hirscher et al., 2020). Ultimately, temperatures above 300 °C are required for dehydrogenation to be sufficiently rapid. If the heat of absorption is not removed, the equilibrium temperature will be reached quickly and the reaction will be reversed. Some experiments have been carried out in special tanks filled not only with the hydride but also with a phase-change material to store the heat released during absorption and make it available for desorption. However, the storage density is dramatically reduced to about 0.32 %_m (0.06 kWh/L). Several ways of improving reaction kinetics have been identified (Walker, 2008); the most promising are related to particle size reduction using additives such as transition metals or even complex hydrides such as LiBH₄, nanoparticle grinding using ball mills (ball milling), or alloying. The aim is to obtain materials with long-term stability, fast kinetics and good thermal properties; the dehydrogenation temperature remains high in any case (Tarasov et al., 2021). However, nanoparticles can degenerate in contact with air and moisture, which necessitates precautions such as the use of coatings. One example is thin films of parylene, which act as a membrane impermeable to oxygen and water, but with slower release kinetics due to the additional diffusion barrier. The long-term gravimetric capacity actually achievable is around 6 %_m, with volumetric pellet storage capacities as high as 86 kg/m³. (Walker, 2008). In aluminium hydrides, hydrogen bonding is weak, and the reaction ΔH is about 7 kJ/mol_{H₂}, with a theoretical storage capacity of 10.1 %_m, and the possibility of rapid release as early as 100 °C. However, the sorption reaction between aluminium and hydrogen gas requires extreme pressures and is therefore virtually irreversible. This means that for AlH₃ to become established as a storage system, a better Al regeneration method must be developed (Walker, 2008). Although there is research into the possibility of electrochemical regeneration, most studies focus on thermochemical regeneration, but there are currently no large-scale applications. However, it appears that the energy requirements are still high, particularly the electricity required to run the vacuum pumps (10.03-13.32 kWh/kg of electricity and 48.5-53.8 kWh/kg of heat). An alternative to elemental hydrides are intermetallic hydrides, A_xB_yH_z alloys in which the element A is strongly bonded to hydrogen while B is weakly bonded to it, giving the hydride intermediate properties (Walker, 2008). A is then often a lanthanide such as Ca or a rare earth mixture called a misch metal; B can be Ni, Co, Al, Mn, Fe, Sn, Cu, Ti. In practice, mainly crystal structures of the form AB₅, AB₂ and AB (but also A₂B₇, AB₃, A₂B) have been studied in which hydrogen occupies interstitial positions. Fig. 1.9 shows the different interstitial sites available for the three most common lattices.

However, it appears that these compounds have too limited a storage capacity for mobile applications due to their low gravimetric density. However, the volumetric capacity is not necessarily so low, since density and porosity have to be taken into account. Nevertheless, they have found application in specific areas, such as powering low-temperature fuel cells for forklifts, where the total weight of the storage system counterbalances the vehicle itself (Bhuiya, Kumar, and Kim, 2015). More generally, they could be of interest for stationary applications. It appears that the long-term stability of these hydrides and their storage capacity is excellent (with capacity losses of 5% after 1300 cycles), but in most cases they are very expensive compounds, both in terms of the raw material and the metallurgical processes required. In complex metal hydrides, the hydrogen is part of an anion bonded to a metal cation. The main groups of interest are aluminium and sodium hydrides ($[\text{AlH}_4]^-$), boron hydrides ($[\text{BH}_4]^-$) and amides ($[\text{NH}_2]^-$) (Walker, 2008). They are generally much lighter than intermetallic hydrides and have attracted the attention of the automotive industry instead. However, many of these require high temperatures for dehydrogenation and the presence of a catalyst or additives. Typically, hydrides are thermal (and electrical) insulators, so changes in material and heat transfer systems are required to achieve good hydrogen sorption, increasing the overall cost of the system as well as its footprint (Hahne and Kallweit, 1998). Hydrides often undergo significant volume changes during hydrogenation and dehydrogenation, so care must be taken in the design of the vessels to avoid excessive forces on the walls. Their solid nature and significant dehydrogenation enthalpies present a challenge for heat transfer and rapid release of hydrogen. The need to use complex and expensive equipment to achieve uniform heat distribution makes this technology interesting for small scale applications.

Chemical Hydrides

Chemical hydrides consist of lighter elements than metal hydrides, which gives them very different properties, and they are generally found in the liquid state under normal conditions. This means that their transport, storage and the design of the necessary heat exchangers are advantageous. Many of the proposed hydrides (methanol, ammonia, formic acid) are chemicals that are commonly synthesised industrially, which simplifies aspects such as transport or production; on the other hand, the use of renewable hydrogen to produce them can help reduce the consumption of fossil fuels otherwise required for synthesis (Hirscher et al., 2020).

- Ammonia is a toxic gas with low exposure limits, which is a significant disadvantage at least for small-scale and decentralised applications; it remains an attractive alternative for long-distance transport on a large scale (Hirscher et al., 2020). While the most common production method is the Haber-Bosch process, alternative electrochemical processes, still under research, could lead to higher energy efficiency (Aziz, Wijayanta, and Nandiyanto, 2020). Compared to other hydrogen storage media, ammonia allows storage as a liquid under mild conditions and the use of transport infrastructure and regulations that are already well established.
- Methanol is particularly interesting because it has a storage capacity of 12.5% (by weight) and is liquid at ambient conditions. It could be fed directly into an MCI or DMFC, although to date direct-use methanol FCs are only commercially available on a small scale (Hirscher et al., 2020). Methanol is converted to hydrogen by a catalytic fuel reformer at about 200-300 °C with moderate energy consumption (Institute, 2021).
- As for formic acid (FA), the gravimetric capacity is limited (4.4%_m), but its high density leads to a volumetric storage capacity of 53.7 g/L. (Hirscher et al., 2020) (Joó, 2008). While the conversion back to hydrogen and CO₂ is relatively straightforward at low temperatures (below 100 °C) by catalytic processes, the hydrogenation of CO₂ to FA is more complex, with formation kinetics less favourable than those of methanol hydrogenation, and requires multiphase processes and auxiliary solvents as well as special arrangements to achieve relevant efficiencies. However, the development of better catalysts could enable a variety of low-cost and high-efficiency rechargeable FCs fuelled by FA produced by CO₂ removal (Singh, Singh, and Kumar, 2016).

In general, longer chain hydrocarbons can be used to store hydrogen by reacting it with CO₂ through Fischer-Tropsch synthesis reactions (Ghorbani et al., 2021). The process is based on three main reactions: the reverse WGS reaction to convert methylene anhydrides bound to a catalyst, with a distribution of products generated related to the probability of chain growth; finally, a hydrocracking reaction to adjust the chain length of the products. Typically, reactions take place in the presence of catalyst at 200-250 °C and 10-40 bar in multi-tubular or slurry phase reactors. The resulting blends (syncrude) are similar to crude oil, so further refining processes can be used to produce products similar to current fuels, allowing the current storage and transport infrastructure to be used. However, this similarity can be a disadvantage, as syncrude is in direct composition with crude oil, and Fischer-Tropsch reactions have not yet been optimised for dynamic and intermittent operation to suit hydrogen production.

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers

Historically, interest in LOHCs began in the 1980s when, following the first oil crises, some researchers in Switzerland investigated the possibility of using nuclear power to electrolyse water. The hydrogen produced would be destined for FC-powered vehicles; the advantages of greater storage capacity and less refuelling time compared to batteries were quickly recognised. Research then resumed around 2010, following the increasing importance of energy production from renewable and fluctuating sources. The first pilot plant for LOHC hydrogenation and dehydrogenation was planned by Chiyoda Corporation in Japan. In Europe, the EU has allocated 2.5 Mn € for the HySTOC project, a project to build a demonstration plant for dibenzyltoluene, which started in 2018 and should complete the construction phase in 2022 (GMBH, 2017).

LOHCs are materials characterised by the ability to undergo reversible processes of hydrogenation and dehydrogenation, both in the liquid state (Hirscher et al., 2020). For this reason, methanol and formic acid, although both organic liquids in the liquid state, are not LOHCs as they are gaseous in their dehydrated form. However, their classification could differ depending on the sources; however, although both are organic fluids in the liquid state, they are not LOHCs because in their de-hydrogenated form they are gaseous. However, their classification could differ depending on the source, but for the purposes of this discussion they are considered to be chemical hydrides. If these species were to be treated as LOHCs, certain precautions would be necessary: in order to avoid the formation of a solid phase at a high melting point, it might be necessary to limit the degree of loading and unloading or to use a solvent; on the other hand, a low boiling point would require a series of purification steps to ensure the quality of the feed.

Note that the requirement for the liquid state is at ambient conditions; however, even if they were gaseous at reaction conditions, separation from the hydrogen stream could occur by simple condensation. In this case it would be desirable to be able to recover the heat of condensation to limit the increased demand associated with having to supply the heat of evaporation. In general, however, all this has implications for process design in terms of logistics, energy and economics. In fact, remaining in a liquid state during the various phases is one of the great advantages of this technology: it ensures that the quality of the hydrogen released is very high, allows low electricity consumption (essentially only related to the pumping phase) and allows integration with today's infrastructure, given the similarity of the properties of many of these liquids to products from the oil industry. In particular, this could facilitate the integration of the technology, reducing both the time and the cost of its deployment, while continuing to use the existing resources of an industry that may be in decline. Specifically, the uptake and release of hydrogen occurs through the saturation and desaturation of carbon-carbon bonds. The different reactions occur in multiple steps and may follow alternative pathways; although there are studies where the concentration of the different intermediates is tracked over time, effective and efficient modelling of the process should fall back to an equivalent concentration and then to mixtures composed exclusively of the fully saturated or unsaturated species. A general overview of the working principle of LOHCs is given in Fig. 1.10, where common pressure levels of both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions are reported. On the other hand, the temperature levels have a wider range.

FIGURE 1.10: Schematic working principles of LOHCs hydrogenation and dehydrogenation.

Others

Glass microspheres: small hollow spheres of glass enriched with sulfur and urea arranged in a bed and heated to about 200 °C to increase the permeability of the walls, immersed in hydrogen gas at high pressure (about 250 bar) so as to fill them (Qi et al., 2012). They are then cooled to room temperature to trap the hydrogen inside, released as needed after the temperature is increased. Characteristic dimensions include a diameter between 1-200 μm and walls less than 1.5 μm thick and porosity between 100-3000 Å. They could be a safe application suitable for small sizes, with photo-induced hydrogen diffusion resulting in rapid release of hydrogen (Shelby, 2008). The nature of the chemical reactions is very similar to those that characterise metal hydride systems. It is therefore possible to continue the parallelism between these two technologies using a model with a common structure. As with metal hydrides, the absorption phase is exothermic and the release phase is endothermic. The amount of heat required for desorption can also be significant, so it is important to integrate these subsystems as much as possible in applications to take advantage of heat recovery during the desorption phase and possibly also to recover the heat released during absorption. The release phase is also particularly critical, not only because of the reaction enthalpy to be supplied to the system, but also because of the high temperatures required for the release phase. These are much higher than those expected for hydrides and can even exceed 300 °C, requiring the use of special heat transfer fluids such as diathermic oils or even molten salts, and precluding strict requirements on the quality of the heat to be supplied. In this respect, research has focused on different LOHCs with different thermodynamic properties. A common trade-off is between more accessible release temperatures and reaction enthalpies and higher storage capacity. The behaviour of these fluids can be studied in parallel using the same model, but taking care to develop appropriate and dedicated equations describing their adsorption and release kinetics. Chapter 2 provides a more detailed description of LOHC technologies.

Hydride slurry: A pumpable mixture of fine particles of solid metal hydrides and a liquid such as mineral oils; magnesium slurries are among these slurry solutions (McClaine, Brown, and Bowen, 2015). This storage medium is pumpable, relatively cheap and can be stored for months at ambient conditions. Hydrogen is stored as a metal hydride with good purity and is released from the organic carrier through chemical reactions, which can be recycled. Research is focusing on optimising slurry production, pumping, storage and recovery.

Bulk Amorphous Materials: Metallic materials consisting of multi-component alloys (e.g. Ti-Al-Fe) packed with interstitial porous defects for hydrogen storage, of controlled

size and distribution, in overflow (Huang et al., 2023). Absorption kinetics appear to be high, with good capacity to resist embrittlement and the possibility of low cost fabrication.

Gas network: The same network as for natural gas could be fed with some hydrogen; in fact methane, being the simplest alkane, has the largest storage capacity (25%_m). Although there is no experience of long-distance transport, for much of the twentieth century households in Germany, the USA and England were supplied with town gas and coke oven gas with a hydrogen content above even 50%_v (EUROPE, 2021). Only later was the installed infrastructure modified to handle natural gas. Several countries have investigated the possibility of injecting a fraction of hydrogen into the grid. For the United States it would be possible to achieve 5-15%_v, for Germany about 10%_v; higher values would require expensive conversions to avoid damage to the infrastructure (EUROPE, 2021). In Leeds (UK), for example, the possibility is being considered of completely converting the gas network, which is mainly used for heating, to hydrogen. Of course, the release of hydrogen from methane would require the implementation of expensive technologies (reforming, water-gas shift reactors, CO₂ removal), so in the event that hydrogen is stored via methane, it would be more cost effective to use it directly afterwards rather than convert (EUROPE, 2021).

1.2.3 Storage Properties

The low molecular weight of hydrogen makes its storage particularly critical. In addition to safety, cost, durability, cyclicity and power quality issues, there is also the low energy density (energy.gov, 2017; USDRIVE, 2017). There are several ways in which hydrogen can be stored, each characterised by different properties, the relevance of which inherently depends on the application in question (Niermann et al., 2019). A list of the main properties characteristic of storage by materials is given in Niermann et al. (2019) and Preuster, Alekseev, and Wasserscheid (2017) and can be summarised as follows:

- Capacity: maximum hydrogen content retained under steady-state conditions. There are several definitions of this, based for example on stability, composition, temperature, number of cycles. A typical measure of capacity is the gravimetric capacity ($w_{\%}$) as a mass percentage of hydrogen in the storage medium, defined as in Eq. 1.8.

$$w_{\%} = \frac{m_{\text{H}_2}}{m_{\text{H}_2} + m_{\text{sample}}} \cdot 100 \% \quad (1.8)$$

- Kinetics: a measure of the rate of sorption or release of a material, which in general can be influenced not only by the intrinsic properties of the material but also, for example, by size, heat transfer effects, the presence of a catalyst and/or additives, particle size. It directly affects the gaseous flux that can be released.
- Thermodynamics: The thermodynamic properties of temperature and pressure particularly affect capacity and kinetics. The latter often constrains the thermodynamic operating conditions regardless of the actual properties required by thermodynamic equilibrium. In general, a low dehydrogenation temperature allows for easier system integration as the recovery heat can be used to supply ΔH_r .
- Cycle life: for materials that can provide a reversible storage mechanism (under practical conditions, thus excluding, for example, chemical slurries and elemental hydrides). Cyclic effects can be evaluated in terms of capacity, e.g. related to structural or chemical degradation, activation phenomena, grain growth. The stability of the substance in the operating temperature range is part of this, so that parasitic reactions are minimised. Durability also extends to the equipment and apparatus involved, as well as any catalysts.

These macro characteristics determine various aspects of the system, starting with weight and overall dimensions. An energy efficiency is then defined that depends on the energy associated with the sorption (absorption/adsorption) of hydrogen and its release, a function rather than the energy required for compression and liquefaction in the storage systems of

Property	Mobility	Energy Transport	Stationary Applications
Capacity	Very important	Important	Secondary
Availability	Secondary	Very important	Very important
Toxicity	Secondary	Very important	Important
Release Temperature	Very important	Secondary	Secondary
Energy costs	Important	Secondary	Very important
Material Handling	Important	Very important	Secondary
Process Complexity	Very important	Secondary	Important
Cyclic Stability	Secondary	Important	Very important
Gas Flow	Very important	Secondary	Secondary

TABLE 1.4: Importance of different properties for different sectors.

the same name. In general, however, the selection phase involves trade-offs, for example between stability (related to chemical inertia) and enthalpy of reaction (Parilla, 2014). The presence of impurities in the hydrogen source can have a significant effect on the cyclic behaviour and, depending on the application, there may be specific requirements for the quality of the feed. It is also good if the substances used are non-toxic, easy to handle, cheap and readily available. For systems that require a liquid carrier (LOHC), ideally it will have a low melting point and a high boiling point so that it remains in a liquid state throughout the process without special precautions. Again, a low vapour pressure reduces storage safety issues and a low dynamic viscosity facilitates pumping. For systems operating below room temperature, an additional relevant parameter is dormancy: as the temperature inside the tank rises, the hydrogen pressure increases until it must be released to avoid exceeding the tank's resistance. The dormancy time is defined as the time interval before this release (boil-off point). However, it is important to remember that different technologies have different levels of technological maturity. In addition, different sectors have different requirements to be met. (Niermann et al., 2019); Tab. 1.4 provides a schematic view of the priority of properties for the mobility, energy transport and stationary applications sectors.

In the automotive sector, storage capacity and energy density are of great importance, as well as the ability to have a short start-up time and good dynamic behaviour; in this respect, the achievable hydrogen flow rate is an important parameter. At the same time, as these applications often involve the use of PEMs, the dehydrogenation temperature must be low. For energy transport, on the other hand, availability and simplicity are key design issues, with safety and handling being more relevant than energy density and storage capacity. Finally, the requirements for stationary applications are mostly focused on cost containment, i.e. stability for good life cycle behaviour, low reaction enthalpy and availability. The different objectives have been summarised by the DOE for a number of areas and defined on different timescales. A table summarising the state of the art in terms of achieving the target for gravimetric capacity for on-board application of storage systems in light-duty vehicles is given in Fig. 1.11. The accumulator density affects the investment cost: the volumetric one determines the size of the accumulator, while the gravimetric one defines the amount of material required. It can be seen that, despite the operating pressures, storage in the form of hydrogen gas is associated with the lowest values of energy density. On the other hand, the two chemical hydrides, ammonia and methanol, have the highest values, followed by the two elemental metal hydrides considered. Storage as liquid hydrogen comes next. A general trend is that the volumetric capacity increases in step with the gravimetric capacity, except for the AB₂ intermetallic hydrides. For metal hydrides, the values given are for individual pellets, so it is clear that stacking them in columns will reduce the actual storage densities. In general, the influence on the weight and volume of the required vessel has been neglected.

It is also possible to evaluate and compare the theoretical energy requirements for filling and emptying the system, which can then be related to the operating costs. The data are shown in Table 1.5. The data shown are obtained by neglecting hydrogen and heat losses during storage and pumping. For hydrogen liquefaction, the target of 6 kWh/kg of electricity has been considered as the electrical consumption. The estimated electrical consumption to bring the hydrogen to hydrogenation temperature was calculated assuming an isothermal

FIGURE 1.11: Gravimetric hydrogen capacity and working temperature requirements for different storage solutions compared to DOE targets.

efficiency of 70%. In addition to the quantities of heat to be supplied, the temperature at which it must be provided can also be estimated. For example, 13% of the heat required for MCH-TOL has to be supplied at about 101 °C and the rest at 350 °C; similarly, for methanol, 66% can be supplied at about 100 °C and the rest at 250 °C. For intermetallic hydrides, a generic hydride has been taken here for which low temperature heat can be used.

In conclusion, metal-chemical hydrides could provide a storage system with better energy density than liquid hydrogen, and with total operating costs that could be even lower in many cases, as the specific cost of the heat required is typically lower than that of electricity. Liquefaction and adsorption have the highest electricity consumption on record, but do not require additional expenditure to provide high temperature heat; intermetallic hydrides do not require large amounts of either high temperature heat or electricity, so the associated operating costs could be low. However, none of the systems considered require significant amounts of electricity at the time of release, which favours the possibility of coupling with hydrogen production systems for electrolysis powered by renewable energy. In this case, hydrogen would be produced when there is a surplus of produced energy (low electricity price) and released when the electricity price is high. Certainly, the possibility of recovering some of the heat of hydrogenation (hydrides, LOHC) could be attractive from an economic and energy point of view, for example by storing it for later use in dehydrogenation. However, large-scale application may not be feasible; even if a phase-change system is considered, the significant amount of material required and the complexity of the exchange system may make this option uneconomical. On the other hand, the use of the heat produced for other applications may be limited by the intermittent nature of flux availability. LOHCs are a promising technology for the future as they combine the advantages of liquid storage and close resemblance to conventional fuels with similar operating physics to MHs, opening up the possibility of extending existing infrastructure. As with hydrides, the amounts of energy required to release hydrogen are significant (e.g. 68 kJ/mol_{H₂} for DBT, about 28% of the LHV of hydrogen!) and the temperature at which it must be provided can also exceed 300 °C. The enthalpy of reaction depends on the chemical nature of the carrier, and a more detailed analysis is given in chapter 2.

1.2.4 Applications

One of the main strengths of hydrogen is its versatility, which lends itself to multiple end uses both as a feedstock and as an energy carrier; hydrogen will be able to play a key role in the energy transition and decarbonisation process. As a raw material, it is used in both the chemical and metallurgical industries, but it is also required for the production of ammonia, and thus fertilisers, and methanol, and thus polymers (Ramachandran and Menon, 1998).

As seen in the previous sections, about 55% of the hydrogen produced worldwide is used in the synthesis of ammonia; 25%, on the other hand, goes to refineries, e.g. to process

Technology	Storage			Release		
	Heat (kWh/kg _{H₂})	Temperature (°C)	Pressure (bar)	Electricity (kWh/kg _{H₂})	Heat (kWh/kg _{H₂})	Temperature (°C)
Gas (100 bar)	-	-	100	1.0	-	-
Gas (200 bar)	-	-	200	1.2	-	-
Gas (700 bar)	-	-	700	1.6	-	-
Liquid H ₂	-	-253.15	-	6.0	-	-
Adosorption	-	-176	40	6.7	-	-
AlH ₃	54	<70	-	10.0	1.0	100
MgH ₂	-	300	30	0.7	10.3	350
Intermetallic MH	-	<80	50	0.8	2-6	<80
NaAlH ₄	-	125	100	1.0	5.7	160
LiBH ₄ - MgH ₂	-	350	50	0.8	6.4	350
2 Li(NH ₂) - MgH ₂	-	150	70	0.9	5.6	150
Methanol	-	250	50	1.3	6.7	250
Ammonia	-	400	250	2-4	4.2	>425
Formic Acid	64	100-180	105	6.7	4.3	<100
MCH-TOL	-	150	30	0.7	11.2	350
DBT-PDBT	-	150	30	0.7	9.0	300
NEC-DNEC	-	150	30	0.7	7.6	220

TABLE 1.5: Storage and release phases costs and working conditions for different hydrogen storage solutions.

intermediate oil products; the remainder is roughly equally divided between methanol production and all other uses. In general, most of the hydrogen produced is for in-situ refining, which does not require a large transport infrastructure. The remaining hydrogen is called commercial hydrogen and is transported and used off-site (IEA, 2022).

Ammonia is produced by the Haber-Bosch process in which nitrogen and hydrogen, generally from air separation units or SMR processes, are reacted in the presence of a metal catalyst under specific pressure and temperature conditions (150-250 bar and 400-500 °C) to synthesise NH_3 (Ghavam et al., 2021). The gas mixture typically passes through more than four catalytic beds and is cooled at each stage. Each one is characterised by the conversion of about 15 % of the gas mixture into ammonia, which is later removed in the liquid state. About 90 % of the ammonia produced is converted into solid salts or, after catalytic oxidation, into nitric acid and nitrates for use in fertiliser production. The high energy required for evaporation means that ammonia can also be used as a refrigerant, known by the nomenclature R-717.

Moreover, hydrogen can be utilized to produce green ammonia, a variant of the traditional Haber-Bosch process, where hydrogen is obtained via water electrolysis powered by renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind. This method drastically reduces carbon emissions compared to conventional ammonia production, which heavily relies on natural gas reforming. Advanced reactors and innovative catalysts are being developed to operate the process at lower temperatures and pressures (e.g., 100 bar and 350 °C), which could further enhance the energy efficiency of ammonia synthesis.

Ammonia is increasingly viewed as a hydrogen carrier and fuel for decarbonized energy systems, thanks to its high hydrogen content and compatibility with existing fuel infrastructure. It can be stored and transported more easily than hydrogen due to its higher energy density and liquid form at moderate pressures. Combustion of ammonia, however, has unique challenges: it has a lower flame speed and energy density, requiring enhanced designs to maintain stability and efficiency (Bedick, 2023). For instance, researchers suggest blending ammonia with hydrogen to improve flame stability and speed in combustion processes. Additionally, ammonia cracking (decomposition into hydrogen and nitrogen) can also enhance combustion properties and reduce NO_x emissions, which are a primary environmental concern during ammonia combustion (Yousefi Rizi and Shin, 2022). Research has demonstrated the potential of cracking ammonia back into hydrogen through catalytic decomposition using materials such as ruthenium or nickel on alumina supports, achieving conversion efficiencies above 90 % under optimal conditions (Yousefi Rizi and Shin, 2022).

Furthermore, ammonia combustion technologies are being developed for use in gas turbines and as a fuel in hybrid systems, with particular focus on mitigating NO_x emissions via selective catalytic reduction (SCR) or advanced combustion control strategies. These advancements position ammonia as a key player in achieving large-scale hydrogen deployment in hard-to-decarbonize sectors, including shipping and power generation (Ryu, Duong, and Kang, 2023). Techniques such as air staging (introducing secondary air injection at different points in combustion) and two-stage combustor concepts are under exploration to further optimize ammonia combustion efficiency and reduce emissions. For instance, using a rich-stage and lean-stage approach in gas turbines can increase hydrogen yield while minimizing NO_x formation, making ammonia a cleaner synthetic fuel option.

Methanol, another hydrogen-derived fuel, offers a liquid alternative with existing distribution channels that make it suitable for fuel cells and internal combustion engines. Methanol production uses the catalytic hydrogenation of carbon monoxide in a fixed bed catalysed by alumina pellets coated with copper and zinc oxides (Dalena et al., 2018). This process is key to producing low-carbon methanol, and when combined with carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies, it provides a pathway to sustainable methanol production. Indeed, in recent years, the possibility of using a direct reaction between hydrogen and carbon dioxide as an application of CCS has been investigated, but the reaction is not yet thermodynamically efficient and the search for an optimal catalyst is still open. Methanol can be used directly as a fuel in internal combustion engines, as a feedstock for fuel cells, for the production of fuel additives, or for the transesterification (conversion of one ester into another ester by reaction with an alcohol) of vegetable oils to biodiesel (Nichols, 2003). The methanol-to-hydrocarbon (MTH) process further expands methanol's potential as a feedstock to produce hydrocarbons for synthetic fuels. This flexibility allows methanol to act as a bridge fuel,

serving both transport energy needs and broader chemical production, including plastics and other materials. Methanol's higher volumetric energy density compared to hydrogen or ammonia makes it an ideal candidate for long-haul transport applications where energy density and ease of storage are crucial.

Hydrogen is a versatile feedstock for producing various synthetic fuels beyond methanol and ammonia, offering potential solutions for decarbonizing hard-to-abate sectors:

- Fischer-Tropsch Hydrocarbons: Hydrogen reacts with carbon monoxide (CO) in the Fischer-Tropsch process to produce synthetic hydrocarbons such as diesel, gasoline, and sustainable aviation fuels (SAF). This technology is already implemented at industrial scales and can integrate green hydrogen for low-carbon outputs (Dry, 2002).
- Dimethyl Ether (DME): DME, derived from methanol or directly from hydrogen and CO₂, serves as a clean alternative to liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and a soot-free diesel substitute. Its high cetane number makes it particularly suitable for heavy-duty vehicles (Semelsberger, Borup, and Greene, 2006).
- Synthetic Natural Gas (SNG): Hydrogen and CO₂ can undergo methanation to produce SNG, a renewable alternative to fossil-derived natural gas, compatible with existing gas distribution and storage infrastructure (Rönsch et al., 2015).
- Formic Acid: Formic acid can be synthesized from hydrogen and CO₂, providing a liquid hydrogen carrier with high energy density and safer handling than gaseous hydrogen (Yang, Y., and Y., 2024).
- Aromatic Hydrocarbons (BTX): Hydrogen can help synthesize aromatic compounds such as benzene, toluene, and xylene, used as chemical feedstocks or fuel additives. This offers pathways to replace fossil-derived sources with sustainable alternatives (Zhang et al., 2016).

Each of these fuels expands the application of hydrogen, leveraging its chemical flexibility and enabling decarbonization in sectors like heavy transport, aviation, and chemical manufacturing.

Another hydrogen application in the chemical industry is the production of hydrochloric acid (Chuang and Bozzelli, 1986). In the presence of UV light, hydrogen and chlorine can react to form HCl, but this is a highly exothermic reaction that is rarely used commercially.

A promising future application is the direct reduction of iron for oxygen separation with an estimated yield of 90-98% (Li et al., 2021). This process is currently carried out in furnaces fired by coal or at most natural gas, while the use of hydrogen has only been established on a pilot scale (Bhaskar, Assadi, and Nikpey Somehsaraei, 2020). Hydrogen is then used commercially to extract tungsten from various minerals (wolframite, scheelite, ferberite) and is also suitable for the extraction of copper. (Xiao et al., 2022; Kekesi, Mimura, and Isshiki, 1995) It could also theoretically be used as a reducing agent in the production of precious metals such as silver, gold and platinum, but there are currently no commercial applications. In refineries, hydrogen is commonly used to remove impurities such as sulphur compounds from natural gas and petroleum liquid cuts through hydrodesulphurisation processes, but also in crude oil processing (Ramachandran and Menon, 1998). In hydrocracking, the molecules of the heavier compounds are broken down into smaller molecules, again with the aid of a catalyst. Particularly in recent years, the use of hydrogen has increased due to stricter regulations on the amount of sulphides in diesel fuel, greater demand for heavy oil cuts (which therefore require more hydrogen) and the boom in oil consumption by economies such as China and India (Alves and Towler, 2002).

In the food industry, hydrogen can be used to convert unsaturated fats into oils and saturated fats in the production of hydrogenated vegetable oils and fats such as butter and margarine (Veldsink et al., 1997). An oil such as seed or sunflower oil is fed into a heated batch reactor in which a vacuum has been created to prevent oxidation. The temperature is raised to 140-250 °C and the homogeneity of the reactor is ensured by means of a stirrer. At this point, solid nickel catalysts mixed with small quantities of oil, followed by hydrogen gas, are pumped into the reactor. As the exothermic reaction proceeds, the heat must be removed from the product; after about an hour the mixture is removed as a slurry and the catalysts are filtered and removed. The vegetable oil is then allowed to solidify.

Simply burning hydrogen is generally not the best way to use resources for energy production. Some of the critical issues (Levinsky, 2021) that arise are related to the following properties:

- High flame temperature and thus high production of thermal NO_x and significant stress on the materials involved.
- High flame propagation speed, leading to the risk of unstable flames.
- Difficulty of compression: in addition to the high specific work required, the low molecular weight facilitates losses through the machine stages.
- Complexity of large-scale storage.
- Low ignition point and consequent danger.

On the other hand, hydrogen can be used to power a fuel cell: an electrochemical device capable of converting the chemical energy of a fuel into electrical energy, but unlike batteries, the reaction does not run out and can provide energy continuously as long as the reagents flow to the electrodes. Since there is no need to establish a thermal cycle, the conversion yields can therefore be higher (60 % even for small sizes, Eq. 1.9) compared to those of thermal machines, which are limited by the Carnot efficiency (Stambouli and Traversa, 2002).

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta G^0}{\Delta H^0} \quad (1.9)$$

If the cell is fuelled with hydrogen, the only reaction products are water and heat; if the hydrogen is green, it is a clean energy conversion. In their simplest form, fuel cells consist of two electrodes (anode and cathode) separated by an electrolyte. FCs are classified on the basis of the electrolyte and the fuel: in theory, any substance that can be chemically oxidised and is in a liquid state can be used to power the anode of a cell, just as any oxidising fluid that can be reduced can power the cathode (energy.gov, 2022b). However, in the case of hydrogen, in addition to the environmental benefits, high anodic reactivity can be expected. One of the most critical aspects of FCs is the three-phase interface where the reactions take place, at the meeting of the electrodes and the electrolyte (Weber et al., 2010). For a site to be active, it must be exposed to reagents and be in electrical contact with the electrode and in ionic contact with the electrolyte; the presence of a catalyst is also required. In liquid electrolyte FCs, the reactant gases diffuse through a thin electrolyte film that wets parts of the porous electrodes; from exposure to the electrolyte they risk finding themselves in flooding conditions, whereby the transport of gaseous species is inhibited with it the electrochemical performance. In solid electrolyte cells, the complexity lies in the design of sufficient catalytic sites at the three-phase interface; this requires electrodes that have the ability to conduct both electrons and ions in close proximity to the catalyst. Research to improve the performance of these devices in recent years has therefore focused on reducing the thickness of the electrolyte (Park and Barnett, 2020), as well as on the design of materials for the electrolyte itself and the electrodes, which also allows the operating temperature range to be extended (Energy, 2009). The role of the electrolyte is not only to transport the dissolved reagents to the electrode and close the electrical circuit, but also to act as a barrier to direct mixing of oxidant and fuel, and as such is one of the most critical design issues (Bernadet et al., 2023).

Reactions taking place at the anode and cathode, respectively, are reported below:

The main types of FC available are:

- Polymer electrolyte fuel cell: the electrolyte is a proton exchange polymer membrane (Gottesfeld and Zawodzinski, 1997). The only liquid in these cells is water, which reduces corrosion problems but makes management critical. The FC must operate under conditions that prevent the water produced from evaporating faster than it is

produced, to keep the membrane hydrated. This means that typical operating temperatures are around 60-80 °C. The electrodes are typically coupled to platinum catalysts and the purity of the fuel must be very high to avoid poisoning the anode. The electrolyte separates the gases effectively and the low temperatures shorten the ignition times; the nature of the environment, which is not particularly corrosive, means that particularly expensive materials are not required for the components. They are the most interesting category of cells for the application of hydrogen as a fuel, except for storage solutions with high endothermic release such as LOHCs.

- Alkaline fuel cell: The electrolyte consists of 85 %_m or 30-50 %_m KOH depending on the temperature range (≈ 250 °C or < 120 °C); catalysts can be of various types (Ni, Ag, metal oxides, noble metals) and high purity of the reagent is required to avoid reaction with KOH. (Ferriday and Middleton, 2021). The main application is in combination with high purity hydrogen, and since even the smallest amount of carbon dioxide is particularly harmful, the same oxygen would be best supplied as pure oxygen. The main applications are related to the space field.
- Phosphoric acid fuel cell: the electrolyte is 100 % phosphoric acid for temperatures between 150-220 °C. (Sammes, Bove, and Stahl, 2004); at lower temperatures phosphoric acid has poor ionic conduction properties and the risk of poisoning the Pt catalyst by CO increases. On the other hand, phosphoric acid has good stability and, as a concentrated acid, water management is much easier as vapour pressures are much lower. In recent years, interest in these FCs has waned in favour of PEFC, which is expected to be more economically viable, although less sensitive to CO.
- Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell: The electrolyte is a combination of alkaline carbonates held in a LiAlO₂ ceramic matrix and the operating temperature is between 600-700 °C to allow the carbonates to form molten salts with high conductivity (Dicks, 2004). At these temperatures it is possible to use a catalyst such as Ni and its oxides and, by avoiding the presence of a noble metal catalyst, it is possible to feed hydrocarbons subject to internal reforming directly as fuel. The interest is linked to large stationary and naval applications where the overall size and weight of the system and the long start-up times are not a problem. The high temperatures lend themselves well to integration with a bottoming cycle to increase efficiency. On the other hand, the operating conditions affect the stability of the materials and increase corrosion problems.
- Solid Oxide Fuel Cell: The electrolyte is a solid non-porous metal oxide, generally yttria-stabilised zirconia, operating at 650-1000 °C to have good conductivity of oxygen ions (Dokiya, 2002). The anode can generally be a Co-ZrO₂ or Ni-ZrO₂ cermet with a Sr doped LaMnO₃ cathode. Current research is focusing on the possibility of further reducing the operating temperatures, for example by reducing the thickness of the electrolyte; however, high temperatures lend themselves to heat recovery in bottoming cycles. However, there are problems associated with the different thermal expansions of the materials used, the limited choice of materials and their complex manufacture. As the electrolyte is in a solid state, it is possible to produce cells with different geometries, and corrosion problems are limited, as is the problem of flooding. The kinetics are fast and the problems of poisoning are almost non-existent; on the contrary, the risk of corrosion of the metal elements is significant. These cells are the most promising for coupling LOHC subsystems as they provide sufficient high temperature waste heat (Peters et al., 2019).

However, in the field of mobility, hydrogen could be used not only in direct applications (in FC if not in combustion engines), but also in indirect applications in Power to X applications. The potential applications cover different levels of technological readiness: aviation, marine, rail, material handling vehicles and urban transport such as buses and cars. However, FCs could also be used for stationary applications, for example as back-up units such as emergency generators and UPS (uninterruptible power supply) (Xu et al., 2013). As heat is also produced by the reaction, these units are also suitable for combined heat and power (CHP) applications; possible domestic applications are therefore micro or mini CHP (Notter

et al., 2015). First principle efficiencies can be up to 95 % with electrical efficiencies up to 45 %, no local emissions and low maintenance costs.

Further applications concern:

- Atomic hydrogen welding: an arc welding process that can be used to weld refractory metals by placing two tungsten electrodes in a hydrogen atmosphere (Suban, Tušek, and Uran, 2001).
- Production of alloys such as manganese compounds (Features, 2023).
- Cooling: for example, for the rotors of large electrical generators (Balitskii, Krohmalny, and Ripey, 2000), which are kept at pressures of around 4 bar. Compared to air, it has the advantages of high thermal conductivity and specific heat, low density (about 10 % of air, and less wind loss due to less resistance to rotor motion), and less tendency to reduce the electrical resistance of the bushings.
- To check for leaks: in production plants after replacing environmentally harmful CClF₃-based gases.
- Hydrogen peroxide production: a powerful oxidising and sterilising agent in common use; typically produced in large quantities by multi-stage, energy-intensive processes from the catalysed reaction of atmospheric hydrogen and oxygen in the presence of an aromatic carrier (anthraquinone, Q). Research is underway in the UK into the possibility of introducing a simpler, single-step process. As a reducing agent in the manufacture of glass plates to prevent the formation of oxides (Hou, Zeng, and Zhang, 2020).
- For chemical analysis: for example, in atomic absorption spectroscopy as a fuel to generate heat and produce neutral atoms at the same time. Another example is related to chromatography, for the separation of volatile substances.
- For weather balloons: being light, it is suitable for transporting meteorological instruments to high altitudes to collect data on air pressure, temperature and humidity (Hunt et al., 2023).

Chapter 2

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: A Theoretical View

2.1 Working Principles

The history of LOHCs begins in the early 1980s, when Taube et al. proposed a methylcyclohexane-based vehicle and first explored the concept of liquid organic hydrides as hydrogen carriers (Taube et al., 1983). The first fluids to be considered were systems of simple cycloalkanes: in a manner not unlike metal hydrides, it is indeed possible to use organic liquids for hydrogen storage (Gambini et al., 2022). The advantages proposed were low cost and full compatibility with transport infrastructures. In this case, absorption and release occur through progressive cyclic saturation and desaturation of the carbon-carbon bonds in the molecule, with heat release during the absorption phase and the need to provide heat for release. Particularly advantageous is the possibility of having chemically bound hydrogen in ambient conditions, without the need to maintain high pressures or advanced insulation systems (enterprises, 2024).

The main compounds on which research has focused today are: methylcyclohexane and toluene (MCH-TOL), dibenzyltoluene and per-hydro-dibenzyltoluene (DBT-PDBT), N-ethylcarbazole and dodecahydro-N-ethylcarbazole (NEC-DNEC), N-ethylcarbazole and per-hydro-N-ethylcarbazole (NEC-H12-NEC) (Bourane et al., 2016). Each of these compounds is aromatic in the dehydrogenated form; the dehydrogenation of cyclic hydrocarbons to produce unsaturated or aromatic compounds is a consolidated practice in the petroleum industry. The catalysts used are usually platinum, but can also be ruthenium, palladium or rhodium.

The LOHC system consists of pairs of hydrogen-lean and hydrogen-rich organic molecules with reversible storage and release of H₂ via repeated catalytic cycles. While some authors also consider compounds such as formic acid or ammonia (Niermann et al., 2019), whose dehydrogenation products are gas mixtures (H₂ and CO₂ or N₂) requiring more complex purification processes, most authors use the term to refer only to high boiling point compounds. This distinction means that the isolation of hydrogen gas from the dehydrogenation product stream could be achieved by condensation (Zheng et al., 2020). In addition, due to their chemical nature, they are highly compatible with existing industrial equipment such as barges, tankers and rail wagons, further reducing both the cost and time requirements of the overall storage system. The main characteristics required are therefore: a wide range of temperatures at which they are liquid (high evaporation point and low condensation point), reversible thermodynamics, fast and selective kinetics, and favourable toxicity and eco-toxicity properties (Niermann et al., 2019). Other relevant parameters are the strength and density of these bonds, the stability of the compounds subjected to cyclic behaviour, the guaranteed hydrogen flow (index of the dynamic behaviour of the system) and the synthesis cost.

- Storage: The practical implementation of LOHC technology depends on the characteristic energy density of the systems. Overall, from worst to best, the gravimetric and volumetric hydrogen densities are 0.3-12.1 %_m and 0.1-3.3 kWh/L.
- Availability: this property is highly dependent on the price and availability of the raw material, which is of paramount importance for large-scale applications. While formic

acid could be synthesised from CO₂, which is both abundant and potentially cheap, other materials such as N-ethylcarbazole have limited availability and high prices.

- De-hydrogenation temperature: ranges from 50-450 K and is the main parameter used to define the reaction kinetics, with the lower end of the range being reached by formic acid via separation into hydrogen and CO₂ using homogeneous catalysts, while the upper end is associated with toluene-based systems. The temperature can be reduced, but usually at the cost of longer reaction times or increased dilution.
- Energy Demand: the hydrogenation reaction, being exothermic, takes place at lower temperature levels and cannot be integrated with the release reactor to support the dehydrogenation. Therefore, a high reaction heat could effectively reduce the storage efficiency.
- Toxicity: while none of the major candidate LOHCs have a Toxicity Potential Indicator (TPI) of zero¹, many have a lower toxicity than diesel fuel (such as NEC). However, this is not the case for all LOHCs, as many others have similar or greater toxicity than diesel fuel, such as toluene and DBT. For the latter, health and safety assessments are available because it is a common heat transfer fluid: it is classified as a low-risk chemical with symbols N, dangerous for the environment, and Xi, irritant; its flammability is low (Brückner et al., 2014). Some others are still poorly characterised; in general, hydrogenated forms of LOHCs are often less known than their dehydrogenated counterparts (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018). For potential heterocyclic LOHCs, the toxicity of 2-methylquinoline and its hydrogenated forms was found to be comparable to that of diesel fuel, while the toxicity of the partially hydrogenated form was similar to that of gasoline (Markiewicz et al., 2015). Potential bioaccumulation concerns have been raised for the H8-NEC, and the NEC pair does not appear to be biodegradable (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018), although others have claimed that nitrogen-containing organic molecules have better biodegradability than alicyclic compounds (Crabtree, 2017), with aromatics typically degrading more readily than cycloalkanes and paraffins more readily than olefins.
- Material handling: this parameter depends on the toxicity, as it depends on the number and type of precautions needed based on the guidelines for working with chemicals to store and transport the LOHC. However, handling is also characterised by the physical properties of the LOHC, which ideally include a low melting point and a high boiling point in order to be in a liquid state during all operations, as well as a low vapour pressure for low storage safety requirements and a low dynamic viscosity for easy pumping.
- Process design: depending on the substrate, different components may be required. The simplest designs consist of a hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactor. Depending on the temperature level and vapour pressures, a further condensation step may be required to separate hydrogen from the LOHC vapours. Downstream purification is required for systems such as toluene-methylcyclohexane due to the low boiling point of these compounds. While the simplest separation process would be condensation at ambient conditions, additional measures such as pressure swing adsorption or membrane separation may be required. In addition, solvents with a higher ignition temperature or flash point could be introduced and then removed.
- Stability: cyclic behaviour in terms of catalytic activity and thermal stability is required to reduce the amount of carrier to be replenished.
- Gas flow: this parameter depends on both the kinetic speed of the reaction and the energy density of the support. In addition, this parameter is affected by the introduction of solvents, dehydrogenation restrictions, or both, to allow operation in the liquid state or for safety reasons, and by fast release times.
- Technical readiness: interest in LOHC technologies has increased significantly in recent years, and several applications are being tested. However, experience with LOHC

¹The value zero is used to indicate substances with no known hazard.

systems is still mostly limited to laboratory scale (TRL 3). New supports and catalysts are being tested, but more advanced studies rely mainly on either MCH, DBT or NEC.

On average, saturation requires temperatures in the order of 130-200 °C and pressures of 10-50 bar (Wan et al., 2012). The typical temperatures required for release are even higher (DBT is around 350 °C (Peters et al., 2019)) due to the stability of the compounds. In the case of DNEC, lower values (160-200 °C (Kiermaier et al., 2021)) are achievable due to the destabilising effect of a nitrogen atom in the structure, which reduces both the reaction enthalpy (50-55 kJ/mol_{H₂} or 25-30 % lower than that required for pure hydrocarbon systems) and the temperature required, depending on the position of the nitrogen atom in the ring or ring system. However, all these compounds have a relatively high ΔH_r (68 kJ/mol_{H₂} for release from methylcyclohexane, 65 kJ/mol_{H₂} for release from dibenzyltoluene). Consequently, the release of hydrogen requires the supply of large quantities of heat at high temperatures, sometimes even above 300 °C, so the possibility of integrating heat recovery from the subsequent use step is only possible if the application reference works at high temperatures (SOFC, turbines, combustion engines). To evaluate the amount of hydrogen stored or released, the degree of hydrogenation is defined as in Eq. 2.1, which generally takes into account the amount of hydrogen bound to the LOHC compared to the maximum amount that can be stored.

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{n_{\text{H}_2}}{n_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}}} \quad (2.1)$$

As such hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions can be studied in terms of DoH considering its evolution over time (Eq. 2.2) with respect to the reacting moles of hydrogen ($n_{\text{H}_2, r}$).

$$\text{DoH}(t) = \text{DoH}(t_0) + \frac{\int_{t_0}^t \dot{n}_{\text{H}_2, r} dt}{n_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}}} \quad (2.2)$$

As an example, the definition of DoH for NEC systems is shown. In these systems, the completely hydrogen-free form is N-ethylcarbazole (0 H-NEC) while dodecahydro-N-ethylcarbazole (12 H-NEC) is the completely hydrogenated form; intermediate products are tetrahydro-N-ethylcarbazole (4 H-NEC) and octahydro-N-ethylcarbazole (8 H-NEC):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DoH} &= \frac{2n_{4\text{H-NEC}} + 4n_{8\text{H-NEC}} + 6n_{12\text{H-NEC}}}{6(n_{0\text{H-NEC}} + n_{4\text{H-NEC}} + n_{8\text{H-NEC}} + n_{12\text{H-NEC}})} = \dots \\ \dots &= \frac{\chi_{4\text{H-NEC}} + 2\chi_{8\text{H-NEC}} + 3\chi_{12\text{H-NEC}}}{3} \end{aligned}$$

having introduced the molar fractions $\chi_{i\text{H-NEC}}$, based on the total moles number n_{NEC} disregarding the amount of hydrogen dissolved in the solution, and any by-products so that it defines the molar fraction of each species in the liquid phase.

If in reality the reaction proceeds in several steps and through the formation of different intermediates, it may be possible to refer to an equivalent mixture for the simulation of the sorption and release processes, i.e. consisting only of the fully hydrogenated and/or hydrogen-free form (Peters et al., 2019). For example, referring to the 0 H-DBT-18 H-DBT couple, even neglecting the presence of species with partially hydrogenated rings, up to six different DBT species can be formed and the release process can follow four different pathways (Shi et al., 2023). The different pathways are due to the dehydrogenation sequence proceeding with either a side-middle-side, mid-side-middle, side-middle-middle or no statistical ring order. However, without going into the merits of the specific chemical equations, it is possible to reproduce the behaviour of these systems with excellent accuracy by referring to equivalent mixtures of only 0 H-DBT and 18 H-DBT, i.e. the fully saturated and unsaturated compounds. A more detailed description of the existing simplification is given in Fig. 2.1, where the overall reaction is divided into three main steps (Yang et al., 2014).

Interestingly, the authors have discovered that 4H-NEC is kinetically stable over the supported Rh catalyst, so much so that it becomes the dominant component in the final product distribution even after 5 h reaction time, effectively becoming the bottleneck of the reaction as this is its rate limiting step. In hydrogenation reactors, the first step is the solvation of hydrogen in the liquid carrier, followed by hydrogen transport to the solid surface of the

FIGURE 2.1: Step-by-step and equivalent reaction pathways for NEC.

catalyst. Only then does the reaction take place. Mass transfer is also thought to play an important role at high temperatures (Eblagon et al., 2010; Gambini et al., 2022), as the kinetics are hindered once a threshold is reached.

2.1.1 Candidates

The most studied pair initially is the toluene/methylcyclohexane system, despite being in gaseous form due to the dehydrogenation temperature of about 100 °C. (Modisha et al., 2019). Toluene is the simplest aromatic that could be used, benzene is a carcinogen, and possible storage capacities are 6.1 %_m, although the volumetric capacity is limited by the density of the MCH. However, the enthalpy of reaction is relatively high, so quite high dehydrogenation temperatures are required to shift the equilibrium to the product side; these properties make the system less suitable for dynamic and flexible applications, so the main interest is in the area of large-scale transport and storage (Niermann et al., 2019). The toxicity properties are not optimal, but currently large quantities of these compounds are already being handled in conventional fuels. For cyclohexane in particular, it has been shown that the release of hydrogen can occur by two different mechanisms (He, Pei, and Chen, 2015):

- Sextet: direct dehydrogenation to benzene occurs when cyclohexane is superimposed on the catalyst.
- Doublet: progressive release of hydrogen if adsorption on the surface of the catalyst occurs laterally via the double bond between carbon.

The main advantage of using cycloalkanes is the relatively high hydrogen capacity, which can be greater than 7 %_m with decalin (He, Pei, and Chen, 2015).

Having been studied for a long time, this couple is well characterised. For example, the equilibrium conversion of MCH as a function of temperature for different pressures is considered archetypal for many pure hydrocarbon LOHC systems. The lower the pressure, the lower the temperature at which MCH is completely converted to toluene. Therefore, from a thermodynamic point of view, the lowest possible system pressure should be chosen for dehydrogenation. However, this is not always beneficial for the catalyst and can favour side reactions and catalyst deactivation (Modisha et al., 2019).

High temperatures and the use of a metal catalyst usually lead to side reactions with coke formation. For similar equilibrium conversions, the dehydrogenation temperature is lower for the alkyl-substituted cycles. Among the polycyclic alkanes, decalin is the only compound that is liquid at ambient conditions. However, all the other compounds are solid at ambient conditions, as are their dehydrogenation products, including naphthalene derived from decalin. Consequently, solvents must be used to obtain liquid solutions of these compounds,

with the disadvantage of reducing the total hydrogen content of the molecule. Pez et al. (Pez et al., 2008) have proposed mixtures of two or more components that can form a eutectic melt at a lower temperature, while more traditional routes rely on toluene. The introduction of substituents such as *n*-alkyl, alkoxy or ether groups to the ring structure of the polycyclic molecule is also mentioned as a way of lowering their melting point, but again at some cost in 'dead weight', which reduces the releasable hydrogen content.

Another interesting pair is indeed the naphthalene/decaline pair, with the possibility of storage up to 7.3%_m, in fact polycyclic aromatic compounds typically have a high gravimetric capacity. However, naphthalene, which is one of the simplest compounds, is solid at room temperature with a melting temperature of 80 °C, so other strategies (limiting the degree of dehydrogenation or forming mixtures with other LOHCs or solvents) must be implemented at the expense of storage capacity. The high storage capacity may make the system interesting for large-scale applications where toxicity properties would not be a problem, as dedicated infrastructure and qualified personnel can be relied upon (Niermann et al., 2019). However, the dehydrogenation step is highly irreversible with negative effects on the LOHC cycle, requiring a new batch of material for each cycle. Apart from the advantage of high hydrogen storage density, these challenges make the molecule unsuitable for hydrogen storage and transport (Modisha et al., 2019). In an effort to develop a suitable catalyst and optimise the process of decalin dehydrogenation, microwave and electrical heating mechanisms are being studied (Suttisawat et al., 2012). In fact, in spite of the good toxicity properties and the already established production cycles, cycloalkanes have unfavourable thermodynamic properties that require operating temperatures above 300 °C, and most catalysts require the addition of alkali or alkaline earth metal promoters to overcome coking processes (He, Pei, and Chen, 2015). Nevertheless, they are still major candidates for large scale and long distance supply due to low prices and abundance of the promoter.

The use of commercial heat transfer oils such as dibenzyltoluene and perhydro-dibenzyltoluene, benzyltoluene and perhydro-benzyl-toluene or the Marlotherm SH and Marlotherm LH pairs has recently been proposed (Fikrt et al., 2017; Preuster, Alekseev, and Wasserscheid, 2017). This approach has a number of advantages, such as the possibility of using fluids that are well characterised in terms of their physico-chemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological properties. These are substances optimised for low melting points and good thermal stability.

For both pairs, a capacity of 6.2%_m can be obtained, with a reaction enthalpy of around 65 kJ/mol_{H₂} and a density such that it can have a volumetric storage capacity 20% greater than systems based on toluene, with which it also boasts the absence of toxicological contraindications. Hydrogenation can be carried out at temperatures and pressures between 80-180 °C and 20-50 bar in the presence of a Ru catalyst. The release of hydrogen is promoted by Pt/alumina catalysts at temperatures above 260 °C, but for long term applications it is important to remain below 330 °C to avoid marked decomposition of the catalyst and the formation of by-products which should be removed by distillation processes.

Regardless, DBT is mainly proposed as mixtures of isomeric DBT since they were first suggested as promising LOHCs for stationary applications by Brückner in 2014 (Brückner et al., 2014). DBT can be hydrogenated to H18-DBT with Pt group metals around 140 °C, and the reverse process can be carried out at 270-320 °C. (Shi et al., 2019). The DBT/H18-DBT system has several advantages for LOHC applications, including high hydrogen storage capacity (6.2%_m), low toxicity and thermal stability. In addition, hydrogenation of DBT using hydrogen-containing gas mixtures containing CO₂ and CO is possible (Dürr et al., 2017a; Jorschick et al., 2018) with suitable catalysts. This prospect is attractive for large scale applications as it fits seamlessly with industrial processes that produce hydrogen containing gas mixtures. As explained above, significant amounts of heat are required for release at times of low energy availability, and this is considered by several authors to be the main drawback of LOHCs. In addition, there is evidence that materials with higher enthalpies of hydrogenation generally require higher temperatures to dehydrogenate, and those with lower enthalpies may no longer be able to be hydrogenated. Research has therefore focused on identifying additional compounds with reduced ΔH_r requirements, such as carbazole.

Researchers have gone so far as to investigate the influence of the N content of the cyclohexane atom in terms of the influence of nitrogen placement on the dehydrogenation temperature (Clot, Eisenstein, and Crabtree, 2007). This contribution appears to be greater

for five-membered rings than for six-membered rings. While these compounds typically have significantly lower thermal stability and technical availability, it has been shown that the presence of heteroatoms such as N and B can reduce the temperature and energy required for the release of hydrogen, as first proposed in some key patents proposed by Pez (He, Pei, and Chen, 2015; Pez et al., 2006). In this respect, heterocyclic compounds such as 12H-NEC and pyrroles, compounds of the C₄H₅NH type, are of interest. In this case, the nitrogen atom has no double bonds, so the release of hydrogen atoms from the same molecule is easier, since it weakens the strength of the bonds: dehydrogenation starts from the five-membered ring due to the weakening of the axial C–H bonds adjacent to the nitrogen atom, producing 8H-NEC as the main reaction intermediate in systems with Pt or Pd catalyst. The fact that the aromatic rings are fully coupled also contributes to this effect and further favours release; fully paired adjacent rings share a double bond and therefore the dehydrogenation of one ring determines an asymmetry in the adjacent one, thus favouring its dehydrogenation.

It appears that the most effective catalysts are Ru or Rh, which are still expensive; in particular, rhodium-based catalysts are preferred because ruthenium has been shown to have a low selectivity for the accumulation of 8H-NEC as a kinetically stable intermediate. The support is an important factor in the activity and stability of a heterogeneous catalyst (He, Pei, and Chen, 2015). Recently it has been reported that noble metals on basic supports (PVPy or MgO (Fang, Machalaba, and Sánchez-Delgado, 2011; Rahi et al., 2012; Fang and Sánchez-Delgado, 2014)) catalyse the hydrogenation of N-heterocycles much faster than on acidic supports (SiO₂ or Al₂O₃). In the hydrogenation of quinoline, the same authors showed that the reaction rate increased monotonically with the basicity of the support and, due to the polarity of the C=N bond in N-heterocycles, a catalytic mechanism involving heterolytic hydrogen splitting and ionic hydrogenation at the metal/basic support interface was proposed (Fang, Machalaba, and Sánchez-Delgado, 2011; Rahi et al., 2012). However, the properties of some NECs, such as 12H-NEC, are still poorly understood because they have no industrial applications and, moreover, work with a mixture of isomers whose composition depends on the type of catalyst and the synthesis conditions.

Other problematic aspects associated with these LOHCs, identified by NEC as the main representative, are (Niermann et al., 2019):

- Current availability of NEC, limited to about 10 000 Mg/y and isolated by tar distillation from coal, with variable quality and high cost of about 40 €/kg.
- NEC is pure in the solid state for temperatures below 68 °C, so either the degree of dehydrogenation and therefore the storage capacity must be limited or a heating system is required.
- NEC does not have good thermal stability, so at temperatures above 270 °C, even in well-catalysed systems, dealkylation reactions are present. In addition, some side reactions such as C-N cleavage, disproportionation and alkyl transfer etc. also occur during dehydrogenation and hydrogenation (Dean, Davis, and Jessop, 2011).
- In addition, the toxicity and ecotoxicity properties of the two compounds have not yet been well studied; several compounds and intermediates typical of the storage cycle have shown variable behaviour in persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity tests.

Nevertheless, it could be interesting for small-scale applications where the price of the carrier and the limited storage capacity would not be too detrimental (Niermann et al., 2019). Despite its various interesting properties, it is a toxic compound with low biodegradability, less available and more expensive than DBT (even ten times more expensive). Other problems are related to the greater susceptibility of the catalyst to poisoning due to the presence of a non-shared electron pair in the nitrogen, and the fact that some N-heterocyclic compounds are no longer liquid at ambient conditions. These limitations mean that, despite the positive effect introduced by the heteroatom, they are generally not the best solution. Table 2.1 summarises the main properties and critical issues for the different types of LOHC, bearing in mind that the capacity requirement is evaluated against a target of at least 9%_m and 70 g/L. A more quantitative comparison is provided in Fig. 2.2 taken from (Abdin, Tang, and Catchpole, 2021).

Property	Cycloalkanes	Polycyclic Alkanes	Hydrocarbons with N, S, O	Ionic Liquids
ΔH_r	Good	Good	Great	Great
Volatility	Great	Great	Great	Great
Reversibility	Good	Good	Good	Good
Liquid State	Great	Critical	Good	Critical
Capacity	Critical	Critical	Critical	Critical
Toxicity	Great	Good	Good	Good
Costs	Great	Good	Critical	Critical

TABLE 2.1: Comparison of different LOHC classes in terms of their main properties.

FIGURE 2.2: Working point and thermodynamic properties of different carriers.

Recently, a new metallation strategy has been employed to optimise the hydrogen storage properties of organic compounds by replacing their reactive H with an alkali or alkaline earth metal to form the metallated counterparts. Crystalline lithiated amines have been synthesised by ball milling primary amines with LiH, demonstrating mild endothermic dehydrogenation and improved selectivity for hydrogen release, requiring significantly less heat to initiate dehydrogenation (Chen et al., 2014). Of particular interest is the performance of perhydrobenzyltoluene compared to perhydrodi-benzyltoluene (Rüde et al., 2022; Modisha and Bessarabov, 2023). At a pressure of 2 bar up to 90 % release is achieved over a Pt catalyst at only 292 °C, making it 30 % more productive than 18H-DBT dehydrogenation. Another class of compounds has recently been suggested by Tang et al. (Tang et al., 2020) as a viable alternative. The authors note that most typical LOHCs, with the exception of NEC, have a dehydrogenation enthalpy that is too high; in addition, fossil-based molecules are not sustainable. A first-principles analysis has therefore been carried out on a number of alkaloids, with generally good results; a more in-depth study of the Amaryllidaceae alkaloids is therefore required. Research is currently underway to find better performing supports to achieve higher energy densities, lower dehydrogenation temperatures and more economically viable solutions.

2.1.2 Catalysts

Different catalysts lead to different performances and the search for an optimal catalyst is one of the crucial aspects for the development and wide diffusion of LOHC systems. The need for a better catalyst is particularly felt for the dehydrogenation phase and could enable lower temperature processes (Cho et al., 2021). Lower temperature levels would allow easier coupling with recovery heat sources, thus reducing the cost of dehydrogenation. Even if the reaction heat is assumed to be constant in terms of temperature and pressure, the higher temperature of the endothermic release process makes heat recovery from the hydrogenation phase impossible. The role of catalysts is therefore fundamental: the main candidates are Pt, but they present problems of deactivation due to coking. The use of additional secondary metals such as W, Ir, Re, Pd or promoters (e.g. Ca) and the choice of support (e.g. Al₂O₃) are factors that can influence coking resistance. In general, catalysts capable of ensuring stable release are not yet available, although the introduction of alkali and alkaline earth metals seems to be the most promising solution. Another interesting property is productivity, defined as the amount of hydrogen absorbed in a given time interval with respect to the amount of noble metal (e.g. Pt) added to the catalyst, Eq. 2.3 (Wan et al., 2012).

$$P_{x-y}(t) = \frac{\Delta m_{H_2, x-y}}{m_{Pt} \Delta t_{x-y}} = \frac{n_{H_2, max} (DoH_y - DoH_x) M_{H_2}}{m_{Pt} (t_y - t_x)} \quad (2.3)$$

The assumption of a constant heat of reaction is actually incorrect, as significant variations with both temperature and pressure are well documented (Pashchenko, 2022). As the temperature increases, so does the enthalpy of the reaction. On the other hand, as the pressure increases, the heat requirement decreases. In any case, the required enthalpy of reaction saturates at the same value, which is about 68 kJ/mol of hydrogen for the methylcyclohexane-toluene system. Nevertheless, most simulations are run assuming constant values for both the activation energy and ΔH_r . This assumption is acceptable as long as the heat supplied keeps the temperature at or close to the initial value, which is the case for most studies (Dennis et al., 2021; Peters et al., 2019). In addition, thermal stability is challenged by the high temperature required to achieve satisfactory kinetic performance and hydrogen depletion from the loaded support, so operating at lower temperatures would extend the life of LOHC systems.

Since hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions would occur repeatedly, efficient storage solutions must be free of significant activity loss between cycles (Shirvani, Hartmann, and Smith, 2023). Loss of activity is mainly due to carbon deposition from side reactions such as polymerisation (Shi et al., 2019), and can lead to significant drops in performance even from the first to the second cycle, despite a decreasing deactivation rate with multiple cycles (Shirvani, Hartmann, and Smith, 2023). Selectivity can be enhanced by the

catalyst structure: for example, the use of ordered mesoporous silica with a 3-D pore structure (KIT-6) as a Pt catalyst support can significantly reduce the amount of by-products during dehydrogenation compared to disordered amorphous SiO_2 or Al_2O_3 catalysts (Ahn et al., 2022). Washing procedures allow up to 60 % of the initial catalyst activity to be recovered during hydrogenation, but only up to 20 % during dehydrogenation, again making the latter process the most critical of the storage solution.

In a study of the dehydrogenation rate of dodecahydro-N-ethylcarbazole and the selectivity to the fully dehydrogenated product, N-ethylcarbazole, both were found to depend on the particle size of the Pd catalyst (Sotoodeh, Huber, and Smith, 2012). The authors attributed the low turnover frequency (TOF)² for dodecahydrocarbazole to strong adsorption of the dehydrogenated products on Pd by the N atom, whereas the ethyl group in dodecahydro-N-ethylcarbazole prevented strong N interaction with the surface. A new catalytic technique has recently been proposed involving the use of weak electric fields (Sekine and Higo, 2021). In fact, when a weak electric field is applied to the catalyst bed, such as Pt with CeO_2 or TiO_2 , there is a strong enhancement of the dehydrogenation activity, resulting in MCH conversions that exceed the thermodynamic equilibrium, with selectivities above 99 %, with no or less deactivation over time (Kosaka et al., 2020). Takise et al. (Takise et al., 2019a; Takise et al., 2019b) have attempted to detail the mechanism of the electric field MCH dehydrogenation reaction. They found that the dehydrogenation rate is positively dependent on the hydrogen partial pressure, contrary to what happens in the conventional process (Kiermaier et al., 2021). The dehydrogenation reaction is promoted by H_2 or its derivatives present in the system thanks to collisions with H^+ conducting over the catalyst surface.

2.1.3 Reactors

Research into the most efficient reactor configurations has been ongoing since the last decade. Technical reports (Cooper et al., 2010) attest to efforts to design and fabricate optimised dehydrogenation reactors coupled with heat exchange systems to deliver hydrogen using liquid organic hydrogen carriers, and to design 0.1-1 kW prototypes. In particular, a microchannel dehydrogenation reactor prototype demonstrated a 7 times improvement over packed bed reactor performance. The microchannel reactor concept focused on separating the liquid carrier from the H_2 being produced to prevent the catalyst from drying out. This is particularly important as the reactor moves from being entirely liquid to containing up to 98 % volume of H_2 gas. The catalyst was then applied to thin porous substrates that wetted the liquid carrier, acting as wicks: the H_2 was separated from the liquid as it was produced to prevent the catalyst from drying out. BMW later completed the design of a hydrogenation unit with 5 litre internal volume, 100 bar and 250 °C maximum operating pressure and temperature, which could return conversion above 99 %; however, the N-ethylcarbazole tested has a small but significant vapour pressure at operating temperatures of 200-230 °C, which limited conversion and suppressed catalyst productivity. Typical reactors consider continuous flow (Peters et al., 2019; Yuranov et al., 2018; Javaid et al., 2013): the carrier is continuously injected by a pump and the reactor temperature is maintained using insulators, oil circulation baths, heaters and thermocouples. Laboratory-scale reactors built in this way have reported stability in excess of 120 h. (Yuranov et al., 2018). Measurements of the dehydrogenation kinetics were carried out by Heublein et al. (Heublein, Stelzner, and Sattelmayer, 2020) by placing a tubular reactor in different spatial orientations and testing different flow configurations and the effect of intermediate hydrogenation of the reaction mixture. In the horizontal reactor, the buoyancy force causes the phases to separate more easily, allowing the gas phase to leave the reactor with a higher purity, so that intermediate gas separation has no significant effect. Conversely, the countercurrent vertical reactor has the highest interaction between the gas and liquid phases and, as such, reports a significant improvement in productivity when coupled with gas separation. Integration of gas burners into the dehydrogenation unit has been proposed as a way of providing reaction heat, but care must be taken to avoid both hot and cold spots (Bollmann et al., 2023). Both H_2 and CH_4 fired burner scenarios have been tested (Badakhsh et al., 2022; Bollmann et al., 2023) and densities of 0.94

²Commonly called the turnover number, N, and defined, as in enzyme catalysis, as molecules reacting per active site per unit time -(Pure and Chemistry, 2012)

and 3.6 kWh/L of thermal energy have been achieved. A fixed bed heterogeneously catalysed reactor has been proposed by Jung et al. for continuous flow operation (Park et al., 2020). Using a rationally designed catalyst support to improve porosity, and various heteroatom ligand sites to allow diversification of heterogeneous catalytic systems, continuous hydrogenation is carried out in a trickle bed: the stainless steel tubular reactor is pressurised and heated and placed in a vertical position under cover; the catalyst powder is charged from the centre of the reactor and covered with glass wool, with the remaining space filled with glass beads to prevent catalyst loss.

A different approach was taken by Tsuru et al. with the introduction of a bimodal catalytic membrane reactor (Meng et al., 2015), where a heterogeneous catalyst is combined with permselective membranes. The membrane removes one of the components, shifting the equilibrium towards the desired product; this method allows higher conversions at lower temperatures. Similarly, a microstructured reactor with multi-stage membranes has been proposed (Wunsch, Mohr, and Pfeifer, 2018) so that a near-isothermal reaction environment is achieved and cold spots are limited. Only the liquid product stream is passed to the next stage of the reactor while the gas phase is separated by the membrane.

Reactive distillation systems have been proposed for DBT (Geißelbrecht et al., 2020) to separate hydrogenated feedstocks through the fully unsaturated LOHC. The system consists of four zones: an evaporator, a separation zone, a reaction zone and a condenser, and exploits the low boiling point of perhydrobenzyltoluene: it is therefore abundant in the upper part of the separation zone, whereas benzyltoluene is located in the lower part of the separation zone. As a result, hydrogen-rich LOHC compounds settle to the top of the column where the catalyst has been placed, while hydrogen-poor LOHCs settle to the bottom. The boiling of perhydrobenzyl toluene increases the thermodynamic driving force for dehydrogenation reactions by reducing the partial pressure of hydrogen in the gas phase. In addition, the efficiency and rate of the reaction is increased by this zone separation.

The most comprehensive design review and analysis has been carried out in the technical report by Jensen and Brayton (Jensen and Brayton, 2018), where they analysed eighteen different layouts. The proposed designs are a counter flow shell and tube reactor with the LOHC in the tubes, the same reactor with the LOHC in the shell, the same two designs but with helical reactors instead of horizontal tubes, a double nested helix with LOHC flowing in the helical tubes, the same design but with cross flow, a vertical crossflow tube reactor, a microchannel reactor with conical tubes, a continuously stirred reactor with a coil heater inside, a LOHC reactor coupled with microwave heating, a surface flow reactor consisting of a vertical packed column with heat provided by hot hydrogen in counterflow, a flat crossflow shell and coil reactor with LOHC in the coil, the same reactor but with stacked coils with either counterflow or crossflow, a shell and stacked coil reactor with progressively larger coils in counterflow, a continuously stirred tank reactor with heat provided by hydrogen bubbles, a counterflow shell and tube reactor with the introduction of a helical shaped turbulator in the linear tube, and a perforated split design with a liquid and gas channel separated by a membrane top and with back pressure regulation. The most efficient design in terms of minimum volume and mass was the nested helix design. However, the single coil design was only slightly less efficient and would be much simpler and more reliable from an assembly point of view.

Finally, if the hydrogen production and consumption takes place locally, an interesting solution is offered by hot pressure swing reactors (Jorschick et al., 2017; Jorschick et al., 2019). Looking at the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation profiles (Wan et al., 2012; Kiermaier et al., 2021), it appears that a similar temperature could promote either hydrogenation or dehydrogenation depending on the pressure level, which would shift the equilibrium towards one side of the reaction. High pressure, according to the Le Chatelier principle, inhibits dehydrogenation by increasing the volume of the gas phase, while promoting hydrogenation. This approach would reduce capital and operating costs, both by simplifying the design and by eliminating the need for a cooling system. However, current applications rely only on tubular reactors (Heublein, Stelzner, and Sattelmayer, 2020) and more complex solutions are still in the early stages of development.

2.2 Applications

Liquid LOHCs are flexible options for different size classes and storage times (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018). Hydrogen losses are minimal or non-existent and they are safe under standard conditions. However, the challenge of the LOHC system is the need to dynamically release hydrogen in a reactor prior to use and the high dehydrogenation heat requirement. To overcome this potential obstacle, direct LOHC FC systems have been proposed (Araujo et al., 2012). Various organic fuels for virtual hydrogen flow cell battery systems have been compared in terms of energy density and open circuit potentials to identify promising organic carriers that could lead to better performances than the hydrogen fuel cell; these technologies are still at an early stage. The LOHC system has already been evaluated for many industrial end uses. Some evaluations of the integrated LOHC systems have shown thermal efficiencies above 60% and power generation efficiencies around 40%, depending on the assumptions made (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018).

Authors in Aziz (2016) have proposed hydrogen production, storage and power generation from microalgae using enhanced process integration technology through exergy recovery and process integration. The system includes supercritical water gasification, hydrogen separation, hydrogenation and a combined cycle. Microalgae (*Chlorella vulgaris*) are converted to syngas, then separated to produce high purity hydrogen, which is stored in the toluene-methylcyclohexane cycle. The remaining gas is used as fuel for combustion in the combined cycle to generate electricity. High overall energy and electricity generation efficiencies are achieved, with 60% and 40% respectively.

A wind park case supplying a cement plant has been evaluated (Krieger, Müller, and Arlt, 2016a). A liquid organic hydrogen carrier system and its suitability as a storage system for industrial applications will be evaluated: LOHCs allow optimised use of waste heat. The waste heat from the cement plant can increase the efficiency of the storage system and the efficiency of the LOHC system can be increased by twelve percentage points. The operating electricity costs of the cement plant are significantly reduced when the LOHC system is added.

In a Concentrated Solar Power plant (Krieger, Müller, and Arlt, 2016b), the introduction of LOHCs (DBT) proves to be the most suitable integration alongside magnesium metal hydrides. Heat storage in concentrated solar power plants is required to compensate for the variable availability of solar radiation; the efficiency of various reversible hydrogenation reactions as thermochemical heat storage systems has been investigated.

Multi-tubular reactors have been tested for the mobility sector (Geiling et al., 2021). Up to 6.6 kW have been achieved with a hydrogen flow rate as high as 0.26 kg/h and with the introduction of PI control.

Other applications relate to seasonal storage in a hydroelectric plant. On a seasonal timescale, LOHC storage (toluene) of hydrogen is equivalent to other carbon-free alternatives and superior to zero emission systems such as batteries, thus providing a competitive route (Newson et al., 1998). Low cost summer electricity is used to electrolyse water to produce hydrogen for toluene hydrogenation. Dehydrogenation in winter provides hydrogen for heat and power generation by fuel cells. The techno-economic potential of seasonal storage of electricity with chemically bound hydrogen in liquid organic hydrocarbons in the methylcyclohexane-toluene-hydrogen (MTH) system has been extensively studied (Scherer and Newson, 1998): these analyses indicate that the cost of winter electricity is 0.23 USD/kWh at an overall efficiency of 0.39 for the whole system.

One of the proposed end uses for DBT-LOHC is the utilisation of stranded gas offshore or at remote drilling sites by converting 5-14% of the methane to hydrogen (Dürr et al., 2017b). The authors propose an integration of CO₂-free hydrogen production by methane decomposition coupled with hydrogen/methane separation and chemical hydrogen storage by LOHC systems. A potential very interesting application is the upgrading of stranded gas, e.g. gas from a remote gas field or associated gas from offshore oil wells, which can be effectively converted in a catalytic process by methane decomposition into solid carbon and a hydrogen/methane mixture, which can be fed directly to a hydrogenation unit to load a LOHC with hydrogen. This scheme allows a straightforward separation of hydrogen from CH₄ and conversion of hydrogen to a hydrogen rich LOHC material. Both the LOHC and

the carbon on metal produced can be easily transported to destinations for further industrial use by established transport systems such as ships or trucks.

Authors of (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018) propose for a general carrier with hydrogen storage capacity around 5.5 %_m, and the FC efficiency as 80 % accounting for utilisation of waste heat, or 43-60 % with respect to only electricity (Climate Change (IPCC), 2014):

- A 55 kW FC powered family car with the autonomy for running at 60 % load for 5 h. That would use 113 kg of LOHC for about 500 km of operation assuming hydrogen consumption 1.0-1.5 kg per 100 km (Sekanina, 2006). For automotive use, a dehydrogenation temperature of approximately 200 °C would be required (Von Wild et al., 2010), so toluene (Sultan, 1975) and NEC based (Von Wild et al., 2010) LOHC systems could be evaluated for vehicles.
- A family house with an annual energy consumption of 5 MW h would need 3400 kg of LOHC. The low efficiency of the LOHC concept could be increased by utilising the waste heat of the exothermic hydrogenation for heating, or cooling purposes, or both, and recovering the waste heat of the FC (Teichmann, Arlt, and Wasserscheid, 2012).
- For a 41 MW, 28 Mg/h of LOHC would be needed. To reduce volume occupation onboard, one tank should be capable of handling both loaded and unloaded LOHC.
- Emission control device to reduce NO_x coupled to a large marine diesel engine. At full load it would need a LOHC mass flow rate of about 31.9 kg/h to reduce 20 kg/h of NO_x³.

A regenerative hydrogen fuel cell system consisting of an electrolyser, hydrogen storage and fuel cell with a liquid organic hydrogen carrier considered for hydrogen storage technology offers good safety, easy handling and high storage density. Based on the analysis performed, such a system was considered to be an attractive option for both weekly (below 100 h) and monthly (below 1000 h) storage (Lee et al., 2021). More specifically, while better daily performances (under 10 h) are achieved with compressed hydrogen gas, the resulting LOHC systems have higher ESOI values (Energy stored on investment ratio in terms of electrical energy and power) than compressed hydrogen, concentrated solar power and lithium battery systems in the mentioned cases.

Polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell couplings have been proposed and tested for bidirectional storage of electrical energy over the course of 725 h by Geiling et al. (Geiling et al., 2023), and stable operation without significant signs of degradation has been reported. The energy balance calculation of the ratio of energy transported to energy consumed for hydrogen delivery in LOHC systems is about 3.9 according to Pradhan et al. (Pradhan et al., 2011), allowing a saving of 345 Mg per year of carbon dioxide emissions per delivery station by replacing petrol with hydrogen for passenger cars using data related to the Indian scenario. In 2019, Sievi et al. (Sievi et al., 2019) propose a PEMFC design using 2-propanol so that the endothermic heat release is compensated by the exothermic water formation of the fuel cell. Similarly, Shiraz et al. consider direct electrochemical hydrogenation to combine hydrogen production and storage, operating at room temperature and atmospheric pressure (Shiraz et al., 2022).

In a dedicated (Dennis et al., 2021) study, a thermally integrated combination of a hydrogen fired 7.7 MW gas turbine and a DBT subsystem is being evaluated. The hydrogen required to fuel the gas turbine is extracted from the preheated LOHC oil in a dehydrogenation reactor using waste heat from the gas turbine process, and the hydrogen is compressed after release to ensure a stable fuel supply to the gas turbine combustor. The most influential operating parameters are the inlet hydrogenation grade of the LOHC oil and the selected system pressure. Overall, the investigated case shows an effective storage density of 1.5 kWh/L of LOHC and a power yield of 0.33 kWh/L of LOHC. At least 3000 m³ of LOHC storage would be required to provide full load operation for at least one week. In addition, the electricity-to-electricity storage efficiency was estimated to be 10.60 % for the case studied; while this value is quite low, it is expected to improve significantly if a more efficient electrolyser, dehydrogenation reactor or gas turbine is incorporated.

³The assumed reaction is $2\text{NO} + 4\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{N}_2 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Criteria \ Technology	LOHC (Liquid)	LH ₂ (Liquid)	GH ₂ (Compr. Gas)	NH ₃ (Ammonia)	Battery	CH ₄ (Methanation)
Energy amounts:	TWh	MWh	kWh	MWh	kWh	MWh
Transportability:	●	●	●	●	●	●
Size:	modularly & small	big	middle - big	middle - big	middle - big	middle - big
Costs:	●	●	●	●	●	●
Use cases:						
→ Car / Truck	●	○	●	●	●	●
→ Coal Power Plant Refit	●	○	○	○	○	●
→ Ship propulsion	●	●	●	●	●	●
→ Train propulsion	●	●	●	●	●	●
→ Real Estate	●	●	●	●	●	●
Storage & Transportation						
Infrastructure existing today:						
→ Truck / Car	●	●	●	●	●	●
→ Ships	●	●	●	●	●	●
→ Pipelines	●	○	●	●	○	●
→ Trains	●	●	●	●	●	●
→ Large Scale Storage Tanks	●	●	●	●	●	●

FIGURE 2.3: LOHC comparison with other storage solutions provided by (enterprises, 2024).

The Combined Heat and Power (CHP) system and the LOHC system were evaluated in terms of self-sufficiency, self-consumption rate and primary energy demand (Haupt and Muller, 2017), and a comparison is made with a battery system. While both systems showed that the addition of an electrical energy storage system can significantly reduce the primary energy demand and improve the self-sufficiency and self-consumption rate, the electrical self-sufficiency is better with a battery, but the LOHC technology can save slightly more primary energy.

A techno-economic evaluation and feasibility study of a stationary electricity storage system has been carried out for a BMW Group production site in Germany (Eypasch et al., 2017). It is assumed that the electricity is generated by wind turbines and photovoltaic systems. The system stores the produced hydrogen using dibenzyltoluene and then feeds it to the Agenitor 312 CHP unit. In particular, heat-intensive process plants, such as food processing plants or refineries, are cited by the authors as the best application sites for integrating the process heat of the LOHC system, as the paper shows that converting excess energy into heat is currently a more economical option than storing electricity using LOHC.

As the methanisation process uses carbon dioxide and hydrogen to produce methane gas, LOHC could be used as a medium for long-distance hydrogen transport. In general, storage of hydrogen in liquid form offers interesting possibilities for transport. It is possible to envisage large-scale storage and long periods without losses, with the only limitations being the containers and the technical availability of the relevant composites. A dedicated study (Naseem, Usman, and Lee, 2021) develops a new method to use the heat from the methanation process for dehydrogenation: the process uses an Air-Brayton cycle to generate the required high pressure and to compensate for the thermal energy demand of LOHC dehydrogenation using a proportionate amount of the methane produced.

2.3 Costs

Fig. 2.3 from (enterprises, 2024) shows how the properties of LOHCs could be exploited. LOHCs could be used to store large amounts of energy, but with modular technology solutions and high transportability. While the costs are shown to be extremely low in the proposed table, these only refer to the transport phase, as the main cost of LOHCs systems is due to hydrogen release (Brigljevic, Byun, and Lim, 2020).

In this article the authors compare four different LOHC systems: a phenyl eutectic mixture, 2-(N-methylbenzyl)pyridine, N-phenylcarbazole and N-ethylcarbazole. The NEC technology has proven to be the most efficient and also the one with the lowest amount of carrier required per net $1 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3$ of hydrogen. For this size, the total installed cost is in the range of 2-3 million USD, and the capital investment for monthly chemical supply is in the range of 24-44 million USD.

While the cost of synthesising LOHCs is lower than that of liquefying hydrogen (with an average cost forecast of 6.9 USD/kg by 2025 (statista.com, 2023)), liquid carriers require an additional step to release the hydrogen, which introduces costs and efficiency losses for re-conversion that may limit their use. Indeed, while production costs vary widely for different carriers, some options could prove to be relatively cheap, such as DBT systems. The HyS-TOC project designers have estimated synthesis costs of less than 4.0 USD/kg, which could be reduced to around 1.6 USD/kg as production increases (HYSTOC, 2019). In each scenario presented (Brigljevic, Byun, and Lim, 2020) the dehydrogenation reactor is the largest cost item, followed by hydrogen compression. For this reason, research is currently focused on studying the chemistry of release in order to develop a catalyst that can optimise its performance (Cho et al., 2021).

To highlight the much lower electricity costs associated with operating LOHCs, the pumping energy requirement is estimated to be 3-16 Wh/kg (of hydrogen) (Eypasch et al., 2017) for DBT and PDBT respectively; in comparison, the heat energy requirement assuming a heat exchanger efficiency of 97.5 % was estimated to be 12.54 kWh/kg (of hydrogen) for the same system during dehydrogenation. The same article presents reactor and total cost estimates made by BMW for hydrogenation and dehydrogenation systems as shown by Eqs. 2.4 to 2.7:

$$c_{hyd,r} = 2840.81 \cdot P_{hyd,max}^{-0.375} \quad (2.4)$$

$$c_{hyd,r} = 5057.29 \cdot P_{hyd,max}^{-0.434} \quad (2.5)$$

$$c_{hyd,r} = 3122.83 \cdot P_{hyd,max}^{-0.375} \quad (2.6)$$

$$c_{hyd,r} = 6888.83 \cdot P_{deh,max}^{-0.424} \quad (2.7)$$

with specific costs expressed in €/kW assuming the reference as the LHV of hydrogen, and the power rating expressed in kW. Similarly, operation and maintenance costs are approximately expected to be about the 4 % of the reactor cost.

By comparing different carrier solutions, DBT was reported as the cheapest option, resulting in lower equipment costs and the highest internal rate of return (Tsogt, 2024). The use of pinch analysis resulted in energy savings of up to 80 %, highlighting the need for efficient use of utilities. In addition, sensitivity analysis revealed a notable influence of LOHC and catalyst prices on the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH). This is particularly true for NEC, as current prices are still very high due to limited global production. In a dedicated study, Niermann et al. (Niermann et al., 2021) found that what makes NEC unsuitable for transport purposes is its high upfront cost. On the other hand, although DBT requires a lower initial investment, it is only a viable solution as long as heat is supplied externally. In fact, methanol gives the best results due to low transport costs, high storage capacity and lower heat requirements.

As far as energy transport is concerned, the movement of LOHCs can be achieved using existing infrastructures. The authors in (Teichmann, Arlt, and Wasserscheid, 2012) compare transport costs and feasibility for both sea and road transport. For sea transport, LOHCs are by far a cheaper solution than LH₂, as the latter requires complex insulation of the cryogenic containers. LOHCs, on the other hand, could be transported on any crude oil tanker. Conversely, while road transport of LH₂ suffers from boil-off losses, LOHCs require greater fuel consumption due to the need to return the unloaded carrier to the first location. Analysis by Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2012) shows that the energy efficiency of LOHC transport without heat recovery is comparable to that of LH₂ and ranges around 60-70 % depending on the dehydrogenation rate; with heat recovery the efficiency increases to 80-90 %.

In Wulf and Zapp (2018), the transport of liquid hydrogen is still more expensive than

that of LOHCs due to the high investment in the liquefaction plant. However, LOHCs perform worse than LNG in all environmental impact categories due to the heat required for dehydrogenation and the lower transport capacity of LOHC trucks compared to LNG trucks. This result can only be mitigated by providing heat by burning the hydrogen itself, but this comes at the expense of efficiency and the results are influenced by the hydrogen generation mechanisms. For example, Preuster et al. (Preuster, Papp, and Wasserscheid, 2017) estimate that at least 27 % of the stored hydrogen is lost when dehydrogenation is achieved by hydrogen combustion.

A demonstration of the logistics of charging the DBT with solar power in Erlangen and by road transport to Stuttgart to release hydrogen to meet a 30 kW demand showed hydrogen delivery costs of 5-55 €/kg, while the market value of hydrogen at the refuelling station would be 9-12 €/kg. (Preuster, Papp, and Wasserscheid, 2017). While chemical production is one of the main costs of LOHCs for some operators such as NEC, the capital cost of key components for the methanol approach is about twice that of LOHCs, mainly due to the expensive CO₂ capture from the atmosphere, which has not yet been commercialised. Based on cost and energy efficiency considerations at this stage, the above suggests that LOHCs may be one of the best options for large scale hydrogen storage for the long term (Abdin, Tang, and Catchpole, 2021).

The estimated global volume of aromatic building blocks (i.e. benzene and toluene) is more than 50×10^6 Mg/y less than 1 €/kg (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018): aromatics, are mostly produced by catalytic reforming in oil refineries from crude oils. Renewable aromatics could also be produced from lignin. Global production of heat transfer fluids was only 466 Gg in 2014 and only partly based on DBT. Nitrogenous aromatics such as NEC can be produced from petroleum, coal or lignin, but NEC production is limited today and the ethylation of carbazole produces a large amount of waste (e.g. KCl or K₂SO₄) aakko₂₀₁₈.

Although they are largely recyclable, the availability of catalysts should also be considered. If the dehydrogenation of 500 Mg of LOHC requires one kilogram of catalyst at a cost of 150 €/kg (Ahluwalia et al., 2011), the use of Pt group metals as catalysts would be a limit to the technology (Aakko-Saksa et al., 2018).

Chapter 3

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: Kinetics

3.1 Kinetic Modeling

A kinetic model is evaluated using NEC as the chosen support Gambini et al., 2022. Unlike DBT, experimental data on the pressure dependence of N-ethylcarbazole are readily available in the literature Wan et al., 2012; Kiermaier et al., 2021. Data are available in a pressure range of 30-70 bar and 0.25-1.00 bar for uptake and release respectively, which means that only relatively high or very low pressure levels are investigated. On the other hand, the temperature ranges overlap, which could be helpful if more advanced solutions were needed Jorschick et al., 2017; Jorschick et al., 2019. Due to the many similarities in their working principles, metal hydrides, which have already been extensively characterised, were used as a reference. For further details on metal hydrides see Appendix A. The multi-step reaction can be studied as an equivalent single reaction starting from or leading to the fully saturated form of the LOHC species, with the effect of the liquid-gas interface and vapour pressures taken into account only for the evaluation of the chemical equilibrium. By assuming the multi-step reaction as its equivalent single-step reaction, the previously defined DoH (Eq. 2.1) can be directly correlated to the equivalent 12 H–NEC concentration.

These simplifying assumptions result in a simple but reliable model, and while a different approach might lead to slightly more accurate simulations, a model including all the reactions occurring simultaneously and in sequence, together with the phase equilibrium, would be considerably more complex Dennis et al., 2021; Peters et al., 2019 and less effective in simulating an entire hydrogen-based energy system. See Appendix C. for more information on the multistep reaction. It has been shown that the rate depends only on the chemical reaction, since both hydrogen transfer processes through the phase interface and through the liquid medium are considerably faster Ye, An, and Xu, 2011. An equation in the form of Eq. 3.1 has therefore been sought to describe both kinetic rates Dennis et al., 2021; Peters et al., 2019, where k is a general function of T and p , and depending on the choice of catalyst for its frequency factor (k_0) Eq. 3.1, and n is the reaction order.

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} = kf(\text{DoH}, n) \quad (3.1)$$

$$k = k_0g(p)z(T) \quad (3.2)$$

Since only one data set was available for each pressure level except 60 bar, and current models do not include a dependence in the form of $\phi(T, p)$, the effects of pressure and temperature were treated separately by independent functions $g(p)$ and $z(T)$, according to the principles of chemical thermodynamics House, 2007. The introduction of a fictitious MH-like equilibrium pressure Gambini, 1994; Muthukumar, Madhavakrishna, and Dewan, 2007 was also investigated but gave unsatisfactory results, demonstrating that the underlying mechanism is inherently different. If there is a correlation between pressure and system temperature, the data currently available are insufficient to define it. However, the role of pressure on the value of the kinetic rate is prominent, so much so that constant-temperature

reactors controlled in a pressure-swinging fashion are considered to be the leading solutions for this technology Jorschick et al., 2017; Jorschick et al., 2019. Although other temperature dependencies exist for specific processes, such as enzyme-controlled reactions, the most common $z(T)$ relationship is in the form of the Arrhenius equation (Eq. 3.3):

$$\log k_{0,p,T} = \log k_{0,p} - \frac{E_a}{R_u T} \quad (3.3)$$

using subscripts to explicitly remark every parameter influence over the kinetic constant k . If the reaction has been carried out at different temperature levels, the collected data can be used to fit Eq. 3.3, providing an estimate of both the apparent activation energy E_a and the frequency factor $k_{0,p}$. The level of pressure applied to a system also affects the rate constant (Eq. 3.4): increasing the pressure on a system in equilibrium shifts the reaction in the direction corresponding to a smaller volume, as stated by the Le Chatelier principle. In this work it has been assumed that a small but essentially constant concentration of the transition state is in equilibrium with the reactants House, 2007, the transition state being defined as the high-energy state that defines the energy barrier of the reaction and is responsible for the rate constant. If the transition state occupies a smaller volume than the reactants, then a higher pressure will shift the equilibrium towards a higher concentration in the transition state, resulting in higher overall rates. This influence can be modelled by the following equation:

$$\log k_{0,p} = -\frac{\Delta V^\ddagger}{R_u T} p + \log k_0 \quad (3.4)$$

$$\Delta V^\ddagger = -b R_u T \quad (3.5)$$

with ΔV^\ddagger in Eq. 3.5 being the activation volume. When current models feature pressure dependencies, they either follow an exponential or a power law for dehydrogenation and hydrogenation respectively Dennis et al., 2021. The first alternative mathematically coincides to Eq. 3.4, however no physical meaning is given the exponent. The latter formula was also evaluated; however, the previously explained method gave the best performance for the datasets used for the validation, which will be presented below. The effect of temperature and pressure on the kinetic rate are thus evaluated so that Eq. 3.2 can be written as Eq. 3.6:

$$k = k_0 \exp(bp) \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) \quad (3.6)$$

with exponential functions representing the effect of both pressure and temperature on the kinetic rate: $g(p) = \exp(bp)$, $z(T) = \exp(-E_a/(R_u T))$. While better results can be obtained if $\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt}$ is integrated, since datasets are provided for constant thermodynamic conditions, the results discussed in the following section were evaluated by means of numeric integration:

$$\text{DoH}_i \approx \text{DoH}_{i-1} + \left. \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} \right|_{t=t_i} \Delta t_i \quad (3.7)$$

because the aim of this model is to provide equations to describe real operating systems, when thermodynamic conditions are not constant.

3.1.1 Hydrogenation

With respect to the basic model outlined, two corrections have been introduced to account for the high temperature phenomena occurring in the hydrogenation process. First, since a maximum kinetic rate is observed once a threshold temperature T_{thr} is reached, a simple but effective correction is proposed that sets the kinetic rate reached at temperature T_{thr} as the maximum possible rate. Thus, after defining a reference temperature (Eq. 3.8), the modified

Arrhenius law can be written as Eq. 3.9.

$$T_{ref} = \min\{T, T_{thr}\} \quad (3.8)$$

$$z(T) = \exp\left(-E_a/(R_u T_{ref})\right) \quad (3.9)$$

Secondly, since hydrogenation is an exothermic process, increasing the temperature levels shifts the chemical equilibrium towards the reactants. This means that saturation effects arise at high DoH, so that the model takes into account a maximum hydrogenation level DoH_{sat} , and Eq. (3.1) for hydrogenation turns into Eq. 3.10.

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} \Big|_{deh} = k_0 g(p) z(T) (\text{DoH}_{sat} - \text{DoH})^n \quad (3.10)$$

The decrease in hydrogen saturation level with temperature, leading to a reduced storage capacity, is modelled by a chemical equilibrium model from the Gibbs free energy of formation (ΔG_f^0 , Eq. 3.11) and the equilibrium constant (K_{eq} , Eq. 3.12).

$$\Delta G_f^0 = -R_u T \log(K_{eq}) \quad (3.11)$$

$$K_{eq} = \frac{\left([\text{12 H-NEC}] \frac{p_{v,12\text{H-NEC}}}{p_0}\right)^{1/6}}{[\text{H}_2] \frac{p}{p_0} \left([\text{0 H-NEC}] \frac{p_{v,0\text{H-NEC}}}{p_0}\right)^{1/6}} = \left(\frac{p_{v,12\text{H-NEC}}}{p_{v,0\text{H-NEC}}}\right)^{1/6} \frac{\zeta^{1/6} (7/6 - \zeta)}{(1 - \zeta)^{7/6} \frac{p}{p_0}} \quad (3.12)$$

Gibbs free energy data are available in the literature Choi et al., 2016 and can be used to evaluate K_{eq} . The equilibrium constant can then be expressed in terms of activities. The reaction takes place between the dissolved hydrogen gas and the liquid organic carrier at the catalyst sites: liquid phases have been treated as ideal, assuming unitary activity, while the vapour pressure of LOHCs has been evaluated by empirical laws Heublein, Stelzner, and Sattelmayer, 2020. Eq. (3.12) can then be solved for the reaction coordinate (ζ), giving the actual maximum degree of hydrogenation DoH_{sat} as the ratio of 12 H-NEC moles to the sum of 12 H-NEC and 0 H-NEC moles at equilibrium. The proposed kinetic equation for hydrogenation is thus expressed as Eq. 3.13, which provides satisfactory modelling results when compared to the experimental data taken by Wan et al. (2012). A more detailed analysis of the chemical equilibrium of LOHC reactions can be found in Sec. B.

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} \Big|_{hyd} = k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T_{ref}}\right) \exp(bp) [\text{DoH}_{sat}(T, p) - \text{DoH}]^n \quad (3.13)$$

Tab. 3.1 showcases the statistical parameters that define the modelling process for the hydrogenation phase. Hydrogenation profiles were included in the modelling procedure only up to the onset of saturation; however, the profiles represented in Fig. 3.1a show the full experimental dataset.

Fig. 3.1 provides information about each modelling step. In particular, Fig. 3.1a and Fig. 3.1b highlight the validity of the first order approximation, which leads to a straight line at the chosen coordinates: the experimental data fit well (Tab. 3.1) until saturation conditions are reached. When saturation is reached, the angle coefficients change and each profile becomes a horizontal line. As a pseudo-first order reaction, it is likely that the excess reagent does not affect the kinetics, so the fit effectively correlates the rate to the unsaturated LOHC concentration.

Fig. 3.1c and Fig. 3.1d illustrate the validity of Eq. 3.3-3.4. The positive angular coefficient in Fig. 3.1d was expected due to the beneficial effect of pressure on the kinetic rate; the trend shown in Fig. 3.1c can instead be explained by the limited influence of temperature on the rate for $T \geq 433 - 453$ K. The experimental data sets clearly indicate a threshold above which the beneficial effect of temperature increase on the kinetic rate is outweighed by additional mechanisms unleashed at high temperature, as discussed above.

Lindfors, Salmi, and Smeds provide the description of a similar case study based on the toluene system. The kinetic rate exhibits a maximum at about 170 °C, similar to NEC's maximum. Authors claim that the rate maximum may be induced by the escape of catalytically

FIGURE 3.1: Hydrogenation modelling results. Both Fig. 3.1d and Fig. 3.1c y-axis have $\ln(1/\text{min})$ as a unit.

	T / K	R_{adj}^2	NRMSE
$p = 60 \text{ bar}$	368	0.9887	0.1060
	378	0.9504	0.1804
	393	0.9919	0.0643
	403	0.9826	0.0852
	433	0.9833	0.0504
	453	0.8912	0.0909
	468	0.9571	0.1165
	483	0.7846	0.2120
	493	0.7695	0.1976
$T = 433 \text{ K}$	p / bar	R_{adj}^2	NRMSE
	30	0.9318	0.1949
	40	0.9858	0.0970
	50	0.9895	0.0602
	60	0.9833	0.0504
	70	0.9930	0.0315
	$E_a/k_{0,p}$	0.9345	0.0700
	b, k_0	0.9151	0.0663

TABLE 3.1: Values of the adjusted R-squared and NRMSE for each fitting. Hydrogenation is modelled as a first-order reaction.

active hydrogen from the Ni catalyst surface at high reaction temperature values. This claim is supported by temperature-programmed desorption studies and chemisorption studies of hydrogen (Lindfors, Salmi, and Smeds, 1993).

Looking at the slope of the higher temperature profiles, it is clear that for temperatures above $\approx 433 - 453 \text{ K}$ the gradients do not become increasingly steeper with increasing temperature, as would be expected if Eq. 3.3 were to hold over the whole temperature range. In fact, the Arrhenius dependence imposed on the experimental data would imply that the activation energy would eventually become zero and then negative as the temperature increases, since the angular coefficient of the fit in Fig. 3.1c is proportional to the activation energy: $m = -E_a/R$.

The maximum value of DoH calculated with Eqs. 3.11 and 3.12 as a function of pressure and temperature, compared with experimental data available in the literature, is shown in Fig. 3.2.

Some error is introduced at lower temperature values, but this has little or no practical effect on the overall effectiveness of the model. On the other hand, the correction allows the model to estimate system performance with good accuracy at higher temperatures and lower pressures. As long as $T < 468 \text{ K}$ there is no evidence of a decrease in storage capacity, so if Eq. (3.12) is considered for any temperature level, slight errors may be introduced in the lower temperature range. This discrepancy is not only small, leading to a minimal deviation as seen in Fig. 3.3a, but does not affect a real operating system because the storage system would not be filled to saturation conditions, but to a lower degree of hydrogenation, usually limited to $DoH_f = 0.9 - 0.95$ Dennis et al., 2021; Peters et al., 2019, to avoid going through the slow saturation phase. Thus no deviation is introduced for a DoH range of practical interest.

Further analysis of the equilibrium conversion will be carried out in future work, taking into account the multi-step reaction. However, given the limited amount of data available to support any theory, combined with a satisfactory fit to the data, the proposed model was considered more than adequate. A different approach was taken in other works Shin et al., 2018, where no pressure correction was given and the actual reaction order was not taken into account Fogler, 2016. Recently, the issue has been addressed for DBT Dürr et al., 2021; however, in this case, the equilibrium conditions were simply evaluated by a fitting procedure and not by a chemical thermodynamic model. Both high temperature corrections are therefore essential to accurately reproduce the experimental data over a wide range of

(A) Experimental and modelled data for $p = 60$ bar. (B) Experimental and modelled data for $T = 433$ K.

FIGURE 3.3: Hydrogenation modelling results; lines: model results; markers: experimental data.

operating conditions, although they are not strictly necessary for low temperature and high pressure systems.

Looking at Fig. 3.3a it is clear that after introducing both corrections, represented by Eqs. 3.8 – 3.12, the model introduces the largest error for low to medium DoH in the 368 and 378 K profiles. Not only is this error significantly smaller than that introduced by the base model at higher temperatures, but these temperature levels would extend the charging times considerably, making them much less relevant than the temperature profiles $T \geq 398$ K. Furthermore, the hydrogenation reaction is exothermic, so in a real system the temperature would initially rise, making the inaccuracy of the model irrelevant in the early stages of hydrogenation at a constant low temperature: indeed, it is reasonable to assume that as the system temperature decreases the achieved DoH would be sufficiently high to avoid the larger errors.

The system performance improves significantly as the temperature rises, until it reaches about 453 K, and the errors would quickly increase again if both corrections were not in place. This is due to the onset of the two high temperature phenomena explained earlier. In the absence of both, Wan et al., 2012 limit the validity of their model to the low temperature range. It is also worth noting that the total charging time, which the model effectively

predicts, is arguably more important than the hydrogenation profile.

The pressure dependence gives good results overall, with the worst performance for the system at 70 bar. Fig. 3.3b suggests that the accuracy of the model can drop rapidly at higher pressures. The data provided suggests that increasing the pressure results in some kinetic gain up to a certain threshold, but this limit is not particularly worrying as systems can be held at constant pressure and there is no kinetic or energetic gain from increasing the pressure above 60 bar. For LOHC-based systems to be effective, hydrogen should not be compressed beforehand, so pressure levels should be around 10-50 bar, which is a reasonable operating range for water electrolyzers Peters et al., 2019.

For 30 bar systems, the maximum amount of hydrogen that can be stored drops to about 94%, which means that chemical equilibrium must be taken into account to give accurate results. An increasing influence is expected at even lower pressure levels, as predicted by the model.

3.1.2 Dehydrogenation

Contrary to what could be seen for hydrogenation, no saturation effect was evident from the experimental data Kiermaier et al., 2021. This is due to the fact that dehydrogenation is an endothermic reaction: since both reactions were tested at high temperature to obtain good kinetics, while hydrogenation, being exothermic, suffered in terms of thermodynamic equilibrium, dehydrogenation was only tested under favourable conditions. If lower temperatures had been tested, the chemical equilibrium would have shifted towards the reactants, and saturation effects would have played a major role at these temperature levels as well. With the given dataset DoH_{sat} is set to zero. The proposed kinetic equation for dehydrogenation is thus expressed as Eq. 3.14.

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} \Big|_{\text{deh}} = k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) \exp(bp) \text{DoH}^n \quad (3.14)$$

Dehydrogenation modelling is illustrated step by step in Fig. 3.4. Experimental data, taken from Ref. Kiermaier et al., 2021, are plotted in Fig. 3.4a-3.4b in coordinates that highlight the underlying reaction order.

Tab. 3.2 summarises the statistical relevance of the parameters that make up the proposed dehydrogenation model. The normalised root mean square error (NRMSE) is defined as the ratio between the root mean square error and the mean of each dataset. The first three rows assess the accuracy of fitting the experimental data as second order reactions; indeed, a second order reaction ($n = 2$) adequately describes the process for all systems held at 0.50 and 1.00 bar (Fig. 3.4a). However, when the pressure is reduced to 0.25 bar, this correlation is lost at 473 K (Fig. 3.4b). Fig. 3.4a-3.4b suggest a reaction order that is a function of both temperature and pressure. While this topic has remained largely untouched since the new interest in LOHCs, a varying reaction order for hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of organic compounds has already been discussed in the literature Lindfors, Salmi, and Smeds, 1993. Indeed, at 0.25 bar and 473 K the best results are obtained by first order modelling. While a second order approximation still gives good results in the early stages of dehydrogenation, second order modelling implies slower kinetics at low DoH. Consequently, any resemblance to the experimental data is lost.

Fig. 3.4c shows the effect of temperature on the kinetic rate for different pressure levels. At 0.50 and 1.00 bar the same angular coefficient fits the model satisfactorily, implying the same activation energy. Conversely, this value cannot effectively reproduce the behaviour of the system at 0.25 bar, where a higher activation energy value is implied if no dataset is excluded. However, if only the 433 and 453 K data at 0.25 bar are considered, a similar angular coefficient would be found. This is consistent with the different behaviour in terms of reaction order discussed above. At present, no single model has a reaction with a $n(T, p)$ dependence, and the data are too limited to suggest one. In any case, although low pressures will result in faster discharge processes, it is unlikely that pressure levels as low as 0.25 bar or even 0.50 bar could satisfy end-user requirements. Furthermore, without a control strategy in place, discharge trends are highly variable over time. As they may conflict with end-user requirements, control strategies must be set to meet end-user mass flow requirements.

(A) Second order reaction approximation for different pressure and temperature levels.

(D) Pressure effect over k . The proposed model is represented by the lilac line.

FIGURE 3.4: Dehydrogenation modelling results. Both Fig. 3.4c and Fig. 3.4d have $\log(1/\text{min})$ as a unit on the y-axis.

		p / bar					
		1.00		0.50		0.25	
		R^2_{adj}	NRMSE	R^2_{adj}	NRMSE	R^2_{adj}	NRMSE
T / K	433	0.9192	0.0451	0.9671	0.0417	0.9971	0.0197
	453	0.9856	0.0570	0.9997	0.0109	0.9978	0.0334
	473	0.9615	0.1268	0.9969	0.0508	0.6724	1.1009
$E_a, k_{0,p}$		0.9975	0.0210	0.9908	0.0220	0.9165	0.3672
b, k_0						1	-

TABLE 3.2: Values of the adjusted R-squared and NRMSE for each fitting. Dehydrogenation is modelled as a second-order reaction.

Any constraints on discharge time arise from the need to meet hydrogen demand and faster reaction kinetics are not necessarily preferable.

Tab. 3.2 shows that the fitting procedure achieves a high degree of accuracy in determining the values of the activation energy E_a , pressure coefficient b and pre-exponential factor k_0 ; however, the coefficient b is calculated with only two values, so no NRMSE can be defined. There is currently no information on the behaviour of the NEC for absolute hydrogen pressures above 1.00 bar, but Fig. 3.4d indicates a relatively stable trend with pressure, suggesting that the found pressure dependence may still hold for pressure levels slightly above 1.00 bar, as explained below.

The dehydrogenation modelling was carried out without the 473 K-0.25 bar data set. Due to the limited number of datasets available and the very different behaviour, its introduction would introduce significant errors in the model (Fig. 3.4d). It is evident that with only these data to work with, the expected accuracy in the proposed range (0.25-0.50 bar and 433-453 K, 0.50-1.00 bar and 433-473 K) is still high, the error in the coefficient of pressure dependence could increase rapidly outside the test conditions. However, a pressure-dependent rate equation is needed to allow more refined control strategies, although no information is currently available for higher pressure levels. When each data set is included in the model, the pressure dependence appears to have a non-linear behaviour and a sort of temperature dependent saturation effect takes place between 0.50-1.00 bar, which actually suggests the possibility of extending the validity of the model for a limited pressure increase.

Thus, Fig. 3.4d shows the effect of pressure on the rate constant; apart from the already discussed trend (magenta line), two configurations have been analysed: one that includes the 433-453 K profiles at 0.25 bar (dark purple line), while the other does not include any 0.25 bar data (light purple line). The two different experimental datasets either include (white star) or exclude (black dot) the 473 K-0.25 bar data. While the inclusion of the above data set leads to a drastically different set of coefficients, the inclusion of the two low temperature configurations at 0.25 bar leads to only a limited variation.

Finally, the model proposed here only includes the 0.50 and 1.00 bar data. These data were chosen because, despite relying on a smaller data pool, they provide better performance both in the 0.50-1.00 bar range (as expected) and ultimately also for $p = 0.25$ bar. Conversely, if the two lowest temperature levels at 0.25 bar are considered, the same activation energy E_a used for the higher pressure systems is still valid (Fig. 3.4c), but the newly found $\log k_0$ and b show small deviations from the original values. If only the actual outlier at 0.25 bar is excluded from the model, the absolute value of b increases by 14.51 %, while k_0 increases by 17.30 %, despite the actual fitting parameter obtained¹ which increases by only 0.55 %. It should also be noted that the limited number of sampling points leads to relatively high R^2 even for the 0.25 bar and 473 K profiles, but looking at the plots (Fig. 3.4b) it is clear that significant errors are introduced. NRMSE values therefore give a better indication of the accuracy of the fit.

Fig. 3.5a shows the time evolution of the degree of hydrogenation, comparing the numerically obtained results with the experimental data: an overall good agreement is obtained, in line with the accuracy of the fitting procedure discussed above. Fig. 3.5b summarises the

¹The procedure returns $\log k_0$.

Parameter	Hydrogenation	Dehydrogenation	Unit
n	1	2	-
E_a	28.07	121	kJ/mol
b	0.038	-1.397	1/bar
k_0	30.33	$\approx 3.0617 \times 10^{12}$	1/min
T_{thr}	433	-	K

TABLE 3.3: Fitting parameters of the model. Dehydrogenation parameters were obtained from 0.50-1.00 bar, while hydrogenation's cover the whole temperature and pressure given range.

errors introduced by the model for the proposed parameter set and the one obtained without the high-temperature, low-pressure profile. The statistical parameter on the y-axis is evaluated as the sum of all relative errors between the numerical and experimental data.

While the two models give similar performance at 1.00 bar, the error introduced at 0.50 bar increases with increasing temperature. Reducing the pressure, the second model (purple marker) gives extremely low errors at 433 K, but its performance drops off at 453 K. On the other hand, the first model (purple marker) performs only slightly worse at 433 K, but much better at 453 K. All in all, the chosen model gives more than satisfactory performance. However, a denser and broader data pool is required to better characterise the behaviour of the hydrogen release process. Including or excluding data at 0.25 bar leads to similar coefficients, demonstrating the reliability of the model within and slightly outside the base test conditions. However, the resulting magnitude of k_0 is so high that it alone makes the dehydrogenation phase more prone to error than the hydrogenation phase.

3.2 Conclusions

Table 3.3 shows the numerical value of the parameters required by the model to be put into Eq. 3.13-3.14, found by fitting the experimental data available in literature. Activation energy values are consistent with those available in literature Wan et al., 2012; Peters et al., 2015. These parameters are used as inputs in the following chapters.

It should be noted that different catalyst setups would result in different performance. Although not explicitly stated, the following chapters assume the use of the catalysts described in the data sources Wan et al., 2012; Kiermaier et al., 2021. As more comprehensive studies are published, the kinetic model should be updated. Currently, it has been shown that supported noble metal catalysts are associated with the best performance, with Pd, followed by Pt being the only ones that can lead to complete dehydrogenation and selectivity, while Ru and Rh have slightly worse performances (Yang et al., 2014).

For the dehydrogenation process, overall fairly accurate models have been obtained, taking into account both temperature and pressure dependencies. However, their validity is limited to a relatively narrow range of thermodynamic conditions due to the relative lack of data. Due to the inconsistent behaviour in terms of reaction order under different thermodynamic conditions, a denser and larger data pool would benefit the reliability of the model. In the end, the proposed model was calibrated with data based only on the 0.50 and 1.00 bar pressure profiles. It performs more than adequately even when extrapolating data at 0.25 bar, demonstrating the stability of the underlying chemical-kinetic model. Future work could focus on developing a functional relationship between the reaction order n and the thermodynamic conditions of the system, and on evaluating the behaviour of the system during dehydrogenation at relatively high pressure, but this would require dedicated experimental data.

In the case of hydrogenation, the model gave excellent results and allowed an exhaustive characterisation. The accuracy is relatively low at low temperatures (368 and 378 K) and high pressures (70 bar); however, the errors are still very limited and these conditions are not optimal for practical applications. Moreover, at these temperatures, the model only loses accuracy at medium-low hydrogen contents, i.e. in the first stage of the hydrogenation process, when the LOHC heats up significantly, well above these temperature levels.

(A) Dehydrogenation modelling for 0.25-1.00 bar systems using the lilac model (Fig. 3.4d). Lines with empty markers: model results; filled markers: experimental data.

(B) Introduced error: datasets 1-3 for systems held at increasingly high temperature and 1.00 bar; 4-6 for systems held at increasingly high temperature and 0.50 bar; 7-8 for 433 and 453 K systems at 0.25 bar.

FIGURE 3.5: Dehydrogenation modelling results.

On the other hand, operating the system at 70 bar would only require higher energy costs and stresses on materials without any significant benefit. When the system temperature is above 433-453 K, a simple kinetic model cannot accurately describe the hydrogenation process. Two novel correction factors have been introduced to extend the validity of the model. The proposed model accounts for both the lack of further acceleration in the kinetic rate and the reduced storage capacity with simple modifications to the base equation. Alternative approaches were not found in the literature and although more complex solutions could be sought, the model already provides excellent agreement with experimental data.

Lastly, the kinetic analysis thus returns information about the correct NEC thermodynamic working conditions for each phase:

- Hydrogenation: temperature still has to be relatively high to favour good kinetics, however there is no demand to be met and so the only kinetic constrain is related to the newly generated hydrogen intermediate buffer size. Depending on the allowable highest pressure that can be reached, ideally about 60 bar as higher values hints at a reduced variability with respect to pressure levels, temperature should fall in the 413-453 K range, to avoid storage capacity reduction.
- Dehydrogenation: conversely, high temperatures while beneficial could lead to more complex coupling with the end user. While SOFCs working temperature are high enough not to pose a temperature limit (650-950 °C (Huang et al., 2022)), for industrial applications different waste heat temperature are available. Studies over waste heat sources from the industry, from power plants, from marine/vessels, and from gas compression stations for Europe, add up to a total of 700 TWh/y of recoverable heat within a temperature range of 80-200 °C (Papapetrou and Kosmadakis, 2022). Regardless, both the catalyst and the carrier thermal stability introduce an additional constrain, as well below 570 K (Xie et al., 2022) as additional mass loss beyond the initial dehydrogenation onset is recorded. As low pressure favours dehydrogenation, and since pressure levels below at least 1-1.5 bar are unlikely to be feasible for a real system, temperature should not fall below the 473 K mark, to avoid the otherwise needed LOHC oversizing to compensate for the otherwise quite low mass flow rate achievable.

Chapter 4

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: Thermodynamic Model

4.1 The Lumped Parameter Approach

Once the kinetic laws have been modelled, a general LOHC-based storage system can be simulated: the two reactions that take place result in a certain amount of heat being transferred, so an external fluid must be used to quench either the temperature rise or the temperature fall. The whole system can be characterised by the following equations in a lumped parameter model, which is very similar to MH-based systems (Gambini, 1994; Gambini, Manno, and Vellini, 2008):

1. Kinetic rate:

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} = f(\text{DoH}, T, p) \quad (4.1)$$

2. Heat Transfer:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \dot{m}_f c_f [1 - \exp(-\text{NTU})] (T - T_{f,i}) \quad (4.2)$$

3. Energy Balance¹:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{a_x \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} [\Delta H_r + c_p(T_g - T_0) - c_v(T_g - T_0)] - \frac{dQ}{dt}}{C_T} \quad (4.3)$$

with Eq. 4.1 being provided in the previous sections and Eq. 4.2-4.3 being written for the charging phase² to evaluate the heat exchanged with the external fluid ($\frac{dQ}{dt}$) and temperature variation ($\frac{dT}{dt}$) as a function of the external fluid mass flow rate and specific heat coefficient (\dot{m}_f, c_f), depending on the exchanger number of transfer units (NTU). The effective temperature change also needs to account for the heat associated with the reaction due to the reaction enthalpy (ΔH_r), as well as the enthalpy and internal energy flows (the specific heat capacities at constant pressure and volume c_p and c_v are indeed referred to hydrogen) and the system thermal capacity (C_T). Concentration to mass conversion factor a_x is expressed through Eq. 4.4.

$$a_x = w_{\%,\text{max}} m_{\text{LOHC}} \quad (4.4)$$

A complete analysis of the system would require the design of its heat exchanger, but to evaluate its behaviour first, only $C_{T,0}$ ³, \dot{m}_f and NTU need to be assigned. For the purpose of this analysis:

- $C_{T,0} \approx C_{T,0\text{LOHC}}$

¹With perfect gas approximation assumption.

²During the discharging phase Eq. 4.2-4.3 are still valid if only with a different sign and T replacing T_g in Eq. 4.3 since hydrogen is released at the LOHC's temperature

³Constant term of heat capacity, independent of hydrogen content.

- Since what really concerns Eq. 4.2 is a combination of \dot{m}_f and NTU only one parameter was assigned as:

$$\text{HTR} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{ext,fluid}}{\dot{Q}_{r,max}} \cdot \frac{T_{des}}{T_{f,i} - T}$$

$$\text{HTR} = \frac{\dot{m}_f c_f [1 - \exp(-\text{NTU})]}{\Delta H_r \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}} / T_{des}}$$

The Heat Transfer Ratio (HTR) was deduced from the reactor thermal balance accounting for the sensible heat provided by the external fluid, and the reaction heat, to assess the heat transfer performance. More specifically, the HTR is defined as the ratio of the heat transferred through the heat transfer ratio per unit temperature difference, by the maximum heat rate induced by the dehydrogenation reaction per the reactor design temperature. By accounting for the reaction enthalpy and the design temperature (i.e. dehydrogenation temperature), this parameter provides an indicator to compare different carriers. A more detailed analysis is provided in Chapter 5.

Simulation data for both phases are summed up by the end of Chapter 4 with temperature and composition averaged data being deployed to describe the thermodynamic properties of the system. Following the work done for MH (see Appendix A), a lumped parameter simplified model of a shell and tube design has been tested. Results are summed up in Appendix C.

4.1.1 Hydrogenation

During the early stages of the hydrogenation process, the temperature of the system could either rise or fall: if the amount of external fluid supplied for a given initial temperature to a given heat exchanger (i.e. for a given heat transfer efficiency) is high enough, sufficient heat will be removed from the system and its temperature will fall to that of the heat transfer fluid. On the other hand, if the reaction heat released is too high, the temperature will rise until the kinetic rate decreases sufficiently. Since the external fluid has to quench the temperature rise, the external fluid temperature must be lower than the LOHC temperature.

This means that because of the actual operating temperature levels, either water or a diathermic oil could be used. While the latter option would result in more expensive systems, it would allow for higher $T_{f,i}$. The lower the value, the lower the temperature of the system would be, thus making temperature management easier, but as the temperature of the system decreases, the kinetics of the system deteriorate. Higher temperature levels could also make heat recovery attractive, so different input parameters were tested.

Looking at Fig. 4.1 it is clear that if the chosen fluid is water, the limited $T_{f,i}$ value would bound the system to have slow kinetics and if HTR falls into this range, a way higher inlet temperature is needed to achieve feasible charging times. As $T_{f,i}$ increases better kinetics are showcased since the system's temperature is generally higher. The lower HTR, the longer it takes for the system to settle on $T_{f,i}$, resulting in greater amount of stored hydrogen. If the inlet temperature is chosen so that $T_{f,i} = T_i$, definitely shorter charging times are required as it can be seen in Fig. 4.2. Much better performances can be pursued as long as the system's temperature settles to higher values regardless of HTR.

As the inlet external fluid temperature is the same as the initial LOHC temperature, a temperature rise is inevitable, but the extent of this will depend on the efficiency of the heat exchanger and the amount of refrigerant available. Higher combinations of these factors will give only moderate temperature rises, resulting in longer charging times than the HTR = 0.5 setup. These considerations could still make a water coupled system interesting: although the temperature of the system is bound to eventually reach low temperature levels, if HTR is sufficiently low, the reaction heat released could be enough to keep the temperature of the system high enough to achieve short charging times. This scenario would require either a reduced mass flow of water or a less efficient heat exchanger, which would benefit the actual economy of the storage system, but not the possibility of recovering some of the heat released.

(A) $T_{f,i} = 300$ K.

(B) $T_{f,i} = 353$ K.

FIGURE 4.1: HTF inlet temperature effect over DoH and temperature profiles.

FIGURE 4.2: Hydrogenation profiles for $T_{f,i} = 433$ K.

However Fig. 4.3 highlights a concerning phenomenon: if the amount of hydrogen being released ($a_x \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt}$) is sufficiently high and the heat exchange is not efficient enough, so that low HTR values result in sufficiently low $\frac{dQ}{dt}$, the system's temperature rises throughout the whole process and above the stability range of the liquid, whose temperature should be below 400 °C. This process could easily lead to even higher temperature with temperature peaks well above 1000 K.

Regardless of whether or not this situation could be easily avoided by proper design, the proposed kinetic model has a flaw: since there is no temperature dependence other than the Arrhenius-like one, an increase in temperature will only accelerate the reaction, resulting in more heat being released and thus even higher temperature levels. This phenomenon does not occur in MH-based systems because of the introduction of the equilibrium pressure, but since any pressure dependence is independent of temperature, there is nothing to stop the kinetics of LOHCs from ever increasing. If this were true, real systems would have to be carefully designed to avoid reaching critical conditions under any operating conditions. However, the data collected on the loading phase are not consistent with this statement.

Looking at the provided data (Wan et al., 2012) two things can be observed:

- Saturation consistently takes place at about 5.8% but when the temperature increases above a certain value, then saturation phenomena appear for decreasing value of hydrogen content.
- Disregarding saturation values, it seems like systems held at different temperature greatly differs from one another when temperature is low, while for the higher temperature profiles the curves are way more alike, with gradients being basically the same and saturation taking place at the same time when the temperature is above a certain level. This is not compatible with the simple Arrhenius like dependency, which should instead lead to ever increasing gaps between profiles belonging to systems held at higher temperature levels. As a matter of fact the proposed model yielded adequate results as long as temperature was below 453 K since simulating higher temperature levels led to almost instantaneous uptakes.

To face both effects two changes in the model can be implemented, acting whenever the system's temperature rises above a critical value:

FIGURE 4.3: Charging process with $T_{f,i} = 353$ K and $HTR = 0.1$.

- Instead of having saturation take place for $DoH = 1$, the limit value that is deployed to evaluate $\frac{dDoH}{dt}$ is lowered to match different equilibrium conditions. LOHCs' hydrogenation is an exothermic reversible process so it is only reasonable that if temperature is too high, only a limited amount of bonds are saturated and lower conversions are achieved.
- Temperature increases lead to faster kinetics as long as it falls in a certain range, above which only marginal benefits can be seen. A modified Arrhenius relation can be deployed, as expressed in Chapter 3.

Although this last consideration could be argued to be rather hazardous, it is consistent with the data presented and implies that at high temperatures the reactants react so rapidly that the rate-determining step changes: this is the case for diffusion-controlled reactions, and even combustion can be considered as such if the temperature is high enough (Roussel, 2021).

To account for a reduced storage capability, the equilibrium constant K_{eq} can be introduced, and its value is a function of temperature. As explained in Chapter 3 the following relation was used:

$$\Delta G_r = -R_u T \log K_{eq}$$

with the values of $\Delta G_{hyd}(T)$ found in the literature for $p = 60$ bar (Choi et al., 2016). They fit with great accuracy the analytical equation in the proposed range 300-500 K, while being expressed as Eq. 4.5. While no additional data was found for higher temperature levels, stability issues limit the foreseeable temperature rise so that a linear extrapolation was still deemed appropriate.

$$\Delta G_{hyd}^0(T[K]) = 0.0961T - 53.3247 \text{ [kJ/mol}_{H_2}] \quad (4.5)$$

For the hydrogenation reaction, the equilibrium constant can be written with respect to the molar concentration (χ) as Eq. 4.6:

$$K_{eq} = \frac{\chi_{12H-NEC}}{6^6 (1 - \chi_{12H-NEC})^7} \quad (4.6)$$

where, as both the equilibrium and the ΔG refer to the same reference pressure, the pressure correction factor introduced by the gaseous component is omitted, and with $\chi_{12H-NEC}$ being the equilibrium concentration of 12H-NEC. Limited information was found about the actual mechanism behind the reaction but related articles (Peters et al., 2019) suggest that hydrogen gas is vented in the a reactor half-filled with LOHC and whether the reaction takes

FIGURE 4.4: DoH_{lim} assuming $\chi_{12H-NEC} \approx DoH_{lim}$, blue line, and accounting for the H_2 correction, orange line.

place at the phase interface or in solution is unknown: it's than debatable how χ should be defined and if hydrogen concentration in the solution should only be due to phase equilibrium or not. Since the hydrogenation phase follows a first order kinetic, arguably due to excess hydrogen being supplied in the system, it is reasonable to assume the reaction takes place at the phase interface. For high values of $\chi_{12H-NEC}$, $DoH \approx DoH_{lim}$. However, while $\chi_{12H-NEC}$ refers to 12 H-NEC concentration in the liquid solution, the degree of hydrogenation is meant to measure how much hydrogen is stored in the LOHC with respect to its storage capability. As a matter of fact, $\chi_{12H-NEC} \equiv DoH_{lim}$ if $\chi_{H_2} = 0$, else a correction could come in the form of Eq. 4.7, assuming the final stoichiometric concentrations.

$$\chi_{12H-NEC} : 1 - \frac{6}{7}(1 - \chi_{12H-NEC}) = DoH_{lim} : 1 \quad (4.7)$$

Fig. 4.4 showcases two different behaviours: if no hydrogen correction is implemented a greater temperature sensibility is to be expected with obviously overall lower conversions achievable. For example, a 493 K system would yield either a $DoH = 0.83$ or $DoH = 0.97$, while experimental data manifest saturation at about $DoH = 0.88$, meaning that while the high temperature sensibility is not present in low temperature systems, all of whom displays a full hydrogenation, it somewhat picks up as temperature increases so that the foreseeable expected saturation level should fall somewhere in the middle of the two lines. This different behaviour could be indicative of other phenomena taking place and influencing the overall reaction.

Equation. 4.6 only holds true for reactions taking place in solutions, the presence of a gaseous compound demands to rewrite the equation to take into account pressure. As such a new form was introduced as in Eq. 4.8 for $p_0 = 1$ bar.

$$K_{eq} = \frac{1}{6^6(1 - \chi_{12H-NEC})^6 \left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right)^6} \quad (4.8)$$

This newly defined K_{eq} does not, however, lead to any satisfactory result as discussed in Appendix B.

FIGURE 4.5: The case nomenclature accounts for: dataset with no correction, and corrected data with either first or second correction applied to either only high temperature values, or the whole temperature range respectively.

FIGURE 4.6: Profiles for $T = 493$ K under different DoH_{lim} assumptions.

Looking at Fig. 4.5 it is clear that Case 3 and Case 4 do not show any significant difference, as the DoH_{lim} correction is too small, and while the maximum temperature reached is still about 50 K lower, the performances are mostly the same as Case 1. In fact, real data show no saturation reduction for temperature levels below 483 K. On the other hand, Case 2 and Case 5 are very different from Case 1 because the correction is more significant. While case 5 saturates at too low a hydrogen content, it shows a much smoother trend than case 2, where the offset limit acts as an on/off control. Both cases result in a reduced temperature peak, although case 2 requires a longer time to saturate because it saturates at a higher hydrogen content. The introduction of these limiting factors has definitely resulted in some difference in the model, but it is now imperative to consider the initial data sets provided (Wan et al., 2012) to evaluate whether this implementation could be physically accurate.

Looking at Fig. 4.6 it is clear that, despite some improvement, the model still cannot describe the behaviour of the real system, with too fast kinetics occurring in the early stages of the hydrogenation process. In order to limit the influence of temperature on the kinetics, it is necessary to define the maximum value of temperature that leads to a faster charging process. Looking back at the experimental data (Wan et al., 2012), the first data set to show some discrepancy between its kinetics and the model belongs to the system held at 453 K.

From Fig. 4.7 it is evident that:

- Since both corrections tackle phenomena that take place at high temperature, the higher the temperature level, the greater the benefit of their introduction.
- For the system held at 453 K saturation actually takes place for $\text{DoH}_f = 1$, so the correction of any saturation level can be omitted, but for the sake of investigating its effect the second saturation correction (orange line) was also implemented. Although its effect is limited, it restrains the kinetics of the system and leads to the best fit in the early stages of the process, while for higher DoH a model with only the Arrhenius correction would be a better choice and is generally sufficient to account for the errors of the original model. Throughout the simulation, the newly added temperature correction gives better results, and this is most evident for low DoH where high concentration (and temperature) gradients would occur in real systems.
- For the system held at 493 K saturation takes place for a reduced amount of stored hydrogen, so the first saturation correction (blue line) was also implemented and this time its implementation is legitimised by the data, the second saturation correction (orange line) could also have been used as it actually has a more meaningful definition

(A) 453 K profiles under different assumptions.

(B) 493 K profiles under different assumptions.

FIGURE 4.7: Experimental and modelling dehydrogenation profiles under different assumptions for low (top panel) and high temperature (bottom panel).

FIGURE 4.8: NEC hydrogenation phase modelling comparison with and without either or both corrections.

and seems to give better results, but the actual behaviour of the system falls somewhere in between the two lines. A smoother transition from a fully saturated equilibrium composition to a saturation-limited one has yet to be implemented. Regardless of the errors in the evaluation of K_{eq} , the expected equilibrium concentrations are not too far from the actual data. If no correction is considered, the model is definitely inadequate to describe the process, and since there is a real reduction in storage capacity at this temperature level, the best performance is always obtained by the model with both corrections. Looking at Fig. 4.6 it is clear that this second correction to the Arrhenius dependence, although less obvious at first sight, is in fact the more effective one.

Having tested the validity of this second claim, it can be implemented in the model and for the same input parameters $HTR = 0.1$ and $T_{f,i} = 353$ K.

As shown in Fig. 4.8 the temperature rise is now limited to about 40 K, this obviously hinders the speed of the reaction as can be seen from the DoH_f . The first saturation limit was implemented but only if the system's temperature were to rise above a critical level. Since the newly added correction prevents the temperature from ever reaching it due to a reduced hydrogenation velocity and thus released heat, profiles 3 and 4 coincide. Since the initial temperature of the system is already set to 433 K, the newly added kinetic limit immediately acts to slow down the hydrogenation process. With less hydrogen saturating the aromatic rings, the heat of reaction released is less and so is the resulting temperature rise, resulting in a much reduced peak occurring somewhat earlier than it would have otherwise. Once the temperature begins to fall, the kinetics are no longer hindered until the temperature falls below the limit: then the process continues, but at a slower and slower rate. The whole process is shown in Fig. 4.9. Longer charging times are required and because of the system's temperature settling to such a low level, saturation is particularly slow. However the process ends for $DoH = 0.9 - 0.95$, taking about 40 min. If the inlet fluid's temperature is set to 433 K the system's loading time go back to being around 20 min. If the inlet fluid temperature is set to 433 K, while keeping $HTR = 0.1$, the system loading time goes back to around 20 min, which is perfectly in line with the data provided (Wan et al., 2012). A short, almost constant time interval occurs in the simulated model due to the ON/OFF implementation of the limited saturation correction. Although it does not lead to a significant error, this effect could be mitigated if the correction was only applied for $\frac{dT}{dt} > 0$.

(A) Final DoH and T trends.

(B) Low HTR simulation with $T_{f,i}$ set to 433 K.FIGURE 4.9: Complete process of hydrogenation for different $T_{f,i}$.

FIGURE 4.10: HTR effect over the DoH and T profiles of NEC's dehydrogenation phase.

4.1.2 Dehydrogenation

Data provided on dehydrogenation are still too limited and fall in such a range that introducing the concept of chemical equilibrium to improve on the performances of the model is not safely doable. However, two considerations can be made:

- Hydrogen release takes place under endothermic conditions, so lower temperature levels inhibit the final conversion while a higher temperature would promote both the kinetic and thermodynamic of the reaction. Because heat has to be provided for the reaction to take place, instability should not be of any concern for dehydrogenation.
- Because the temperature drop is localized in the early stages of the reaction, as long as the heat transfer fluid's inlet temperature is high enough, the final charging state can easily be set as low as desired since the system's temperature would eventually settle on $T_{f,i}$.

This means that the dehydrogenation phase is inherently less susceptible to both of the phenomena that ultimately occur during hydrogenation, so running the program without modification was considered acceptable and appropriate in the absence of more meaningful data. The data provided in the literature relates only to low pressure systems, but despite better performance at lower pressure levels (Kiermaier et al., 2021) a pressure below 1 bar is inappropriate. To provide a meaningful hydrogen release temperature, it must be at least 473 K, which means that the heat transfer fluid cannot be water. While a more accurate analysis would require the design of the heat exchanger and the choice of fluid, this is irrelevant for the purposes of this analysis.

Having set both T_i and $T_{f,i}$ to 473 K, Fig. 4.10 highlights that an increase in HTR only yields considerable improvements until a certain minimum value of the parameter; any further increase would only lead to marginal improvements but at the cost of either higher efficiencies required or higher heat transfer's mass flow. The temperature drop is definitely lower than the peak during the hydrogenation process because dehydrogenation's kinetic is slower as confirmed by experimental data.

For a heat transfer ratio value of $HTR = 0.5$, extending the simulation to longer time periods (Fig. 4.11) still does not lead to the desired discharge state of $DoH_f = 0.1$, but this

FIGURE 4.11: Extended simulation DoH and temperature profiles.

result is only consistent with the experimental data provided. As soon as low concentration levels are reached the process slows down despite temperature being constant. This difference between the two phases could be due to the different concentration dependence. Since hydrogen uptake can be schematised as a first order reaction, while hydrogen release follows a second order approximation, the kinetics of the latter is more hindered in the final stages of the process. This difference in behaviour is intrinsic to the process as hydrogen release cannot be schematised as a pseudo first order reaction as there is no excess of reactant.

Even increasing the initial temperature of the system (and the inlet temperature of the external fluid) does not give the desired speed increase. If the system has to provide hydrogen with this catalyst and in this temperature range, it would require a significant oversizing (i.e. $\text{DoH}_f > 0.1$) to allow for decent release times. This is consistent with the data provided (Kiermaier et al., 2021), although the model does indeed provide a slightly slower kinetic during the final stage of the process. A final case scenario is therefore shown in Fig. 4.12: a temperature increase leads to faster kinetics during the whole process but significant improvements are registered only for high DoH.

4.2 Conclusions

In thermodynamic system modeling, the level of complexity required can vary significantly depending on the intended purpose of the study. This principle holds particularly true in the context of Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs), which, despite their promising potential as hydrogen storage solutions, are still in the early stages of technological readiness. The current state of LOHC technology, characterized by a lack of robust experimental setups and a limited amount of detailed information available in existing literature, suggests that overly intricate modeling approaches may not only be impractical but could also lead to speculative conclusions that are not firmly grounded in empirical evidence.

Given the nascent stage of LOHC development, a simplified modeling approach appears to be both necessary and effective. Preliminary studies have shown that such an approach can yield valuable qualitative insights into the system's behavior while also achieving a high degree of accuracy, provided certain conditions are met. In particular, the assumption of a constant temperature across the reactor section, which is more easily maintained in batch reactors, has been identified as a key factor in ensuring the validity of simplified models. Batch reactors are typically used for small-scale applications and are equipped with efficient

FIGURE 4.12: DoH and T profiles for increasingly high HTF inlet temperature.

stirring mechanisms, which play a critical role in maintaining temperature homogeneity and facilitating the removal of released hydrogen.

The importance of temperature control in batch reactors cannot be overstated, as it directly influences the reaction kinetics and the overall safety of the process. Contrary to what indicators such as the Biot number might suggest, the interplay between reaction heat and Arrhenius-type chemical kinetics can actually promote temperature homogenization within the reactor. This phenomenon is particularly significant during the hydrogenation phase, where the exothermic nature of the reaction poses a risk of temperature instability. If not properly managed, these temperature fluctuations could force the reactor to operate at levels beyond the recommended limits for the substances involved, potentially compromising both the efficiency and safety of the process.

However, it is important to note that the reaction kinetics do not increase indefinitely with temperature. As the reaction progresses, the rate of reaction becomes increasingly constrained by the availability of hydrogen itself. This self-limiting aspect of the reaction provides a natural check against runaway temperature increases, reducing the likelihood of thermal instability even in the absence of complex thermal management systems. This inherent safety feature reinforces the case for adopting a simplified modeling approach, particularly in the early stages of LOHC technology development, where the primary goal is to establish a foundational understanding of the system rather than to achieve precise predictive accuracy.

The focus on batch reactors in preliminary studies is justified not only by their relative simplicity but also by their suitability for small-scale applications, which are the most likely initial use cases for LOHC technology. Batch reactors offer several advantages in this context, including better control over reaction conditions and the ability to quickly adjust parameters in response to observed system behavior. Moreover, the efficient stirring mechanisms typically employed in batch reactors help to mitigate the challenges associated with temperature control, further supporting the use of simplified models.

In conclusion, while the ultimate goal of LOHC research may be to develop comprehensive models that can accurately predict system behavior under a wide range of conditions, the current state of the technology necessitates a more pragmatic approach. The lack of extensive experimental data and the early stage of technological development mean that

highly detailed modeling efforts would likely be speculative and could divert attention from more immediate research priorities. Instead, a focus on simplified models, particularly for batch reactors, allows researchers to gain valuable insights into the fundamental behavior of LOHC systems without overextending the available data.

This approach not only provides qualitative understanding but also ensures that the models remain relevant and accurate as long as key assumptions, such as constant temperature across the reactor, are maintained. As LOHC technology matures and more experimental data becomes available, these simplified models can serve as a foundation for more sophisticated simulations, ultimately contributing to the development of robust, reliable, and scalable hydrogen storage solutions. For now, however, the emphasis should be on practical, attainable objectives that align with the current state of the technology, ensuring that research efforts are both productive and grounded in reality.

Chapter 5

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: Reactors

5.1 Batch Reactor

5.1.1 Description

Batch reactors are constant-volume vessels not unlike common cooking pots Smith, Inomata, and Peters, 2013. A batch reactor has no inlet or outlet flows, and perfect mixing is assumed in the ideal reactor, so that the reaction rate is independent of position Foutch and Johannes, 2003. In a LOHC system, reaction kinetics is influenced by temperature, as such a perfectly mixed batch reactor would also be isotherm.

Regardless of the model, heat is provided to the system through the reactor. Two alternative designs of a batch reactor are evaluated: the jacketed and coiled reactors (Fig. 5.1), differing in how heat is provided to the system. Heat transfer performances and the expected range of variability for each parameter were taken from Gavin Gavin, 1999, with reference to the conventional jacket with agitation nozzles and the half-pipe coils designs.

An optimisation process was held considering both the thermal efficacy of the reactor and the power consumption for the heat transfer fluid circulation and LOHC stirring. Power requirements for the agitation nozzles were considered negligible. The global optimum was found through Matlab's Global Optimization Tool, while the external fluid's properties were evaluated through the CoolProp library for Dowtherm Q.

The Heat Transfer Ratio (HTR), introduced in Section 4 as Eq. 5.1, to assess the heat transfer efficacy; in a specific application, different requirements may have to be considered if additional conditions have to be respected. For the scope of this analysis, thermal energy consumption is the prime driver of the optimization procedure, thus making the HTR a fundamental parameter, see Sec. 5.1.4.

$$\text{HTR} = \frac{\varepsilon \dot{m}_f c_f}{\Delta H_r \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}} / T_{\text{des}}}. \quad (5.1)$$

As for the actual sizing procedure, given the volume required to host the carrier, for a given aspect ratio AR (Eq. 5.2), usually in the range of 1-4, both the height (H) and inner diameter (d_i) of the batch can be evaluated (Eq. 5.3).

$$\text{AR} = \frac{H}{d_{in}} \quad (5.2)$$

$$V = \frac{\pi}{4} \frac{H^3}{\text{AR}^2} \quad (5.3)$$

It should be noted that H is here defined in terms of filling level but the actual height of the reactor is likely to be somewhat higher to allow for easier gas – liquid separation. Regardless, this upper empty space mostly unconcerns the heat transfer performances and was then neglected in this analysis.

Having defined the wall thickness (δ_w) (usually about 7 mm) the batch outer diameter is easily derived from Eq. 5.4.

$$d_e = d_{in} + 2\delta_w \quad (5.4)$$

FIGURE 5.1: Batch reactor designs; going from left to right: jacketed batch reactor and coiled batch reactor.

In a similar fashion jacketed reactors have an additional external diameter to define. The jacket outer diameter (d_j) is evaluated as seen in Eq. 5.5 as function of the jacket thickness (δ_j), usually in the 0.020-0.050 m range. For coiled-pipe reactors a tube diameter (d) input size is to be chosen.

$$d_j = d_e + 2\delta_j \quad (5.5)$$

For a given spacing (s) both the number of pipes (N_{pipes} , Eq. 5.6) and the heat exchange surface (A_{hex}) are derived (Eq. 5.7-5.8) for both jacketed and coiled designs; commonly represented spacing values range from 0.035-0.050 m. Eq. 5.8 showcases that in a well design reactor coil act like fins and even the residual wall surface partakes in the exchange with a certain efficiency (ε_f). In this type of reactor pipes do not have a circular section, and they are characterised by an angular opening (β). This value was set as 180° ; another common value is 270° . Most pipes have a diameter around 5.08-10.16 cm¹.

$$N_{pipes} = \text{int}_{min} \left(\frac{H + s}{d + s} \right) \quad (5.6)$$

$$A_{hex} = \pi d_e H \quad (5.7)$$

$$A_{hex} = \pi d_e \left[(H - N_{pipes}d)\varepsilon_f + N_{pipes}d \right] \quad (5.8)$$

Having set the mean external fluid speed (v) given the cross section (A_f) from Eq. 5.9-5.10 for the jacketed and coiled reactor respectively, the mass flow (m_f) is obtained (Eq. 6.9). The external fluid speed is commonly set to be around 0.50-1.50 m/s.

¹These values are equivalent to the 2-4 in range.

$$A_f = H \frac{d_j - d_e}{2} \quad (5.9)$$

$$A_f = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \cdot \frac{\beta}{360^\circ} N_{pipes} \quad (5.10)$$

$$\dot{m}_f = \rho_f v A_f \quad (5.11)$$

To determine the HTR, the heat transfer effectiveness (ε , Eq. 5.12) is to be evaluated, as a function of the number of transport units (NTU, Eq. 5.13).

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp \text{NTU} \quad (5.12)$$

$$\text{NTU} = \frac{U A_{hex}}{\dot{m}_f c_f} \quad (5.13)$$

In jacketed reactors the convective heat transfer coefficient (α_f) can be estimated from empirical formulae such as Eq. 5.14 as a function of the Reynolds number (Re) evaluated with the hydraulic diameter), the Prandtl number (Pr) and an entrance correction (Ge) as defined in Eq. 5.15:

$$\text{Nu} = 0.0192 \text{Re}^{0.795} \text{Pr}^{0.495} \exp \left[-0.0225 \left(\log \text{Pr}^2 \right) \right] \left[1 + 0.059 \left(\text{Re} \frac{d_{hyd}^2}{d_{in}^2} \right)^{0.34} \right] \text{Ge} \quad (5.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ge} &= 1 & \text{Re} \frac{d_{hyd}^2}{d_c^2} &\leq 4.72 \\ 1 + 5.71 \frac{d_{hyd}}{\pi d_e} \left[1 - \exp \left(1 - 0.07 \frac{\pi d_e}{d_{hyd}} \right) \right] & & \text{Re} \frac{d_{hyd}^2}{d_c^2} &> 4.72 \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

and having defined the curvature diameter (d_c) through Eq. 5.16-5.17.

$$\alpha_c = \arctan \frac{2H}{\pi d_{in}} \quad (5.16)$$

$$d_c = \frac{d_{in}}{\cos \alpha_c} \quad (5.17)$$

In coiled reactors α_f (Eq. 5.18) is a function of the Reynolds number (evaluated with the hydraulic diameter), the Prandtl number and the ratio between the hydraulic and curvature diameter.

$$\text{Nu} = 0.0225 \text{Re}^{0.795} \text{Pr}^{0.495} \exp \left[-0.0225 \left(\log \text{Pr}^2 \right) \right] \left[1 + 0.059 \left(\text{Re} \frac{d_{hyd}^2}{d_{in}^2} \right)^{0.34} \right] \quad (5.18)$$

The pumping power requirement is conversely evaluated from Eq. 5.19, having defined the concentrated and distributed pressure losses (Eq. 5.20-5.21) and the fanning friction factor (f , Eq. 5.22-5.24 for jacketed and coiled reactors). The curvature effect is accounted by K_{elbow} in Eq. 5.20 as a tabulated value function of d_{hyd} , d_e for a 90° bending. As for the Gnielinski correlation (Eq. 5.22) the value of Re^* has to be evaluated through Eq. 5.23.

$$P = \dot{m}_f \frac{\Delta p_C + \Delta p_D}{\rho_f} \quad (5.19)$$

$$\Delta p_C = 4K_{elbow} \rho_f \frac{v^2}{2} \quad (5.20)$$

$$\Delta p_D = f \frac{\pi (d_e + d)}{d_{hyd}} \rho_f \frac{v^2}{2} \quad (5.21)$$

$$f = (1.8 \log_{10} \text{Re}^* - 1.5)^{-2} \quad (5.22)$$

$$\text{Re}^* = \frac{\text{Re} \left[\left(1 - \frac{d_e^2}{d_j^2}\right) + \left(1 + \frac{d_e^2}{d_j^2}\right) \log \frac{d_e}{d_j} \right]}{\left(1 - \frac{d_e^2}{d_j^2}\right) \log \frac{d_e}{d_j}} \quad (5.23)$$

$$f = \frac{16}{\text{Re}} \quad \text{Re} < 2100$$

$$f = \frac{0.0791}{\text{Re}^{0.25}} \quad 2100 \leq \text{Re} \leq 10^7 \quad (5.24)$$

$$f = 0.0014 + \frac{0.125}{\text{Re}^{0.32}} \quad \text{Re} > 10^7$$

It must also be noted that the hydraulic diameter defined for pressure loss evaluation is not the same as the one required for heat transfer analysis since the reference wet perimeter is different. To promote homogeneity and optimised reaction conditions, an impeller is thus required to mix the bulk liquid. Its power consumption scales with its diameter, rotational speed, LOHC density and viscosity. This section uses correlations available in the literature Scargiali et al., 2017, assuming a Half Hold-up impeller (Eq. 5.25).

$$d_{imp} = \frac{D_{in}}{3} \quad (5.25)$$

Power consumption is evaluated from empirical equations having defined three dimensionless numbers: the power number (N_p), the impeller-imposed Reynolds (Re_{imp}) number and the Froude number (Fr) as respectively reported in Eq. 5.26, 5.27, 5.28.

$$N_p = \frac{P}{\rho_L \omega^3 d_{imp}^5} \quad (5.26)$$

$$\text{Re}_{imp} = \frac{\rho_L \omega d_{imp}^2}{\mu_L} \quad (5.27)$$

$$\text{Fr} = \frac{d_{imp} \omega^2}{g} \quad (5.28)$$

It has been proven that stirring has a key influence on the reaction rate Wan et al., 2012. Currently no information is given on the advised correlation between the rotational speed (ω) and the reactor size. Since laboratory tests are held over small samples it is reasonable to assume that actual stirring conditions could be characterised by a lower rotational speed (10.0-16.6 Hz is advised in Wan et al., 2012) to limit the tip velocity.

As such ω was evaluated imposing a super-critical regime (Eq. 5.29), defined as the transition between a non-aerated (sub-critical) and aerated (super-critical) conditions.

$$N_{cr} = \left(\frac{k_S}{k_K}\right)^{7/10} \left(\frac{\mu_L}{\rho_L}\right)^{1/21} g^{10/21} d_{imp}^{-4/7} \quad (5.29)$$

As seen from Eq. 32, it is safe to assume a reduced required rotational speed as the size of the system increases. N_{cr} is also a function of the liquid thermophysical properties, and

FIGURE 5.2: Finite volume grid chosen for the batch reactor.

the impeller type, with k_S and k_K being empirical parameters and $k_K = 13.5$, $k_S = 9.5$ for the Half Hold-up impeller.

The power consumption is thus deduced from Eq. 5.19, with the power number being evaluated as the minimum value between Eq. 5.30-5.31 for $500 < Re_{imp} < 250\,000$.

$$N_p = k_K Re_{imp}^{-0.3} \quad (5.30)$$

$$N_p = k_S (Re_{imp} Fr)^{-1/3} \quad (5.31)$$

5.1.2 Modeling

Most LOHCs-based literature features a plug-flow reactor coupled with one-dimensional modelling to account for axial gradients. In a batch reactor, however, gradients are expected to arise mainly over the radial direction.

Both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation rates depend on temperature; as the reactions occur, heat is transferred to or from the system. As a result, heat and mass transfer are mutually dependent in LOHCs systems, just like in MHs Gambini, 1994. To solve the associated ODE system, a finite volume approach was chosen. Grid elements are thus defined (Fig. 5.2) in the radial direction to account for any temperature variation due to a different distance from the wall.

The greater the temperature gradient inside the bulk liquid, the more varied the reaction rate is expected to be, which leads to expect that a 0D approach could be unsuitable for studying the system's performance. Since temperature influences the reaction rate only until the optimum threshold value is reached, as explained in Chapter 3 Gambini et al., 2022 and observed for many other carriers Wan et al., 2012; Ye, An, and Xu, 2011, temperature gradients may lead to significant differences between the 0D and 1D models only during dehydrogenation. Most carriers display a maximum hydrogenation kinetic rate at about 453-473 K: any further temperature increase not only does not lead to faster reactions but if a more significant increase occurs, the conversion is hindered. So, if the operating temperature is set around its optimal value and adequate heat sinking is in place, minimal differences should arise between the 0D and 1D models.

In batch reactors, the liquid carrier moves due to the stirring action; however, the influence of convection inside the reactor is expected to be negligible as only moderate speed is given to the carrier since the stirring process is only required to mix the liquid. Moreover, since all kinetic tests rely on small samples, the safest and most conservative approach would be to assume that only conduction takes place inside the bulk of the carrier.

This assumption allows neglecting the effect of mass diffusion as well. While no information is currently available on the mechanism behind diffusion between the saturated and unsaturated compounds, relatively limited gradients are implied.

Each annular element (Fig. 5.2) is thus described by a temperature $T_i(t)$ defining the instantaneous kinetic rate as expressed in Eq. 5.32, which in turn affects the energy balance Sabt, 2015. As the number of elements in the grid (n) increases, the simulation results must converge.

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}_{i,r}}{dt} = k_0 \exp - \left(bp + \frac{E_a}{R_u T_i} \right) \text{DoH}_i^2 \quad (5.32)$$

To provide a more readable text, time dependence in the form of (t) is omitted, however it must be remembered that these systems follow a dynamic behaviour.

Eq. 5.33,5.34,5.35 provide the energy balance for the first, last and inner elements respectively, here written neglecting the influence of the metal wall, and with q_i (Eq. 5.36) representing the mass flow effect over the temperature trend.

$$\rho_L c_p V_1 \frac{\Delta T_1}{dt} = \lambda A_2 \frac{T_2 - T_1}{dr} + q_1 \quad (5.33)$$

$$\rho_L c_p V_n \frac{\Delta T_n}{dt} = \lambda A_{n-1} \frac{T_{n-1} - T_n}{dr} + q_n + A_n \alpha_f (T_f - T_n) \quad (5.34)$$

$$\rho_L c_p V_i \frac{\Delta T_i}{dt} = \lambda A_{i-1} \frac{T_{i-1} - T_i}{dr} + \lambda A_{i+1} \frac{T_{i+1} - T_i}{dr} + q_i \quad (5.35)$$

$$q_i = \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2,i} \left[\Delta H_r + (c_p - c_v) (T_i - T_{ref}) \right] \quad (5.36)$$

Assuming radial flow to be negligible, $\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2,i}$ coincides with \dot{m}_r . Having defined DoH as in Eq. 2.1, it can be proven that the two quantities are related through Eq. 8.6.

$$m_{\text{H}_2} = (w_{\%} m_{\text{LOHC}}) \text{DoH} \quad (5.37)$$

When heat is exchanged with the system through convection and propagated inside the system through conduction, the accuracy of a lumped parameter approach is usually estimated with the Biot number (Bi), as evaluated in Eq. 5.38.

$$\text{Bi} = \frac{\alpha L}{\lambda} \quad (5.38)$$

No experimental data is available for LOHCs conductivities at high temperature, however, using a model found in the literature Bioucas et al., 2020, the conductivity can be estimates as $\lambda = 0.09 \text{ W}/(\text{m K})$ at about 480 K. Even assuming low values of the convective heat transfer coefficient as $\alpha = 1.0 \text{ kW}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K})$, Bi is bounded to be higher than unitary.

However, a lumped parameter approach might still prove effective because the overall reaction heat depends on temperature. If more hydrogen is released (higher temperature), more heat is sunk, thus slowing down the heating action ensured by the external liquid. This balancing mechanism allows for the 0D modelling of MHs Gambini, 1994 and can be tested in LOHCs through comparison with a 1D model. The ODE system derived can be solved with an explicit third-order Runge-Kutta scheme.

The equation set representing the 0D model features only one equation to describe the reaction, so Eq. 5.32 is to be rewritten in terms of an effective mean temperature \bar{T} .

Different values of \bar{T} have been considered (Eq. 5.39,5.40,5.41) since the actual value depends on the real temperature distribution.

$$\bar{T} = T_{r=0} \quad (5.39)$$

$$\bar{T} = T_{r=R} \quad (5.40)$$

$$\bar{T} = \frac{\int_{r=0}^{r=R} T(r) 2\pi dr}{\pi R^2} \quad (5.41)$$

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Net Energy Content	5 kWh	Efficiency	45 % _{HHV}
DoH _{t₀}	0.95	DoH _{t_f}	0.20
Reaction Heat	50.6 kJ/mol _{H₂}	Hydrogen Pressure	1.0 bar
Reactor Aspect Ratio	1.7	\dot{m}_f	0.718 kg/s
T _{t₀}	473.15 K	T _{f,t₀}	473.15 K

TABLE 5.1: Shared input parameters for 0D and 1D simulations.

The inner temperature distribution was evaluated assuming that heat is conducted through a cylinder (Eq. 5.42). This assumption implies the mass flow and its correlated heat flow to only have a moderate influence over the energy balance and is discussed in the section below.

$$T(r) = T_{r=0} + (T_{r=R} - T_{r=0}) \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 \quad (5.42)$$

As such, the energy balance was written for both the centre of the reactor ($r_j = 0$) and its outer rim ($r_j = R$), as seen in Eq. 5.43, with heat transfer effectiveness (ϵ , Eq. 5.12) expressed with respect to the number of transport unit (NTU, Eq. 5.13).

$$C_{T,tot} \frac{dT_{r=r_j}}{dt} = \dot{m}_r \left[\Delta H_r + (c_p - c_v) (T_{r_j} - T_{ref}) \right] + (T_{f,i} - T_{r_j}) \dot{m}_f c_f \epsilon_i \quad (5.43)$$

The overall heat transfer coefficient (U) is then expressed as either Eq. 5.44-5.45.

$$U_{r=0} \approx \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_f} + \frac{R}{\lambda} \right)^{-1} \quad (5.44)$$

$$U_{r=R} \approx \alpha_f \quad (5.45)$$

To compare the one dimensional approach's to the 0D performances, the equivalent degree of hydrogenation has to be evaluated, considering the effective amount of hydrogen released in each element. This 1D equivalent system is compared to the three different 0D models.

5.1.3 Results

1D-0D comparison

Both one-dimensional and zero-dimensional simulations were firstly carried out, assuming a simplified reactor design. Input parameters are shown in Tab. 5.1.

Grid independence for 1D simulations was obtained with a 200-element grid (Fig. 5.3). It must be noted, however, that although conventional heat conduction problems require integration steps to verify the condition $\frac{\alpha \Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \leq 0.5$, due to the inner heat source, adequate integration time steps for a finer grids were considerably higher.

Subsequently, the 1D model was compared to the equivalent 0D model in Fig. 5.4. As shown in Fig. 5.4a, the 0D model yield poor results both with the internal and averaged temperature. On the other hand, the outer rim's temperature shows a good agreement with the 1D run.

Fig. Fig. 5.4b explains these results, where each 0D temperature profile over time is compared to the equivalent 1D temperature profile. The latter was evaluated from the overall DoH, assuming no temperature gradient inside the bulk liquid.

These results highlight the influence of the reaction over the temperature distribution: averaging temperature assuming pure conduction through the bulk liquid returns poor agreement with the actual performances. As stated, despite an expected reduced temperature level going towards the centre of the reactor, this very reduction slows down the reaction kinetics. So, further temperature drops are limited as less reaction heat is sunk.

As expected, the innermost temperature level is a poor candidate for representing the kinetic performance because it not only applies to a limited percentage of the LOHC sample

FIGURE 5.3: One-dimensional modelling results for 100, 200, 300 elements. Overall DoH and relative error over time.

(A) DoH over time for the 200-elements 1D model and the 0D simulations. (B) Temperature over time for the 200-elements 1D model and the 0D simulations.

FIGURE 5.4: Comparison of the 0D and 1D models.

FIGURE 5.5: Efficacy HTR influence over the reactor performances in terms of DoH and temperature.

but also represents the worst conditions (even more so due to the inadequacy of the pure conduction hypothesis).

Conversely, the outer rim provides an overall trend which is definitely closer to both the equivalent 1D temperature profile and the actual trend over time of each element.

At first, the carrier is at equilibrium with the external fluid, and due to high gradients, fast kinetics occur, leading to an initial temperature drop. As the lower temperature and hydrogen content slow down the reaction, and higher temperature differences between LOHC and external fluid arise, the system's temperature rises. Progressively less heat is released, and thermal equilibrium with the external fluid is eventually reached.

While the entity of the temperature drop is heavily influenced by the radial distance from the wall, whose presence influences progressively more distant regions of the bulk fluid, the equivalent profile features a smooth monotone trend, accounting for averaged temperature profiles weighted accordingly to their actual mass content.

A numerical correction $f(\text{DoH}, T)$ defined as $T_{1D,eq} = f(\text{DoH}, T_{r=R}) T_{r=R}$ cannot be defined as it would not be a function. Regardless, the proposed 0D model was deemed satisfactory for a preliminary evaluation of the system.

The same matching accuracy can be achieved for both relatively lower and higher batches if high enough heat transfer effectiveness is granted. While an increasingly higher mismatch is expected to arise for large-scale applications, batch reactors are best suited for smaller applications; thus, the modelling hypothesis validity is verified. Additional information about 0D-1D comparison can be found in the Appendix (see C).

Design optimization

The optimisation process was led by introducing a nonlinear condition over the Heat Transfer Ratio. Fig. 5.5 displays the influence of the Heat Transfer ratio over the DoH (Fig. 5.5a) and temperature level (Fig. 5.5b). While no actual bound is given for the latter since faster realises are not necessarily required nor preferred, control through poorer heat transfer performances should be avoided.

The different discharged hydrogen content is clearly a result of lower temperature levels. For HTR values of 0.054/(h K) and higher, no significant variation takes place, so raising this value further, either through a higher external fluid's mass flow rate or more expensive design choices, would lead to no gain. The HTR threshold value was then assumed to be 0.054/(h K).

Starting from the HTR threshold value, changing the HTR by $\pm 15\%$ leads to a mean root square variation of DoH of about 0.39-0.52% (Fig. 5.6). Changing the size of the system

FIGURE 5.6: Overall influence of a HTR variation from the threshold value with respect to size.

leads to almost identical results assuming the same threshold value. This is consistent with the definition of the HTR since it is independent from the size.

For any given size the greater the HTR, the more limited the temperature drop is going to be. Consequently, higher temperature levels enhance the kinetic performance of the system. Since the relatively heat demand is the main drawback of LOHC-based systems, it is crucial to strike the right balance between energy costs and release kinetics.

Only marginal kinetic improvements are achieved for higher values of the Heat Transfer Ratio, and as such a threshold value is defined to mark this saturation effect.

As seen in Fig. 5.6 a $0.054/(\text{hK})$ value already provides only about a 0.5% faster discharge than a 15% lower HTR configuration (with major effects in the very early stages of release). A 15% increase leads to even less evident effects.

While the actual best choice for the HTR_{thr} value might differ to account for specific operating conditions and control strategies, performances are overall consistent in a wide range of sizes.

As seen from the optimisation outcome (Tab. 5.2), the half-pipe coiled reactor provides a better solution in terms of energy savings due to a power requirement that is almost halved. The gap between the two options is likely to be even higher as agitation nozzles' power supply was neglected.

These results indicate that in a LOHC system, the reactor can be operated with little power and energy requirements. The impeller's power consumption was also evaluated with Nagata's correlations, as reported in [33], with a similar outcome.

Both cases feature high AR values around 3.6-3.7 to limit the stirring power consumption, whose effect is indeed more prominent in the jacketed reactor since an optimal unitary AR is returned when only pressure losses are evaluated.

Running local optimisation processes shows that similar results can be reached with multiple parameter combinations. Consequently, if additional constraints regarding either the heat transfer effectiveness or other aspects such as material usage and volume, or both, were to be introduced, different choices might be best suited. Thus, those alternative designs

Jacketed Reactor		Half-pipe Coiled Reactor	
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Height (H)	49.74 cm	Height (H)	50.36 cm
Inner Diameter (d_i)	13.67 cm	Inner Diameter (d_i)	13.58 cm
Outer Diameter (d_e)	15.07 cm	Outer Diameter (d_e)	14.98 cm
Ext. Fluid Speed (v)	0.58 m/s	Ext. Fluid Speed (v)	0.71 m/s
Ext. Fluid Mass Flow Rate (\dot{m}_f)	7.59 kg/s	Ext. Fluid Mass Flow Rate (\dot{m}_f)	7.12 kg/s
Jacket Width (t)	5.0 cm	Pipes Diameter (d)	10.16 cm
-	-	Pipes Spacing (s)	3.24 cm
Power Consumption (P)	0.11 W	Power Consumption (P)	0.06 W
Heat Transfer Ration (HTR)	0.054/(h K)	Heat Transfer Ration (HTR)	0.054/(h K)

TABLE 5.2: Design parameters for both layouts in the optimised reactors.

FIGURE 5.7: Influence of the different design parameters over the HTR.

would not significantly impact the energy demand of the system and the overall storage efficiency.

Increasing the size of the system requires further analysis since large-scale batch reactors might not be commercially available or sufficiently effective in terms of efficiency. The additional requirement should therefore account for parallel reactor configurations as well.

A sensitivity analysis was run to evaluate each parameter's influence over the Heat Transfer Ratio and the power requirements, varying each parameter in its range while setting the others to their optimal value.

Fig. 5.7 highlights that for a set value of the other parameters, both the AR and the pipes diameters have a huge influence on the actual effectiveness of the heat transfer. Conversely, due to a limited variability for the set size of the reactor, spacing has a limited impact on the final outcome. The external fluid velocity on the other hand is the most important parameter with the Heat Transfer Ratio showcasing an almost linear dependency. As a matter of fact higher velocities lead to both a greater mass flow rate and better convection. It must be remembered, however, that HTR higher than 0.054/(h K) lead to no performance improvement (Fig. 5.5).

Fig. 5.8 reaffirms the importance of AR and d over the resulting power requirements,

FIGURE 5.8: Influence of the different design parameters over power consumption.

with discontinuities arising due to the number of pipes being an integer value. The spacing holds a more limited influence, while v still has the greatest impact on the final result in the same fashion as explained in the paragraph above.

Coupling this result with Fig. 5.5 lead to a key finding: enhancing the heat transfer to keep a constant temperature is both pointless and highly detrimental in terms of power consumption, since the most reliable way to raise the HTR is through velocity. Doubling the optimal speed leads to a 600 % increase in the power requirement even with an optimal geometry. As such, even though the final optimised consumption is limited, great variability is to be expected with un-optimised configurations.

Conclusions

The 0D simplification is shown to be effective enough to guide the predesign stage of a batch reactor, and the optimisation process was led to minimising the power consumption of the system, while still granting the maximum heat transfer effectiveness. Different objectives could also be featured in the optimisation phase, such as materials minimisation, volume reduction and different definitions of heat transfer effectiveness, here accounted for through the introduction of the Heat Transfer Ratio. This parameter only needs to reach a certain threshold value and is not to be maximised since no further kinetic improvements would be achieved once the threshold value is reached.

The significant amount of different parameters combinations that satisfy the effectiveness lower bound with similar energy requirements hints at relatively flexible conditions, and additional constraints could likely be included without hindering the system performance.

While higher values are nonconsequential in terms of thermodynamic performances, the associated working conditions would most likely require a higher external fluid velocity with a marked increase in power consumption.

This design strategy could be applied for other reactor types (such as PFRs), although the lumped - parameter hypothesis would need to be tested again. Fast and simple implementation of dedicated components in object-based programming languages will then

be possible, allowing for a straightforward analysis of complex energy systems, including dynamic simulation and control strategies.

5.1.4 Heat Transfer Ratio

The topic of heat transfer ratio has been explored in depth in a dedicate paper Gambini et al., 2023c, in which it is used as the mean index of kinetic performances, in the definition of the optimal BR set-up. Power constrains are still expressed as seen above.

A preliminary alternative take on the HTR parameter implied the replacement of the denominator term $\dot{Q}_{r,max}/T_{des}$ with the hydrogen energy content ($m_{H_2}HHV$); however, as the derived value did not account for the effective kinetic parameters, its interpretation returned more mixed results. Additionally, this last definition is not dimensionless, leading to less general conclusions. The final parameter is introduced as a measure of the kinetic performances of the actual LOHC system compared to the corresponding isothermal system.

Heat transfer performance is thus evaluated by introducing a new definition of HTR as a dimensionless parameter, whose value directly correlates to the heat rate required by the carrier's dehydrogenation reaction.

Therefore, the numerator is the product of heat transfer effectiveness ε and HTF flow heat capacity $\dot{m}_f c_f$, while on the denominator side, the maximum heat rate depends on the heat of reaction ΔH_r and the maximum hydrogen flow rate, which is obtained, based on Eq. 5.46, at the beginning of the dehydrogenation process thanks to the highest value of DoH, provided that the reactor is heated to the desired reaction temperature beforehand, so that $T(t = t_0) = T_{des}$:

$$\dot{m}_{H_2,max} = \dot{m}_{H_2}(t = t_0) = w m_1 k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_{des}}\right) \exp(-bp) \text{DoH}_{max}^n. \quad (5.46)$$

By this definition, the HTR can be used to assess the heat transfer performance not only for different reactor sizes, but also for different LOHCs with similar reaction kinetic characteristics (for example, the same reaction order). More importantly, since different LOHCs vary in both release trends and reaction heat, the kinetic performances achieved with similar HTR following the HHV definition for different carriers may have led to less reliable information, as losing track of the effective mass flow rate released and the temperature requirement.

Despite the more complex definition and the need to collect data on the kinetic release parameters, Eq. 5.1 was considered to be overall more significant due to the greater amount of information returned and the potential to be applied to different LOHCs.

To improve the heat transfer performance, higher values of HTR can be achieved as:

- more heat is provided through a higher HTF flow heat capacity, better effectiveness of the exchanger, or both;
- the reaction temperature is set to a higher value;
- a reduced temperature drop takes place;
- less reaction heat is sunk.

Consequently, while the first two bullet points are likely detrimental in terms of the system's costs and overall efficiency, the remaining scenarios are actually desirable. Note that a reduced reaction heat could only be achieved by tackling applications at lower hydrogen power demand, since the dehydrogenation enthalpy is a constant. Finally, it should be reminded that the HTR is introduced as a measure of the kinetic performances of a real LOHC system with respect to its corresponding constant-temperature equivalent system.

The heat transfer performance of the reactor was analysed through the HTR: in particular, the effect of an increase in HTR, leading to an improvement in the heat transfer between HTF and LOHC, is studied to identify a threshold HTR value, representing the best trade-off between thermal design and kinetic performance, above which the improvement kinetic response is not significant.

To this end, the impact of HTR on reactor performance is first assessed in a test case represented by a storage system with an available hydrogen content of $m_{H_2} = 282.1$ g, which

FIGURE 5.9: DoH and temperature evolution over time for different values of the HTR parameter.

corresponds to a net energy output of 5 kWh by a fuel cell with a 45 % HHV-based efficiency; the required LOHC mass is $m_L = m_{\text{H}_2} / w = 4.855$ kg.

The batch reactor is subjected to a spontaneous constant-pressure discharge process, that is, the discharged hydrogen flow rate is not controlled and results from the instantaneous operating conditions, namely temperature and DoH. The duration of discharge is set at 180 min.

Fig. 5.9 shows the influence of the HTR on how dehydrogenation and reactor temperature proceed with time; the temperature trend is remarkably similar to data available in the literature Rao, Lele, and Patwardhan, 2022, albeit for a PFR, providing an indirect validation for the model presented. The different discharged hydrogen content is clearly a result of different temperature trends. With higher HTR values, the temperature drop for a given system progressively decreases. Consequently, faster kinetics is ensured, and a higher mass of hydrogen is discharged by the 180 min mark, by which a 0.2 DoH threshold can be reached using either NEC Kiermaier et al., 2021 or DBT Peters et al., 2019 as carriers (Fig. 5.9 shows the behaviour of a reactor based on NEC). As HTR increases, the gap between different temperature profiles is reduced, and the overall temperature does not stray far from the original design temperature T_{des} : the kinetic performance thus progressively tends to a constant-temperature trend, and only marginal improvements become possible with a further increase in HTR. Further raising the HTR above about 100 for this system, either through a higher HTF mass flow rate or more expensive design choices, would not lead to practical gains. In this way, a threshold value can be identified, which in this case is $\text{HTR}_{thr} \approx 100$.

The HTR parameter can be used to compare different LOHCs. Fig. 5.10 shows the final DoH reached by reactors containing NEC or DBT in the 180 min constant-pressure discharge described above, compared to the value that could be obtained in a constant-pressure, constant-temperature discharge process (dashed lines). Looking at the performance of NEC and DBT, a threshold HTR value of about 90-100 is needed in both cases to achieve a final deviation lower than 5 % with respect to the constant-temperature release profile. The temperature levels were chosen to ensure a final $\text{DoH}(t = 180 \text{ min}) \approx 0.20$ at $p = 1.00$ bar, corresponding to 473 and 583 K respectively for NEC and DBT, given their different thermodynamic properties.

In particular, Fig. 5.10 shows, on the left, how the higher HTR decreases the final degree of hydrogenation asymptotically with respect to the performance of the constant-temperature

FIGURE 5.10: HTR influence over NEC and DBT systems. Dashed lines represent constant-temperature simulations. Left: DoH reached at $t = 180$ min for different values of HTR; right: deviation of the real reactor from the DoH reached in an ideal constant-temperature reactor.

profile. As such, significant improvements are achieved only at low HTR values (≤ 100), above which the performance is already similar to those granted by a constant-temperature discharge. On the right, it shows the relative difference in final DoH between the tested reactor and the constant-temperature process: the remarkable similarity between the curves representing NEC and DBT shows that the HTR is useful in assessing heat transfer performance for different LOHCs, at least when the reaction order is similar (the reaction order for DBT has been shown to be very close to 2 Peters et al., 2019); preliminary results for other carriers hint at a possible correlation between the reaction order and the threshold value.

Consistent with the lumped-parameter approach and the definition of HTR, which is independent of size, both the scaling up and down of the sample leads to the same kinetic performance if the HTR parameter is kept constant. For any given size, the greater the HTR, the more limited the temperature drop will be. Consequently, higher temperature levels enhance the kinetic performance of the system. Since a relatively high heat demand is the main drawback of LOHC-based systems, it is crucial to strike the right balance between energy costs and release kinetics.

Only marginal kinetic improvements are achieved for higher values of the HTR, and, as such, a threshold value is defined to mark this saturation effect. Although the actual best choice for the HTR_{thr} value might differ to account for specific operating conditions and control strategies, a threshold value of $HTR_{thr} = 100$ was used in this article, allowing for a deviation from the DoH reached in an ideal constant-temperature reactor $\Delta\% DoH_{i,const T} \leq 5\%$.

It must be reiterated that HTR is intended to be a tool for assessing how close the actual kinetic performance of the system is to that of an ideal, constant-temperature reactor. However, the amount of heat required is strictly correlated to the carrier itself and the reaction temperature: further and broader analyses are needed to optimise the efficiency of the whole system.

5.2 Plug Flow Reactor

5.2.1 Open Loop

Two different designs can be envisaged to take into account the release of hydrogen.

FIGURE 5.11: PFRs basic designs: full or partially filled section.

With reference to Fig. 5.11 it is clear that if it is planned to exploit the entire circular section to increase the exchange surface with the external fluid, then the hydrogen will be released directly to the exhaust together with the dehydrogenated LOHC. The notation LOHC^- and LOHC^+ refers to the assumption that the hydrogen carrier goes from its fully saturated (LOHC^+) to its fully unsaturated form (LOHC^-). The mass difference between the two is the released hydrogen mass. Obviously it will be necessary to evaluate the actual final volumetric dimensions of the flow of hydrogen and LOHC^- , furthermore the increasing concentration of hydrogen will inhibit the reaction in favor of the reverse hydrogenation reaction.

Therefore an alternative design is proposed, in which only a percentage of the tube section is exploited (typically 50% in the literature, see Peters et al.) thus providing that the hydrogen is instantly released from above.

With respect to this second design, we can proceed with an initial sizing by defining the minimum length required to go from DoH_0 to DoH_{des} in $z = L$.

In this regard, taking advantage of what has been seen for batch reactors, one can imagine that, especially for reduced d/L ratios, a one-dimensional representation is sufficient to describe the behavior of the carrier. The temperature can therefore be assumed constant and homogeneous on each section. Furthermore, by optimizing the heat exchange it is possible to approximate the characteristic temperature with the design one, providing for a certain oversizing in terms of residence time in the reactor, to take into account the actual initial (but limited) drop in temperature.

Modeling

Starting from a second order reaction like Eq. 5.47, where the reaction constant k_0 has been rewritten via Eq. 5.48 to go from mol/s to mol/m³:

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dV} = -k_0 e^{bp} e^{-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}} \text{DoH}^2 \quad (5.47)$$

$$k_0 = \frac{k'_0}{\bar{u}\Omega} \quad (5.48)$$

the rate can be thus rewritten by introducing: $\kappa = \frac{k'_0}{\bar{u}} \exp bp \exp -\frac{E_a}{R_u T}$ leading to Eq. 5.49:

$$L = \frac{1}{\kappa} \frac{\text{DoH}_{max} - \text{DoH}_{min}}{\text{DoH}_{max} \cdot \text{DoH}_{min}} \quad (5.49)$$

with DoH_{max} and DoH_{min} set to the initial and final DoH value, respectively.

The procedure can be generalized for any order of the reaction, rewriting Eq. 5.47 as a function of the generic order n (Eq. 5.50).

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dV} = \kappa \text{DoH}^n \quad (5.50)$$

At this point the equivalent section can be found as a function of the total volume of LOHC (Eq. 5.51)

$$A_{cs} = \frac{V_{lohc}}{L} \quad (5.51)$$

Assuming that 50% of the circular section is intended for the circulation of the carrier and the remaining half for the release of hydrogen, the diameter (D) (Eq. 5.52) and the wetted perimeter (P_w) of the reactor can be deduced (Eq. 5.53).

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi} A_{cs}} \cdot 2 \quad (5.52)$$

$$P_w = \pi \frac{D}{2} \quad (5.53)$$

Imagining a steady-state scenario² the following subset of equations (Eq. 5.54- 5.57) is needed:

$$\frac{dT}{dz} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2} (\Delta H_r + \Delta h - \Delta u) - \dot{Q}}{c_{\text{LOHC}} \dot{m}_{\text{LOHC}}} \quad (5.54)$$

$$\dot{Q} = (P_w \cdot dz) U (T - T_f) \quad (5.55)$$

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dV} = -k_0 e^{bp} e^{-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}} \text{DoH}^2 \quad (5.56)$$

$$\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2} = [(\dot{m}_{\text{LOHC}} w_{\%}) \cdot (dz A_{cs})] \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dz} \quad (5.57)$$

In this type of reactor, by providing a single pass, the spatial coordinate can be directly assimilated to the residence time in the reactor³.

To integrate the equations on the length of the reactor, a variable step $dz(z)$ is defined. In this case its definition is linked to $\tau_0 \approx 1 \times 10^{-4}$ s defined with the previous solver, via

²This is actually in conflict with the definition of A_{cs} and therefore the "single pass" hypothesis. In order for the LOHC to fully discharge, every compound molecule needs to go through the full reactor's length, implying that at t_0 the reactor is completely empty. As such, as the first $\dot{m}_{\text{LOHC}^+} = \rho v dA$ enters the reactor, the dA fluid column would reshape and spread along the reactor axis. The desired rigid fluid column progression implied is thus a schematization unless continuous operation with new fresh LOHC⁺ is implied.

³Remember: as they are defined, T and DoH must be integrated with respect to dz and dV respectively!

FIGURE 5.12: Open loop hydrogen release assuming only one crossing of the reactor.

Eq. 5.58 for $z = 0$ m. Subsequently, having introduced a dz_{max} and a proportionality parameter a_k whose value is defined empirically, Eq. 5.59 is applied.

$$dz = \bar{u} \cdot \tau_0 \quad (5.58)$$

$$dz = \min \left[\tau_{max}; \frac{a_k}{\max \left[\frac{dT}{dz}; \frac{dDoH}{dV}; \dot{m}_{H_2} \right]} \right] \quad (5.59)$$

As regards the global exchange coefficient U , this is given by Eq. 5.60, with α_f and α_L respectively obtained with the Gnielinski and Dixon-Cresswell methods Rao, Lele, and Patwardhan, 2022 taking into account that $Nu = \alpha D / \lambda$ (Eq. 5.61-5.62).

$$U = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_L} + \frac{d_{in} \log(d_{out}/d_{in})}{2\lambda} + \frac{d_{in}}{d_{out}} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} \right)^{-1} \quad (5.60)$$

$$Nu_f = \frac{\frac{f}{8} (Re_f - 1000) Pr_f}{1 + 12.7 \left(\frac{f}{8} \right)^{0.5} (Pr_f^{2/3} - 1)} \quad (5.61)$$

$$Nu_L = 0.523 \left(1 - \left(\frac{d_p}{d_t} \right) \right) Pr_L^{0.33} Re_{L,d_p}^{0.738} \quad (5.62)$$

Where f in Eq. 5.61 stands for the friction factor calculated with the Blasius equation, i.e. according to Eq. 5.63, d_p is the pipe diameter, and d_t the hydraulic diameter.

$$f = 0.3164 Re^{-0.25}. \quad (5.63)$$

Results

By simulating the dehydrogenation process the results described in Fig. 5.12 are obtained.

These trends verify the initial hypothesis of a roughly constant temperature, used to size the reactor. Clearly this is possible thanks to the effectiveness of the heat exchange with the heat transfer fluid: if less heat is available to contain the drop in temperature, i.e. the flow rate of the HTF is lower, then it will be necessary to compensate for the slowdown of the kinetics ensuring a greater reaction time or with lower speeds, or with longer reactors.

FIGURE 5.13: Closed loop design in the absence of intermediate vessels.

The case presented concerns a reactor with 50 kWh of useful energy net of a system efficiency of 45%. The equivalent reactor therefore has a total length $L = 25.1$ m and a diameter of 54.8 mm. In reality $\text{DoH}(t_f)$ is slightly greater than the target of $\text{DoH}_f = 0.20$, due to the albeit minimal deviation from the isothermal condition.

Fig. 5.12 had the average speed set to 3.0 mm/s so as to keep the length of the reactor limited, and the associated operating times are therefore approximately 140.0 min, compatibly with the isothermal case.

5.2.2 Closed Loop

This term was used to define LOHC reactors in which more than one passing of the active length is required. More specifically, two different classes of designs are introduced, with respect to the inclusion of one or more vessels in the overall design.

Simple closed loop design

An evolution of the design proposed in Sec. 5.2.1 is the closing of the loop. In this way it is possible to reduce the size of the reactor, although it is necessary to provide a pipe of equal length and halved section.

With reference to Fig. 5.13, an initial filling phase is therefore expected, after which the system operates in a closed loop. The catalyst is placed in the active section and the dehydrogenation reaction takes place: to compensate for the absorbed reaction heat, an exchanger with concentric tubes is provided along the same and only active section, so as to maintain the temperature close to the set point.

By following the previously illustrated procedure, the length necessary for complete dehydrogenation to occur in the case of an isothermal reaction is defined, see Eq. 5.49. This data is to be understood as a residence time in the reactor: $t_{\text{reaction}} = L_{\text{reaction}} / \bar{v}_L$.

However, having created a closed circuit, the actual physical length of the same can be reduced by providing for more steps (n_{turns}), and taking into account that only half of the LOHC will be found instantly in the reactor, Eqs. 5.64-5.65 are deduced .

$$L_{\text{reactor}} = \frac{L_{\text{reaction}}}{n_{\text{turns}}} \quad (5.64)$$

$$A_{\text{cs}} = \frac{V_{\text{lohc}}}{2 \cdot L_{\text{reactor}}} \quad (5.65)$$

It therefore follows that the final architecture of the reactor strongly depends both on the speed of movement of the LOHC and on the number of passes envisaged. As reported in Fig. 5.14, as the speed increases the length $L = L_{\text{reactor}}$ increases, since the reaction time is fixed by chemical kinetics and consequently the diameter decreases rapidly⁴ (Eq. 5.65-5.52). On the other hand, the length L is inversely proportional to the number of passes in the reactor (Eq. 5.64); substituting in Eq. 5.65-5.52, reveals that the diameter is instead proportional to $\sqrt{n_{\text{turns}}}$.

⁴Note that in the graph on the left the ordinate axis for the diameter of the active section is in logarithmic coordinates; vice versa, in the graph on the right the logarithmic ordinate was used for the length trend.

FIGURE 5.14: Size of the reactor as v_L and n_{turns} vary.

Modeling

When modeling the reactor it is necessary to divide the integration domain taking into account that half of the defined elements will be active and therefore subject to reaction. In this case therefore the reference equations are Eq. 5.66 to Eq. 5.69 to evaluate the outlet and inlet mass flow rates for the LOHC⁺ and hydrogen only respectively.

$$\dot{m}_{out}^i = \dot{m}_{in}^i - \dot{m}_{H_2,r}^i \quad (5.66)$$

$$\dot{m}_{in}^i = \dot{m}_{out}^{i-1} \quad (5.67)$$

$$\dot{m}_{H_2,out}^i = (w_{\%} \text{DoH}^i) \dot{m}_{out}^i \quad (5.68)$$

$$\dot{m}_{H_2,in}^i = \dot{m}_{H_2,out}^{i-1} \quad (5.69)$$

Since the degree of hydrogenation that characterizes contiguous elements is generally different, the variation of the DoH is no longer linked to the chemical reaction alone (Eq. 5.70); therefore it is necessary to resort to its definition, as reported in Eq. 5.71.

$$\dot{m}_{H_2,r}^i = a_x^i \frac{d\text{DoH}^i}{dt} = a_x^i \left[k_0 \exp \left(- \left(bp + \frac{E_a}{R_u T^i} \right) \right) (\text{DoH}^i)^n \right] \quad (5.70)$$

$$\text{DoH}^i = \frac{m_{H_2}^i}{a_x^i} \quad (5.71)$$

With the conversion factor a_x from DoH to m_{H_2} , Eq. 5.72.

$$a_x = w_{\%} m^i \quad (5.72)$$

Note that depending on the definition of $w_{\%}$, which can be immediately obtained from the chemical formula of the carrier in its hydrogenated and de-hydrogenated form, and therefore from the different molecular weights, the mass m^i referred to it can alternatively be the total one of the integrating element, or the same one reduced by the hydrogen content by directly imagining considering the LOHC as made up of a constant part (LOHC⁻) to which is added hydrogen mass contribution. In this section the symbol m^i refers to the total mass.

Therefore the set of Eqs. 5.66-5.72 constitutes the mass balance within the active sections.

For the energy balance (Eq. 5.73) the contribution of the reaction heat (Eq. 5.76), of the heat flow supplied through the heat carrier (Eq. 5.75), and the mechanical energy flows (Eq. 5.74) are considered.

Velocity [v , m/s]	Turns [n , -]	Diameter [D , m]	Length [L , m]
2.500	1000	0.04	20.9
0.025	1000	0.43	0.21

TABLE 5.3: Sizing results for the two layouts under analysis.

$$c_L^i m^i \frac{dT^i}{dt} = \dot{Q}_f^i + \dot{Q}_r^i + \dot{E}_m^i \quad (5.73)$$

$$\dot{E}_m^i = \dot{m}_{in}^i (\Delta h^{i-1} + 0.5v^{i-12}) - \dot{m}_{out}^i (\Delta h^i + 0.5v^{i2}) \quad (5.74)$$

$$\dot{Q}_f^i = \dot{m}_f c_f \epsilon (T_f - T^i) \quad (5.75)$$

$$\dot{Q}_r^i = \dot{m}_{H_2,r}^i (-\Delta H_r + (\Delta u_{H_2}^i - \Delta h_{H_2}^i)) \quad (5.76)$$

Having also incorporated the contributions of internal energy and enthalpy flow into the reaction term \dot{Q}_r , assuming that the mass variation within the individual elements is essentially linked to the chemical reaction.

To determine the the LOHC velocity (v^i), reference is made to Eq. 5.77-5.78, with Ω^i being the cross section filled of LOHC in a given point of the reactor⁵.

$$\Omega^i = \frac{m^i}{\rho_L^i dz} \quad (5.77)$$

$$v^i = \frac{\dot{m}_{out}^i}{\rho_L^i \Omega^i} \quad (5.78)$$

In the inactive sections, the equations will be the same but $\dot{m}_{H_2,r} := 0$, and in the absence of a heat exchange bank also $\dot{Q}_f := 0.0 \text{ W}$.

Results

The results obtained can be compared by running the simulation in two settings: the first imposing an average speed v_L of 2.5 m/s, and the second instead using a speed value similar to that used in the case of open loop reactor with $v_L = 2.5 \text{ mm/s}$. The dimensions of the reactor resulting from setting the number of crossings of the reactor at $n_{turns} = 1000$ are reported in Tab. 5.3.

With reference to Fig. 5.15-5.16, the simulation results are returned by sampling along the spatial coordinate or in time. These figures showcase how heat is delivered only in the first half of the system, i.e. in the active part of the reactor.

The time trends illustrated in Fig. 5.15 follow the expected trends characteristic of dehydrogenation reactors: the release occurs gradually with a slower speed as the DoH decreases, and after an initial drop in temperature, T_L increases again due to both the ΔT established between the heat carrier and LOHC, and the lower reaction heat absorbed as the release slows down. The heat required therefore has a peak that immediately follows the drop in temperature, after which it decreases.

In both cases, up at the higher speed and down at the lower speed, there is a negligible spread along the spatial coordinate, and a slightly greater variability observed in the longer reactor.

The time required to release the total hydrogen content is more than double that expected from laboratory conditions: if the reaction were isothermal, in fact, it would be sufficient to double this value, however a reduction in temperature is recorded. This is greater for the case of the shorter reactor, where the heat exchange efficiency is drastically lower: although the temperature drops significantly more, recovery is slower and less heat is absorbed. It

⁵Even though it is not explicitly stated, as it is a function of m^i , Ω^i changes over time, and is thus different from A_{cs} previously defined in Eq. 5.51 as a constant structural property of the reactor.

FIGURE 5.15: Trends of DoH, temperature and heat supplied to the system Q_f over time at different points of the system.

FIGURE 5.16: Trends of DoH, temperature and heat supplied to the system Q_f along the reactor for different time instants.

FIGURE 5.17: DoH trend over time along the reactor length.

would then become necessary, if this were the final architecture of the system, to perform an optimization analysis to determine the aspect ratio ($AR = D/L_r$) of the reactor.

The spatial trends illustrated in Fig. 5.16 highlight the greater inhomogeneity along the spatial coordinate of the first layout (therefore the one with $v_L = 2.5$ m/s). These deviations are more marked in terms of temperature and are reabsorbed over time.

Note that since the sampling is discrete, the maxima appearing in one or the other figure are to be interpreted as local or global with consultation of the second representation.

What has been said can also be represented with two-dimensional maps as in Fig. 5.17-5.19.

It is then very clear from Fig. 5.17 how hydrogenation proceeds more slowly in the second reactor. This is due to the consistently lower temperature highlighted by Fig. 5.18, net of the thermal energy to be supplied which is substantially greater in the medium - long term, despite the slower hydrogenation and lower efficiency making the lower initial thermal power, as seen in Fig. 5.19. For a larger number of crossings, the longitudinal variation would be more pronounced; however, the high n makes the axial gradients small.

Closed loop and vessels designs

To address the need to compact the design, multi-pass configurations were tested. In this way it is possible to reduce the length of the reactor, and guarantee a more constant flow of hydrogen compared to that naturally released with a single pass design as in Fig. 5.11. In fact, the time necessary to deliver all the stored hydrogen expands: at any given moment, only a part of the LOHC is in the reactor. This involves continuous mixing between LOHCs at different degrees of DoH with a consequent relative homogenization of the release.

Referencing Fig. 5.20, the three different designs feature some interesting traits.

1. The first scheme involves a single tank, so LOHC exiting the reactor is continuously refluxed into the initial tank, mixing with LOHC at a higher DoH. The representation of the inactive section is to be considered schematic: even assuming a semicircular connection between the reactor (active section) and the return pipe (inactive section), the latter will have a smaller diameter than the reactor since it is not a reaction site and therefore does not need a free ceiling for the release of hydrogen, as illustrated in Sec. 5.2.1.

FIGURE 5.18: Temperature trend over time along the reactor length.

FIGURE 5.19: Exchanged heat trend over time along the reactor length.

FIGURE 5.20: Closed loop with vessels PFR designs.

FIGURE 5.21: Final PFR design: tubular reactor in closed loop with two vessels.

2. The intermediate scheme involves the introduction of a second reactor where the LOHC coming out of the reactor is deposited and then re-sent from there to the first reactor. In this case the second stretch could be either active or inactive.
3. A logical and more compact evolution of the previous configuration sees the collapse of the two sections into a single active section: the LOHC flowed from the first reactor is sent towards the second reactor, initially empty, and then reverses the direction of travel when the active reactor.

Of these designs presented, the third was explored in depth. Compared to the second configuration, in fact, it presents a more streamlined apparatus with the same functions. The first proposed scheme is instead intermediate with respect to the configuration 2 presented in Sec. 5.2.2.

In fact, compared to the latter it also allows operation intermittently: the reactor could be designed to accommodate any fraction of fluid f_r (Eq. 8.5), so as to be undersized compared to the case depicted in Fig. 5.13, and whether or not to provide for an inactive section as its presence is not necessary when a tank is inserted.

$$f_r = \frac{V_{tube}}{V_{tot}} \quad (5.79)$$

Compared to this scheme, the third proposed design introduces an additional reactor, where the size of both could be subject to optimization studies, but simplifies and minimizes the LOHC path. In addition to lowering the associated pumping cost, this configuration lends itself better to controlled operation, opening up the possibility of emptying and filling logistics optimized with respect to the needs of the end user.

Note that in general the presence of a tank in the scheme, where this (or one of the two present, in the case of the third design) does not coincide with the medium-term storage tank of the saturated carrier, may or may not be associated with exchange benches thermal.

Imagining that there is also no heating system on the vessel, maintaining the insulation towards the outside, the temperature that will be established in the tank will be a function of mixing with the incoming LOHC flow rate. However, since the reactor is kept at a roughly constant temperature with respect to the set point, the deviation of T_{vessel} will be very limited. Therefore, the energy consumption associated with maintaining the temperature is also very limited and negligible compared to the remaining consumption items. More details are provided below for the third configuration, but the results are qualitatively valid also for the other designs presented here.

Modeling

Therefore, with reference to Fig. 5.21 design, the operation of the system is divided into several rounds, i.e. cyclical filling and emptying of the tanks, and three components to be modeled are identified:

1. The "active" tank: this tank is the one instantly responsible for the supply of LOHC, i.e. its level lowers over time and guarantees a certain flow rate characterized by the DoH in force inside it at the reactor input.
2. The "passive" tank: this tank is the one at the end of the reactor, i.e. its level rises over time. Contrary to the active tank, the current DoH is not exactly constant along the single lap but witnesses a transient of variable duration depending mainly on f_r .
3. The reactor: fed by the active tank, the dehydrogenation of the LOHC takes place along its spatial extension. To ensure good kinetics, heat is supplied via a concentric tube exchanger. The geometry and operation is not dissimilar to what we have seen so far.

The active and passive tanks thus described, however, are not uniquely associated with one or the other of the physical tanks, but are rather functions that both cover alternately during the operation time. In this discussion we consider the case of complete emptying of the two tanks, however the possibility of reversing the operation once a non-zero predefined emptying level has been reached could be strategic for the homogenisation of the released flow rate, being at all times by definition $\text{DoH}_{v,active} > \text{DoH}_{v,passive}$, having the LOHC in the active tank immediately generally fewer passes through the reactor.

For simplicity, imagine that at the switch between one revolution and another, the reversal of motion inside the reactor is instantaneous. In reality, the flow field that will be established will be more complex and subject to sloshing; conceivably there could also be a mixing and consequently homogenization of the associative LOHC and DoH.

Imagining to keep the temperature constant in both tanks, Eq. 5.80 is defined; from this relation the heat necessary to supply so that $\frac{dT_v}{dt} = 0$ is derived. Eq. 5.81 instead imposes the emptying law, where the extraction flow rate $\dot{m}_{v,a}$ is constant and linked to the emptying time t_v through Eq. 5.82 and having chosen a certain extraction speed v_0 .

$$c_l m_{v,a} \frac{dT_{v,a}}{dt} + c_l T_{v,a} \frac{dm_{v,a}}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{v,a} - \dot{m}_{v,a} \left(\Delta h + \frac{v_0^2}{2} \right) \quad (5.80)$$

$$\frac{dm_{v,a}}{dt} = -\dot{m}_{v,a} \quad (5.81)$$

$$\dot{m}_{v,a} = \frac{m_{vessel,LOHC^-}}{t_v} \quad (5.82)$$

Note that \dot{m}_0 and t_v remain unchanged over time since their definition is linked to the mass of LOHC^- . It should also be noted that reference is made to flow rates \dot{m} defined as positive, and by compensating for the incoming or outgoing direction with the algebraic sign; on the other hand, the time derivatives $\frac{dm}{dt}$ are defined as positive or negative depending on the direction of slip.

The definition of m_{vessel} is instead linked to the same Eq. 8.5, so given f_r Eq. 5.83 is obtained.

$$m_{vessel} = \rho_l V_{tot} (1 - f_r) \quad (5.83)$$

Having defined the total mass present in the reactor, in this case a function of the degree of hydrogenation⁶; to maintain a constant reference we must pass to $m_{vessel,LOHC^-}$ from Eq. 5.84-5.85.

$$\text{DoH}_0 = \frac{n_{LOHC^+}}{n_{LOHC^+} + n_{LOHC^-} = n_{LOHC}} \quad (5.84)$$

$$m_0 = m_{LOHC^-} + m_{LOHC^+} = m_{LOHC-,eq} + m_{H_2} \quad (5.85)$$

⁶The quantity V_{tot} is in fact derived from having established the size of the system with respect to η_{system} and E_{system} of the end user and is therefore the volume of the system at the initial moment, before the discharge takes place.

Eq. 5.81 thus described is then referred to the mass of the LOHC⁻ alone; if one wanted to trace the evolution of the hydrogen mass it would therefore be sufficient to multiply both members by a correction factor that takes into account the DoH, constant during the single passage in the active reactor, and $w_{\%}$ (Eq. 5.86). However, this relationship does not introduce useful information for modeling purposes.

$$\frac{dm_{v,a}^{\text{H}_2}}{dt} = -w_{\%} \text{DoH}_{v,a} \dot{m}_{v,a} \quad (5.86)$$

For the passive tank, Eq. 5.87-5.88 are defined to describe the energy balance, and therefore obtain the heat to be supplied to keep its temperature constant, and the mass balance.

$$c_1 m_{v,p} \frac{dT_{v,p}}{dt} + c_1 T_{v,p} \frac{dm_{v,p}}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{v,p} + \dot{m}_{\bar{i}} \left(\Delta h + \frac{v_{out,\bar{i}}^2}{2} \right) \quad (5.87)$$

$$\frac{dm_{v,p}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{\bar{i}} \quad (5.88)$$

Specifically, the index \bar{i} refers to the last reactor element directly adjacent to the passive tank, i.e. by maintaining a constant grid between one pass and another, we have the following definition:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{i} &= 1 \text{ during even turns;} \\ \bar{i} &= N \text{ during odd turns.} \end{aligned}$$

Differently from what happens in the active tank, the degree of hydrogenation is variable over time, so from Eq. 5.88-5.89 Eq. 5.90 is derived.

$$\frac{dm_{v,p}^{\text{H}_2}}{dt} = -w_{\%} \text{DoH}_{\bar{i}} \dot{m}_{\bar{i}} \quad (5.89)$$

$$\text{DoH}_{v,p} = \frac{m_{v,p}^{\text{H}_2}}{m_{v,p} w_{\%}} \quad (5.90)$$

All properties used to model tanks' and reactor equations for dynamic simulation and sizing are defined as functions of temperature and DoH (see Appendix B).

For the reactor, however, the equations used are essentially the same as those illustrated in Section 5.2.2, however taking into account that in this case the direction of advancement is periodically reversed. For example, with reference to the third diagram in Fig. 5.20, imagine dividing the reactor into N elements from the left (element 1 adjacent to the vessel 1) to the right (element N adjacent to vessel 2) and to start the discharge with vessel 1 in active mode⁷. This operation means that the LOHC flows in the generic i-th element of the reactor have the directions indicated in Fig. 5.22 depending on the turn in question. Hydrogen release is clearly missing from this picture, however its direction is strictly outgoing in any operational setting and does not propagate from element to element.

This leads to the operational need to foresee the U-turn. A quick and effective method to do this is the introduction of two coefficients: c_1 and c_2 defined at each turn (j_{turn}) as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= \text{mod } j_{turn}, 2 \\ c_2 &= \text{mod } j_{turn} + 1, 2 \end{aligned}$$

In this way during the odd rounds $c_1 = 1$, $c_2 = 0$ and vice versa in the even ones. Therefore, referring for example to the flow rates entering the different elements, without having to resort to an *if* cycle, the formula described in Eq. 5.91 can be used.

$$\dot{m}_{in} = [\dot{m}_{v,a}, \dot{m}(1 : N - 1)] \cdot c_1 + c_2 \cdot [\dot{m}(2 : N), \dot{m}_{v,a}] \quad (5.91)$$

⁷Consistent with the definition of the subscript \bar{i} : in odd turns the sliding is therefore left to right, vessel 1 empties while vessel 2 fills; vice versa in even-numbered rounds.

FIGURE 5.22: Schematic representation of the LOHC flows inside the reactor in one of its generic elements. Inlet and outlet flows direction depends on the turn number.

Results

This section reports the results of the simulations carried out. Starting with the input data for sizing $f_r = 0.2$, $t_v = 4$ min, and $v_{L,mean} = 0.1$ m/s is obtained for a system of 50 kWh and $\eta = 45\%$ powered by an NEC storage with $DoH_0 = 0.95$ and $DoH_f = 0.20$ a reactor of $L = 6$ m and $D_t = 69.5$ mm.

Performance is calculated for a system heated by *DowTherm Q* with $v_{f,mean} = 1.5$ m/s, predicting a flow rate three times that of the LOHC. This information is expressed in terms of f_x in Eq. 5.92, and along with $v_{f,mean}$, $v_{L,mean}$, f_r and t_v make up the main design parameters, as discussed in Sec. 5.2.2.

$$f_x = \frac{\dot{m}_f}{\dot{m}_L} \quad (5.92)$$

The results thus obtained can be visualized in terms of degree of hydrogenation, temperature and heat flows in the reactor as shown respectively in Figs. 5.23, 5.24 and 5.25.

For degree of hydrogenation and temperature, spatial trends are also reported in the form of a color map. These, however, demonstrate an almost homogeneity along the reactor. In both cases, the average trends reported in the figures below illustrate a moderate excursion. These trends are due precisely to the imperfect homogeneity, and to the fact that with each new lap what was the final section in the previous lap becomes the entrance section of the LOHC. This is therefore powered by LOHC at a different temperature and with a different DoH.

In reality, however, this excursion is limited both for the degree of hydrogenation, having chosen a layout with a small reactor as a consequence of the low value of f_v . Precisely for this reason it is necessary to provide a greater number of passes in the reactor than those that would be required if f_r were greater, for the same crossing speed⁸.

In the case in question, 200 passes were simulated, but we see that the expected target is reached after 700 min, i.e. 175 passes. In particular, Fig. 5.26 shows the trend of the overall degree of hydrogenation in the reactor and in the two tanks. Precisely because the layout thus defined in terms of design parameters is capable of providing large quantities of heat, the temperature of the LOHC remains essentially constant (evident from the trend of the average temperature in the reactor in Fig. 5.24) and this is reflected in the fact that the exercise time required to reach the expected target is roughly $t_f \approx t_{f, const T} / f_r$.

Note that the DoH defined as DoH_{ave} in Fig. 5.25 differs from that defined as DoH_{tot} in Fig. 5.26 since they are respectively defined as:

$$DoH_{ave}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N DoH_i(t)}{N}$$

$$DoH_{tot}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N m_i^{H_2}(t) + \sum_{j=1}^2 m_{v,j}^{H_2}(t)}{m_{LOHC, tot} w\%}$$

Fig. 5.25 is representative of the different energy flows in the reactor, representing the internal energy variation and the mechanical energy flows associated with the input and

⁸This therefore translates into a longer reactor, and therefore with residence times higher for each pass.

output LOHC as equivalent heat flows (of equal power), to highlight each contribution to the system temperature.

In particular, both \dot{Q}_{H_2} and \dot{Q}_L just mentioned offer a weakly positive or negative contribution to Eq. 5.87, with respect to which they correspond respectively to the second term of the left-hand member, and to the second term of the right-hand member.

Consistently with what has already been seen in the graphs in Fig. 5.24, and therefore in Fig. 5.23, the term \dot{Q}_f is comparable to and slightly greater than the power absorbed due to the reaction heat \dot{Q}_r .

This operating structure is associated with rapid kinetics, limited only by the set point temperature, but consumption is considerable. Introducing the quantity Q_0 , total energy necessary for the LOHC to be brought from the initial temperature to the operating temperature and expressible with Eq. 5.93:

$$Q_0 = \int_{T=T_0}^{T=T_f} c_l T dT \quad (5.93)$$

the total energy consumption required for operation can be evaluated in terms of thermal energy, and therefore considering Q_0 , Q_f and $Q_v = Q_{v,a} + Q_{v,p}$ to maintain at the temperature pre-established LOHC in the tanks assumed negligible losses due to exchange with the external environment.

Figs. 5.27a-5.27b represent respectively the highest and lowest heat consumption required. These values are associated with different case studies: the first case study assumes LOHC at room temperature, while the second assumes the LOHC initial temperature at the setpoint for hydrogenation.

In both cases the prevailing term is clearly the one relating to Q_f , therefore necessary to compensate the ΔH_r of the endothermic reaction and keep the LOHC temperature essentially constant on the set-point temperature, as seen in Fig. 5.24.

In the transition from the worst case to the best case, the heat associated with storage contracts significantly, going from being a secondary term to an almost negligible effect. However, compared to the case presented in Fig. 5.27a, it must be specified that the NEC is in the solid state under conditions of ambient pressure up to the temperature of about 60 °C, and therefore it is good that from the moment of hydrogenation, the temperature of the LOHC does not fall below this threshold. As regards the second case, the temperature taken as reference for the hydrogenation reaction is 433 K, the kinetic optimum temperature Gambini et al., 2022.

Although these values are intended as indicative of actual consumption, they could be associated with different configurations: a first case in which the LOHC is saturated - perhaps in a centralized way - and subsequently distributed, so it is not conceivable to maintain the high temperatures required by the kinetics of reaction during the charging phase, and a second case in which the LOHC is instead used as a storage system to be able to convert energy on site at a later time, imagining maintaining the temperature as close as possible to that of exit from the reactor hydrogenation.

These collected data correspond respectively to an overall consumption of 75.6 MJ and 72.4 MJ. Comparing this data with the total energy content of the system, i.e. 50 kWh = 180 MJ⁹, we obtain that the expense in terms of thermal energy alone that must be incurred for the operation of the system, in order for the performances illustrated here to be guaranteed, is approximately 40% of E_{system} .

It must be remembered that the exergetic content of $E_{auxiliary}$ and E_{hyd} is however different from that associated with the heat to be supplied to the system, where the recovery heat is generally of lower quality as it is released at a lower temperature, while for the useful energy will depend on the type of end user to whom the system belongs.

It is clear that recovering reaction heat during the charging phase opens up great margins for efficiency. In fact, even taking into account that part of the reaction heat will be used to guarantee that the temperature entering the reactor is that required for hydrogenation, the

⁹In reality this value is slightly higher since the expense energy is obtained by integrating the simulated powers during the run, i.e. until reaching a DoH slightly lower than the DoH_{min} initially estimated in the sizing phase (Fig. 5.26). This means that the actual energy costs are lower, even though the little hydrogen released in the last 100 min of operation leads to a low absorbed reaction heat, and therefore the expected deviation is also negligible.

FIGURE 5.23: DoH map representative of the hydrogen content evolution in the reactor and DoH time trend averaged over L .

FIGURE 5.24: Heat map representative of the temperature evolution in the reactor and temperature time trend averaged over L .

FIGURE 5.25: Total power instantly absorbed by the LOHC in the form of heat supplied by the external fluid.

FIGURE 5.26: Total DoH trend over time.

(A) Worst case scenario.

(B) Best case scenario.

FIGURE 5.27: Heat composition for different starting conditions.

FIGURE 5.28: Heat costs and maximum theoretical recovery heat, with reference to Fig. 5.27.

FIGURE 5.29: LOHC content in both vessels over time.

Fig. 5.27a e 5.27b, as far as they refer to dehydrogenation, however clearly indicate that to bring the LOHC from the minimum temperature that guarantees the liquid state, to the reaction temperature, a very small portion of the reaction heat is sufficient¹⁰.

Comparing in Fig. 5.28 the total reaction heat released during hydrogenation¹¹ to the two thermal costs, it emerges that this is evidently lower but of the same order of magnitude. The fact that it is smaller is linked to the fact that \dot{Q}_f is instantly derived from T_{lohc} , which in turn is also a function of a term to take into account the internal energy and mechanical energy flows on entry and exit. However, this item still constitutes approximately 93.7% and 97.8% of the two calculated consumptions.

Obviously, this energy content could not even theoretically cover the entire heat consumption of the de-hydrogenation reactor, since the reaction temperature is higher for the release of hydrogen. Regardless of which energy source is used, it remains essential that the highest possible percentage of Q_f is guaranteed as recovery heat.

Fig. 5.29 shows the temporal trend of the LOHC mass content for the two tanks, limiting it to the first hour to return more readable data. As expected, the tanks empty and fill in parallel alternating operation phases. As the reaction progresses, the maximum LOHC content in the reservoirs is reduced due to the effect of dehydrogenation, although this effect is limited, as the contribution of hydrogen to the total mass is relatively small.

Finally, the trend of the DoH in the two tanks over time is shown in Fig. 5.30. This very closely highlights the overall behavior of the system, as can be seen from the comparison with Fig. 5.26. However, temporal excursions are predominant compared to spatial ones, and therefore it is necessary to focus attention on a small time interval to observe the actual trends.

By limiting the analysis to the first 15 steps, very appreciable trends are observed. At any time one of the two tanks plays the role of active tank and therefore its DoH is constant until the mass content reaches zero (Fig. 5.29). In the meantime, the other tank is in passive mode: the mass content increases, while the DoH has an overall decreasing trend in which two phases can be seen: at first it actually decreases due to the entry of LOHC which has transited further long in the reactor; subsequently, as the tank is activated and emptied, the DoH stabilizes due to the homogeneous starting conditions. The initial phase is in fact linked to the inversion of the direction of operation and therefore the change in the DoH associated with $\dot{m}_{v,a}$. In the case in question the stabilization is very short since t_v is quite brief.

¹⁰In fact this $Q_r \approx Q_f$ as seen from the comparison over time of the two associated flows reported in Fig. 5.25.

¹¹An analogous to what was seen for the useful energy applies: the data refers to a discharge that reaches a slightly lower DoH to the minimum value initially expected, and therefore this value actually needs to be increased albeit by a very small percentage.

FIGURE 5.30: DoH trends for both vessels.

At the same time, the total DoH has a regular trend which is always lower than the value established in the active tank. As the discharge proceeds, the total DoH tends to the value that is settling in the filling tank: the quantity of LOHC in the active tank decreases and more and more LOHC has passed through the reactor for prolonged times. The fact that immediately after the switch the total DoH is slightly lower than the value in both tanks is because the new active tank remains crystallized on the DoH value immediately before the switch, which is essentially the result of an average (Eq. 5.90) in which it was taken into account that initially the input had higher DoH (first phase with decreasing DoH): this means that the DoH in the extreme parts of the reactor adjacent to it was lower than that established. Changing direction, the now passive tank starts from empty and is fed by LOHC which until recently was located near the inlet, therefore characterized by a relatively high DoH. Therefore the minimum DoH is not initially the one entering the passive tank, however the reduced extension of the reactor makes this phase very short.

Design parameters

The reference layout for the different case studies was defined starting from an optimization of the preliminary design of the reactor based on the efficiency of the heat exchange and pressure drops. The free parameters are therefore f_r, t_v, v_L, v_f, f_x .

In particular, it was chosen to optimize the reactor so that there is a heat exchange efficiency of at least 90%. This condition is then limited by the need to contain the pressure drops, defining a maximum acceptable value as the 1% of the useful reference power defined as in Eq. 5.94-5.95. Each term depends on the reference mass flow rate chosen to evaluate the associated quantities. For instance, terms associated at mid DoH are:

$$\dot{m}_r = (w_{\%} m_{tot, lohc} f_v) \cdot \left[k_0 \exp \left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T} + bp \right) \left(\frac{DoH_{max} + DoH_{min}}{2} \right)^2 \right] \quad (5.94)$$

$$P_{diss,max} = 0.01 \cdot (\dot{m}_r HHV \eta) \quad (5.95)$$

To estimate the pressure drop, the Colebrook-White and Darcy-Weisback formulas were used (Eq. 5.96-5.97) assuming a roughness of the steel tube of $\epsilon_{tube} = 3$ mm and is used to calculate the dissipated power (Eq. 5.98) to compare with the value defined in Eq. 5.95.

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f}} = -2 \log \left(\frac{\epsilon_{tube}}{3.7 D_{hyd}} + \frac{2.51}{Re \sqrt{f}} \right) \quad (5.96)$$

$$\Delta p_{diss} = f \frac{L}{D_{hyd}} \frac{\rho v^2}{2} \quad (5.97)$$

$$P_{diss} = \frac{\Delta p_{diss} \dot{m}}{\rho} \quad (5.98)$$

Initially, sensitivity analyzes were carried out, setting the different parameters on their average values respectively. For a useful 50 kWh application as presented in this module, the results described by Fig. 5.31 are obtained, where the maximum value defined by Eq. 5.95 is reported in a dotted line.

The results demonstrate that with the standard parameter set identified as $t_v = 300$ s, $f_r = 0.3$, $f_x = 1$, $v_L = 0.20$ m/s and $v_f = 1.00$ m/s when varying:

- f_r ¹²: the efficiency value is always in line with the predefined target ($\geq 90\%$), while the dissipated power increases considerably and almost exponential for values of $f_r \geq 0.6$; for lower values, the dissipated power is less than the maximum acceptable one. This effect is linked to the fact that as the factor f_r increases, the dimensions of the reactor increase and therefore the length of the reactor is greater, but above all by increasing

¹²By the definition of the $P_{diss,max}$ given in Eq. 5.94-5.95, this is the only case in which its value is variable with the abscissa.

FIGURE 5.31: Sensitivity analysis for different design parameters.

the quantity of LOHC in the reactor, by definition the flow rate of heat transfer fluid for the definition of f_x .

- t_v : in this case there is instead a significant excursion in efficiency and a more moderate increase in dissipated power. The variability range within which both optimization requirements are satisfied is between approximately 2.0 min and 7.5 min. As the emptying time increases, the reactor section is reduced but the length of the reactor increases, and since all other data are fixed it influences the ratio between the diameters of the LOHC and heat transfer tubes.
- v_L : in accordance with the data seen for the sensitivity study in f_r , the configuration is extremely efficient, and since the reference value of f_r is low, the power absorbed is less than the maximum acceptable one, or increases in the reference range. Low values of v_L are ideal for limiting the length of the reactor, however it is best not to exceed them to avoid stagnation conditions. The efficiency values obtained highlight that the layout is already significantly optimised; the low variability of the efficiency is associated with the high value of the exchange coefficient defined by the Dixon - Cresswell equation (Eq. 5.62).
- v_f : contrary to the previous case there are significant excursions in efficiency, α_f being smaller, and therefore limiting, than α_L . As the speed increases, pressure losses clearly increase significantly. The acceptable range of variability for the problem conditions is for values of v_f between $\approx 0.18 - 1.20$ m/s.
- f_x : finally, as this parameter increases, a reduction in efficiency is observed: in fact, if for low f_x there is a roughly unitary efficiency, this then decreases as by increasing, it increases the NTU denominator. At first glance, the consumption trend is also peculiar, however these are decreasing since in the layout already defined, the diameter of the LOHC tube is relatively small compared to the circulating flow rate, and therefore there are more severe pressure drops for low f_x . The optimal conditions are satisfied for values greater than 0.6.

Starting from the highlighted results, a rough design can therefore be defined against which the calculation routine can be run to estimate efficiency and consumption as the speed of the external fluid varies; this analysis will define the values of v_f to be used for the controllability study.

Fig. 5.32 is obtained by fixing the values of the remaining parameters as $t_v = 4$ min, $f_r = 0.25$, $f_x = 1$, and $v_L = 0.10$ m/s; this choice was dictated both by the performance results already defined and by the desire to create a compact reactor. The size of the reactor is therefore 8 m in length, and the internal diameters of the LOHC and external fluid tubes are 67 mm and 106 mm respectively.

It is observed that the desired conditions are therefore obtained for speed values between 0.58-1.25 m/s.

5.2.3 Convergence

The results illustrated so far were obtained by discretizing the reactor along its longitudinal extension into 200 elements. This value allows you to contain the computational cost of the routines and to return reliable data.

The convergence of the runs can be evaluated with respect to the DoH_{tot} and its trend over time, both in terms of maximum deviations and the time necessary for the total dehydrogenation of the LOHC to occur.

What has been said can be visualized in the graphs shown in Fig. 5.33-5.34.

The trends reported in Fig. 5.33 clearly show that a lumped parameter approach does not make sense for a PFR, coherently with the type of design itself since it intrinsically foresees an evolution along its length. If significantly different performances are already obtained from the transition from 5 to 25 integration elements, by continuing to refine the grid the differences decrease rapidly. Finally, the profiles obtained with 150 and 200 elements are essentially coincident, and almost overlapped with the profile obtainable with 100 elements.

FIGURE 5.32: Performance of the reactor as the speed of the heat transfer fluid varies.

The convergence of the system can be visualized even more clearly in Fig. 5.34. Here the relative error defined as follows is introduced:

$$\text{rel. err.}(n_z) = \frac{|t_f^{200} - t_f^{n_z}|}{t_f^{200}}$$

$$t_f = t \text{ tc.: DoH}(t) = 0.2$$

and reporting the values of the percentage error and the time t_f for the different runs, we observe that in fact in the passage from 150 to 200 elements no significant difference is recorded. On the other hand, the error is just over 5 % already for just 50 elements, and well below this threshold for 100 elements.

5.3 Conclusions

In the pursuit of optimizing hydrogen release and uptake processes in Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier (LOHC) systems, various reactor designs have been modeled and tested under different design parameters. The primary objectives have been to identify conditions that ensure efficient hydrogen management, minimize electrical consumption, and reduce thermal energy requirements as much as possible, ideally limiting them to the theoretical minimum. This effort has revealed the complexities and trade-offs associated with different reactor configurations, particularly when comparing plug flow reactors (PFRs) with batch reactors.

Modeling and simulation efforts have highlighted that PFRs present a more complex challenge than batch reactors. While batch reactors can often be adequately described using simplified assumptions, PFRs require a more sophisticated one-dimensional modeling approach. This complexity arises because the behavior of a PFR, especially in the initial stages

FIGURE 5.33: Degree of total hydrogenation of the LOHC system over time for differently dense discretizations.

of operation, is highly sensitive to variations in temperature, flow rates, and reaction kinetics along the reactor length. To capture these dynamics accurately, it is necessary to discretize the reactor into a series of elements. However, even with a modest number of elements, it is possible to achieve a reasonable degree of accuracy in the model, ensuring that errors remain within acceptable limits.

One of the significant challenges in PFR design is maintaining thermal stability and uniformity. This issue can be mitigated by thermostating and closely controlling the reactor, which reduces the impact of temperature gradients that might otherwise lead to inefficiencies or safety concerns. Effective thermal management is crucial for preventing hot spots, which could accelerate the reaction rate unevenly or even lead to undesirable side reactions. The adoption of precise thermal controls ensures that the reactor operates within the desired temperature range, thereby maintaining consistent performance and minimizing the risk of deviations from expected behavior.

Another critical aspect of PFR design is the need to minimize the physical footprint of the reactor system. This requirement has driven the development of alternative configurations where the reactor is part of a more integrated system. In these designs, the reactor itself is accompanied by two storage tanks, which play a pivotal role in the overall system's functionality. This configuration not only helps in maintaining the desired reaction conditions but also decouples the system's performance from the specific energy-power ratio inherent to the chosen LOHC. The gravimetric capacity and density of the carrier are closely tied to the reaction kinetics, and by incorporating storage tanks, the system gains greater flexibility in managing these parameters.

The inclusion of storage tanks in the reactor system introduces several advantages. First, it allows for better control over the reaction environment, as the reactants can be pre-conditioned before entering the reactor, and the products can be efficiently handled after exiting. Second, this setup facilitates the integration of the reactor system with downstream processes or

FIGURE 5.34: Time required to reach the objective in terms of final DoH depending on the discretization performed, and relative error associated.

end-user applications. By decoupling the reactor's operation from the direct constraints imposed by the LOHC properties, it becomes easier to tailor the system to meet the specific needs of different applications, whether they require steady hydrogen production or intermittent supply. This flexibility is crucial for ensuring that LOHC technology can be adapted to a wide range of industrial and commercial uses.

Moreover, the integration of storage tanks within the reactor system enhances the overall efficiency by providing a buffer that can absorb fluctuations in reaction rates or energy demands. This buffer capacity is particularly valuable in applications where consistent hydrogen supply is critical, such as in fuel cells or hydrogen refueling stations. The ability to smooth out variations in supply ensures that the downstream systems can operate without interruption, even if the reactor experiences temporary deviations from optimal conditions.

In conclusion, the modeling and testing of various reactor configurations for LOHC systems have underscored the importance of careful design and control. While PFRs pose greater challenges in terms of complexity and thermal management compared to batch reactors, they also offer significant advantages in terms of efficiency, footprint, and flexibility. By adopting a one-dimensional modeling approach and integrating storage tanks into the reactor system, it is possible to achieve a balance between accuracy and practicality, ensuring that the reactors perform optimally under a range of conditions.

The advancements in PFR design, particularly the incorporation of alternative configurations with storage tanks, represent a significant step forward in the development of LOHC technology. These innovations not only enhance the feasibility of using LOHCs for hydrogen storage and release but also pave the way for more widespread adoption by making the systems more adaptable to different end-user requirements. As LOHC technology continues to evolve, the insights gained from these modeling efforts will be invaluable in guiding future developments, ensuring that the reactors are not only effective and efficient but also versatile and reliable in real-world applications.

Chapter 6

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: Controllability

The heat demand to dehydrogenate the carrier is highly variable over time if no control strategy is implemented. This fluctuation is due to the dependence of the reaction rate's concentration on the reactants. Even if constant pressure and temperature conditions could be granted, the release process would gradually slow as more hydrogen has been discharged. At first, a high amount of hydrogen is released quickly, and then the process continues at a slower and steady pace for a medium to low Degree of Hydrogenation (DoH). For example, assuming operation from an initial DoH of 0.95 to a final DoH of 0.20 Peters et al., 2019 the second-order release rate of NEC becomes 95 % slower Gambini et al., 2022.

Since the reaction rate of dehydrogenation reactions depends on hydrogen pressure and temperature Gambini et al., 2022, strategies to control the otherwise highly-variable hydrogen flow rate must rely on either pressure or temperature control. Metal Hydrides (MHs) are characterised by a similar dependence of hydrogen release on pressure and temperature, although the pressure dependence follows, in this case, a Van't Hoff law Gambini, Manno, and Vellini, 2008: therefore, the research conducted on MH systems can be a reference for devising control strategies applied to LOHC systems.

Currently, very few studies in the literature deal with how to control the hydrogen release from a LOHC system, and these studies refer to specific applications without discussing general controllability properties. For example, Bollmann et al. investigate the dehydrogenation of a LOHC using the exhaust gas of a methane-fuelled porous media burner and controlling the reaction through the temperature of the unit by means of a PID controller acting on the burner Bollmann et al., 2023. A PI controller is implemented in another study to control the current generated by a Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cell acting on the hydrogen release pressure Geiling et al., 2021, while in another study, hydrogen release is controlled through reactor temperature and LOHC pumping rate Fikrt et al., 2017.

In contrast, control strategies for MH systems have been widely analysed and discussed. Cho et al. developed a comprehensive general approach to these control systems, taking into account the influence of the initial pressure, temperature and flow rate of the circulation water, the overall heat transfer coefficient and the volume fraction of the bed on the discharge rate. A PID controller was set in place to follow a periodic step function, and the controllability range was estimated in terms of operating time with respect to the control variables' set values Cho et al., 2013. The design of a predictive controller model of multiparametric types for MH reactors was also carried out and presented as a general framework Panos et al., 2010. A neuro-fuzzy PID control system was applied to an MH reactor, deploying a conventional PID control and a back-propagation learning mechanism Nuchkrua and Leephakpreeda, 2013. Through step changes in the voltage input, a dynamical response in terms of the reactor's temperature and pressure is achieved with no overshoot and a reduced rising time with respect to a conventional PID controller. Later, a fuzzy PID control system was evaluated again with great emphasis on the control system design Aruna and Jaya Christa, 2020.

The similarity in the reaction rate equation between LOHCs and MHs makes it possible to devise control strategies for LOHC systems following the approach used in the previously mentioned studies on MH control systems. Therefore, the aim of this section and its novel contribution to the literature is to provide an overall assessment of the controllability

Control variable		Reference value	Range
Reactor pressure	p/bar	1.00	0.50-3.00
HTF inlet temperature	T_f/K	473	288-500
HTF velocity	$v_f/(\text{m/s})$	2	0-5

TABLE 6.1: Reference value and variability range for each control variable.

of LOHC systems acting within a general framework regardless of the specific application field. In particular, the control system is applied to a batch reactor with NEC used as the hydrogen carrier; the batch reactor is designed and modelled with a lumped-parameter approach devised and described in Chapter 5 Gambini et al., 2023c. Alternative control strategies are compared under different working conditions in terms of controllability time, that is, in terms of how long the system can supply the required hydrogen flow rate, which is a measure of the actual efficiency of the storage system under different loads. Research on the performance of control systems highlights the operational constraints of this technology. Relevant information on the controllability range and the energy-to-power ratio is deduced independently from the system size by scaling a constant power demand with respect to the uncontrolled release trend. Such a general approach is meant to serve as a preliminary guide for matching LOHC storage systems to specific applications, depending on the availability of controllability options and power demand.

6.1 Batch Reactor

In real-life applications, hydrogen release should follow the end user's demand. As such, the system's pressure, temperature, or both, must be controlled. A PI controller was thus introduced, and a Simulink/Simscape model was built, introducing a newly defined library for the LOHC system from the ground up. The schematic modelling used for the simulations is illustrated in Fig. 6.1.

The heat exchange efficiency module relies on the procedure developed for a batch reactor Gambini et al., 2023c and calculates the heat transfer effectiveness based on the HTF velocity v_f and temperature T_f , together with the geometric data related to both the reactor and the HTF pipes. The heating system module then solves the energy balance of the reactor, while the hydrogen release module evaluates the mass flow rate of released hydrogen.

Once a target hydrogen mass flow rate is defined on the basis of the user's load, the change between the actual instantaneous release and its target value is fed to PI controllers acting on release pressure, HTF inlet temperature, and HTF mass flow rate. To keep the results general so that they apply to the LOHC subsystem itself regardless of the specific application, the different hydrogen demands evaluated are defined as constant demands. The values of these parameters are obtained as the sum of a constant term and a correction, which is set to the respective PI output when that variable is chosen as the actual control variable or to zero when it is kept as a constant design parameter. A saturation block introduces reasonable limits to the allowed variations. In Fig. 6.1, pressure is chosen as the control parameter, as highlighted by the solid line of the switch connected to the correction dp obtained from the controller.

Three PI control logic procedures were introduced based on the control of the reactor pressure level, the inlet temperature of the HTF and its mass flow rate through control of the fluid's speed. For the latter, the instantaneous heat transfer effectiveness was evaluated to account for the different heat capacities and convection coefficients. Each control strategy was tested independently of the others. In the simulations, the control variables were first set at the reference values and then varied in the ranges given in Table 6.1.

Two parameters were used to assess the controllability of the system. The first depends on the actual period of time ($t_{control}$) during which the system is able to supply the required hydrogen flow rate \dot{m}_{target} ; the parameter t_R normalises this period of time with respect to the theoretical maximum release time τ (Eq. 6.1), defined as the ratio of stored hydrogen

FIGURE 6.1: Schematic models of the heated reactor and the control apparatus.

FIGURE 6.2: Mass flow rate and DoH over time at 473 K and 1 bar for the hydrogenated NEC sample. The bold line accounts for the mean release, while the thin lines represent the 3rd, 5th, 7th, and 8th deciles used in the simulations.

$m_{\text{H}_2, \text{stored}}$ to the required flow rate (Eq. 6.2).

$$\tau = m_{\text{H}_2, \text{stored}} / \dot{m}_{\text{target}} \quad (6.1)$$

$$t_R = \frac{t_{\text{control}}}{\tau} = \frac{m_{\text{H}_2, \text{rel}}}{m_{\text{H}_2, \text{stored}}} \quad (6.2)$$

The variable $m_{\text{H}_2, \text{rel}} = \dot{m}_{\text{target}} t_{\text{control}}$ represents the amount of hydrogen that the system can release at a constant mass flow rate thanks to the control system (neglecting the brief initial transient). Therefore, this normalised time t_R can be seen as a measure of the control system's efficiency, as the second definition in Eq. 6.2 clearly demonstrates.

The second parameter is the time delay t_D , after which the released mass flow rate reaches its target value. Thus, this parameter is not related to the efficiency of the controlled system; it assesses how quickly the controlled system responds to user demand.

The time ratio t_R is independent of the storage size, so the results obtained are general and can be extended to storage systems of any size. However, a normalised measure of power must also be introduced to describe its effect on the time ratio in a size-independent way. To untie the influence of load on the controllability performance from the size of the system, a quantile analysis was performed on the uncontrolled mass release profile at constant pressure and temperature, which is represented in Fig. 6.2 for a net 5 kWh NEC system taking into account a fuel cell with an overall HHV-based efficiency of 0.45 Peters et al., 2019, corresponding to 282 g of available hydrogen. At constant temperature and pressure, the reaction rate is solely determined by the second-order dependence on hydrogen concentration; a discussion about hydrogen release at constant operating conditions can be found in the literature Dong et al., 2016. The uncontrolled LOHC system provides a highly variable flow rate if kept at constant pressure and temperature: as Fig. 6.2 shows, the mass flow rate is reduced by more than 95 % as the DoH decreases from 0.95 to 0.20.

The data on the flow rate time evolution were sorted and divided into ten intervals by deciles so that each group contained exactly one-tenth of the collected data. The power demand P , which is proportional to the required hydrogen flow rate \dot{m}_{target} , was then divided by the corresponding eighth-decile value so that the time ratio t_R and the time delay t_D can be represented against the normalised load $P/P_{8^{\text{th}} \text{decile}}$ to obtain a generalised assessment of the properties of the LOHC storage system, regardless of the size of the storage system.

Simulations were run for the third, fifth, seventh, and eighth deciles (represented as

Power decile	3 rd	5 th	7 th	avg.	8 th
τ/h	6.14	4.10	2.47	2.10	1.81

TABLE 6.2: Theoretical discharge time (energy-to-power ratios) for the deciles of power considered in the simulations, with 473 K and 1 bar as reference temperature and pressure.

dashed lines in Fig. 6.2) and the averaged mass flow rate value (continuous line). The mean hydrogen release mass flow rate ($m_{H_2, released} / \Delta t$) falls between the seventh and eighth deciles. For more than 20% of the operating time, the flow rate would be higher, with a maximum of approximately five times higher. These results are consistent with the significantly faster release that occurs for high values of DoH.

The theoretical release time τ provides an alternative way to identify the load in a size-independent way if the energy content of the storage system is kept constant (clearly, the higher the load, the lower the theoretical release time). For the system represented in Fig. 6.2, the theoretical release time corresponding to the deciles considered in the simulation varies approximately in the range 2-6 h, as shown in Table 6.2.

Under the assumption of a constant rate of hydrogen release, the degree of hydrogenation would decrease linearly with time and the reaction rate would be constant, as shown in Eqs. 6.3-6.4

$$\text{DoH}(t) = \text{DoH}_0 - \text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}t \quad (6.3)$$

$$-k_0 \exp(-bp) \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) \text{DoH}(t)^2 = -\text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H} \quad (6.4)$$

The reaction rate $\text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}$ can be determined as the ratio between the overall change in the degree of hydrogenation ($\Delta\text{DoH} = 0.75$) and the theoretical discharge time τ . So, for example, in the case of the averaged mass flow rate ($\tau = 2.1$ h), the reaction rate is $\text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H} = \Delta\text{DoH} / \tau = 9.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The previous equations show that the hydrogen pressure and temperature should change with time in the following way to maintain a constant rate of dehydrogenation (Eq. 6.5)

$$\exp(-bp) \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) = \frac{\text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}/k_0}{\text{DoH}(t)^2} \quad (6.5)$$

Therefore, the theoretical performance of the controlled system can be studied analytically in a straightforward way under the assumption that hydrogen pressure is constant if the reaction is controlled through the system temperature or that temperature is constant if pressure is taken as the control parameter (Eqs. 6.6-6.7).

In the latter case, setting the system temperature to its reference value $T_{ref} = 473$ K, hydrogen pressure should be varied by the control system according to the following equation:

$$p(t) = -b^{-1} \log\left(\frac{\text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}/k_T}{\text{DoH}(t)^2}\right) \quad (6.6)$$

where $k_T = k_0 \exp\left(-E_a/(R_u T_{ref})\right) = 1.89 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. So, as hydrogenation decreases with time, the controller should decrease the hydrogen pressure proportionally to its logarithm: $p \propto 2b^{-1} \log \text{DoH}$.

On the other hand, if the system temperature is the control parameter, with the assumption of constant pressure ($p = p_{ref} = 1$ bar), the following equation is obtained:

$$T(t) = -\frac{E_a/R_u}{\log\left(\frac{\text{D}\dot{\text{O}}\text{H}/k_p}{\text{DoH}(t)^2}\right)} \quad (6.7)$$

where $k_p = k_0 \exp(-bp_{ref}) = 1.08 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This equation shows that, as hydrogenation decreases with time, the controller should act in such a way that the system temperature

	$T_{f,i}$	G_f	p
P	1.0×10^5	1.5×10^1	1.0×10^2
I	5.0×10^2	1.1×10^3	1.0×10^4

TABLE 6.3: PI controller parameters used for BR designs.

increases proportionally to the inverse of the logarithm of the degree of hydrogenation.

The variation with time of the theoretical values of pressure and temperature derived from Eqs. 6.6-6.7 is presented in the next section, compared to the actual values of hydrogen pressure and HTF inlet temperature obtained with the PI controller described above.

6.1.1 Results

This approach relies on a single controlled parameter (Fig. 6.3) whose value is corrected through a PI controller.

However, more complex configurations can be evaluated as well when multiple variable parameters are taken into account. This choice could prove fundamental when control requirements lead to extreme control parameters values. Preliminary considerations are given in Sec. 6.3. PI controller parameters are summed up in Tab. 6.3.

For BRs a quantile approach guided the target definition. Deciles are defined with respect to the uncontrolled release rate trend, whose shape is related to reaction kinetics (DoH) scaled with a size-factor due to the overall mass content of LOHC. The effect of different loads on the controllability of the system is represented in Fig. 6.4, in terms of the time ratio t_R (Eq. 6.2), which assesses the efficiency of the system, as discussed in the previous section. Setting reasonable bounds to the control variables range, higher power requirements can only be met for a limited time period, while lower requirements can be met for extended time periods, allowing for a deeper discharge. Due to controllability issues, a certain amount of hydrogen cannot be effectively released by the system, and its quantity depends on the power demand. The higher the target power, the higher the unreleased hydrogen content, since the contribution of $z(\text{DoH})$ to the kinetic rate is too low to be counterbalanced by variations in $f(p)$ or $g(T)$ in the given range of variability of the controlled variables.

The HTF inlet temperature provides the most effective control over the entire power range since the largest amount of hydrogen can be released with the required mass flow rate: the efficiency is above 90 % for power demands up to the 8th decile, that is, for energy-to-power ratios τ above approximately 1.8 h for the given reference thermodynamic conditions. Pressure control yields an adequate match for a low hydrogen demand, but displays a sharper drop in efficiency as the power requirement increases: efficiency remains above 80 % only for loads up to the 5th decile ($\tau \geq 4$ h). Lastly, mass flow rate control is by far the least effective, as efficiency is at most 80 % in all situations considered: hence, to keep the release rate above its low tail values, either a temperature or pressure increase is required. However, mass flow rate control is at its core a temperature control strategy that relies on a variable heat capacity to either increase or decrease the heat rate \dot{Q}_f , which is, however, still exchanged at the same temperature $T_{f,in,0}$. As such, even without an upper limit for v_f greater releases than those obtained in the constant temperature and pressure sample cannot be achieved.

In contrast, the time delays (Fig. 6.5) to reach the set value decrease with higher power levels according to the release curve, since the initial release is the highest and more limited restrictions are required. Temperature control is still the most effective, with an almost instantaneous theoretical response. Pressure control has a significantly higher but still low response time that ranges between 1 – 2 min. Mass flow rate control has the poorest reactivity, dramatically increasing at low loads since even the unheated system has a relatively high temperature.

These results can be explained in detail by looking at Fig. 6.6, which shows how the mass flow rate and the DoH change over time for the average mass flow rate ($\tau = 2.10$ h). The initial mass flow rate is significantly lowered to meet the targeted goal, and a constant release is maintained for a widely different time span depending on the control logic. Temperature control reaches the desired mass flow rate faster than the other strategies, resulting in a

FIGURE 6.3: Simulink scheme for deployed to lead the simulations.

FIGURE 6.4: Relative time controllability for increasing values of power. Markers indicate the deciles considered in the simulation: 3rd, 5th, 7th, and 8th deciles.

FIGURE 6.5: Time delay to reach the target power for increasing values of power. Markers indicate the deciles considered in the simulation: 3rd, 5th, 7th, and 8th deciles.

FIGURE 6.6: Hydrogen mass flow rate and DoH over time for the averaged mass flow rate target. In this figure numerical data are relative to a 5 kWh system.

shorter time delay t_D as seen in Fig. 6.5, and keeps a steady supply for a longer period of time, resulting in a higher time ratio t_R as shown in Fig. 6.4. While, at first, the mass flow rate control has a slightly lower DoH due to a more pronounced delay to reach the target release, the DoH trends are mostly similar during the controllability range. When the DoH term gets too small, the system can no longer supply the required mass flow rate, so the curves corresponding first to the mass flow rate control and then to the pressure control deviate from the temperature-controlled system behaviour. A lower mass flow rate is released, resulting in higher levels of DoH.

Fig. 6.7 better explains why each control strategy deviates from the target mass flow rate at a specific time instant. Due to the finite variability range, once the respective bounds are reached, no further regulation margin is available to control the release. In particular, the time evolution of the hydrogen pressure (Fig. 6.7a), the HTF inlet temperature (Fig. 6.7b), and the HTF velocity (Fig. 6.7c) are presented for a target mass flow rate corresponding to the average value, as in Fig. 6.6.

In Fig. 6.7a pressure is shown to increase rapidly to limit the reaction rate, then it decreases steadily until the lower threshold is reached: consequently, the mass flow rate is shown to deviate from then on in Fig. 6.6. The pressure level set by the PI controller (solid line) is consistently lower than the theoretical value deduced from Eq. 6.6, mainly because the system temperature is generally lower than its reference value due to the endothermic nature of the dehydrogenation reaction; however, the shape of the curve is remarkably similar.

Fig. 6.7b shows how the HTF inlet temperature must change with time to return the desired result. An ambient-temperature mass flow rate is required first to cool off the reactor; then, the heating fluid must supply the reaction heat to fuel the release. A smooth increase is observed over time, saturating at the range's upper bound. The theoretical system temperature is shown for comparison, but it must be observed that the two curves are related to the temperature of two different systems: the HTF inlet temperature (solid line) and the hydrogen-LOHC system (thin line with markers). The HTF must obviously be hotter than the LOHC to be able to transfer the heat required to sustain the reaction, but the trend is the same that could be foreseen by means of Eq. 6.7.

Lastly, Fig. 6.7c shows how an increasingly higher mass flow rate is needed as time passes, obtained through an increased velocity of the thermal fluid. A secondary beneficial effect is also provided by the variation in heat transfer effectiveness due to a different v_f . However, it is evident that even if the actual discrepancy with the target power occurs at

FIGURE 6.7: Pressure (a), HTF inlet temperature (b), and HTF velocity (c) variation over time for each respective control strategy.

FIGURE 6.8: Relative time controllability for different control logic at various thermodynamic set points.

$t \approx 67$ min, a substantial increase in velocity is needed from about $t \approx 50$ min, corresponding to $\text{DoH} \approx 0.65$, to compensate for the reduction in the term $z(\text{DoH})$ to the rate through an increase in temperature. This result is consistent with Fig. 6.7b, as the required T_f increases above the reference temperature at approximately the same instant.

Further simulations were performed by changing the initial HTF inlet temperature by ± 10 K and then increasing the working pressure to 1.25 bar, a value that could be more reasonable for a real batch system. Fig. 6.8 highlights how time controllability changes for different thermodynamic set points.

Mass flow rate control is still the least effective. Slightly better performance is achieved for higher pressure levels, but with a greater influence of the set temperature. For low values, better utilisation is achieved since the reduced tail-end release requires a higher temperature in the reactor to reach the set power target. As such a high $T_{f,inlet}$ increase the effectiveness of a mass flow rate control. On the contrary, a 10 K temperature increase produces dramatically worse results, with less than 30% usage for the eighth decile.

Pressure control benefits from higher set pressure levels since they provide a greater control margin at the tail end as the lower bound of the variability range is reached. The higher the temperature, the lower the effectiveness of the pressure control due to the greater influence of the temperature factor to the rate.

Lastly, temperature control yields slightly worse performance at high load and high pressure, since the pressure influence is more marked. A lower reference temperature benefits controllability performances as a greater $\Delta T_{f,inlet}$ is available to speed up the reaction. Similarly to mass flow rate control, the higher the set level, the lower the effectiveness with a sharp decrease related to the need to raise the temperature level above its set value to improve kinetics at low DoH.

The various time delays are represented in Fig. 6.9 with respect to the power demand and the thermodynamic conditions. Temperature control is still almost instantaneously tuned to the set value for every simulation scenario. A more variable trend is showcased by pressure control, with a reduced delay time for high-temperature and low-pressure simulations. However, mass flow rate control has a widely variable reactivity. Since the initial regulation requires a dramatic reduction in release, this time high-temperature values speed up the process as the PI controller establishes a null mass flow rate. High pressure levels are again related to longer time delays. Regardless, mass flow rate control is still definitely the least convenient option.

Therefore, the sensitivity analysis reaffirms the whole temperature control strategy as the

FIGURE 6.9: Time delay for different control logic at various thermodynamic set points.

best fit to enhance controllability throughout the power range. Even though the set variability ranges of pressure and temperature moving from the lower to the upper bound lead to a 500.0% and 73.6% (considering the inverse of the temperature due to the rate equation) increase, the 121.0 kJ/mol activation energy and the 1.397 bar^{-1} pressure coefficient Gambini et al., 2023c give temperature a relatively more marked influence over the kinetic rate.

In general, when using temperature or pressure as control parameters, a power demand equal to or less than the fifth decile can be met with relatively high efficiencies (90% or above). Unless a high reference temperature is needed, for example if a high release rate is sought, such efficiencies can be reached with temperature as the control parameter even for higher loads.

Although the importance of heat recovery for the competitiveness of LOHC-based storage systems cannot be understated, the required high-temperature heat sources might prove difficult to find, limiting the possible applications of this storage technology. So, even though changing the HTF inlet temperature has been shown to be the most effective way to control the release process, the temperature of the heat source could significantly restrict the range of variability for this control parameter. However, the enthalpy change of the dehydrogenation reaction is less than 20% of hydrogen's HHV Gambini et al., 2023c, so it is the quality of the available waste heat (the temperature of the heat source) rather than its quantity that represents the main constraint on the feasibility of this technology. Moreover, in most applications the HTF inlet temperature would be determined by the performance of a recovery heat exchanger where waste heat is recovered, and the heat exchanger dynamics should be taken into account in the model of a specific application. Similarly, both low- and high-pressure levels are challenging because of storage-to-user coupling and the need for hydrogen compression. Therefore, a multiparameter approach could be introduced to increase the controllability or limit the respective variability range, or both. Moderate regulation of the mass flow rate could be studied as a support control strategy; however, the sensitivity analysis highlighted its poor performance when a medium-low DoH is reached.

Looking at individual release curves returns the same results. Fig. 6.10-6.12-6.14 showcase the effect of different singular control systems in terms of the actual hydrogen mass flow release with respect to the first, fifth and tenth decile.

Looking at Fig. 6.10a it is evident that in a $T_{f,i}$ -based control system, to achieve such low values of hydrogen mass flow, its value is quickly lowered and slowly raised as time goes on to account for the less conspicuous DoH driver (Fig. 6.11a). If \dot{m}_f is the controlled variable (Fig. 6.10b), the target value requires \dot{m}_f to be null for the first few minutes of operation, and very low amounts are needed as time goes by (Fig. 6.11b). These values are

(A) Temperature-based control system.

(B) Mass flow-based control system.

(c) Pressure-based control system.

FIGURE 6.10: Control systems performances set aiming for the first quantile.

unreasonably low, considering the high quality of heat required to reach $T_{f,i}$. Regardless, control through changes in the external fluid mass flow \dot{m}_f is slower, since ultimately it can be seen as a temperature-based control. At the same time, it might be a waste to heat the LOHC system up to T_0 , only to have it releasing heat towards the external fluid. As such, T_0 should be reduced, and the best course of action might include a smaller \dot{m}_f . If pressure is the main driver (Fig. 6.10c), higher p values have to be imposed, and they slightly lower over time, with little to no temperature excursion experienced by the system as small amount of released hydrogen imply limited reaction heat (Fig. 6.11c).

For higher targeted release requirements (Fig. 6.12, 6.13), the desired temperature drop with controlled $T_{f,i}$ is more limited and its excursion is definitely more pronounced with quicker adjustments required, with might comprise a limit. As such, a variable mass flow might be needed to optimize this control strategy. If \dot{m}_f is the only controlled variable, at first null mass flows are required but then some kind of parabolic growth takes place. Though only small values are needed, the relative increase is significant. When pressure is the control variable, the maximum p required is lower than before, but its excursion is more marked. Again, through pressure control the system appears to have reached an equilibrium state, in which the external heat exchange perfectly balance the reaction heat. Conversely, under a temperature based control strategies matching the mass demand leads to system to be fundamentally in equilibrium with the external fluid.

The best matches are achieved for the fifth quantile (Fig. 6.12), which is reasonable due to this value being close to the median discharge rate of the unbridled system.

Lastly, when a high amount of hydrogen is required, both the pressure and temperature based control systems reach $\text{DoH} = 0.20$ before the end of the simulation¹ (Fig. 6.14).

Actually the \dot{m}_f ruled control system, while it cannot satisfy the high mass flow demand for long, and it is effectively the least adequate method, it keeps releasing hydrogen for as long as the simulation takes place due to \dot{m}_f influencing T but with a peak limited to $T_{f,i}$ (Fig. 6.15). Conversely, the best fit system is apparently the temperature reliant one, in spite of some overshooting in the early stages. It could be seen as well in the previous cases, but for higher demands its presence is more evident. However these PI parameters are only roughly defined through trial and error, since no automatic tuning is in place due to the system being non-linear. To achieve the desired performances when low DoH are reached, very high temperature levels have to be established, and they might be incompatible with the LOHC stability and the available heat source. At the same time very low values of pressure are required. Again, as pressure control is set in place, the system settles to thermal

¹ t_f was the approximate amount of time required for the uncontrolled system to go from $\text{DoH} = 0.95$ to $\text{DoH} = 0.20$ and as such the system cannot provide that high amount of mass flow for the same time period!

(A) Temperature-based control system.

(B) Mass flow-based control system.

(C) Pressure-based control system.

FIGURE 6.11: Main system variables aiming for the first quartile.

(A) Temperature-based control system.

(B) Mass flow-based control system.

(C) Pressure-based control system.

FIGURE 6.12: Control systems performances set aiming for the fifth quantile.

(A) Temperature-based control system.

(B) Mass flow-based control system.

(C) Pressure-based control system.

FIGURE 6.13: Main system variables aiming for the fifth quantile.

(A) Temperature-based control system.

(B) Mass flow-based control system.

(C) Pressure-based control system.

FIGURE 6.14: Control systems performances set aiming for the tenth quantile.

(A) Temperature-based control system.

(B) Mass flow-based control system.

(C) Pressure-based control system.

FIGURE 6.15: Main system variables aiming for the tenth quantile.

balance. As pressure reaches its lowest value and the mass release gets slower, temperature gets higher. To grant the desired mass flow a combination of pressure and temperature control might be beneficial as to reduce both requirements. The mass flow based control is the least effective because as soon as the maximum amount of \dot{m}_f is required, no further control can be exerted over the system, whose temperature settles to $T_{f,i}$, and the final discharge curve is not unlike the one of the base unbridled model, since only a moderate hindering action is felt at the very beginning of the process, which is in turn compensated by faster thermal equilibrium between the two fluids.

6.2 Plug Flow Reactor

Controllability of the system is evaluated through the definition of a reference mass flow rate: different power demands scenarios are then tested with three alternative control strategies, as explained below.

Again, as different power demands for a given system size (E content) are intrinsically correlated to a different allowable discharge duration, controllability performances are evaluated in terms of the minimum hydrogen content at which the system can effectively meet the demand.

It must be noted that mass flow rate and power demands are strictly correlated through Eq. 6.8, and as such these terms are used interchangeably in this section

$$P_t = \dot{m}_t \text{HHV}_{\text{H}_2} \eta \quad (6.8)$$

In a similar fashion, HTF mass flow rate is applied through the HTF velocity control (Eq. 6.9) and then mass flow rate and velocity control are used as synonyms, even though velocity control has a secondary effect over the heat transfer coefficient.

$$\dot{m}_f = \rho_f \Omega_f v_f \quad (6.9)$$

Instead of a quantile-based approach Gambini et al., 2023b, discharge targets are defined in terms of $\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}}$ (Eq. 6.10) to provide a more intuitive reference.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}} = f_r(w_{\%} m_{\text{LOHC}^-}) \left[k_0 \exp \left(- \left(bp + \frac{E_a}{R_u T} \right) \right) \text{DoH}_0^n \right] \quad (6.10)$$

Consequently, targeted rates are rewritten with respect to the maximum mass flow rate as in Eq. 6.11.

$$\dot{m}_t = f_t \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}} \quad (6.11)$$

To lead a size-independent analysis, data are then presented in terms of the target scale factor (f_t), with a maximum value of $f_t = 1$ when \dot{m}_t coincides with $\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}}$. Theoretically, the system should be able to meet this very scenario requirements only for an infinitesimally small period, however, range variability for each control variable can extend controllability over time.

While real applications could require a degree of load modulation over time, as seen by Preuster et al. Peters et al., 2019 where a SOFC is required to either release 100 % or 50 % of its nominal load, this section is meant as sizing guide. Moreover, capability to follow a variable load is heavily reliant on the definition of an end-user, which is beyond the scope of this analysis.

The selected control variables are:

- Pressure (p): it has a direct influence over \dot{m}_r as seen in Chapter 3. The higher the pressure, the slower is the release while low pressure favors dehydrogenation according to experimental data Kiermaier et al., 2021 and the LeChatelier principle.
- Temperature (T_f): \dot{m}_r changes accordingly to, again, Chapter 3; however, an indirect influence is introduced since the actual control variables is the HTF temperature, so that LOHC temperature changes due to a different heat exchange with the external fluid. The higher the temperature, the faster the reaction while lower temperature levels might also hinder the release acting on the equilibrium concentrations of the endothermic reaction.
- Velocity (v_f): similarly to T_f , v_f indirectly influences \dot{m}_r through a different heat capacity of the external fluid. Unless a T_f lower than the carrier temperature is set, higher values favor higher T and, consequently, faster release. While the primary effect of v_f is over the mass flow rate (Eq. 6.9), and thus the heat capacity, a secondary effect is introduced over ϵ . However, unless low values of v_f are required, thus lowering α_f and resulting in a less effective heat transfer, this effect is mostly negligible due to the previous optimisation step.

TABLE 6.4: Design, kinetic, and thermodynamic parameters used for the simulations.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Ref.
Available H ₂ mass (m_{H_2})	2.821	kg	-
LOHC mass (m_L)	64.40	kg	-
Design temperature (T_{des})	473.15	K	Gambini et al., 2022
Design pressure (p_{des})	1.50	bar	Caroline et al., 2011
Initial hydrogen content (DoH _{max})	0.95	-	Peters et al., 2019
Final hydrogen content (DoH _{min})	0.20	-	Peters et al., 2019
<i>NEC properties</i>			
Gravimetric density (\bar{w})	5.84	%	-
Activation energy (E_a)	121×10^3	kJ/kmol	Gambini et al., 2022
Pressure coefficient (b)	1.397	1/bar	Gambini et al., 2022
Frequency factor (k_0)	2.609×10^{12}	1/min	Gambini et al., 2022
Reaction enthalpy (ΔH_r)	50.6	kJ/mol _{H₂}	Bourane et al., 2016
<i>HTF properties (reference values)</i>			
Inlet temperature (T_f)	473.15	K	-
Velocity (v_f)	0.58	m/s	-
Mass flow rate ratio (f_x)	1.00	-	-
<i>Miscellaneous design properties</i>			
LOHC velocity (v_L)	0.10	m/s	-
Vessel emptying time (t_v)	240	s	-
Reactor mass ratio (f_r)	0.20	-	-

Limiting upper and lower bounds for each variable range were selected as follows:

- Pressure: pressure inside the reactor must not drop lower than 1.0 bar to avoid additional measures to work below the environment pressure level; on the other hand, p cannot be higher than 5.0 bar above which different storage systems might be better suited.
- Temperature: the lower bound is set to be 298.15 K, so that it matches the reference temperature; conversely, thermal stability of the carrier itself impose a maximum acceptable temperature of 500.15 K Xie et al., 2022.
- Velocity: a minimum value of $v_f = 0.0$ m/s was chosen to simulate the lack of HTF mass flow rate, while the upper threshold is set to 1.25 m/s, accordingly to the optimisation constrain over the maximum pumping power required to overcome pressure losses.

Such limits influence the performances of each control system, and they could be subject to further discussion. Regardless of their exact value, the proposed ranges of variability are representative of the actual realistic control range for each variable.

The broad architecture of the Simulink model can be seen in Fig. 6.16

To allow the dynamic system to run in spite of discontinuities due to the two operational-modes definition (see Chapter. 5), a simple Stateflow integration is required. Inputs to define transition conditions are provided by specific simulink blocks. Both units can be seen in Fig. 6.17.

Lastly, Tab. 6.4 sums up again the design used to run the model. For the input parameters shown in Tab. 6.4, the reference mass flow value defined by Eq. 6.10 is $\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}} = 0.19$ g/s.

6.2.1 Results

The layout proposed in Chapter. 5 is simulated and different control strategies are presented and compared.

(A) Thermodynamic and kinetics blocks.

(B) Output variables.

(c) Thermophysical properties definition blocks.

(d) Control blocks: above, target definition; below, control strategy definition.

(E) Operation mode transition blocks.

FIGURE 6.16: Overall view of the main simulink blocks.

(A) Transition regulators tracking vessels filling level.

(B) Stateflow unit for active vessel definition.

FIGURE 6.17: Transition block content: Simulink and Stateflow units.

Controllability performances are then tested with a *Matlab/Simulink* model as described in the previous section, having provided custom-made blocks to account for the kinetics and thermodynamics equations describing both the reactor and the two vessels. Transition between the two operation modes is regulated with *Stateflow* as the active vessel is completely empty (every t_r). Lastly, Ragone diagrams are presented in Sec. 6.2.2.

Uncontrolled system performances for the reactor layout are here presented in terms of the carrier DoH. More specifically, a total DoH is introduced and defined as Eq. 6.12, and compared to the two vessels DoH.

$$\text{DoH}_{tot}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N m_i^{\text{H}_2}(t) + \sum_{j=1}^2 m_{v,j}^{\text{H}_2}(t)}{m_{\text{LOHC}^-, tot} w\%} \quad (6.12)$$

Results for the uncontrolled system are thus presented in Fig. 6.18 in terms of DoH_{tot} and each vessel's DoH.

Design parameters have been chosen so that the whole system, while showcasing different properties throughout its components and length, has similar DoH in the reactor and vessels alike. As a matter of fact, this is a consequence of the many turns needed to fully discharge the LOHC, and the small reactor length. As such, temporal variations are more marked than spatial variations, and to better understand the trends a zoomed plot of the first 15 turns is provided.

At every time one of the vessels acts as the active vessel, as such its DoH is constant until its mass content is null. In the meanwhile, the other vessel is in passive mode: its mass content increases while the DoH overall decreases and goes through a first drop due to LOHC with higher reaction time entering it, and a consequent phase in which the DoH settles to some level as the transient effect of the operation mode switch wears off. The drop is actually due to the change in the DoH associated with $\dot{m}_{v,a}$. Different t_r and reactor length values would influence the balance between these two phases.

In the meanwhile, the total DoH has a smooth trend with $\text{DoH}_{v,a}$ serving as its upper limit. As the discharge proceeds, DoH_{tot} gets closer to the passive vessel DoH: LOHC content in the active vessel decreases, and an increasing amount of LOHC has already passed through the reactor for long time periods. Just after the switch DoH_{tot} is actually slightly lower than both vessels. This is because the active vessel DoH is set to the DoH level just before the switch takes place, which is an averaged value accounting for the two alternating phases highlighted just before. As such, DoH in the adjacent elements to this vessel is lower than the new $\text{DoH}_{v,a}$, which was kept high by the initially higher degrees of hydrogenation of the entering carrier. On the other hand, as it changes direction, the now passive vessel is fed by LOHC that had just been fluxed by it, and has as such a high DoH level. It follows that the minimum DoH is not initially located at the adjacent elements of the passive reactor so the overall DoH is lower than both vessels'. The small length of the reactor keeps this phase is very brief.

Controllability results are here presented for each controlled parameter (Sec. 6.2.1, 6.2.1, 6.2.1), distinguishing between low ($f_t \leq 0.5$) and high ($f_t > 0.5$) power demand.

While more complex control strategies could lead to either a reduced strain over the system, an extended controllability, or both, depending on the application it could be feasible (economically, technically, or both) or not to apply one or more strategies. Additionally, experience with the batch reactors has shown conflicting results which are not easily generalized without end-users definition. As such, only single variable controls have been tested.

Regardless, a utilisation factor e can be introduced to measure the amount of hydrogen supplied to the end user against the available hydrogen stored in the system; the utilisation factor can also be interpreted as a dimensionless useful energy delivered by the system. The utilisation factor is defined in the following equation, where τ is the discharge duration, corresponding to the time instant when the system is no longer able to supply the required flow rate, and $m_{\text{H}_2,u}$ is the hydrogen mass that the system actually delivers to the end user for a given power demand:

$$e = \frac{\int_{t_0=0}^{\tau} \dot{m}_r dt}{m_{\text{H}_2}} = \frac{m_{\text{H}_2,u}}{m_{\text{H}_2}}. \quad (6.13)$$

FIGURE 6.18: Hydrogenation degree of the two vessels and the whole system over time, with a zoomed sub-picture to better highlight how the system works.

FIGURE 6.19: System performances with pressure control for f_t ranging from 0.10 – 0.50. Markers chosen for the mass flow rate and the DoH are \diamond and \circ respectively.

FIGURE 6.20: System performances with pressure control for f_t ranging from 0.60 – 1.00. Markers chosen for the mass flow rate and the DoH are \diamond and \circ respectively.

Pressure control

Fig. 6.19 showcases the achievable performances of a pressure control for f_t ranging from 0.100.50. Release curves in Fig. 6.19a highlight good system response for the lowest demand ($f_t = 0.10$), as controllability is lost when the DoH is even lower than the 0.20 design target. As the demand increases, operation time decreases due to physical constraints: since the energy content of the system is constant, theoretical operation time is intrinsically lower, however the lower bound over the controlled variable is not low enough to allow for greater controllability. As a matter of fact, to achieve these results pressure must first be raised to hinder the release, as the actual demand is quite low, but as the DoH decreases, to meet the \dot{m}_t target, pressure has to drop until it reaches its lower bound and further control is not possible, Fig. 6.19b. The upper bound defined for pressure is actually higher than required; this is beneficial as it lowers costs. If higher pressure were needed, a more efficient way to satisfy the demand might actually be to lower the system temperature.

When the hydrogen demand is high, as in Fig. 6.20 where f_t ranges from 0.60 – 1.00, controllability is limited. Fig. 6.20a highlights that the target can only be met for a high DoH, as pressure cannot be adequately lowered to match the desired \dot{m}_t , Fig. 6.20b. As long as pressure can be changed accordingly to match the demand, the DoH has a linear trend. Afterwards, it follows the performances of the uncontrolled system with the equivalent thermodynamic conditions, and \dot{m}_r decreases with DoH^2 , due to the reaction being of second order. In these cases, pressure still has to be raised but for the 0.90 and 1.00 scenarios, as a pressure drop is required even in the early stages.

FIGURE 6.21: System performances with temperature control for f_t ranging from 0.10 – 0.50. Markers chosen for the mass flow rate and the DoH are \diamond and \circ respectively.

Temperature control

Similarly to pressure control, performances of temperature control are deeply influenced by the demand.

Again, only a demand as low as $f_t = 0.10$ (Fig. 6.21) leads to optimal discharges and $\text{DoH}_f \leq 0.20$. Increasing f_t results in a drop in controllability. A final DoH of almost $\text{DoH} = 0.10$ is reached in Fig. 6.21a for the lowest demand, while higher values do not match the power target for the whole operation time. Still, the final DoH is lower than the equivalent results in a pressure-controlled environment. A significant drop in temperature ($\Delta T \geq 20$ K) is first required for the $f_t = 0.10$ and 0.20 scenarios, with a minimum temperature level of 440 K (Fig. 6.21b). Other case studies still have a temperature drop but it is far more moderate. As such, it could be beneficial for the system to set a design operating point to lower temperature for the lowest scenarios, resulting in a slight reduction in heat consumption.

It must be noted that temperature T here represented is the mass averaged temperature throughout the length of the reactor.

Conversely, high demands can only be satisfied for a limited time period (Fig. 6.22) and result in higher final DoH. Fig. 6.22a shows a drop in the expected performances and while a final DoH of ≈ 0.47 is reached for the highest demand, a more consistently deep discharge is still possible even at these levels. Outside of the controlled regime, mass flow rate has the typical trend of the uncontrolled system. As such, a transient due to the switch between different operational modes is followed by a steady release.

Such an alternating trend is also required by the controlled variable, whose value in Fig. 6.22b has a crescent trend throughout almost the whole operation time. Controllability is lost as the upper bound is reached.

Velocity rate control

The heat transfer fluid velocity, and so mass flow rate, control performances are summed-up in Fig. 6.23-6.24 for low and high demands respectively.

Differently to the pressure and temperature control strategies presented in Sec. 6.2.1-6.2.1, in which satisfactory results are achieved for low demands, the lower bound of velocity can only avoid heating of the system. As such power demands in the 0.10-0.20 f_t range is never met, with the $f_t = 0.20$ goal only reached by the end of the simulation time (after 400 min!), and with a DoH already below 0.60 (Fig. 6.23a). Their velocity profile is thus the same (Fig. 6.23b), as no mass flow rate is required to have temperature drop low enough that the kinetic rate slows down to the desired level. Raising the f_t to 0.30 grants to meet the target but only after about 80 min, which is a consistent time delay when compared to pressure and temperature control systems. The 0.40-0.50 f_t demands are met much earlier, however controllability is lost for still high DoH levels, even as still great controllability margins are allowed for v_f , because the low demands result in low temperature drops and

FIGURE 6.22: System performances with temperature control for f_t ranging from 0.60 – 1.00. Markers chosen for the mass flow rate and the DoH are \diamond and \circ respectively.

FIGURE 6.23: System performances with HTF velocity control for f_t ranging from 0.10 – 0.50. Markers chosen for the mass flow rate and the DoH are \diamond and \circ respectively.

as such increasing the external fluid heat capacity is ineffective to regulate the discharge. As the control strategy is so ineffective, oscillations can easily be observed, and would require the introduction of an intermediate hydrogen buffer to smooth them.

On the other hand, higher demands can only either be met very briefly or not at all, Fig. 6.24a, as $f_t = 0.60$ results in a final DoH above 0.70. As the required reaction rate is relatively high, sunk heat due to reaction enthalpy $\dot{Q}_r = \dot{m}_{ceH_2,r} \Delta H_r$ must be balanced by heat externally provided. As such, Fig. 6.24b showcases a much tighter correlation between velocity changes and controllability time, in spite of a still residual possible control over v_f that leads to no significant control enhancement over the release rate.

6.2.2 Ragone diagrams

Pressure and temperature controlled systems' performances are used to draw Ragone diagrams in Fig. 6.25. In the left diagram, both axes are normalised: the power demand is expressed in terms of the power fraction values f_t , Eq. (6.11), and as such can only vary between 0-1; the energy content, on the other hand, can be higher than unity since it is normalised through Eq. (6.13), where the upper threshold for the numerator is the total hydrogen content, while the denominator is the available mass of hydrogen m_{H_2} in a discharge process taking into account the minimum and maximum design values of the degree of hydrogenation.

As a matter of fact, normalisation is expressed as Eq. 6.13, and featured integral does have an upper limit, but it is the total hydrogen content in the LOHC (with its initial DoH), disregarding the assumed DoH_{min} value. As such, the numerator term can be higher than E_{system}

(A) Controlled hydrogen release over time.

(B) HTF velocity trend over time.

FIGURE 6.24: System performances with HTF velocity control for f_t ranging from 0.60 – 1.00. Markers chosen for the mass flow rate and the DoH are \diamond and \circ respectively.

since $m_{\text{H}_2, \text{tot}}$ is greater than $m_{\text{H}_2, 0}$ (Eq. 6.14), and would only coincide if dehydrogenation took place from DoH = 1.00 to DoH = 0.00 (Eq. 6.15).

$$m_{\text{H}_2, 0} = \frac{E_{\text{system}}}{\text{HHV}\eta} \quad (6.14)$$

$$m_{\text{H}_2, \text{tot}} : (\text{DoH}_{\text{max}} - \text{DoH}_{\text{min}}) = m_{\text{H}_2, 0} \quad (6.15)$$

The diagram on the right shows the specific chemical energy \tilde{E} delivered to the end user against the specific chemical power demand \tilde{P} , which are defined with reference to the total LOHC mass available in the storage system as follows:

$$\tilde{E} = m_{\text{H}_2, \mu} \text{HHV} / m_L \quad (6.16)$$

$$\tilde{P} = \dot{m}_t \text{HHV} / m_L \quad (6.17)$$

The maximum energy-to-power ratio represents the theoretical discharge duration τ_{max} of the storage system, while the actual duration τ depends on the effective amount of energy discharged, and hence it is the product of utilisation factor and theoretical discharge duration Gambini et al., 2023a:

$$\tau_{\text{max}} = \tilde{E}_{\text{max}} / \tilde{P} = m_{\text{H}_2} / \dot{m}_t \quad (6.18)$$

$$\tau = \tilde{E} / \tilde{P} = m_{\text{H}_2, \mu} / \dot{m}_t = e\tau_{\text{max}} \quad (6.19)$$

The Ragone diagram representing specific quantities allows identification of an effective range of discharge duration resulting in utilisation factors above 80%: in the case of the control system relying on HTF temperature, this range is approximately 5-40 h, while for pressure control it is around 10-40 h. However, it is important to recall that the ratio f_r of the LOHC mass within the reactor and the total stored LOHC mass directly affects these values and, in particular, the specific power: since only the mass within the reactor, equal to $f_r m_L$, contributes to the reaction, an increase in f_r obviously leads to a corresponding increase in specific power and a decrease in discharge duration. For example, doubling the ratio f_r halves the value of τ corresponding to the same utilisation factor, meaning that the system is more suitable for relatively high power demands compared to the energy stored. In other words, the highest specific power and the fastest discharge duration are obtained with $f_r = 1$, representing a storage system without vessels and the entire LOHC mass directly contained in the reactor: in that case, the specific power and discharge duration would be five times higher and lower, respectively, than in the case analysed in this section, as found in a previous case study, where a simplified reactor and only pressure control was considered Gambini et al., 2023a.

As discussed in this chapter, low values of power requirements allow for a deep discharge: this is beneficial in terms of compactness and energy density. As normalised power

demand increases, the amount of hydrogen that can be effectively discharged decreases, leading to a reduction in the utilisation factor. This effect can be seen as a reduction in the energy density of the system, since the desired mass flow rate can only be provided for high values of DoH, and at lower values the system is unable to feed the end-user. Temperature control has better performances: controllability is both higher and more consistent. However, to reach a utilisation factor of at least 80 % of the standard storage capacity, the normalised power demand f_t must be lower than 70 % and 30 % for temperature and pressure control, respectively.

In the case of not-constant demand coupling, these graphs have to be read as follows. Given a control strategy (i.e. pressure) and a normalized power demand either assuming a higher (i.e. $f_t = 0.6$) or lower (i.e. $f_t = 0.2$) value: the system capability to meet the desired demand is only hindered by the end-user possibility to follow a dynamic load up until the normalized energy delivered level associated to the higher demand is met (in this case, about 0.55, see $f_t = 0.6$). Afterwards, the low demand can still be met effectively, while at high demand the system is beyond controllability: the lower pressure bound has been met, so no further control is achievable, and the release follows the uncontrolled system unloading associated to that pressure and temperature level.

6.3 Future advancements

As already introduced in the previous sections, more complex control strategies could prove better suited to match high power demands. A system of parallel PID controllers has then been tested, as seen in Fig. 6.26. Results are hereby given for the BR configuration.

Since the effect of \dot{m}_f is mainly about temperature convergence to $T_{f,i}$, the most effective combination² is a pressure - temperature control system. When this control logic is in place (Fig. 6.27) it is possible to grant the required hydrogen demand for almost the whole time period, and with a limited overshoot. Low pressure levels are only required in the very final stages of the discharge process, and temperature variability is more limited. Alternatively the system could achieve almost the same conditions with a higher p_{min} value, whose reduced variability is compensated by the inlet temperature of the external fluid (Fig. 6.28).

While the controllability range features an extension with respect to the single-variable scenario, a more advanced set-up is needed. As stated at the beginning of this section, feasibility of complex control strategies is anything but a trivial matter and should be investigated for any given scenario. Consequently, no further general consideration can be made. Regardless, this analysis proved mass flow rate control of the external fluid to potentially hold a valuable contribution, regardless of the poor controllability performances already seen in this chapter.

6.4 Conclusions

Different control strategies can be implemented to influence the kinetic rate, acting on the temperature and pressure of the reactor. For a given size and reasonable ranges of variability for each control variable, a maximum controllability time can be defined with respect to the power demand; this parameter identifies the system storage efficiency under different loads, as it measures the actual amount of hydrogen released against the stored hydrogen. Both the batch and plug flow reactors are used to test their controllability. As the amount of hydrogen released depends on both qualitative (reaction rate) and quantitative (LOHC mass content) factors, controllability assessments should be defined with respect to a dimensionless parameter, so that they can be representative of the technology.

In this analysis, different constant demand values were considered and defined; to allow for general considerations a quantile-based representation has been chosen in the batch reactor study. On the other hand, the controllability performance of a plug flow reactor are

²This section is meant as a theoretical approach, feasibility of each control strategies has to be determined for every specific application.

defined with respect to the maximum hydrogen release defined by assuming design operation. Both representations need the definition of design thermodynamic conditions, i.e. a design temperature.

For a batch reactor, practical values of theoretical release time, corresponding to the energy-to-power ratio, are found in the interval 2-6 h for LOHC systems. Regarding the feasibility of each control strategy, the temperature control shows the best results: efficiency remains above 90 % over the entire range of loads considered, that is, for energy-to-power ratios τ as low as 1.5-2.0 h; pressure control only leads to satisfactory performance at low load ($\tau \geq 4$ h). Although easier to implement, mass flow rate control alone shows a lacklustre controllability, resulting in an efficiency below 80 % over the whole load range considered, and both controllability and delay times are significantly worse than those achieved with different control strategies.

Although temperature control allows for over 90 % discharge even for the eighth decile, pressure control leads to similar performances for lower-than-median loads. On the other hand, the energy stored is fully released at a load corresponding to the fifth decile ($\tau \approx 4$ h) with temperature control. As such, this energy-to-power ratio could identify the best power level to operate the reactor as the best trade-off between storage efficiency and power output.

Under different reference thermodynamic conditions, temperature control is still the most effective, losing effectiveness only if higher reference temperature levels are required. Consistently lower but overall adequate performances are achieved through pressure control, again suffering the influence of a higher temperature. Mass flow rate control remains the least reliable control logic, dramatically losing effectiveness for higher temperature.

More complex control strategies could be investigated, introducing a synergistic multi-parameter control to make use of the good controllability of pressure and temperature while reducing the strain in the required variation range. This approach has been briefly tested, however the much increased system complexity may not be justified by the increased controllability performance. Different results could be obtained for a variable load profile, but would require the definition of a specific case study thus losing generality. Overall, complex control strategies could be too expensive and hard to implement for small scale applications, and would probably be better fit for plug flow reactor applications; see Chapter 8.

Controllability of a plug flow reactor system is evaluated with the newly introduced layout (reactor coupled with two vessels) which allows for discontinuous operation and reduced length. Note that by injecting only a fraction of the LOHC volume, the high variability of the uncontrolled LOHC release profile is intrinsically reduced. As the reactor cycles through its two operational modes, a transitory phase marks each directional shift. However, as soon as the transitory is extinguished, the mass release settles to a constant value, and remains constant up until the active vessel volume has been fully emptied. Depending on the volume fraction characterizing the system sizing (reactor and vessels volume), the allowable E/P ratios can widely vary. On the other hand, the cycling period (residency time of the LOHC molecule in the reactor for a given pass) and the vessel emptying time (time interval between one operational mode and the other) both affect the length of the transitory phase.

No significant difference between the two configurations has been observed. Again, both temperature and pressure control schemes showcase great controllability with low power demand. While pressure control performances quickly decrease as the demand increases, temperature control is more consistent. Regardless, a power demand greater than 70 % of the reference value would lead to unsatisfactory degrees of utilisation. These results are used to plot Ragone diagrams, highlighting these performances. On the other hand, the heat transfer fluid mass flow rate is inadequate to lead reaction rate control, and should only be used coupled with other controlled variables.

Although not presented here, plug flow reactors would also allow for more sophisticated control strategies, such as optimizing hydrogen release by manipulating a temperature gradient along the reactor. However, it is not possible to generalize such a strategy, and its modeling would be significantly more complex. Additionally, it is important to note that pressure control relies on the assumption that the reaction kinetics do not change drastically outside the range of the provided data.

FIGURE 6.25: Ragone diagrams of a NEC storage system under pressure and temperature control: normalised diagram on the left, specific values of energy delivered and power demand on the right.

FIGURE 6.26: Simulink scheme with two controlled variables.

(A) Hydrogen mass flow delivered.

(B) Main system variables aiming for the tenth quantile.

FIGURE 6.27: Pressure and Temperature-based control system.

(A) Hydrogen mass flow delivered.

(B) Main system variables aiming for the tenth quantile.

FIGURE 6.28: Pressure and Temperature-based control system with higher p_{\min} .

Chapter 7

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: SOFC Applications

High dehydrogenation temperatures and heat demands require any reasonable LOHC application to have available waste heat to devolve for the hydrogen release. One possible pathway comes in the form of Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) coupling. As SOFCs operate at high temperature above the design dehydrogenation temperature of the LOHCs, and provide a good amount of waste heat to recover, such coupling would limit the costs associated to the dehydrogenation step. Heat generated by SOFC drives the LOHC reactor, while hydrogen released in the reactor drives the SOFC reaction.

In this chapter SOFC heat generation model is presented and validated (Sec. 7.1), and coupled with a LOHC subsystem (Sec. 7.2).

7.1 Waste Heat Model

There are four main heat rejection mechanisms in SOFCs: putting aside the very electrochemical reaction, which releases heat due to the entropy increase, the remaining three sources are related to overpotentials (V) which result in heat generation proportional to the SOFC current (I).

The heat model provided is largely taken by (Hafsia et al., 2011), while an additional validation of the computed data for each overpotential source is made with respect to (Ranjbar et al., 2014). Activation overpotential is evaluated with the formula provided in (Ranjbar et al., 2014) due to a lack of information about how to evaluate the charge transfer coefficient otherwise required.

- Ohmic overpotential: Ohmic overpotential is related to the resistance of the each component of the electrochemical cell. Electric conductivities (σ) of the electrolyte, the cathode, and the anode can be evaluated with Eqs. 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3¹ respectively.

$$\sigma_{el} = 3.34 \times 10^4 \exp \frac{-10300}{T} \quad (7.1)$$

$$\sigma_{ca} = \frac{4.2 \times 10^7}{T} \exp \frac{-1200}{T} \quad (7.2)$$

$$\sigma_{an} = \frac{9.5 \times 10^7}{T} \exp \frac{-1150}{T} \quad (7.3)$$

These values are used to evaluate the overpotential for each component accounting for the layer thickness (δ) and the SOFC current, as seen in Eq. 7.4

$$V_{ohm} = \sum_j \frac{\delta_j}{\sigma_j} \cdot I \quad (7.4)$$

¹All three equations return σ in $1/(\Omega \text{ cm})$, taking temperature in K as input.

- Activation overpotential: due to activation loss at the electrode - electrolyte interface. The exchange current in the cathode and anode (i_0) are evaluated with respect to activation energy (E), an exponential factor (γ) and temperature as Eq. 7.5:

$$i_{0,k} = \gamma_i \frac{R_u T}{2F} \exp - \frac{E_i}{R_u T} \quad (7.5)$$

with F being the Faraday constant². The resulting overpotential is expressed by Eq. 7.6 with the arcsinh method.

$$V_{act} = \sum_j \frac{R_u T}{F} \operatorname{arcsinh} \frac{i}{2i_{0,k}} \quad (7.6)$$

The symbol i is used for the current density, derived from dividing the SOFC current by its area.

- Concentration overpotential: this term is due to concentration of the reactants at the triple phase boundary (TPB) being different than those in the bulk, so it's related to a mass diffusion-limited regime. For cathode and anode regions Eqs. 7.7 and 7.8 are applied.

$$V_{con,c} = \frac{R_u T}{4F} \log \frac{p_{ceO_2}}{p_{ceO_2,TPB}} \quad (7.7)$$

$$V_{con,a} = \frac{R_u T}{2F} \log \frac{p_{ceH_2} p_{ceH_2O,TPB}}{p_{ceH_2,TPB} p_{ceH_2O}} \quad (7.8)$$

Partial pressure values are evaluated using Eqs. 7.9, 7.10, and 7.11 as highlighted by (Yang et al., 2013).

$$p_{O_2,TPB} = p - (p - p_{O_2}) \exp \frac{j R_u T \delta_c}{4 F D_{eff,c} p} \quad (7.9)$$

$$p_{H_2,TPB} = p_{H_2} - \frac{j R_u T \delta_a}{2 F D_{eff,a} p} \quad (7.10)$$

$$p_{H_2O,TPB} = p_{H_2O} + \frac{j R_u T \delta_a}{2 F D_{eff,a} p} \quad (7.11)$$

The effective diffusivity is evaluated respectively as Eqs. 7.12 and 7.13:

$$D_{eff,c} = D_{O_2,eff} \quad (7.12)$$

$$D_{eff,a} = \frac{p_{H_2O}}{p} D_{H_2,eff} + \frac{p_{H_2}}{p} D_{H_2O,eff} \quad (7.13)$$

with individual species having diffusivity coefficients expressed as Eqs. 7.14, 7.15 and 7.16:

$$D_{O_2,eff} = \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} \left(\frac{1}{D_{O_2-N_2}} + \frac{1}{D_{O_2,K}} \right)^{-1} \quad (7.14)$$

$$D_{H_2,eff} = \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} \left(\frac{1}{D_{H_2-H_2O}} + \frac{1}{D_{H_2,K}} \right)^{-1} \quad (7.15)$$

$$D_{H_2O,eff} = \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} \left(\frac{1}{D_{H_2O-H_2}} + \frac{1}{D_{H_2O,K}} \right)^{-1} \quad (7.16)$$

having used symbols ϵ , τ for the electrode porosity and tortuosity. Knudsen diffusivity is then evaluated as Eq. 7.17 as a function of the mean pore diameter, which is reasonably set to about the mean particle diameter, and the ratio of the temperature

²The Faraday constant $F = 96.485\,336\,5 \times 10^5$ C/mol is the total electric charge of a mole of elementary particles.

and molecular weight.

$$D_{i,K} = 48.5d_p \left(\frac{T}{M_i} \right)^{0.5} \quad (7.17)$$

Lastly, binary diffusivity is evaluated using Fuller equation as a function of pressure, temperature, a representative mean molecular weight (Eq. 7.18), and the diffusion volume (v), Eq. 7.19).

$$M_{ij} = 2 \left(\frac{1}{M_i} + \frac{1}{M_j} \right)^{-1} \quad (7.18)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{0.00143T^{1.75}}{pM_{ij} [v_i^{1/3} + v_j^{1/3}]^2} \quad (7.19)$$

- Chemical reaction: lastly, the associated source can be evaluated with Eq. 7.20 as a function of the enthalpy formation of H₂O, and the voltage.

$$Q_{chem} = -\Delta H_{f,H_2O} - 2FV \quad (7.20)$$

The first term can be evaluated with an empirical formula with respect to temperature (K) as Eq. 7.21. Voltage provided by the fuel cell is instead the ideal potential (E_{ideal}) less each loss factor mentioned above (Eq. 7.22), and with E_{ideal} depending on the Nernst potential (E^0 , Eq. 7.23) corrected by a term which accounts for the effective thermodynamic conditions of the SOFC in terms of temperature and concentrations (Eq. 7.24).

$$\Delta H_{f,H_2O} = -(240506 + 7.3835T) \quad (7.21)$$

$$V = E_{ideal} - (V_{ohm} + V_{act} + V_{con}) \quad (7.22)$$

$$E^0(T) = 1.2723 - 2.7645 \times 10^{-4}T \quad (7.23)$$

$$E_{ideal}(T) = E^0(T) - \frac{R_u T}{2F} \log \frac{\chi_{H_2O}}{\chi_{H_2} \chi_{O_2}^{0.5}} \quad (7.24)$$

M [kg/mol]	O ₂	15.999×10^{-3}
	N ₂	28.020×10^{-3}
	H ₂	2.016×10^{-3}
	H ₂ O	18.015×10^{-3}
ν	O ₂	16.30
	N ₂	18.50
	H ₂	6.12
	H ₂ O	13.10
λ_v	O ₂	0.21
	N ₂	0.79
	H ₂	0.97
	H ₂ O	0.03
r_p [pm]	O ₂	152.0
	H ₂	120.0
	H ₂ O	137.5
γ [A/m ²]	Anode	6.54×10^{11}
	Cathode	2.35×10^{11}
E_a [J/mol]	Anode	140 103
	Cathode	137 103
δ [μ m]	Anode	500
	Cathode	50
	Electrolyte	10
Electrodes	Porosity	0.375
	Tortuosity	2.750

TABLE 7.1: List of the input parameters required to model SOFC heat and power generation.

7.1.1 Validation

A table is provided to sum up every input parameter mentioned in the modelling section (Tab. 7.1).

Validation with (Ranjbar et al., 2014) is illustrated by Fig. 7.1 for 1000 K and 1 atm.

Comparison between the two highlights that all loss sources, in spite of having used different equations to model them, lead to the same V . Concentration overpotential may actually diverge at some point for high current density values, however given the provided data a good match is actually achieved.

On the other hand, while V_{loss} is effectively modelled, the resulting V is different³. More specifically, the proposed model hints at higher voltage values, accordingly to Eqs. 7.23 and 7.24. Authors in (Ranjbar et al., 2014) actually rely on a more analytical approach, as the Nernst potential is evaluated with respect to the Gibbs free energy change. However, comparing the modelled results with other sources (such as (Cimenti and Hill, 2009)) highlights a good match (Fig.7.2).

The only actual difference which may explain this different behaviour is due to the Nernst-to-ideal conversion used in (Ranjbar et al., 2014), which both accounts for the activities of the different species (conversely, concentration values are used in the proposed model), and for pressure loss terms.

Overall, a good consistency is achieved: heat sources are model in good agreement with the literature, and as such recovery heat for LOHC dehydrogenation can effectively be simulated. Power generation, on the other hand, may require a correction factor so that it is reduced to account for the highlighted discrepancy.

The resulting performances in terms of electric power and loading curve are thus presented in Fig. 7.3. Voltage loss due to ohmic resistance is consistently low, and it only actually plays a role for low values of j . Activation overpotential accounts for a significant amount of voltage losses, while concentration overpotential is quite low at first, but it greatly increases

³Note that the source paper used to validate the model only provided data for a fraction of the full cell operating range. Full modelling up until $V = 0V$ is provided in the next figures.

(A) Potential and overpotential sources trends as published by (Ranjbar et al., 2014) for 1000 K and 1 atm.

(B) Potential and overpotential sources trends as modelled for 1000 K and 1 atm.

FIGURE 7.1: Model validation through comparison with Ranjbar et al. (2014).

(A) Nernst equation trends for different fuels as published by (Cimenti and Hill, 2009).

(B) Nernst potential as modelled with Eq. 7.23.

FIGURE 7.2: Model comparison with (Cimenti and Hill, 2009).

at high current density values, as mass diffusion becomes the limiting step in the reaction. The sharp turn of the loading curve is determined by overpotential due to concentration, and the maximum current density is reached as soon as the log factor in Eqs. 7.8-7.7 tends to zero.

These results can be seen in terms of power conversion when multiplying the voltage output by the current density, so that a power curve is obtained. This curve has a maximum value which falls near the knee. Due to the sharp trend when moving from the peak to its right, it is advisable to set the working point on the left side of the peak, where smoother transitions take place.

Additionally, having defined the output power as Eq. 7.25⁴, and given the relationship between current and mass flow rate (Eq. 7.26⁵), with U_f being the utilisation factor, it follows that $P_{input} \propto I$, so Eq. 7.27 returns an efficiency with the same trend of the voltage. Consequently, the right branch of the power curve is associated with lower efficiency values. Overall, the effective working point has to be a trade-off between power density and efficiency.

$$P_{output} = V \cdot I \quad (7.25)$$

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = n_{cells} \frac{IM_{H_2}}{n_{el}FU_f} \quad (7.26)$$

$$\eta_{FC} = \frac{P_{output}}{P_{input} = \dot{m}_{H_2} \cdot HHV} \quad (7.27)$$

Lastly, every heat source is plotted with respect to the current density, providing the HHV and LHV-based hydrogen inlet energy flow, and the power curve illustrated above, as a reference. The greatest heat source comes from the chemical reaction, which becomes even greater than the output electric power for $j \geq 3 \times 10^4 \text{ A/m}^2$. These values are, however, marked by very low η . As for the other major contributions, they are the activation and concentration terms related to the anode. This is mainly due to the anode's greater thickness.

Similarly to other technologies, SOFCs design features a tradeoff between electric efficiency and power density. Fig. 7.4 shows both trends with respect to the current density. Both curves are affected by the overpotential terms; more specifically, as the current density increases the cell voltage lowers with a sharp turn at high current density levels due to the concentration overpotential. At first the voltage drop is moderate compared to the current density increase; then the voltage reduction is too sharp to be compensated by the current density increase. As such the power density curve features a maximum point.

On the other hand, dividing the power output by the input chemical power due to the hydrogen mass flow rate (i.e. proportional to the current density produced), the resulting energy efficiency follows a similar trend to the voltage profile. The higher the current density, the lower the efficiency and the trend slope depends on the current density value: for both low and high values of current density the efficiency drop is more marked due to the different influence of the overpotential terms under varying loading conditions.

The different trend of the two performances indicators return a valuable information. When designing the fuel cell stack to have an overall high power density it is safer to oversize the system. While the power density may suffer a bit, its trend is locally almost flat so the resulting power density is only marginally lower while the electrical efficiency is higher and by oversizing the system the effective working point is granted to not fall on the right side of the power curve, where performances degrade fast.

⁴These equations are given for dimensional quantities, since they are defined with respect to I , however simulations are held with respect to j , as illustrated by x-coordinates in the presented plots.

⁵The number of electrons involved in the reaction is $n_{el} = 2$, as $H_2 + O^{2-} \rightarrow H_2O + 2e^-$.

(A) Loading curve for a 1000 K and 1 atm SOFC.

(B) Electric power converted by the SOFC.

(C) Heat sources made available by the SOFC.

FIGURE 7.3: Model results in terms of voltage output, electric power, and heat sources.

FIGURE 7.4: Power density and electrical efficiency trends with respect to the SOFC current density. The maximum power design point is highlighted with a black dot.

7.2 Dynamic modeling

The presented model is coupled in a PFR LOHC subsystem coupled with two vessels. More specifically, there are two links between the SOFC and LOHC subsystems:

- The amount of hydrogen released by the reactor \dot{m}_{H_2} defines the feed of the SOFC, unless a third external element is deployed. Hydrogen is assumed as the limiting agent in the reaction, meaning that enough oxydant is provided at any time, not to hinder the kinetics. Air with 21 %_v O₂ is chosen as the oxydant.
- Heat to subtain the release is provided by the fuel cell at SOFC operation point, which is set at 1000 K and 1 bar. Heat generation is more than sufficient to keep the system temperature constant (Peters et al., 2019).

As heat generation is modelled with respect to the current density (j) of the SOFC, its area has to be defined. Sizing is carried out by:

1. Assuming a SOFC efficiency η_0 to carry out the LOHC subsystem sizing.
2. Looking for the current density, for given T and p conditions, that returns $\eta_{\text{SOFC}} \equiv \eta_0$.
3. Choosing a working point in terms of f_t . This value defines the design mass flow rate, and thus the current produced is expressed by Eq. 7.28:

$$I_{f_t} = \dot{m}_r \cdot f_t \cdot \frac{zFU_f}{MW_{\text{H}_2}N_{\text{cells}}} \quad (7.28)$$

where z is the number of electron involved in the reaction (2), and for given fuel utilization factor (U_f), which can be reasonably set to 85 % (Ryu, Duong, and Kang, 2023).

4. Lastly, by linking I_{f_t} to j_η which satisfies point 2 the surface area in Eq. 7.29 is returned.

$$A_{\text{SOFC}} = \frac{I_{f_t}}{j_\eta} \quad (7.29)$$

With respect to the defined design configuration, different working points (f_t) can still be met. Due to the high amount of heat released, a SOFC-coupled reactor works mostly at constant temperature by design.

For this simulation the exact number of individual cells has not been defined. Depending on the required voltage, a different number of cells may be required. For the scope of this analysis, the main variable is the stack area ($A_{\text{cell}} \cdot N_{\text{cell}}$). Assuming the same behaviour and design for every cell, the total voltage output of the stack is expressed in Eq. 7.31 and the effective power converted is expressed by Eq. 7.30.

$$\dot{P} = V_{\text{cell}}j \cdot A_{\text{cell}}N_{\text{cell}} \quad (7.30)$$

$$V_{\text{tot}} = N_{\text{cell}}V_{\text{cell}} \quad (7.31)$$

The presented SOFC model has been coupled with the LOHC subsystem described in Chapter 6 making use of the vessels-paired plug flow reactor layout, which has been sized for 50 kWh net output and design isothermal operation at 473.15 K for 800 min; the resulting performance is presented below in Figs. 7.5 to 7.8. A discussion about the LOHC and SOFC coupling can be found in Chapter 8, along with the schematic overview of the system (see Fig. 8.2).

While this first simulation focuses on the isothermal functioning of the LOHC reactor, the SOFC sizing procedure is made assuming the reference efficiency (0.45 over the HHV) to take place for a f_t value of 0.7. Higher values are marked by a drop in controllability, as such the expected load should be equal or less than 0.7 meaning that the electric efficiency is going to be at least the one assumed in the pre-design stage, Fig. 7.4.

Fig. 7.5 represents the resulting power output and efficiency values over time trends due to the changing load point. Those results are obtained by imposing the efficiency over the

FIGURE 7.5: SOFC performances indicators over time due to the decreasing current density; efficiency values refer to a HHV-based input.

$f_t = 0.7$ corresponding mass flow rate; for a resulting current density of 1.21 A/cm^2 the necessary area is about 0.91 m^2 . Under this configuration the reaction heat required to drive the hydrogen release is about 3.49 kW , even assuming only the reaction heat to be recovered, this value is still much higher and about 8.10 kW ; as such the SOFC waste heat is more than enough to drive the dehydrogenation reaction.

Since the target factor is relatively high (i.e. close to one) under uncontrolled release SOFC operation is marked by higher efficiencies for most of its operation; efficiency values below the pre-design input are present at the early stages of release as the high DoH pushes the mass release rate, and thus the current density, above the sizing factor. On the other hand, as the design point has been chosen on the left side of the power curve, the resulting power output only decreases over time.

Fig. 7.6 and Fig. 7.7 portray the time and spatial evolution of the DoH in the reactor. In Fig. 7.6 the overall DoH of the system is compared to the reactor hydrogenation degree evaluated at different length positions. At first the two profiles are mostly the same, but as the simulation proceeds the difference between the two profiles increases. This behaviour depends on the relation between the time to empty one vessel and the time to cross the reactor, and the reactor size. In this simulation the lower DoH of the LOHC stored in the passive vessel pushes the overall DoH consistently below the average value inside the reactor.

Zooming over the corresponding 375 – 425 min time interval to visualize the space-dependent behaviour of the LOHC, otherwise lost when compared to the time-scale variation profile, reveals the already discussed behaviour: transitioning between vessels leads to the reactor ends to be interchangeably characterized by either the highest or lowest DoH value. After a short transient, LOHC molecules closer to the active vessels are overall more hydrogenated than those by the other end of the reactor due to the latter longer residence time inside the reactor itself.

These variations are however overall quite small when considering the complete operation time, Fig. 7.7. As a matter of fact, the DoH profiles look flat and constant throughout the reactor length. However, when plotting only a few minutes of the reaction the effective length-wise dependence is highlighted.

As seen below, the slope of the trend depends on the timestamp: when moving from one operation mode to the other (vessel-wise) the slope sign changes; on the other hand, moving from one mode to the other makes the least hydrogenated point move from one end to the other so that it can fall at central values just like in the profile lines reported on the bottom of the figure.

FIGURE 7.6: DoH trend over time for different grid positions over the reactor. Above: complete overview; below: zoom on the 375 – 425 min time interval. The black line represents the overall vessels and reactor system DoH.

FIGURE 7.7: DoH trends over the reactor length at different timestamps. Above: initial, middle and last stages of the reaction; below: focus on the middle stage of the reaction.

FIGURE 7.8: Vessel mass content of hydrogen (blue) and total LOHC (orange) over time. For clarity, only selected time intervals are plotted; from left to right pane: first, central, and last 30 min.

Lastly, Fig. 7.8 shows the mass content of vessel one and two over time, distinguishing between hydrogen and total mass. The reduction over time of both profiles are only due to hydrogen loss, having assumed negligible LOHC vapor fraction in the products. These trends and each mode change are responsible for the different slopes of Fig. 7.6 and Fig. 7.7.

7.2.1 Control

For the scope of hydrogen release control, the fuel cell provides heat at such a higher temperature that the external mass flow rate and the temperature control strategies collapse into a single control strategy. By changing the amount of waste heat redirected towards the LOHC reactor its temperature can either increase or decrease to satisfy the demand target: this procedure is represented by a variable degree of valve opening.

Similarly, pressure control is still possible and can be represented in the same way but the control range of this variable is quite low, hinting at a small potential for controllability.

This section assumes a constant demand and only these two options are evaluated. However, a different approach could be taken. Section 8 presents a LOHC-SOFC system case scenario for maritime applications: given the changing nature of the power demand, an effective control strategy should rely on LOHC mass flow rate variability over time.

As such results are presented for both low and high target factor values (0.3 and 0.7) assuming either temperature, pressure, or both control strategies. For both scenarios, off-design cases are evaluated assuming a different load than the given sizing input.

Fig. 7.9 and Fig. 7.10 present the SOFC and LOHC behaviour under a constant demand corresponding to $f_t = 0.3$ and $f_t = 0.7$ respectively, and pressure control at a fixed temperature of 473.15 K. As highlighted by the previous analysis over general control systems the pressure variable is not enough to carry out complete dehydrogenation for high mass flow rate demands. On the other hand, the low demand scenario features a significant improvement over the high demand case in terms of controllability, so much so that the controlled to uncontrolled transition is by far less evident when looking at the DoH trend.

Both SOFCs work at the given power rate with the designed efficiency as long as the constant demand is satisfied; afterwards the power output decreases and the efficiency increases. SOFC behaviour in the following figures of this chapter is described by the same consideration as the above mentioned cases, and will not be further discussed. Trends are plotted and included to still provide a visual representation of the controllability performances.

Fig. 7.11 and Fig. 7.12 present the SOFC and LOHC behaviour under a constant demand corresponding to $f_t = 0.3$ and $f_t = 0.7$ respectively, this time under temperature control at a fixed pressure of 1.5 bar. Temperature control is much better fit to satisfy the low demand scenario providing complete dehydrogenation: as the DoH reached its final value the required temperature is even lower than the set upper bound (500.15 K), meaning that there is still room for further discharge, and thus resulting in a possibly higher energy density.

Similarly, the high power demand is granted for a longer time period, however complete discharge is still not possible. Regardless, switching from a pressure to a temperature control provides an additional 33% energy release as the demand is satisfied for slightly less than 300 min, compared to the slightly less than 200 min coverage of the previous control strategy.

Fig. 7.13 to Fig. 7.16 provides a multi-parameter control strategy, with both pressure and temperature being controlled to satisfy the demand. This control strategy has already been discussed in Sec. 6 for batch reactors. While higher controllability had been achieved, the derived improvements are not necessarily significant enough to warrant the higher complexity. For the sake of completion, this strategy has been tested again for the SOFC-coupled LOHC system.

The low demand set-point (Fig. 7.13, $f_t = 0.3$) can already be fulfilled by the temperature-only control strategy, as such the overall controllability was already granted. On the other hand looking at the pressure and temperature profiles reveals that the final desired temperature is lower than otherwise needed. Interestingly enough, using both control strategies at the same time results in the pressure controller to force the temperature profile to grow faster (compared to the temperature control at fixed pressure) due to the initial pressure increase and the slower regulation. On the other hand, as the controller drives the pressure decrease, the temperature profile sees only a small increase: pressure acts as the main driver of the hydrogen release. As the lower bound of the pressure control range is reached, temperature has to grow at a faster rate. The end value is however close to the single variable scenario.

Similarly, Fig. 7.14 feature some controllability improvement, however this is only marginal as the defined pressure range is too modest to comply to the high demand value.

FIGURE 7.9: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variable (p) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.3$.

FIGURE 7.10: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variable (p) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.7$.

FIGURE 7.11: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variable (T) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.3$.

FIGURE 7.12: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variable (T) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.7$.

FIGURE 7.13: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variables (p , T) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.3$.

FIGURE 7.14: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variables (p , T) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.7$.

FIGURE 7.15: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variables (p , T) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.7$ during sizing mode but with an actual demand of $f_t = 0.5$.

FIGURE 7.16: SOFC performances indicators, total DoH, and control variables (p , T) trends over time. Power demand factor set to $f_t = 0.7$ during sizing mode but with an actual demand of $f_t = 0.9$.

Lastly, Fig. 7.15 and Fig. 7.16 provide an overview of the system behaviour when coupled with a different demand than the one used to size the SOFC model. Both have been sized for a power demand factor of 0.7, and they are coupled with a constant demand of 0.5 and 0.9 respectively. This change with respect to the pre-design stage only affects the SOFC performances.

In the low demand scenario the efficiency is always above the sizing value; the LOHC controllability of the multi-variable PI controller is enough to provide complete dehydrogenation⁶.

On the other hand, in the high demand scenario controllability is reduced, with the pressure controller reaching saturation at about 150 min. SOFC performances are marked by the initial lower efficiency and higher power output. This time to satisfy the demand, the temperature profile has to undergo deeper oscillations⁷ and in the early stages the coupling of the two control strategies results in some spikes in the SOFC indicators profiles, which are more prominent in the power output trend.

7.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, the coupling of a SOFC system with a LOHC feed removes the need for an external and costly heat source to drive the dehydrogenation reaction. Under this configuration it is possible to keep the reactor under constant temperature, however the hydrogen release would vary over time. As the reaction proceeds, the power output would be lower but the SOFC conversion would be more efficient. A generic SOFC module is modelled and characterized by focusing on the electrical power output and on the waste heat. More accurate stack modelling would require further characterization, however the proposed system can effectively be used for preliminary studies. Validation with literature references has shown a remarkable agreement between the simulated and the published data.

If a control strategy is introduced, consistent performances can be granted over time as long as controllability is granted. Using a PI controller it is possible to meet the user power demand by changing the reactor's pressure, its temperature, or the inlet mass flow rate. The latter option is presented in Chapter 8 and contextualized in a maritime sector application. The first control strategy, pressure control, is run by assuming the SOFC pressure to be uncoupled from the reactor's pressure. This would be possible through the physical separation of the two environments. Similarly, temperature control is expected to take place through mass flow rate control applied over a constant temperature heat source. The reaction temperature of the SOFC stack is thus assumed constant regardless of the set-point, which only affects the reactor.

For a preliminary study, the controllability results of the LOHC-SOFC coupling are evaluated with respect to a constant power demand. There is no significant difference in performances with respect to the general case study presented in Chapter 6, as SOFCs check the main LOHC requirements. Note that as the controlled variable reaches its control range bound, the SOFC power output decreases but the conversion is more efficient.

Temperature-control is still by far the better option for enhanced controllability, with the pressure control option being drastically lower at high target power factors. If the targetted demand is moderately low, both control strategies are theoretically viable, and requires less extreme thermodynamic conditions. This means that the LOHC systems should be operated at low f_t values: the cycle stability would increase (limiting LOHC degradation), and a high hydrogen content usage would be achieved. End user applications should thus be characterized by high E/P ratios, thus pushing the carrier to operate far from the uncontrolled release scenario, which is marked by highly variable and relatively fast release.

When coupling the pressure and temperature controller additional controllability margins are unlocked, however those are mostly marginal. Further analysis focusing on more complex controllers or finer parameter tunings could lead to some further improvements, however those are expected to be quite low. Indeed, the variability range of both variables

⁶Remember: LOHC systems are mostly designed to work for DoH values ranging between 0.2-0.95.

⁷These are still due to the layout of the LOHC plant, and more specifically to the alternating flow in the reactor as the vessels are kept at constant temperature (473.15 K).

are moderate at best. Additionally, high pressure reaction rates are insufficiently characterized in the literature.

Chapter 8

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: Maritime applications

8.1 System Sizing

8.1.1 Preliminary Design

This section provides an insight into the possible application of liquid organic carriers in the maritime sector. More specifically, a LOHC-SOFC system is preliminarily sized using a realistic load scenario taken from Di Micco et al. (Di Micco et al., 2024). The results of the sizing process are reported for different carriers, namely: dibenzyl toluene (H0-DBT) - perhydrodibenzyl toluene (H18-DBT), N-ethylcarbazole (H0-NEC) - perhydro-N-ethylcarbazole (H12-NEC), Naphthalene (H0-NAP) - Decalin (H10-DEC), and toluene (H0-TOL) - methylcyclohexane (H6-MCH). Feasibility is evaluated in terms of the dynamic behaviour of the system, which is evaluated through a *Matlab-Simulink* model, making use of a multi-parameter control strategy to meet the hydrogen demand. Simulation results are reported for NEC systems, however the proposed method could be used to simulate any other carrier by changing the specific kinetic law. Sizing results are then compared to ammonia's to evaluate the potential of LOHCs storage for alternative green solutions for the maritime sector. Comparison is made with respect to volume, mass and heat management constraints.

For the proposed system layout, preliminary sizing comprises two consecutive steps: SOFC sizing, and LOHC sizing. While the former relies on only the load profile, the latter depends on the conversion efficiency as well. The dynamic behaviour of the system is then simulated to evaluate whether the power demand can actually be met. To meet the power demand, three control strategies are implemented: mass flow rate, temperature, and pressure control. SOFC waste heat is used to cover the heat demand of the LOHC subsystem.

The power demand analysed is taken from Di Micco et al., which presents the design, modeling, and feasibility assessment of two NH₃-based fuel cell powertrains (a PEMFC, and a SOFC system) to power a container ship (Di Micco et al., 2024). The authors provide a comparison with respect to a conventional diesel layout with emphasis on the cargo reduction due to the additional weight (and volume) introduced by the ammonia system, as well as on the need to valorizing the avoided CO₂. Mass and volume of the fuel storage are taken as reference for the LOHC systems, while the economical aspects of the analysis are beyond the scope of this article.

Di Micco et al. provides the loading factor over time of the main and auxiliary engines of a container ship with 11 271 ton of dead weight tonnage and cruise duration of 172 h at average speed of 18.5 knots; the rating power for the engines is 8.4 and 3.5 MW respectively. The two demands can be combined, and since the overall power demand is below the power rating of the main engine, they can both be satisfied by a singular fuel cells stack.

The load profiles assumed for the purpose of this analysis have been smoothed to filter out low scale fluctuations, and are presented in Fig. 8.1.

Additionally, Fig. 8.1 expresses the effective load profile in terms loading factor. The auxiliary and main engine load profile peaks are shifted, and their relative magnitude lead to a final demand that is, most of the time, below the reference threshold of 65 % (Di Micco et al., 2024; Aijjou, Raihani, and Bahatti, 2019). This value is associated with the oversizing

FIGURE 8.1: Simplified main and auxiliary engines power demand, and corresponding overall loading factor for a unified conversion system with a rated power of 8.4MW. The main engine and the total load have the same power rating, while the auxiliary engine has a rated power of 3.5 MW.

TABLE 8.1: SOFC modeling parameters. C., A. and E. abbreviations stand for cathode, anode and electrolyte.

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
Effective diffusivity (C.)	$5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	Effective diffusivity (A.)	$2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$
Exponential factor (C.)	$2.35 \times 10^{11} \text{ A}/\text{m}^2$	Exponential factor (A.)	$6.54 \times 10^{11} \text{ A}/\text{m}^2$
Activation energy (C.)	137 103 J/mol	Activation energy (A.)	140 103 J/mol
Thickness (C.)	50 μm	Thickness (A.)	500 μm
Thickness (E.)	10 μm	H ₂ HHV	141.8 MJ/kg

required to face adverse weather conditions which would increase the load factor associated with navigation.

Given the power demand to feed to the SOFC stack, its polarization curve returns the associated efficiency for a given load factor. More specifically, the SOFC efficiency is evaluated as in Sec. 7. The SOFC surface is evaluated by assuming the maximum power density working conditions to take place for the power rated. Due to the polarization curve shape, by working at partial load, the resulting efficiency is always greater than at the just defined design point. Parameters used for the SOFC sizing are summed up in Tab. 8.1.

8.1.2 LOHC Design

Stack sizing allows to associate the stack efficiency to each load conditions. The effective energy required to satisfy the power demand is defined in Eq. 8.1 as the integral of the power demand divided by the SOFC efficiency; the average SOFC efficiency is thus expressed as Eq. 8.2.

FIGURE 8.2: LOHC sub-system layout: a plug flow reactor is coupled with two vessels allowing for multiple reactor passages. Three possible control strategies are viable: pressure, temperature, and mass flow rate control.

$$\epsilon = \int_0^T \frac{P(t)}{\eta(t)} dt \quad (8.1)$$

$$\bar{\eta} = \frac{\int_0^T P(t) dt}{\epsilon} \quad (8.2)$$

The hydrogen mass (m_{H_2}) needed is easily derived from the energy sizing (Eq.8.3). The amount of LOHC to supply m_{H_2} depends on the LOHC maximum gravimetric energy density ($w_{\%}$) and the expected degree of hydrogenation lower and upper bound, Eq.8.4.

$$m_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{\epsilon}{\text{HHV}} \quad (8.3)$$

$$m_{\text{LOHC}} = \frac{m_{\text{H}_2}}{w_{\%} (\text{DoH}_{\text{max}} - \text{DoH}_{\text{min}})} \quad (8.4)$$

The corresponding volume can then be evaluated and used to initialize the reactor design. Fig. 8.2 provides a brief description of the reactor - vessels layout; a detailed sizing overview is given in (Gambini et al., 2024); a detailed description is provided in Chapter 5.

As complete discharge can last up to just a few hours depending on the thermodynamic conditions (Gambini et al., 2022), the much longer operation time of the maritime application imply that the release rate has to be hindered. By changing the volume distribution between the reactor and the vessels (f_r , Eq. 8.5) the system E/P ratio can be shifted to better match the system requirements. Control strategies are further described in Sect. 8.2.

$$f_r = \frac{V_{\text{reactor}}}{V_{\text{tot}}} \quad (8.5)$$

Thermal management of the LOHC system is evaluated accounting for the dehydrogenation heat requirement, which is mostly due to the reaction enthalpy, and comparing it to the SOFC waste heat. NEC thermo-chemical properties have been evaluated using a group contribution approach validated, whenever available, with the available data (mainly at room

TABLE 8.2: Controlled variables upper and lower bounds, and PI controllers proportional and integral gains. Controllers operate in parallel over the hydrogen release error. Mass flow rate control bounds are set with respect to the nominal inlet LOHC mass flow rate.

Variable	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Proportional Gain	Integral Gain
Temperature	433.15 K	500.15 K	20.00	2.00
Pressure	1.1 bar	5 bar	2.00	0.20
Mass Flow Rate	0 %	200 %	10.0	0.01

temperature (Brigljevic, Byun, and Lim, 2020)) while kinetic parameters were defined using experimental data (Kiermaier et al., 2021; Wan et al., 2012) as described in chapter 3. DEC, and MCH properties are taken from the PubChem database while DBT data are extracted the cited HySTOC report (SUPPLY and (HYSTOC), 2018). Dehydrogenation enthalpy is taken from the literature (Rao and Yoon, 2020).

To meet the user demand multiple control strategies are put in place. Both temperature and pressure control have already been proposed in a previous chapter (Sec. 7). As hydrogen release is ruled by kinetic rates, either variable can be changed to either fasten or slow down hydrogen release. For a given catalyst (k_0), a higher pressure level results in lower hydrogen release while a temperature increase leads to faster kinetics.

As the ship operation time is significantly longer than the reaction time of LOHCs, the double vessel layout can be equipped through the introduction of a valve system to enable mass flow rate control. As the effective hydrogen mass flow rate is evaluated with Eq. 8.6, increasing the inlet LOHC mass flow rate results in higher amount of hydrogen releasable. This control strategy is further favoured by the half empty reactor section.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2} = w_{\%} m_{\text{LOHC}} \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt}(T, p, \text{DoH}) \quad (8.6)$$

All three control strategies are executed through individual PI controllers operating over the evaluated error between the actual hydrogen release and the target release. Additional control goals could shift the layout, and one or more controllers could be set to meet the additional demands. In the proposed layout the primary control parameter is the valve opening, with temperature and pressure acting as secondary and tertiary control parameters. The hierarchical order of action is enforced by inserting time delays over both the temperature (one step) and pressure (two steps) controllers; this is further reinforced by each proportional constant gain value.

Tab. 8.2 sums up the proportional and integral gains and the lower and upper variable bounds for the temperature, pressure and mass flow rate control. Temperature and pressure bounds have been discussed in (Gambini et al., 2024) (see Chapter 6) but the actual controller gains have been changed to allow for stable operation in the new parallel control set-up. As for the mass flow rate control, that takes place over valve opening regulation: throughout the operation it can be changed from zero to double the design value. The valve is further subjected to an additional check to avoid reactor overfilling (i.e. LOHC volume greater than the reactor volume).

In spite of the amount of control strategies deployed, transitories, while short, are still associated with a misalignment between hydrogen release and demand. Introduction of a small vessel to serve as a hydrogen buffer may lead to better transitory management. While the hydrogen buffer component is not modelled in this analysis, the release - target error cumulative integral is evaluated. The vessel level would rise as the instantaneous error is positive, while the vessel empties when the actual release does not meet the demand. If the cumulative integral value is negative, the amount of hydrogen release by the system up until a given time instant is less than the amount needed to meet the demand. Otherwise, if the integral is always positive, the introduction of the hydrogen buffer would enable both higher autonomy and better usage of the energy storage; however, the overall volume and weight of the LOHC subsystem would increase.

TABLE 8.3: SOFC stack sizing and main features. (Di Micco et al., 2024) stack are reported to ease the comparison.

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
Surface	232.43 m ²	Volume	831.68 m ³
Mass	456.52 ton	Current density range	0.27-3.7 A/cm ²
Average efficiency	41.28 % (HHV)	Average efficiency	48.38 % (LHV)
Efficiency range	35.99-57.17 % (HHV)	Average loading factor	0.37
Reported average efficiency	47 % (LHV)	Reported mass	451.1 ton
Reported volume	821.8 m ³	-	-

FIGURE 8.3: SOFC derived power density (left y-axis), and corresponding stack efficiency over the HHV (right y-axis).

8.2 Results

Results are presented below following the same layout as proposed at the beginning of this chapter, distinguishing between the sizing sections (SOFC and LOHC), and the dynamic evaluation of the system. Each step is described in details: while the first section is uninfluenced by the carrier choice, the second section makes use of NEC, DBT, DEC, and MCH properties and compares the results with ammonia storage (Di Micco et al., 2024). The NEC system is analyzed in terms of its dynamic behaviour as well to test the technical feasibility of LOHC systems to follow a dynamic load.

While sizing of the LOHC system is required to proceed with the dynamic simulation, the latter returns key information about system feasibility. As such, the load response subsection is presented just after the SOFC design. LOHC design and comparison with ammonia-based systems is evaluated by the end of the section.

8.2.1 SOFC Design

Tab. 8.3 sums up the main characteristics of the SOFC stack sizing.

Stack surface has been retrieved by setting the maximum power density point in Fig. 8.3 so that it takes place for unitary load factor.

FIGURE 8.4: SOFC loading curve for $T = 750^\circ\text{C}$ and $p = 1.1\text{ bar}$, as in (Di Micco et al., 2024). Red dots are associated with the load scenarios of Fig. 8.1.

The efficiency profile for the sized stack with respect to the power factor are plotted as in the reference paper, Fig. 8.4. For reference, the load scenarios identified by Fig. 8.1 have been highlighted.

The model returns similar efficiency values when compared to Di Micco et al.¹. Given the gravimetric and volumetric power density, provided in the reference paper, set to 18.4 kW/ton and 10.1 kW/m^2 respectively, the resulting SOFC mass and volume are as featured in Tab. 8.3. Values reported by (Di Micco et al., 2024) are associated with a peak power of 8.3 MW instead of the nominal 8.4 MW , but otherwise align perfectly.

Tab. 8.3 provides the efficiency range associated with the lowest (high efficiency) and highest (low efficiency) demand for the given stack, which indeed are respectively lower and higher than the average value. The latter would be associated with a an average power factor of 0.37 , which is confirmed by the total input energy required. Dividing the energy requirement by hydrogen's heating value returns the minimum hydrogen mass required onboard. The current density range is reported as well, and is associated with an overall stack voltage of 480 V as proposed by Di Micco et al.

Overall, the ammonia and LOHCs power train systems do not feature significant differences. It must be noted, however, that in the future ammonia-powered ships could possibly rely on alternative more compact solutions such as engines and direct ammonia fuel cells (Brinks, 2021; Dincer and Zamfirescu, 2014).

8.2.2 Dynamic Load

The carrier chosen for this analysis is N-ethylcarbazole (NEC), its kinetic and thermophysical properties have been taken from previous chapters and have been summed up in Tab. 8.4 along with the the initial conditions of the proposed simulation.

Fig. 8.5 portrays the effective hydrogen release over time, compared to the hydrogen mass flow rate demand evaluated coupling data from Fig. 8.1 and Fig. 8.4. The LOHC system is flexible enough to cover the demand throughout the whole operating time. In spite

¹The actual reported value is 57% (LHV). However using the provided data to evaluate the average loading factor reveals that the actual efficiency is 10 percentage points below.

TABLE 8.4: NEC main properties: kinetic parameters are discussed at length in (Gambini et al., 2022), while the reaction enthalpy value is taken from (Bourane et al., 2016). Simulink simulation initial conditions are presented below.

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
Activation energy	121×10^3 kJ/mol	Reaction enthalpy	50.6 kJ/mol _{H₂}
Pressure coefficient	1.397/bar	Frequency factor	2.609×10^{12} min/DoH
Temperature	473.15 K	Pressure	1.1 bar
Inlet mass flow rate (LOHC)	1.99 ton/s	DoH	0.95

of the high load variability, delay time and overshooting are limited in duration and intensity. Switching to more realistic ramp-like load modulation would reduce the associated misalignment, as highlighted by the ramp transition zoom panel.

Fig. 8.6 provides the trend for each control parameters which led to the presented release profile.

Analysis of the profiles reveals that the inlet mass flow rate is mostly about the design value (100 % in the top panel), with fast increases or decreases corresponding to the step transitioning in Fig. 8.1. Similarly, after the initial temperature drop and pressure increase both profiles follow more variable trends. As a hierarchical action order has been introduced through time delays, it appears that fast variation associated with load step changes are mostly regulated by mass flow rate variability, with temperature and pressure control modulating the discharger to compensate for the decreasing DoH value over time. The two profiles are quite similar due to both being associated to the hydrogen discharge through an exponential factor (Gambini et al., 2022), although pressure has to increase to hinder the reaction, while the opposite is true for temperature. Additionally, temperature variability is higher when compared to pressure's.

It must be highlighted that while, due to a lack of high pressure experimental data, the kinetic model is likely to return less accurate results as the pressure increases, high pressure values hinder the reaction. Since those value are needed to slow down the release if the effective kinetic is slower than modelled, the actual commanded pressure value would just be lower. This means that while more complete experimental campaigns are required, the trend here provided would still be valid but would need to be scaled down. Overall, lower pressure set-points would actually favor the components design.

The overall degree of hydrogenation is plotted in Fig. 8.7. As expected, the final DoH is approximately 0.20, aligning with the design choice and highlighting the negligible quantitative aspect of the error, as could have been deduced from Fig. 8.5. Steeper slopes are associated with higher load factors; the final DoH value is actually about 0.1998 due to the effect of transitories.

As a matter of fact, plotting the cumulative error over time returns a final positive value, Fig. 8.8, associated with a hydrogen release slightly higher than designed.

Horizontal traits are associated with stationary (load) conditions, where the release error with respect to the demand is null. Increasing traits mean that the release is actually higher than the demand, while decreasing traits mean that the hydrogen released is lower than the target value. While limited, even the ramp-like transition in the bottom panel of Fig. 8.5 is actually associated with an error. More specifically, about 3.0 kg of hydrogen surplus are released additionally to the about 117.6 kg of the hydrogen demand.

As the cumulative error sign is always positive (initial negative value at 0s) it means that the introduction of a hydrogen buffer could complement well the already satisfactory performances of the PI controllers. The cumulative error would thus correspond to the mass content of the vessel (maximum 11.4 kg, 0.0347 % of the minimum hydrogen supply). Decreasing mass traits would be associated with the emptying of the buffer, and the demand would be fully satisfied even during transitories making use of the surplus hydrogen release stages which would otherwise be wasted.

Overall, the dynamic behaviour of the LOHC system seems capable of following the changing load requirements. Different carriers are expected to return similar results in terms

FIGURE 8.5: Hydrogen demand (dashed line) and effective release (solid line) over time. A complete overview is provided (top panel) as well as a zoom view over step (left panel) and ramp (right panel) load transitioning.

FIGURE 8.6: Required controlled parameters trend over time to meet the hydrogen demand of Fig. 8.5. From top to bottom: mass flow rate control, and temperature (left) and pressure (right) secondary control.

FIGURE 8.7: Overall DoH trend over time, evaluated over the whole system (vessels and reactor).

FIGURE 8.8: Cumulative error over time between the hydrogen released and the target.

TABLE 8.5: Hydrogen storage subsystem main characteristics by LOHC candidate. Ammonia sizing results of (Di Micco et al., 2024) are reported in the bottom line.

Variable	Value	Variable	Value
Min. Hydrogen mass	32.87 ton	Effective Hydrogen mass	41.64 ton
Loaded NEC and H ₂ mass	748.28 ton	Volume (NEC and H ₂)	778.80-912.26 m ³
Loaded DBT and H ₂ mass	690.93 ton	Volume (DBT and H ₂)	756.77 m ³
Loaded MCH and H ₂ mass	700.66 ton	Volume (MCH and H ₂)	909.95 m ³
Loaded DEC and H ₂ mass	594.83 ton	Volume (DEC and H ₂)	663.88 m ³
Ammonia mass	355.40 ton	Ammonia volume	402.20 m ³

of target matching, with control variables following different trends.

8.2.3 LOHC Comparative Design

Tab. 8.5 sums up the results of the LOHC sizing, first introducing the associated hydrogen mass requirement, and then providing the different LOHC volume and weight requirements. Ammonia data are presented below. Mass content is evaluated with respect to the molecular weight of each carrier, while volume of the DBT, MCH, and DEC systems are evaluated with the density provided at 293.15 K; this value clearly underestimates the effective volume requirement of the operating system, as can be seen from the NEC density range, with is defined as the density value associated with the 293.15-473.15 K temperature range, as the upper bound is indicative of the typical operating temperature. As such, if the LOHC-containing vessel is pre-heated, effective volume requirements are expected to be much higher for DBT, MCH, and DEC systems.

Coupling of the input power load profile with the sized SOFC stack returns a required chemical energy input of 1295 MW h, corresponding to the minimum hydrogen mass value in the table. This value is much lower than the required ammonia mass and about one order of magnitude, reasonably so due to the respective heating values.

However, the effective supply mass is higher, to account for the carrier mass content. For NEC systems operated within the 0.20-0.95 range, the final supply mass rises up to 748.28 ton so about 1.8 times the loaded mass of ammonia. While this value is associated with an even higher hydrogen surplus of more than 26 % due to the DoH set range, which could be made use of to some extent to provide a safety margin in case of a higher power demand, complete discharge (DoH = 0) is unlikely to be achievable. As such, while the power demand with respect to the energy required is high enough that very low kinetic rates are required to meet the target, the exact lower threshold cannot be arbitrarily defined. If, theoretically, dehydrogenation could take place between DoH levels of 0.0-1.0 the required total mass would drop to 562.77 ton, but still be about 1.4 times its ammonia equivalent. NEC overall mass content is the highest, which is reasonable given that the hetero-atom in the aromatic ring (nitrogen inclusion) leads to lower dehydrogenation temperature and ΔH_r but at the cost of a reduced storage capacity (Le, Tran, and Lee, 2024). The lower value is represented by the decalis system, which still more than 1.6 the amount of ammonia required.

Similarly, the average density value of the NEC compounds in the operating temperature range has been set to about 820.2 kg/m³ resulting in 2.5 times the volume occupied by the ammonia storage. For the other LOHC system only the ambient temperature density values have been evaluated, as such those are compared with respect to the ambient temperature density of NEC. The MCH system is most likely going to be the one with the highest volume due to the low density of the hydrogenated compound. The other two systems actually display a lower volume requirement than the ambient temperature NEC, with again DEC providing the greatest reduction, but still leading to a volume increase of again about 1.6 times the ammonia requirement.

These results are further aggravated when accounting for the different handling of the reaction products. While ammonia produces nitrogen, which can be released in the atmosphere, unloaded LOHCs still need to be stored onboard. Additionally, the effective volume

FIGURE 8.9: SOFC waste heat, NEC reaction enthalpy with respect to current density, and maximum possible heat demand. SOFC overpotential terms have been validated with (Ranjbar et al., 2014).

requirements should account for the reactor volume as well. Di Micco et al. provide a rough estimate of about 27.1 m³ and 19.2 ton for the heat exchanger, which should be compared to about at least a 10 % volume increase over the proposed volume data associated with reactor volume fraction $f_r = 0.1$ as chosen for this analysis.

Fig. 8.9 provides a last remark about SOFC-LOHC integration. LOHC dehydrogenation requires a heat supply to drive the endothermic reaction which provides the main heat sink source. Regardless, the sensible heat associated to control the LOHC temperature can be evaluated; assuming an average specific heat capacity of 2.3 kJ/(kg K) for the NEC compounds, and let the gravimetric storage capacity $w_{\%}$ be defined with respect to the unloaded molecule (Eq. 8.7), the equivalent heat capacity with respect to hydrogen mass rises to approximately 39.6 kJ/(kg K) (Eq. 8.8).

$$w_{\%} = \frac{m_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}}}{m_{\text{LOHC, unloaded}}} = \frac{n_{\text{H}_2} MW_{\text{H}_2}}{MW_{\text{LOHC, unloaded}}} \quad (8.7)$$

$$c_{\text{coverH}_2} = c \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{w_{\%}} \right) \quad (8.8)$$

SOFC waste heat is plotted to account for either every heat source, or just the reaction enthalpy; similarly, LOHC (NEC) heat sinks are plotted to account for either the reaction enthalpy, or the reaction enthalpy as well as the temperature control increase. Even assuming the maximum additional heat required for temperature control ($\Delta T_{\text{max}} = T_{\text{max}} - T_{\text{min}}$) which is definitely never required for the given power load (see the temperature panel in Fig. 8.6) and accounting for only the reaction heat of the SOFC, the latter still provides enough heat to fully cover the LOHC requirement.

The SOFC system provides about 502.6 MW h of total waste heat through the course of the operation. Compared to the 229.20 MW h needed to supply NEC reaction heat, about 45.6 % of the heat needs to be directed to the LOHC system, at the expense of other possible cogenerative use. Temperature control of the NEC system presented in Sect. 8.2.2 returns an effective heat demand increase of about 0.3 MW h. The about 0.1 % increase is lower than predicted by Fig. 8.9 as the effective temperature profile required far differs from the pejorative ΔT assumption.

Not accounting for the negligible heat requirement of the temperature control, the heat required to drive the hydrogen release in a DBT, MCH, and DEC system is respectively: 296.24, 309.37, 289.64 MW h. If only the reaction heat of the ammonia system is accounted for, than its heat requirement is just 139.57 MW h (Ristig et al., 2022). While this value should be increased to account for the additional heat requirements, it still is about 40 % lower than NEC associated heat.

Reaction temperature of a NEC system can range from 433.15-500.15 K (Gambini et al., 2024), that is significantly lower than ammonia's operating temperature which is about 663.15-763.15 K (Moszczyńska et al., 2023). In comparison, DBT, MCH, and DEC dehydrogenation takes place in the following temperature ranges: 563.15-623.15 K (Park, Naseem, and Lee, 2021), 453.15-500.15 K (Tsai et al., 2023), and 483.15-563.15 K (Suttisawat et al., 2012) respectively. While LOHC temperature ranges are lower than the operating temperature range of ammonia, even NEC systems, which are associated with the lower temperature range, still require relatively high quality heat. SOFC coupling is most likely to provide the required heat source for every application.

Overall, the NEC carrier features the higher volume and mass constraints than any other evaluated LOHC, but with a much lower heat requirement and with the lowest reaction temperature. Conversely, the decalin system is the second next less heat expensive carrier, and features both the lowest mass and volume constraints and moderate reaction temperature. The MCH system, while featuring a mass content second to only the decalin system, is associated with the highest volume, and reaction heat although the latter is provided at low temperature, just like in the NEC system. DBT provides more intermediate properties both in terms of size and energy requirements, but features by far the highest reaction temperature. Ammonia systems are associated with both lower sizing constraints, and heat requirements, but it has to be supplied at a higher temperature.

8.3 Conclusions

Current barriers to using hydrogen as marine fuel include lack of safety requirements; low maturity of technology; onboard storage space required; and, the high investment cost. Demonstration projects have been initiated for both ICEs and fuel-cell installations. Using compressed or liquefied hydrogen in fuel cells is a realistic option for the short-sea shipping segment in the medium term. While only two hydrogen projects for ships above 5000 DWT were initiated before 2020, six new projects have since begun. For smaller vessels, twelve projects were initiated before 2020, and five since. This demonstrates a shift towards hydrogen projects focusing on larger ships, however ammonia is expected to return the best performances, especially for large scale applications (Hammer et al., 2021).

This study provides both a feasibility study of LOHC storage solutions for cargo ships, and a comparison between ammonia and LOHC based storage. Di Micco et al. (Di Micco et al., 2024) system with a SOFC power train and ammonia storage has been chosen to serve as a reference; feasibility of the system is evaluated in terms of dynamic behaviour with respect to the changing load. Sizing and heat management aspects are presented for four LOHC systems (DBT, MCH, DEC, and NEC), with the latter being used to show dynamic behaviour. Dynamic simulations of the ship load reveals that LOHC systems would likely be capable of meeting the changing target requirements, thanks to primary mass flow rate control and secondary additional temperature and pressure control systems. The inlet mass valve opening goes through an initial fast variation due to the step increase or decrease, while temperature and pressure variations mostly deal with keeping the set-point release over time. Different strategies could be used, including a shifted priority order, depending on the specific requirements of each application scenario. However, the possible variability range of each variable is expected to not be any wider than those presented.

Going from step to ramp load variations further alleviates transitory phases error, which is already limited and only affects a short time fraction. Intermediate hydrogen buffers could potentially remove any error, but at the cost of further volume constraints. As a matter of fact, in spite of the dynamic feasibility of the system, the LOHC volume and mass required to store the needed hydrogen are by far much higher than those of ammonia systems. Decalin features the lowest size, with NEC the highest mass and MCH the highest volume. This

huge gap is actually due to the much lower gravimetric density of LOHCs when compared to ammonia. Literature reviews indicate that the possible variability range of the *wt.%* for LOHC compounds is strictly far below ammonia's. Future developments are unlikely to change this finding.

On the other hand, ammonia systems are also associated with a lower dehydrogenation heat, meaning that SOFC systems operating under co-generation schemes are less impacted by the subsystem coupling. The lowest energy requirement in LOHC systems is associated with NEC, while MCH features the highest. Reaction temperature ranges are lower for LOHC systems than ammonia's, however even those are already relatively high thus high quality heat is needed in both cases. Overall, while capable of meeting the user demand, LOHC systems suffer from low energy densities, both volume and gravimetric-wise, when compared to ammonia systems. Load reduction to accommodate for the additional fuel loading onboard, and the higher heat sink from different co-generation applications make LOHC systems unlikely to find a market share in the maritime sector.

Chapter 9

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: Ragone Diagrams and Maps

9.1 Ragone Diagrams

Hydrogen storage systems are energy storage devices where the chemical energy of hydrogen is stored and delivered to the end user. As such, specific energy and specific power, i.e. the energy and power that can be effectively released per unit mass, are key performance indicators, as for any energy storage device. Specific energy and specific power are represented in so-called Ragone plots, which were introduced by Ragone (1968) to describe how the useful energy delivered by electrochemical storage devices decreases as the power required by the end user increases. Long since extended to thermal storage systems (Yazawa, Shamberger, and Fisher, 2019), material-based hydrogen storage systems are first characterised in terms of Ragone plots by Gambini et al. to describe in a comprehensive and systematic way the inverse relationship between power demand and discharged energy.

The ratio of available hydrogen mass and constant mass flow rate delivered to the end user represents the theoretical discharge duration τ_{max} , i.e. the time that would be required to fully discharge the hydrogen storage system for a given value of discharge flow rate, and is defined as Eq. 9.1. The actual discharge time is less than the maximum value because energy storage systems generally deliver a decreasing proportion of stored energy for increasing values of constant power output. This has been discussed at length in Chapter 6, as a result of the reaction order.

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\text{DoH}_{dis}} \quad (9.1)$$

9.1.1 Metal Hydride and LOHC Comparison

Both LOHCs (Chapter 3) and metal hydrides (Appendix A) feature a concentration dependent factor in their kinetic law, meaning that the actual τ difference with respect to its ideal value is thus a function of the power output: as the demand increases, the control parameters are pushed towards the upper or lower variability thresholds at a faster rate, meaning that the controllability range decreases. To model the systems, three main governing equations are needed in the form of implicit Ordinary Differential Equations 9.2 to 9.4, (Gambini et al., 2023a).

$$\dot{x} = -k_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{R_u T}\right) f(p) x(t)^n \quad (9.2)$$

$$\dot{y}_\rho = -(\dot{x} - \dot{x}_d) \quad (9.3)$$

$$\tau_T = \dot{\theta} = -\theta + \delta(1 - \dot{x}/\dot{x}_d) \quad (9.4)$$

The first equation is the kinetic law, expressed with respect to the x variable which is the hydrogen concentration (DoH) measure in either the MH or LOHC. Eq. 9.3 is the dimensionless mass conservation equation, which y_ρ the dimensionless density $y_\rho = \rho/\rho_{max}$ of the hydrogen in the storage material, which is normalised by $\rho_{max} = V/(w\%m)$ maximum density obtained if the entire amount of hydrogen stored were released and confined in the

volume (V). The normalised density in the buffer volume depends on the difference between the hydrogen entering the buffer (i.e. released) and the hydrogen discharged, which is here assumed as a constant demand.

Lastly, Eq. 9.4 is the dimensionless energy conservation, where the temperature-related variable (θ) is defined as: $\theta = T - (T_f - \delta)$, and δ used to define the steady-state temperature difference $\delta = \dot{Q}_r / (\epsilon \dot{C}_f)$ (see Chapter 4 for a full analysis of the energy conservation equation); lastly, τ_T is the temperature time constant defined as $\tau_T = C / (\epsilon \dot{C}_f)$. Simulations have been executed under the assumption of constant temperature and variable pressure.

The performance indicators used to assess the different systems are:

- Dimensionless power (Π): defined as: $\Pi = \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2,d} / \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2,max} = \dot{x}_d / \dot{x}_{max}$.
- Utilisation factor (dimensionless discharged energy, e): amount of hydrogen released in a constant-flow-rate discharge and defined as $e(\Pi) = E_d / E_{max} = m_{\text{H}_2,d} / (w_{\%} m) = \tau / \tau_{max}$, where the last relation is the result of the discharge process ending when the pressure variability can no longer compensate for the reduced x drive in Eq. 9.2, which happens at $x(\tau) > 0$.
- Specific power (\hat{P}): rate of chemical energy released per unit mass of active substance $\hat{P} = -w Q_{HHV} \dot{x}_d$.
- Specific energy ($\hat{E}(\hat{P})$): $\hat{E}(\hat{P}) = w Q_{HHV} e(\Pi)$, which also means that $\hat{P} = e \hat{E}_{max} / \tau$.

The constant-flow-rate discharge process can be assessed by means of a simplified model, under the assumption of constant temperature and a negligible effect of the capacitance of the hydrogen volume (buffer), so that it is possible to find an analytical solution representing the discharge process. Under these assumptions, there is no accumulation of hydrogen; hence, the rate of hydrogen released by the reactor is instantaneously equal to the discharged flow rate. A more complete analysis of the full model is described by Gambini et al. in Gambini et al. (2023a).

Fig. 9.1 proposes the Ragone plot for a typical metal hydride and a second (NEC) and first (DBT) order LOHC system, to assess how the different technologies pair up with the different loads. In general, LOHCs can achieve higher specific energy values than MHs due to the higher gravimetric density; however, the specific power (related to the mass flow rate discharged per unit mass of active material) has similar ranges for the two storage options, as it is not affected by the gravimetric density but by the kinetic properties of the reaction involved. Obviously, the range of specific flow rates that can be achieved by these storage systems depends on the kinetic properties of the active ingredient and the reactor, which can vary significantly depending on the catalyst used, reactor configuration, etc. However, the order of magnitude is similar and can be reasonably identified from the Ragone plot.

More importantly, the Ragone plot highlights the range of energy to power ratios, represented by the discharge duration, that result in acceptable levels of utilisation factors. In other words, the Ragone plot suggests a threshold energy to power ratio below which it is impossible to effectively use the hydrogen stored in the system, as a significant amount cannot be discharged in a constant-flow discharge process (it could only be delivered by reducing the flow rate to the end user). The figure shows that a hydrogen storage system based on this MH can operate with a utilisation factor above 60% with energy to power ratios as low as 0.25 h; instead, LOHC-based systems appear to be more suitable for longer discharge durations, with 25 h and 2.5 h required to achieve the same 60% utilisation factor for DBT and NEC respectively.

Interestingly, by testing more complex modelling assumptions Gambini et al. (2023a) suggests that most of the LOHC behaviour can indeed be adequately described under simple static modelling assumptions. While Ragone plots can be effectively used to guide LOHC sizing when coupling the hydrogen storage system to a given power demand, the static representation of the LOHC system can be further extended by defining modelling maps.

FIGURE 9.1: Representative Ragone plot of hydrogen storage systems based on LaNi, NEC and DBT. Markers indicate the utilisation factors 20, 40, 60, 80% from left to right.

9.2 Maps

Maps can be a useful tool for modelling complex energy systems. Assuming that the influence of transient phases on the overall system behaviour is negligible, the state of a given LOHC subsystem is uniquely defined by:

- Degree of hydrogenation,
- Temperature,
- Pressure;

these three variables are responsible for the hydrogen release kinetics.

The lack of a significant experimental data pool and the reduced range of variability make pressure unsuitable for controlling the mass flow rate released. The hydrogen that can be released or absorbed by the system is therefore a function of the state of charge (DoH) and the reaction temperature. These three quantities are then uniquely correlated and can be used to generate a map for any given carrier after defining the catalyst (E_a, k_0) and setting the pressure level. The latter can be assumed to be constant throughout the operation¹. Different strategies for map generation can be used to highlight different aspects of the LOHC behaviour, depending on the design requirements.

Dehydrogenation

Modelling of isothermal release for NEC systems showed an optimum reaction temperature of about 200 °C, associated with complete hydrogen discharge² even at higher pressure levels (i.e. above at least 1 bar) and well below the thermal stability of the NEC (about 250 °C). Similar results are obtained for each support, so the typical reaction temperature ranges are quite narrow. Thus the maximum isothermal hydrogen release can be estimated from the kinetic rate, assuming a reference temperature of 200 °C and an initial (maximum) DoH of 0.95. Dividing the instantaneous hydrogen release by this value gives a new parameter as

¹Dehydrogenation simulations over realistic setups yielded pressure loss values less than 0.1% of the nominal pressure level (1.5 bar).

²A final DoH of zero would actually require too much time to reach, as the reaction rate describes a second order reaction. Consequently, and consistently in various publications, the final DoH value is usually set to 0.20.

FIGURE 9.2: Required temperature level for any given DoH with respect to the needed power demand during NEC dehydrogenation.

Eq. 9.5, with the power demand factor f_t in the range 0-1 during isothermal release.

$$f_t = \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} / \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} \Big|_{T=200^\circ\text{C}, \text{DoH}=0.95} \quad (9.5)$$

To meet a constant power demand, temperature control proved to be the most effective choice: having defined a temperature range of 160-230 °C, the reaction can be modulated so that it still proceeds and the system is kept below dangerous levels, and the release can be stabilised and set to a constant value.

Depending on the value of f_t , it may or may not be possible to achieve complete dehydrogenation:

- A high degree of dehydrogenation is associated with a fast reaction, which means that for a low power requirement it is necessary to cool the support.
- As the reaction progresses, even low power demands require a temperature increase. The higher the demand, the greater the need to compensate for the reduced DoH kinetic contribution via the kinetic rate. On the other hand, it is actually possible to achieve low power factors even at DoH less than 0.20 without requiring unsuitable temperature levels.

Similarly, the first modelling procedure is based on the definition of progressively higher power demand factors, in the range 0.1-1.0: temperature and instantaneous energy content are evaluated and tracked over time.

Fig. 9.2 provides a two-dimensional visualisation of this approach: for a given energy content (from 0.95 to 0.10), the reaction temperature required to meet the desired demand f_t is shown by a colour map. A temperature above 500 kelvin would actually be required in the lower right-hand corner, but the colour scale saturates at the maximum allowable temperature. Once this value is reached, further discharge would require too high a temperature level: this value therefore marks the maximum allowable discharge.

Essentially, to provide complete dehydrogenation of the LOHC subsystem, the power requirement must be no greater than 0.20. Note that the complete dehydrogenation of the LOHC implies the capability to meet the demand up until a final DoH of 0.2 or lower. A three-dimensional view of Fig. 9.2 is provided by Fig. 9.3. Using two perspectives to better understand the shape of the surface, the temperature controlled behaviour of the NEC is mapped. The implementation of this approach in a more complex energy system requires

FIGURE 9.3: Visualization of the T - DoH - f_t map; the colormap follows the upper and lower bounds described in Fig. 9.2.

FIGURE 9.4: Dehydrogenation map with dashed isothermal lines from 450-500 K. Fit model performances are visualized through temperature evaluation of the white dot points; input data have been randomly generated.

the definition of a scattered interpolant function: taking as input both the energy content and the power demand, the temperature required to meet the user's needs can be easily evaluated.

Fig. 9.4 shows the map from Fig. 9.3 enriched with isothermal dashed lines and the results of the scattered interpolant function. The data points have been randomly generated to better test the accuracy and reliability of the method.

The method just presented requires the definition of a reference mass flow, which is evaluated assuming a design temperature of 200 °C. However, Figs. 9.2 - 9.4 show that this design value (473.15 K) is only transient for a given constant power demand. Alternatively, another approach would be to focus on the dehydrogenation rate itself. In fact, both the dehydrogenation rate and the power factor are dimensionless: while the former approach immediately gave some information about the stress on the control (i.e. low values are immediately characterised by lower temperature levels), it required the definition of a reference.

By running several isothermal simulations with T ranging from 160-230 °C from an initial DoH of 0.95 to the final 0.10 DoH, the reaction rate can be evaluated and tracked.

FIGURE 9.5: Resulting dehydrogenation rate for any given DoH with respect to the current temperature level.

FIGURE 9.6: Visualization of the T - DoH - $\frac{dDoH}{dt}$ map; the colormap follows the upper and lower bounds described in Fig. 9.5.

The resulting map can be visualised with a two-dimensional map as in Fig. 9.5: the huge impact of the DoH factor on the reaction rate is evident from the huge difference when comparing high and low DoH release rates at a given temperature. The same results are shown in Fig. 9.6 with a three-dimensional map. The different shape of the surface can be explained by the subtle difference between the energy demand factor and the dehydrogenation rate.

The implementation of this second method requires no additional interpolation, since for any given state (DoH, T) the dehydrogenation rate is defined by the kinetic law itself. Thus, for any given power demand, having defined the system size, the temperature setpoint for the controller is returned by Eq. 9.6:

$$T = k_E \cdot \frac{1}{\ln \left(k_p \frac{dDoH}{dt} \right)} \quad (9.6)$$

where the constant value k_p includes both the frequency factor k_0 and the pressure dependence as the inverse of their product, and k_E is the argument of the temperature exponential, but without the 1 by T factor.

This second approach is considered to be more suitable for implementation in real power systems as it does not require the definition of a reference; the hydrogenation step has therefore been modelled without the definition of a reference.

Hydrogenation

The hydrogenation reaction is exothermic, so the higher the temperature, the more the chemical equilibrium is shifted towards the reactants: saturation occurs for decreasing DoH_{sat} values as the temperature increases. In addition, further temperature increases above 453 K do not lead to faster kinetics. As a result, test temperatures in the 393–453.15 K range have been chosen to ensure that saturation occurs for the maximum DoH value (i.e. 1).

As uptake is favoured by high pressure and electrolysers can effectively provide hydrogen to meet the kinetic requirements, three pressure level scenarios are presented below (Fig. 9.7). In each case the hydrogenation reactions are fast and the charging time is in the range of 25 – 70 min. Hydrogen production over a longer period of time therefore requires a setup with several LOHC batches for successive charging.

Fig. 9.7 shows hydrogenation reactions illustrated by colour maps. It should be noted that although the maps agree with the laboratory test results, the performance at several temperature levels has only been shown for systems operating at 60 bar. As heat is released by the reaction, it is reasonable to assume that the reaction would take place at a constant temperature and be used as a recovery heat source. Thus the two dimensional maps of Fig. 9.7 show the energy content of a LOHC system at given pressure and temperature set points and after a given operating time. An initial starting point of DoH equal to 0.15 has been chosen.

These results are shown in a three dimensional visualisation in Fig. 9.8. As the input experimental data is more robust at 60 bar, this value has been chosen as the default pressure level. The resulting trend is largely regular, despite a changing slope highlighted by the view below for high DoH values.

To compare the loading and unloading phases, the same coordinates have been chosen for the dehydrogenation map, Fig. 9.9. Due to the already lower kinetic constant (k), the relatively high pressure and the higher reaction order, the latter reaction requires a much longer residence time in the reactor. This phenomenon is definitely more significant at lower temperature values, as can be seen from Fig. 9.10. In addition, as the hydrogen release follows a second order reaction, the shape of the three-dimensional surface is different and the rate variability is increased as the latter stages of the reaction are much more hindered.

While the time aspect was not present in Fig. 9.2, Fig. 9.10 clearly highlights the key role of temperature (i.e. thermal management) over the discharging process. With a run time of 10 h, the 0.15 DoH mark is reached for temperature values greater or equal to 470 K; by raising the final DoH value to 0.20, the temperature threshold is still above 460 K. Interestingly enough, the 470 K system reaches a DoH value of 0.15 after almost 10 h, and the 0.20 mark after (only) about 350 min, meaning that 250 min are required to release the remaining 0.05 ΔDoH .

As a result, a comparison between the two phases is necessary to define the starting conditions for either phase. Thermal management is key to defining the maximum discharge capability.

9.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, the integration of static modeling approaches for LOHC (Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier) systems highlights the potential of bypassing transient and dynamic behaviors to focus on steady-state conditions. By assuming that the influence of transitory phases on the overall system behavior is negligible, one can define the state of a given LOHC subsystem using three key parameters: degree of hydrogenation (DoH), temperature, and pressure.

This approach allows for the creation of detailed maps that link these variables to hydrogen release kinetics. For instance, the dehydrogenation process can be effectively modeled

FIGURE 9.7: Hydrogenation at a given temperature and time for 50, 60, 70 bar. The dashed black line marks the final DoH value.

FIGURE 9.8: Hydrogenation map evaluated at 60 bar: temperature - time - DoH trends of NEC with $DoH_0 = 0.15$. Hydrogenation rate is shown as a colorbar.

FIGURE 9.9: Dehydrogenation map evaluated at 1.5 bar: temperature - time - DoH trends of NEC with $DoH_0 = 0.95$. Dehydrogenation rate is shown as a colorbar.

FIGURE 9.10: Dehydrogenation at a given temperature and time for 1.5 bar. The dashed lines mark the DoH value of either 0.15 (black) or 0.20 (red.); at low temperature values the lower or both targets are not met by the end of the simulation.

under isothermal conditions, revealing critical insights into the optimal operating temperatures (around 200 °C for NEC systems) and the influence of varying degrees of hydrogenation on the release rates. Similarly, by controlling the temperature within a defined range (160-230 °C), one can stabilize the hydrogen release to meet different power demands.

The static maps derived from these models provide a powerful tool for predicting system behavior without delving into the complexities of transient dynamics. This is particularly useful in practical applications where maintaining a constant power output and ensuring efficient thermal management are crucial. The ability to predict the required temperature for specific DoH values under varying power demands simplifies the control strategies needed for both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation phases.

Moreover, the comparative analysis of the charging (hydrogenation) and discharging (dehydrogenation) phases underscores the importance of thermal management. The time-dependent maps presented illustrate that achieving the desired hydrogen release levels depends heavily on maintaining appropriate temperature conditions, especially as the reaction progresses.

Thus, a static approach that bypasses the need for detailed dynamic simulations can effectively evaluate the potential of LOHC systems. It allows for the design of efficient and reliable energy systems by focusing on the critical parameters that govern hydrogen release and uptake, streamlining the assessment of LOHC performance and guiding the development of control strategies for real-world applications.

Chapter 10

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers: DBT and NEC modelling comparison

By modelling the multistep reaction pathway as an equivalent reaction among the fully hydrogenated and dehydrogenated carrier, LOHC modelling complexity is significantly reduced. Not only is the kinetic rate law reduced to just one equation, but the system is uniquely defined by its degree of hydrogenation. A detailed kinetic equation would, however, be necessary if more accurate depictions are needed. Heat management, volume constraints, LOHC's vapor removal from the H₂ outsource, and reaction optimization are all affected by the exact LOHC mixture. The latter may be particularly interesting in the presence of one limiting step; single pass plug flow reactors can be optimized by allocating different catalysts over each reactor cross section.

In this section the multi-step modelling of the NEC and DBT systems is evaluated and compared to its equivalent counterpart under the assumption of simplified reaction. Due to lack of data for the DBT dehydrogenation process, multi-step modelling is only applied over the hydrogenation phase.

10.1 DBT modelling

Hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of didenzytoluene/perhydro-dibenzyl-toluene follow a multi-step reaction pathway. Fig. 10.1 highlights the consecutive steps characterizing the progressive saturation of the DBT molecule C=C bonds. The multiple steps are commonly simplified and aggregated into an equivalent reaction between the fully saturated and fully un-saturated carrier (Peters et al., 2019). LOHCs charging and discharging is indeed mostly characterized in terms of their degree of hydrogenation (DoH).

FIGURE 10.1: Hydrogenation steps from 0H-DBT to 18H-DBT, (Li et al., 2024).

From its general definition (Eq. 10.1), Eqs. 10.2 - 10.3 are used to describe the multi-step and simplified approach respectively¹.

¹In both Eq. 10.2 and Eq. 10.3 the denominator term assumes every molecule has been saturated into 18H-DBT.

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{n_{\text{H}_2}}{n_{\text{H}_2, \text{max}}} \quad (10.1)$$

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{9 \cdot n_{18\text{H-DBT}} + 6 \cdot n_{12\text{H-DBT}} + 3 \cdot n_{6\text{H-DBT}}}{9 \cdot n_{\text{tot}}} \quad (10.2)$$

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{n_{18\text{H-DBT}}}{n_{\text{tot}}} \quad (10.3)$$

A simplified approach has been tested for both reactions using experimental data (hydrogenation: (Li et al., 2024), dehydrogenation: (Peters et al., 2019)², (Bulgarin et al., 2020)³). Modelling of the hydrogenation step has actually proven to be more complex, requiring to evaluate the full multi-step reaction pathway; on the other hand, dehydrogenation at relatively high pressure (i.e. not below ambient pressure) needs to account for the chemical equilibrium (Dürr et al., 2021).

Data provided by Li et al. for the hydrogenation step are modelled by the authors as a three-steps process through the consecutive hydrogenation of H0-HBT, H6-DBT, and H12-DBT. They are all modelled as roughly first order reactions (1.06, 0.976, 1.36 respectively), and a pressure dependence of about first order (0.79, 0.74, 0.745 *b* coefficients, respectively). The activation energies of each step are 59.254, 56.061, 64.641 kJ/mol highlighting how the last reaction is the rate-determining step. As the reaction order is higher, it also features slow saturation. Reactions at different temperature levels are not homogenized into a common model, as such there is no temperature dependence in the fitting model and different coefficients are returned.

10.1.1 Single-step

Having provided equivalent DoH profiles, an approach similar to the one proposed for dehydrogenation has been tested, and its results are proposed in Fig. 10.2. The best fit is returned by a 0.5 order reaction, with activation energy of about 50.07 kJ/mol and a $k_{0,p} = 97.6/\text{s}$. Those values differ from the proposed coefficients of the different reaction steps, and the different reaction order does not allow for direct comparison between them.

While experimental data in the early stages of the hydrogenation process are close to a line (zero-order reaction), that changes as the DoH increases. This is explained by the different *n* proposed by the authors. The final fitting can only provide a rough estimate of the DoH levels, with significant differences observed at low DoH for low temperature profiles, and at high DoH for high temperature profiles. This issue is exacerbated by the necessity to model DoH equilibrium conditions. There is no other experimental data to fit a temperature-based profile in the effective operating range. Equilibrium concentrations are thus chosen to be reflective of the proposed dataset, but those are badly conditioned, so that no reliable function can be fitted.

As such, a multi-step approach has been tested.

10.1.2 Multi-step

Li et al. highlight how the final hydrogenation step starts as soon as the first two steps lead to no residual concentration of either H0-DBT and H6-DBT. The fitting procedure proposed in the reference paper thus follows the schematization presented in Fig. 10.3. The intermediate products H6 and H12 are featured into two reactions: the first one generates them (increasing concentration) while the latter is responsible for their decreasing concentration.

Due to the proposed claim, Li et al. model each reaction step independently, by fitting the two different sides of each peak as individual datasets. With respect to Fig. 10.3, 0H-DBT to H12-DBT hydrogenation is modelled using data from the yellow box, while the orange box data are used for the last step. A similar approach has been chosen for every step.

To fit the experimental results with a more rigorous approach, every reaction has been modelled at the same time, by searching for the optimal coefficients that return the lowest

²Temperature dependence.

³Pressure dependence.

FIGURE 10.2: Hydrogenation modelling as an equivalent reaction.

FIGURE 10.3: Hydrogenation reactions at 40 bar and 160 °C. Concentration levels of 0.1 mol/L correspond to total saturation of a LOHC compound.

TABLE 10.1: Coefficients found for the optimal fit at 40 bar.

parameter	0H-6H	6H-12H	12H-18H
$k_{0,p}$ 1/s	-1174.8	-572.2	-3511.3
E_a kJ/mol	56.97	54.18	66.07
n	0.75	0.50	1.50

TABLE 10.2: Coefficients found for the optimal fit for 20-60 bar and 160-210 °C.

parameter	0H-6H	6H-12H	12H-18H
k_0 1/s	-32.8	-14.1	-1544.4
E_a kJ/mol	56.97	54.18	66.07
b	0.969	1.004	0.223
n	0.75	0.50	1.50

error when fitting the system proposed below:

$$r_0 = k_{0,p} \cdot \chi_{0H-DBT}^{n_0} \exp - \frac{E_{a,0}}{R_u T} \quad (10.4)$$

$$r_1 = k_{1,p} \cdot \chi_{6H-DBT}^{n_1} \exp - \frac{E_{a,1}}{R_u T} \quad (10.5)$$

$$r_2 = k_{2,p} \cdot \chi_{12H-DBT}^{n_2} \exp - \frac{E_{a,2}}{R_u T} \quad (10.6)$$

$$\frac{dC_{0H-DBT}}{dt} = r_0 \quad (10.7)$$

$$\frac{dC_{6H-DBT}}{dt} = r_1 - r_0 \quad (10.8)$$

$$\frac{dC_{12H-DBT}}{dt} = r_2 - r_1 \quad (10.9)$$

$$\frac{dC_{18H-DBT}}{dt} = -r_2 \quad (10.10)$$

The coefficients used to produce Fig. 10.4 are summed up in Tab. 10.1. Reaction orders are different but still close to those found by the original authors but for the intermediate step. This is due to the different approach chosen, which also returns more smooth trends and shifts and lowers the concentration peaks of the intermediates. On the other hand, the activation energy values found are in good agreement with the proposed values, although those are not effectively used in their r definition.

Unfortunately data collected at different pressure are not sampled uniformly across different steps, and to make use of the same approach data would have to be interpolated. Using raw data provided in the form presented in Fig. 10.5, pressure dependency of the different steps are evaluated and used to find the k_0 coefficients by taking the $k_{0,p}$ values proposed in the table and assuming the same pressure dependency just found. The results are summed up in Fig. 10.6.

The final coefficients proposed are summed up in Tab. 10.2, highlighting a much milder pressure-dependence of the last step when compared to the first two steps.

Overall the resulting performances of the hydrogenation multi-step fitting are much better than those obtained by the single step reaction, although the concentration peak of the intermediates are underestimated. The multi-step approach does not require modelling of the equilibrium concentrations, thus enhancing the reliability of the model. As a matter of fact, by comparing the two models in terms of DoH agreement with the data (Fig. 10.7), the saturation effect arises more organically as a result of the full reaction path. Two sets of n values have been tested for the first reaction step, including the one already discussed. Indeed, comparison between the different models highlights a smoother and more reliable depiction of the more complex modelling, especially at high temperature values.

FIGURE 10.4: Hydrogenation reactions at 40 bar in terms of concentration over time and equivalent DoH.

FIGURE 10.5: Experimental data at 200°C collected during the first reaction step.

FIGURE 10.6: Pressure dependency modelling for each reaction step. Note that values 0, 1, 2 refer to the first, second, and last reaction step (H_0 -DBT to H_6 -DBT, H_6 -DBT to 12 H-DBT, and 12 H-DBT to 18 H-DBT) respectively.

FIGURE 10.7: Final comparison between the experimental DoH data and the two modelling hypothesis. Thin lines ("all" caption) refer to the equivalent model; bracketed numbers indicate alternative values of the first step reaction order.

FIGURE 10.8: Experimental and modelling results for DBT dehydrogenation according to Eq. 10.11 (Peters et al., 2019). The y-axis represents the concentration of H18-DBT normalized by the initial concentration (1), and is thus equivalent to the DoH.

10.1.3 Dehydrogenation

Preuster et al. provide equivalent DoH(t) profiles (Eq. 10.3) taken at ambient pressure for temperature levels set at 260, 280, 290, 300, 310 °C. The reaction has been modelled by the authors as in Eq. 10.11, with r being the reaction rate of the 18H-DBT dehydrogenation.

$$r = 125.241/\text{s} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{119.8 \text{ kJ/mol}}{R_u T}\right) \cdot c_{18H-DBT}^{1.98} \quad (10.11)$$

The results are reported in Fig. 10.8: it can be seen that at higher temperature levels there is mostly good agreement with the experimental data, however the initial dehydrogenation at 310 °C is over-estimated by the model; similarly, lower temperature profiles seem to reach saturation for low DoH values, however the model does not account for such effect and over-estimates the release.

In contrast, Fig. 10.9 represents the results of the newly proposed kinetic model. The proposed model accounts for both pressure dependency and for the equilibrium term, which changes Eq. 10.11 to Eq. 10.12.

$$r = k_0 p^b \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) (C_{18H-DBT} - C_{18H-DBT,eq})^n \quad (10.12)$$

The optimal parameters are found with the SciPy optimization curvefit tool as the lack of experimental data available prevents the analytical approach presented in Chapter 3. These parameters return better agreement with the experimental data, but for the initial dehydrogenation of the 200 °C profile. The effective reaction order is actually 1.5 and the activation energy is about 423.4 kJ/mol, much higher than predicted by Preuster et al. On the other hand, constant term $k_0 \cdot p^b$ is just 1.68/s, which is much lower than predicted. Direct comparison is, however, hindered by the different reaction order. Additionally, by accounting for the equilibrium concentration of H18-DBT, the late dehydrogenation rate is reduced.

The equilibrium DoH is directly associated with the concentration of H18 (single step approximation), and has been modelled as a spline map using experimental data collected in the 1-9.9 bar range by Preuster et al. (Dürr et al., 2021). This representation is graphically modelled as in Fig. 10.10, and at ambient pressure and for the proposed temperature range

FIGURE 10.9: Proposed DBT dehydrogenation.

(260–310 °C) returns equilibrium values of 0.53, 0.31, 0.20, 0.10, 0.03 with the final equilibrium concentration lowering as the temperature increases.

To account for the pressure dependence, so that $k_{0,p}$ can be decomposed into k_0 and b as in the proposed equation model, further data are extracted from the literature (Bulgarin et al., 2020); in the first reference there is no clear specification about the exact catalyst composition which is only stated to be Pt/Alumina based. In the second reference and third reference, both proposed by the same authors, a more clear wt. composition is provided; catalysts are assumed to be compatible.

As data were collected at ambient pressure, $k_{0,p}$ numerically coincides with k_0 , and the found pressure coefficient b results to be -0.4504 , Fig. 10.11. Interestingly enough at low pressure (ambient pressure) the different temperature profiles tested are scarcely dispersed when compared to those at higher pressure. As values are obtained by evaluating the average $k_{0,p}$ from the collected point, the resulting close to constant values for different temperature levels are in good agreement with the model.

10.2 NEC modelling

As data availability is scarce, pressure dependence modelling and fitting is not possible for the full reaction. Hydrogenation rate of NEC is evaluated using data from Fei et al. (2017). Data are acquired at 70 bar and 170, 180, 190, 200 °C respectively, with a 5wt.% Pd/MoO₃ catalys. The reactions involved in the full hydrogenation process are as follows:

FIGURE 10.10: Spline modelling of the equilibrium DoH for pressure in the 1-9.9 bar range.

FIGURE 10.11: Pressure dependence fitting results. Data are provided only at 1.0 and 2.5 bar and for $T = 287, 292, 297^{\circ}\text{C}$.

thus featuring two intermediate compounds. For a set level of pressure, the kinetic system is thus characterized by the kinetic laws Eqs. 10.13 - 10.16, where each compound concentration is defined as moles of LOHC compound over the total LOHC moles number, and is indicated by χ_i , and the equivalent DoH is evaluated as Eq. 10.17.

$$\frac{d\chi_{0\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} = -k_0 \exp -\frac{E_{a,0}}{R_u T} (1 - \chi_{0\text{H-NEC}})^{n_0} \quad (10.13)$$

$$\frac{d\chi_{4\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} = \frac{d\chi_{0\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} - k_1 \exp -\frac{E_{a,1}}{R_u T} (1 - \chi_{4\text{H-NEC}})^{n_1} \quad (10.14)$$

$$\frac{d\chi_{8\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} = \frac{d\chi_{4\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} - k_2 \exp -\frac{E_{a,2}}{R_u T} (1 - \chi_{8\text{H-NEC}})^{n_2} \quad (10.15)$$

$$\frac{d\chi_{12\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} = \frac{d\chi_{8\text{H-NEC}}}{dt} \quad (10.16)$$

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{3\chi_{12\text{H-NEC}} + 2\chi_{8\text{H-NEC}} + \chi_{4\text{H-NEC}}}{3} \quad (10.17)$$

Note that by introducing the $1 - \chi_i$ factors in the kinetic laws, an underlying implication is made, and more specifically the hypothesis is that the system would reach full saturation for an infinite time. As seen from Chapter 3, that is only true in a moderate range of temperature values, as the exothermic nature of the reaction would otherwise shift the chemical equilibrium towards the reactants.

To retrieve each set of parameters (n, E_a, k) a similar approach to the one used in Chapter 3 has been chosen, by first fitting Eqs. 10.13 - 10.16 for each temperature level and by encapsulating both the catalyst and temperature factors in: $k_T = k \cdot \exp -\frac{E_a}{R_u T}$. Then, a common set of n values is chosen, assuming each reaction order carries over the temperature range, so that different values of k_T are fitted for each reaction and temperature value. Then, those are used to find the k and E_a values of each reaction. The same approach is used to fit the equivalent model, which replicates the procedure already proposed for the new catalyst, but instead of fitting the χ values over time, the equivalent DoH level (Eq. 10.17) is applied for each snapshot, and then fitted.

Fig. 10.12 sums up the fitting results of the modelling procedure associated to the parameters proposed in Tab. 10.3.

Both models show a good agreement with the experimental data, and feature similar kinetic parameters. Particularly important is the reaction order n , which seems to mostly carry over the subsequent steps, with only the first step having a slightly higher n . This finding justifies the possibility to effectively model the full reaction with a simplified approach without introducing significant errors. Similarly, it seems that the activation energy corresponding to the first step, mostly coincides with the equivalent activation energy. Interestingly enough, the activation energy of the final step is much lower than the other two values. As such, it means that the final step appears to be the least affected by temperature changes. On the other hand, the frequency factor of the intermediate step is one order of magnitude lower than those of the other reactions, while the equivalent reaction is mostly shifted towards the last value.

Looking at Fig. 10.12 reveals that the multi-step approach seems to be the better option when modelling high temperature reactions, while the single-step provides a better depiction of the high DoH values at a low temperature, as the final reaction step otherwise overestimates the fully hydrogenated compound concentration. Overall, while the full reaction

TABLE 10.3: Hydrogenation parameters for the experimental data provided by Fei et al. (2017). Multi-step reaction parameters are sorted from 0-2 (Eqs. 10.13 - 10.16).

• Parameter	Model	
	Single-step	Multi-step
n	0.7	0.75, 0.70, 0.70
k (1/s)	155.8	213.2, 13.9, 144.1
E_a (kJ/mol)	53.25	52.84, 41.04, 14.86

FIGURE 10.12: Hydrogenation phase of a 70 bar NEC system over a 5wt.% Pd/MoO₃ catalyst. Black dots and lines refer to the DoH values over time.

model provides the best agreement for the experimental data collected at high temperature (above 180 °C), the simplified model seems more reliable.

10.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, the study of the kinetics of LOHCs through simplified equivalent reactions presents both strengths and limitations that vary depending on the specific carrier system being modeled. The most common approach involves condensing the complexity of multi-step reactions into a single, equivalent reaction. This method offers a practical and efficient way to simulate and understand the behavior of LOHC systems, often capturing a significant portion of the actual kinetic behavior with reasonable accuracy. However, the validity of this approach is not universal and is contingent upon certain factors, particularly the variability in reaction degrees across different steps of the reaction process.

For N-ethylcarbazole (NEC), this method proves to be particularly effective. The homogeneity in the degrees of reaction across the multiple steps of NEC's reaction pathway means that the simplified model closely mirrors the actual system. The equivalent reaction approach allows for a significant simplification without a substantial loss in accuracy, making it a robust and reliable tool for modeling NEC. Even though this approach may not always be the optimal one, its robustness and the consistent results it delivers across various conditions make it a valuable tool in the modeling of NEC kinetics. Both the simplified and more detailed models provide excellent results, further validating the use of the equivalent reaction approach for this particular LOHC.

In stark contrast, the case of dibenzyl toluene (DBT) highlights the limitations of the equivalent reaction model. One of the most critical challenges in modeling DBT is the paucity of experimental data, especially during the hydrogen release phase, where available sources are often incomplete or entirely absent. This scarcity of data significantly hampers the ability to accurately characterize the system and, consequently, to develop reliable models. In the hydrogenation phase, the reaction degrees across the different steps exhibit significant heterogeneity. This heterogeneity leads to a considerable deviation between the equivalent degree of hydrogenation (DoH) and the DoH derived from experimental data over much of the simulation, particularly during the intermediate stages.

This divergence necessitates the introduction of artificial fitting functions to replicate the physical process, an approach that, while allowing the model to achieve reasonable accuracy, imposes substantial limitations and introduces artificiality into the model. The necessity of these fitting functions underscores the challenge of accurately modeling DBT with the simplified equivalent reaction approach. The importance of reaction intermediates in DBT is further highlighted by the pronounced peaks in their concentration profiles, which are much more significant than those observed in the NEC system. The stark contrast in the behavior of intermediates between DBT and NEC suggests that while the equivalent reaction model is a powerful tool, it may introduce significant modeling errors depending on the nature of the LOHC under consideration.

Given these findings, it is clear that while the equivalent reaction model can be a potent and useful tool in the modeling of LOHC kinetics, its application must be carefully considered. The model's effectiveness is highly dependent on the specific characteristics of the LOHC, particularly the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the reaction degrees across the steps involved. For LOHCs like NEC, where there is a high degree of homogeneity, the model is both efficient and accurate. However, for more complex systems like DBT, where heterogeneity is more pronounced and experimental data is limited, the model may fail to accurately capture the system's behavior without significant modifications.

In practical terms, this means that a preliminary assessment of the reaction degrees across the steps is essential before adopting the equivalent reaction approach for a given LOHC. This assessment will help determine whether the simplification is likely to yield accurate and reliable results or whether it might introduce significant errors that could compromise the validity of the model. For systems like DBT, where significant discrepancies can arise, alternative modeling approaches or more detailed reaction mechanisms may be necessary to achieve the desired accuracy.

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of tailoring modeling approaches to the specific characteristics of the LOHC system under consideration. While the equivalent reaction model offers a powerful tool for simplifying and understanding LOHC kinetics, it is not a one-size-fits-all solution. The decision to use this model should be informed by a careful consideration of the specific system's reaction dynamics and the availability of experimental data. In cases where the equivalent reaction model is applicable, it can greatly simplify the modeling process while still providing accurate and reliable results. However, for more complex systems, such as DBT, a more nuanced approach may be necessary to accurately capture the kinetic behavior and to avoid the introduction of significant modeling errors. The research thus highlights the need for a flexible and context-dependent approach to LOHC kinetics modeling, one that recognizes the strengths and limitations of the equivalent reaction model and applies it judiciously to achieve the best possible outcomes.

Chapter 11

Conclusions

Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs) represent an emerging technology for hydrogen storage and transport, offering a promising alternative to traditional methods like compressed gas or liquid hydrogen. LOHCs are organic compounds that can absorb and release hydrogen through chemical reactions, allowing for the storage of hydrogen in a liquid form at ambient conditions. This process involves two main steps: hydrogenation, where hydrogen is chemically bound to the carrier, and dehydrogenation, where hydrogen is released for use. LOHCs have several advantages, including high volumetric hydrogen density, safety in handling, and the ability to use existing fuel infrastructure for storage and distribution. However, the commercialization of LOHC technology faces significant challenges, particularly related to the energy efficiency of the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes, the stability and recyclability of the carriers, and the need for catalysts that can operate efficiently under mild conditions. A literature overview of the hydrogen systems and the literature background on LOHCs is provided in Chapter 1 and Chapter 2.

Chapter 3 begins with the kinetic characterization of a LOHC compound. The proposed method has been used to fit the hydrogen release and uptake of the N-ethyl Carbazole (NEC). Lack of published data limits LOHCs characterization: only few carriers can be modelled, and pressure dependency are mostly omitted as most data are published for a single pressure value. Noble metal catalysts like palladium (Pd) and platinum (Pt) were identified as the most effective catalysts, capable of achieving complete dehydrogenation and high selectivity. However, even with these catalysts, the models are limited by the narrow range of thermodynamic conditions for which experimental data is available. The chapter discusses the fitting of isothermal experimental data to derive kinetic parameters, which were then used to develop models capable of predicting reaction behavior under various conditions. The activation energy values and other kinetic parameters obtained were consistent with those reported in the literature, providing a solid foundation for subsequent modeling efforts.

For dehydrogenation, the model was particularly accurate at pressures of 0.5-1.0 bar, and could even be extrapolated to 0.25 bar with good results, indicating the robustness of the chemical-kinetic framework. In hydrogenation, while the model performed well overall, some inaccuracies were observed at low temperatures and high pressures. These conditions, however, are not optimal for practical applications, and are unlikely to be effectively required. On the other hand, the influence of the chemical equilibrium seems to affect high temperature hydrogenation uptake; to account for the limited uptake capability, the kinetic law has been adequately modified. Additionally, it seems that for temperature values above 433 K, further temperature increases do not lead to kinetic gains, hinting that some external factor may influence the reaction rate.

Overall, the proposed model provide valuable insights into the optimal thermodynamic conditions for both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes, and seem to greatly benefit from the introduction of the correction factors. Future work should focus on refining these models by incorporating more experimental data, particularly at higher pressures to improve their predictive power and applicability across a broader range of conditions. This first modelling approach relies on the definition of an equivalent reaction, which bypasses the intermediate reaction steps between the fully saturated and unsaturated compounds.

Chapter 4 discusses the thermodynamic modeling of LOHC systems, emphasizing the importance of simplicity and practicality in the early stages of technology development.

Given the current limitations in experimental data and the nascent state of LOHC technology, the chapter argues for a simplified modeling approach that still offers valuable insights while avoiding overly speculative conclusions. As such a lumped parameter approach is proposed as a viable mean to model a simple reactor, such as a batch reactor. The use of batch reactors as a primary focus for modeling is justified due to their simplicity and suitability for small-scale applications, which are likely the first practical uses of LOHC technology.

Simplified models that assume constant temperature across the reactor section have proven effective, especially when supported by efficient stirring mechanisms that promote temperature homogenization. The chapter details how maintaining a constant temperature in these reactors is crucial for accurate modeling, particularly during the exothermic hydrogenation process. While reaction kinetics generally increase with temperature, the availability of hydrogen becomes a limiting factor, naturally curbing the risk of runaway reactions, and aiding reactor homogenization; similarly, the modified Arrhenius law accounting for the maximum kinetic gain associated with temperature increases, further limits the inner variability. This inherent safety feature of the LOHC system supports the use of simplified models at this stage of development.

On the other hand, dehydrogenation reactions are inherently better fit for 0D modelling. If a hot spot appears in the reactor, the kinetic rate locally increases resulting in higher hydrogen release. However, as the local DoH decreases, the kinetic rates swiftly drops (second order reaction); additionally, the increased release leads to great amount of heat being sunk to provide the required reaction heat, thus lowering the local temperature. The chapter concludes that as LOHC technology matures and more data becomes available, these models can serve as a foundation for more complex simulations, ultimately aiding in the development of scalable hydrogen storage solutions.

In exploring reactor design and control strategies for LOHC systems, chapter 5 compares the performance of plug flow reactors (PFRs) and batch reactors under various conditions. The primary goal is to optimize hydrogen release and uptake while minimizing energy consumption and maintaining efficiency. Pressure loss and stirring power consumption further inform the design choice. Due to its endothermic nature, LOHC system design must focus on the hydrogen release phase; as such, from this point onwards this thesis mostly covers the dehydrogenation phase only. The aim of this section is not to provide a detailed design of the reactor set-ups, but rather to preliminary describe a LOHC subsystem in terms of its main characteristics.

PFRs, despite their greater complexity compared to batch reactors, offer significant advantages in terms of efficiency and are better fit for large scale applications. The chapter discusses the need for one-dimensional modeling of PFRs to accurately capture the variations in temperature, flow rates, and reaction kinetics along the reactor length. Effective thermal management is critical in PFRs to avoid hot spots and ensure uniform reaction rates, which can be achieved through precise temperature control.

The integration of storage tanks into the reactor system is another key aspect covered in the chapter. Different configurations have been tested, leading to a novel final design where the tubular reactor is coupled with two vessels to limit the otherwise too extensive reactor length. This configuration not only enhances control over reaction conditions but also decouples system performance from the inherent properties of the LOHC, allowing for greater flexibility in application. The chapter emphasizes that such integrated systems are better suited for real-world applications, where consistent hydrogen supply is essential. Indeed, the high variability of the uncontrolled hydrogen release rate needs to be smoothed to accommodate for the end-user requirements.

Both the batch and plug flow reactors are subjected to alternative control strategies, and their performances are presented in chapter 6. This chapter evaluates different control strategies for managing the kinetic rates of LOHC reactions, focusing on the trade-offs between temperature, pressure, and heat transfer fluid mass flow rate controls. The analysis is conducted with a particular emphasis on maximizing hydrogen release efficiency under varying power demands, by normalizing the amount of hydrogen that can be released for any given power demand with respect to different references.

Temperature control emerges as the most effective strategy, maintaining high efficiency across a range of loads even under demanding conditions. Pressure control, while effective at lower loads, loses effectiveness at higher demands, and mass flow rate control proves to

be the least reliable, especially at elevated temperatures. Mass flow rate control can only provide good results when the system needs to satisfy a low power demand, as it acts like the temperature control but can only limit the kinetic rate.

The chapter also explores more complex control strategies, such as multi-parameter controls, which could potentially enhance performance by combining the strengths of temperature and pressure controls. However, these approaches increase system complexity and may not be justifiable for small-scale applications, though they could be more appropriate for plug flow reactors. In conclusion, the chapter highlights that while simpler control strategies like temperature control are currently the most practical and effective, further research into more sophisticated methods could yield significant benefits for larger and more complex LOHC systems. The findings serve as a guide for optimizing control strategies in future LOHC applications, ensuring that the systems can meet diverse operational requirements while maintaining efficiency and safety. With the introduction of Ragone plots, the chosen generic approach can inform the system sizing when coupling the energy storage to the end-user demand.

Finally, the chapter underscores the importance of balancing complexity with practicality in reactor design. While more sophisticated control strategies, such as temperature gradients along the reactor, could optimize hydrogen release, these approaches require more complex modeling and may not be feasible for small-scale applications. The chapter suggests that future research should focus on refining these models to improve their applicability and efficiency across different use cases.

Chapter 7 discusses the coupling of a SOFC system with a LOHC feed, which removes the need for an external and costly heat source to drive the dehydrogenation reaction. A SOFC module is modeled, characterized, and validated in terms of electrical power output and its associated waste heat. Introducing a control strategy can ensure consistent performance in LOHC-SOFC systems, provided controllability is maintained. A PI controller allows for adjusting the reactor's pressure, temperature, or inlet mass flow rate to meet user power demands.

Pressure control assumes decoupling of the SOFC pressure from the reactor's pressure, achievable through physical separation of the two environments. It is generally less effective at high target power factors but can still be viable at moderate power levels. Temperature control is preferred for enhanced controllability. It involves regulating the mass flow rate over a constant temperature heat source, assuming the SOFC stack temperature remains constant regardless of the set-point, which only affects the reactor. Temperature control generally performs better, especially at high power factors, and results in higher efficiency when the controlled variable approaches its bounds.

For preliminary studies, the LOHC-SOFC coupling's controllability is evaluated under constant power demand. Performance is similar to the general case presented in the previous chapter, with SOFCs meeting LOHC requirements. At lower target demands, both control strategies are viable, requiring less extreme conditions. Operating LOHC systems at low power output values improves cycle stability and hydrogen usage. Combining pressure and temperature controllers offers some additional controllability, but the improvements are marginal. More complex controllers or refined parameter adjustments may yield further benefits, but these are expected to be limited due to moderate variability in control variables. Additionally, high-pressure reaction rates are not well-characterized in the literature.

Note that with respect to the control strategy presented in Chapter 6, Chapter 7 describes temperature control through HTF mass flow rate control as the reaction temperature of the SOFC stack (about 1000 K) is far higher than the reactor temperature. On the other hand, mass flow rate control in chapter 6 assumes the external fluid temperature to be set to the design temperature of the reactor.

Chapter 8 focuses on hydrogen as a marine fuel, evaluating LOHCs and comparing them with ammonia. Current barriers to hydrogen adoption in the maritime sector include a lack of safety standards, underdeveloped technology, significant onboard storage requirements, and high investment costs. Despite the initiation of demonstration projects for both internal combustion engines (ICEs) and fuel cells, large-scale adoption remains limited.

The feasibility of LOHC systems for cargo ships was examined, using a SOFC power train with ammonia storage as a reference. Four LOHC systems—DBT, MCH, DEC, and NEC—were assessed for their dynamic behavior under varying loads. The analysis revealed

that LOHC systems can adapt to changing demands with appropriate control mechanisms. However, these systems require significantly larger volumes and masses compared to ammonia systems, primarily due to LOHCs' lower gravimetric density. Among the LOHCs, Decalin requires the least volume, whereas NEC demands the highest mass and MCH the highest volume. Despite the lower reaction temperatures of LOHCs, the overall energy density remains inferior to that of ammonia. LOHC systems also necessitate high-quality heat for dehydrogenation, with NEC needing the least energy and MCH the most. In contrast, ammonia systems offer superior energy densities, both volumetric and gravimetric.

Moreover, ammonia systems are associated with lower dehydrogenation heat, which benefits the overall system efficiency. Waste heat utilization is indeed necessary to reduce emissions in the maritime sector. Given their better performance metrics and energy efficiencies, ammonia systems are expected to be more viable, particularly for large-scale marine applications. Overall, while LOHC systems exhibit dynamic feasibility and can meet operational demands, their lower energy densities and higher storage requirements make them less competitive compared to ammonia in the maritime sector. Thus, ammonia is anticipated to be the more advantageous solution for large-scale marine fuel applications.

The integration of static modeling techniques for liquid organic hydrogen carriers is presented in chapter 9, and emphasizes the value of focusing on steady-state conditions rather than transient dynamics. By assuming that transient effects are negligible, static models can define the state of LOHC subsystems through key parameters: degree of hydrogenation (DoH), temperature, and pressure. This approach enables the creation of detailed maps linking these variables to hydrogen release kinetics.

For example, the dehydrogenation process can be effectively modeled under isothermal conditions, which provides insights into optimal operating temperatures (approximately 200 °C for NEC systems) and the impact of varying DoH on release rates. By maintaining the temperature within a specified range (160-230 °C), the hydrogen release can be stabilized to meet different power demands. The static maps derived from these models serve as a powerful tool for predicting system behavior without the complexity of dynamic simulations. This is particularly advantageous in practical applications where consistent power output and efficient thermal management are critical.

The ability to predict the necessary temperature for specific DoH values under varying power demands simplifies control strategies for both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation phases. Additionally, the comparative analysis of charging (hydrogenation) and discharging (dehydrogenation) phases underscores the importance of effective thermal management. The time-dependent maps illustrate that achieving desired hydrogen release levels is heavily dependent on maintaining appropriate temperature conditions throughout the reaction. This approach bypasses transitory phases, however those are expected to be very brief when compared to the overall operating time since LOHC systems have been proved to be better fit for high energy-to-power ratios. Such representations could be useful to evaluate the integration of LOHC modules in more complex energy systems.

The study of LOHC kinetics through simplified equivalent reactions reveals both strengths and limitations. The prevalent method of condensing multi-step reactions into a single equivalent reaction offers a practical and efficient means of simulating LOHC behavior, often capturing a significant portion of the actual kinetics with reasonable accuracy. However, this approach's validity is not universal and varies depending on the carrier system being modeled, particularly regarding the variability in reaction degrees across different steps.

As such, chapter 10 evaluates the multi-step modelling of two hydrogen carriers: NEC, and dibenzyl toluene (DBT). Those are compared to their equivalent counterpart. Since no data was available for DBT hydrogen release, comparison is held over the hydrogenation step, and DBT dehydrogenation is still presented so that both NEC and DBT are fully characterized.

For N-ethylcarbazole, the simplified model is particularly effective due to the uniform reaction degrees across its pathway, allowing the equivalent reaction approach to accurately reflect the system's behavior. This robustness and consistency in results validate the use of the equivalent reaction model for NEC. However, the equivalent reaction model faces challenges when applied to systems like DBT, where limited experimental data and significant heterogeneity in reaction degrees complicate accurate modeling. The scarcity of data and pronounced deviations in reaction degrees necessitate the use of artificial fitting functions,

which, while improving accuracy, introduce limitations and potential artificiality into the model.

The stark differences in behavior between DBT and NEC highlight the limitations of the equivalent reaction model, particularly for complex systems with significant reaction step heterogeneity and limited data. This suggests that while the equivalent reaction model is a valuable tool for some LOHCs, its application must be carefully considered based on the specific characteristics of the LOHC system. For LOHCs like NEC, where reaction steps exhibit high homogeneity, the model provides accurate and efficient results. Conversely, for more complex systems such as DBT, alternative modeling approaches or detailed reaction mechanisms may be necessary to ensure accuracy and avoid substantial modeling errors.

Overall, the research underscores the importance of tailoring modeling approaches to the specific LOHC system under consideration. While the equivalent reaction model offers a streamlined method for understanding LOHC kinetics, it is not universally applicable. A preliminary assessment of reaction degrees and data availability is crucial for determining whether this approach will yield reliable results. For complex systems, a more nuanced approach may be required to capture kinetic behavior accurately and mitigate potential errors. The study thus emphasizes the need for a flexible and context-sensitive approach to LOHC kinetics modeling, recognizing the model's strengths and limitations and applying it judiciously to achieve the best outcomes.

In summary, this thesis has explored various aspects of LOHC technology, from kinetic modeling and thermodynamic analysis to reactor design, control strategies, and applications. The findings underscore the importance of simplicity and practicality in the early stages of LOHC development, given the current limitations in experimental data and technological readiness. However, as the field progresses, more sophisticated models and control strategies will be necessary to fully realize the potential of LOHCs for hydrogen storage and transport. While LOHCs offer significant advantages, particularly in terms of safety and storage density, they are not without limitations. The relatively low energy density and the need for significant heat input at moderately high temperatures remain major challenges. Furthermore, the commercial viability of LOHC technology will depend on continued research to better characterize these substances and develop more efficient catalysts and processes. Preliminary results reveal that ammonia could provide a better alternative, requiring less reaction heat and introducing more moderate volume and mass constraints.

Future studies should focus on overcoming these challenges, with particular attention to improving the energy efficiency of hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes and exploring alternative reactor designs and control strategies. Despite the current limitations, the ability to transport hydrogen safely and efficiently using LOHCs holds great promise, especially for applications where conventional hydrogen storage methods are impractical or unsafe. Therefore, continued research and development in this field are essential to unlocking the full potential of LOHC technology.

Appendix A

Metal Hydrides

This appendix is divided into two sections. The first section presents the working principles of metal hydrides from a kinetic and thermodynamic perspective. The second section outlines the modelling steps required to characterise the reactions and the reactor.

The initial subsection presents an overview of the current state of knowledge regarding Metal Hydrides (MHs), as documented in the literature. Despite the different nature of the two reaction types, this overview was used as a reference and starting point for LOHC modelling, due to the similarities in the modelling of LOHC and MH technologies and the lack of a comprehensive review of LOHC technologies, unlike for MHs (Fukai, 2010; Hampton et al., 2002; Bambakidis, 1981). These references have been used to document Sec. A.1.

In particular, a pressure dependence replicating the state-of-the-art phase transition discussed in the upcoming sections was searched in the experimental LOHC data. If confirmed by the data, this hypothesis would have resulted in a pressure-temperature coupled dependency in the kinetic equation. However, a reduced pool of available data and the lackluster results returned by the afore-mentioned model have indicated that this method is unsuitable. Nevertheless, a similar dependency is likely to exist; access to more detailed and complete experimental results could allow for further characterisation.

The second subsection of this appendix validates and compares the 0D thermodynamic model of a metal hydride system with different reactors. This overview, first started during the course of a previous thesis of mine¹ has been reviewed and extended during the first months of my PhD. Given the considerable number of publications on MH systems when compared to those on LOHCs, the former technology has been identified as a safer option to test the 0D method frame work. While further characterisation has been provided, the work done on MHs has established a robust foundation for guiding future developments in this research. This section builds upon the modelling work previously conducted Gambini, Manno, and Vellini (2008) revisiting and extending their work to provide a more comprehensive characterisation (Gambini, Manno, and Vellini, 2008; Gambini, 1994).

A.1 Working principles

A.1.1 Kinetics

Chemical reaction rates are influenced by a number of factors. For instance, in the case of heterogeneous reactions, the reactants are in different physical states and the rate also depends on the surface area, given that the reaction can only occur at the interface. In accordance with the collisional theory, which posits that for a reaction to occur, the molecules must collide with each other, concentration is thus a determining parameter. As the concentration of molecules in a given space increases, the frequency of their collisions also increases.

Furthermore, temperature exerts a considerable influence. At elevated temperatures, molecules possess greater thermal energy and a heightened probability of colliding with one another. Additionally, they exhibit augmented vibrational energy, thereby increasing the likelihood that a collision will prompt a reaction. In addition to exerting a direct influence, temperature also affects equilibrium pressure, which is in turn linked to the driving force established during the charging and discharging processes.

¹Laurea Magistrale di Ingegneria Energetica.

FIGURE A.1: Effect of the catalyst over exergonic reactions ($\Delta G < 0$).

The presence of a catalyst also increases the reaction rate, although the change in the Gibbs free energy of the reaction is unchanged, Fig. A.1). However, it should be noted that the catalyst itself undergoes chemical changes during the reaction, which are ideally reversible. As a result, the catalyst is present among both the reactants and the products.

The study of reaction kinetics is of fundamental importance for hydrogen material storage options, as the rate of reaction ultimately determines the quantity of hydrogen that can be practically made available for a given application, regardless of the material's gravimetric capacity. In essence, the reaction kinetics can be regulated by a number of factors, including surface interactions, transport phenomena, the underlying hydrogen storage mechanism, and phase changes. External parameters such as pressure and temperature exert a significant influence on both sorption and desorption kinetics, making the reactor's heat exchange a key factor.

The variability of the kinetic data for each individual reaction in relation to the experimental set-up and the different external parameters makes comparison between different datasets a complex undertaking. To address this issue, one may choose to refer to averaged data of hydrogen release/uptake; however, a more effective approach may be to compare the shape of the kinetic curves.

The mobility of hydrogen in the hydride is linked to diffusion phenomena through the interstitial sites in the metallic structure. The dynamics of the interstitial motion are expressed on a wide time scale, ranging from 10×10^{14} Hz for vibrational motions up to 10×10^{10} Hz for diffusion in the bulk. These mechanisms are highly temperature-dependent, see Eq. A.1.

$$D = D_0 \exp -\frac{E_a}{k_B T} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

In general, hydrogen can be stored in a hydride in two ways: on the surface (adsorption) or in the bulk of the material (absorption). The bond with the surface is relatively weak; however, for the hydrogen to diffuse into the bulk and cross the surface layer, it must be in atomic form. This indicates that molecular hydrogen must be dissociated by interacting with the hydride surface. The dissociation efficiency can be enhanced by enriching the surfaces with metal catalysts. The potential energy can be plotted with respect to the distance from the surface, as illustrated in Fig. A.2.

The surface energy (Fig. A.3) is the prime cause of the dissociation of hydrogen in chemical sorption processes. The potential energy of interaction of hydrogen gas with the surface can be represented by simple curves. In regions external to the surface, the two curves are separated by the heat of dissociation, denoted as E_D . This is defined as the amount of energy required to separate a hydrogen molecule into its constituent atoms, with a value of $E_D = 218 \text{ kJ/mol}_{\text{H}_2}$. The initial interaction with the surface is through van der Waals forces, resulting in a state of physical adsorption at a distance of approximately the order of the molecular radius (0.2 nm) The interaction of hydrogen gas with the metal to form a stable

FIGURE A.2: Potential energy curves for activated and non-activated dissociation of hydrogen from a metal surface, followed by endothermic and exothermic formation of the hydrogen solution in the bulk.

FIGURE A.3: Surface interaction of hydrogen over a metal hydride lattice.

solid solution or an intermetallic is described by the $H_2 + M$ curve from its E_P minimum to the intersection with the $2H + M$ curve. In the event that the intersection is below zero, the dissociation is energetically favourable ($E_{NA} < 0$). If the value is less than zero, the process occurs spontaneously; otherwise, a positive quantity of activation energy, (E_A), is required.

From the point of interaction onwards, it is necessary to follow the $2H + M$ curve, which describes the transport of hydrogen in the bulk of the material. This curve has a minimum near the interface between the surface and the bulk, which is characterised by the chemisorption heat, E_C , which is approximately equal to 50 kJ/mol. This makes transport in the bulk impossible for molecular hydrogen. The absorbed hydrogen then shares its electron with the metal atoms, which allows it to diffuse into the lattice.

In the event that the concentration of hydrogen atoms in comparison to the metal atoms within the lattice is relatively low (i.e. less than 10%), the hydrogen atoms remain dispersed in a solid solution, which involves an expansion of the lattice of 2-3 Å per atom of hydrogen. If the concentrations are higher, the strong interaction between hydrogen atoms leads to the formation of the actual hydride, with an expansion of the lattice of approximately 10-20%.

In the context of chemisorption, the surface properties of interest, such as the chemisorption heat of formation (E_C) and the sticking probability² depend on the concentration. This dependence is linked to the coverage of the surface by atomic hydrogen. This, in turn, depends on the mobility of atomic hydrogen, both on the surface and in the bulk of the material. Nevertheless, the step that typically governs and limits the kinetics is the diffusion

²The probability that the molecules remain trapped by adsorbing on the surface

between the stable sites of surface chemisorption and the absorption sites in the bulk of the material ($E_c - E_s$), which affects the structure of the surface itself.

The kinetics appear to be influenced by a closed loop between concentration and surface interaction. In practice, however, the metal surface may become contaminated. It is frequently observed that the surfaces of elemental metals are passivated by oxygen, which serves to inhibit the dissociation reaction and the diffusion of atomic hydrogen into the bulk. Conversely, intermetallic compounds frequently retain highly reactive surfaces even after exposure to oxygen or other contaminants, including water, nitrogen and carbon dioxide. It appears that the surface chemical composition may undergo a rearrangement with the aim of reducing the surface energy, leading to a selective oxidation of specific alloy elements. This phenomenon can be described as surface segregation.

A further impediment to the transportation of hydrogen is associated with the formation of surface hydrides. It is, in fact, necessary to transport the hydrogen that has been dissociated on the surface internally, away from the first rows of atoms. If the transport properties are inadequate, the substrate and hydrogen react and form a hydride on the surface. This significantly inhibits the kinematic performance, to the extent that diffusion through this hydride layer becomes the rate-limiting step of the reaction.

As anticipated, the kinetics is influenced by heat exchange, which in turn is influenced by the mass transport of the reactants, as well as by the possible growth of the grains. Given that the materials in question are often in powder form with limited contact between particles, the heat transport is not governed by the thermal conductivity of the storage material. Instead, it follows many of the principles applicable to heat exchange through porous media. In porous media, heat exchange occurs through a network of pores and the material itself. The size distribution of the pores with respect to the mean free path of hydrogen at a given temperature, as well as the structure of the material itself, determine the nature of this exchange. Consequently, unless a lumped parameter approach is adequately introduced, both mass and heat transport through the hydride bed must be modelled.

During the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of the metal lattice, it undergoes expansions and compressions. The different dimensions of the lattice lead to the formation of defects at the metal-hydride interface and possibly to the formation of cracks. This means that through the cycles, the material breaks into increasingly smaller particles, forming fine dust; this phenomenon is called decrepitation. The degree of decrepitation is influenced by the number of cycles and the plastic behavior of the metal or alloy, and altering the packing can lead both to an impedance to the transport of the gas and to worse heat transfer coefficients due to the loss of contact with the heat transfer fluid. Typically, decrepitation behavior tends to stabilize after at most a few dozen cycles, returning to the activation processes. In fact, in general, the cyclic behavior of materials should not be evaluated in the first activation cycles which are therefore not representative of the actual performance achievable in the long term, resulting for example in greater capacity.

A.1.2 Thermodynamics

Depending on the concentration, pressure of hydrogen, and temperature, there can be two distinct hydride phases, which are generally characterised by different phase diagrams. Typically, the phase diagrams of metal hydrides are represented as two-dimensional projections of isotherm profiles, plotted in conditions of equilibrium between the pressure of hydrogen gas and the concentration of hydrogen in the metal. An illustrative example of a phase diagram is provided in Fig. A.4.

In the low-pressure and low-concentration range, hydrogen is typically present in a solid solution designated as the α phase. As the pressure of the hydrogen is increased, further absorption occurs until the hydrogen-hydrogen interactions become significant. At this point, the hydrogen atoms occupying the interstitial sites in the lattice begin to form the hydride, which is called the β phase. In general, the nucleation and growth of this phase can occur at the grain boundary, on free surfaces or in the bulk of the metal, depending on the diffusion mechanisms. In an ideal equilibrium state, the hydrogen pressure reaches a constant value at which the phases coexist in equilibrium, resulting in a plateau in the PCT diagram. As the β phase increases, the hydrogen content also increases until the α phase is fully transformed into the β phase. At this juncture, the pressure rises along with the hydrogen concentration,

FIGURE A.4: Phase diagram of a generic metal hydride, showcasing the influence of temperature.

given that the latter is dissolved in the β phase in a solid solution. The transition between the two phases occurs rapidly above the critical temperature. Fig. A.5 highlights the main aspects of the reactions.

The slope and length of the plateau section are of particular significance with regard to storage applications. A flat plateau allows for reversible storage and release of hydrogen through shifts of the surrounding pressure, which is stacked against the equilibrium value of the plateau. In general, the release of hydrogen is achieved by reducing the pressure or heating the material, thereby transforming the hydride into the α phase. The length of the plateau determines the circumstances under which hydrogen can be reversibly stored in the hydride. However, this does not provide information on the ease with which this occurs, which is dependent on the kinetics. In many applications, the objective is to work with a plateau pressure that is close to ambient pressure, in order to utilise less expensive containers. Additionally, it is possible to moderately modify the plateau pressure through the formation of alloys. For example, in the case of the LaNi_5 hydride, this can be reduced by adding small percentages of tin.

At point A, the solid solution is saturated and the absorption of hydrogen results in the precipitation of the β phase. At point B, the entire solid solution has undergone transformation, leaving only one phase, namely MH_b . At this juncture, all available interstitial sites have been occupied. However, depending on the pressure and temperature, the formation of a non-stoichiometric compounds and the absorption of further hydrogen are still possible. The reactions that occur are therefore as follows:

FIGURE A.5: Phase diagram and derived Van't Hoff plots for a generic hydride.

It must be remembered that hydrogenation follows Gibbs law (Eq. A.2).

$$d.o.f. = n_{components} - n_{phases} + 2 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In a system comprising two elements (hydrogen and a homogeneous compound) and two phases (solid and gaseous), the number of variables is two. As the pressure increases, the concentration of hydrogen rises. The formation of an additional phase results in a reduction in variance and a concomitant loss of degree of freedom. Consequently, at equilibrium, the hydrogen pressure remains constant during the transformation while the composition of the hydride undergoes change.

Van't Hoff diagrams (Fig. A.5) are a commonly employed method for determining the thermodynamic properties of storage materials, for comparing the operating temperature and pressure values of different hydrides, and are constructed from a series of PCT measurements at various temperatures. Subsequently, the trend of the desorption plateau pressure is plotted on a logarithmic scale against the inverse of the temperature, which has been appropriately scaled (Eq. A.3).

$$\frac{1}{2} \log \frac{p_{eq}}{p_0} = \frac{\Delta H_r}{R_u T} - \frac{\Delta S_r}{R_u} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

This slope, which is clearly negative, can be used to determine the reaction enthalpy; alternatively, the intersection with the abscissas can be used to calculate the reaction entropy. The equation is known as the van't Hoff equation and is an approximation; therefore, it cannot be guaranteed that all the measured profiles align with the linear profile. Of particular significance is the assumption that the enthalpy of reaction is independent of temperature. In the event that nonlinear effects are pertinent, the equation must be rewritten in accordance with Eq. A.4.

$$R_u T \log \frac{p_{eq}}{p_0} = \Delta H_{rT_0}^0 + T \Delta S_{rT_0}^0 + \Delta C_p^0 \left[(T - T_0) - T \log \frac{T}{T_0} \right] \quad (\text{A.4})$$

It is of great importance to note that pressure is always taken at the same concentration, which is typically central. This is particularly crucial for materials that exhibit a sloping plateau. The slope of the plateau is associated with lattice defects and atomic disorder. An increase in the degree of disorder results in a corresponding increase in the inclination of the

FIGURE A.6: Phase diagram and derived Van't Hoff plots for a generic hydride.

plateau. The crystalline structure has a minimal slope, whereas the amorphous material exhibits a slope that is so high as to render the plateau essentially unobservable. In such materials, it can be challenging to reproduce a van't Hoff diagram. As a consequence of hysteresis phenomena, the plateau pressure during desorption is lower than that during absorption. In practice, the values are typically reported in comparison to the desorption pressure, given that the dehydrogenation temperature represents a crucial parameter for this technology. This pressure difference implies that the phase diagrams of absorption and desorption are distinct, and that the reaction enthalpy itself differs. Consequently, the plateau regions become metastable regions. Fig. A.6 provides a graphical representation of this phenomenon.

At point A, the increase in the hydrogen concentration causes the compound to follow the AB stretch. Under pressure-depletion effects the system is stable, while between the desorption pressure (p_{des}) and pressure-swing effects (p_{ass}), it is metastable, and the transformation occurs according to the BC path. Upon reversal of the direction of the process, the path followed differs, as the system is not reversible. This is demonstrated by the reactions below.

The compound in β phase passes through metastable states along CD; in the D point, a phase transformation occurs. The two reactions are distinct, resulting in differences in Gibbs free energy and reaction enthalpy. The hysteresis observed in the context of cyclic behaviour

can be attributed to two distinct causes: extrinsic effects, which are attributable to measurement errors and insufficient time between measurements for equilibrium to be reached; and intrinsic effects, which represent a loss of efficiency in storage mechanisms and the origins of which remain a topic of debate. The most promising theory to explain the intrinsic nature of hysteresis phenomena in MHs focuses on the variation of plastic deformation and on the dislocations formed during hydrogenation and dehydrogenation. During the absorption of hydrogen, the lattice deforms, leading to a stretching of the atomic bonds without their breaking. This results in the storage of a quantity of excess energy in these bonds, which is referred to as mechanical strain energy. This elastic energy is of the order of the amplitude of the area of the cycle. When the tensile stress reaches a critical level, the bonds are broken and dislocations are formed, which can then move within the material. Experimental evidence indicates that dislocation arrays of comparable density are formed during both phases of the hysteresis loop. However, it appears that these are subsequently annihilated while maintaining a saturation value for the dislocation density. Consequently, following the initial $\alpha - \beta - \alpha$ cycle, a subsequent cycle results in the restoration of the initial dislocation state. The energy expended during their formation is dissipated as heat transferred to the surrounding material. The work done by the system on the material is equal to this released heat, resulting in an increase in the material's entropy. In the literature, this additional term of energy required for plastic deformation is referred to as ΔH_{dis} , representing the energy dissipated as heat during the cycle. This can be visualised on a diagram that relates the Gibbs free energy per mole of metal to the composition of the composite. However, there is a critical temperature for which the effects of hysteresis disappear. For Pd-D systems, the critical temperature is approximately 536 K. It should be noted that for low hydrogen concentrations, the isotherms present a common slope, which confirms a dependence similar to that described by Eq. A.5. The slope of the tangent lines ($\frac{dG}{dx} |_{T,p}$) represents the chemical potential of hydrogen.

$$x \propto \sqrt{p} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

This relationship is known as Sieverts' law and is applicable to a considerable number of MH systems. The dependency is a consequence of the dissociation of hydrogen molecules into atoms as a result of their dissolution in the metal. At elevated pressures, the discrepancy between the observed behaviour of hydrogen and that predicted by the ideal gas model results in a solubility that is greater than the one predicted by Sieverts' law.

A significant proportion of hydrogen storage materials exhibit a granular structure. At the interface between two grains, a region can be observed where the bonds are stretched to align with the differing orientations of the grains. These same bonds represent stored excess energy. The reduction in grain size results in an increase in the interface area, which in turn affects the thermodynamics of the reaction and the rate of reaction. Nevertheless, it is not definitively established that the reaction enthalpy increases; rather, this depends on the specific material and the interface in question. It should be noted that the data on reaction enthalpy in the literature does not always include the enthalpy required for the formation of the solution. Solution enthalpy, entropy, and free Gibbs energy are evaluated as in Eq. A.6, A.7, A.8.

$$\Delta H_s = H_s - \frac{1}{2} H_{H_2}^f \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\Delta S_s = S_s - \frac{1}{2} S_{H_2}^f \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\Delta G_s = \Delta H_s - T\Delta S_s = R_u T \log p^{\frac{1}{2}} + R_u T \log \frac{b-c}{c} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Furthermore, the enthalpy of solution appears to exhibit a similar trend across the three rows of elements in the periodic table, underscoring the influence of the electronic structure of the metal matrix on bond stability. It is possible to identify a number of different models in the literature that have been developed to predict the reaction enthalpy. Of particular note is the semi-empirical model that is based on the Griessen and Driessen band structure. This model indicates that the energy required for a reaction depends on two key factors: the energy of the Fermi level and the energy of the first conduction band of the host metal (Eq. A.9). A correlation has been identified between the hydrogen concentration and the enthalpy of

solution, which is attributed to the interaction between hydrogen atoms. The presence of interstitial hydrogen typically causes dilations in the lattice, which in turn interact with the stress field of the individual hydrogen atoms. This results in a lowering of the heat of solution in proportion to the concentration of hydrogen itself. This represents the mean elastic interaction, which is referred to as the mean-field contribution.

$$\Delta H_r = \frac{n_s}{2} \left[\alpha \left(E_f - E_s \right) - \beta \right] \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The entropic term is instead mainly linked to the transition from molecular hydrogen to diffuse hydrogen in a solid solution, with a contribution approximately equal to the standard entropy of hydrogen, and therefore has an approximately constant value for the different metals, of $\Delta S_s \approx 120 - 130 \text{ J/kmol}_{\text{H}_2}$. This change in entropy is reflected in the flow of heat exchanged with the external environment, resulting in an endothermic process during desorption and an exothermic process during absorption. However, complex hydrides can exhibit markedly disparate values of ΔS_s .

In general, the majority of binary metal hydrides exhibit markedly negative enthalpies of formation, indicating the formation of highly stable hydrogen-metal bonds that require substantial amounts of heat and temperature for release. The enthalpy of formation can be significantly diminished by the utilisation of intermetallic hydrides.

Among the main types studied (AB, A₂B, AB₂, AB₃, A₂B₇, and AB₅) the most researched compounds are AB, AB₂ and AB₅, due to their good storage capacity, the ease of synthesis through traditional technologies, the flexibility in the possibility to determine its thermodynamic properties, good cycle behavior and absorption and desorption kinetics. The AB hydrides have a simple cubic structure in which it is possible to have hydrogen absorptions up to H/M mole fractions of 1.0-1.5. On the other hand, AB₅ hydrides have a hexagonal structure and are mainly known for LaNi₅. Many researchers have focused their studies on it to improve its properties through substitutions: the La in site A can be replaced by rare earths (Ce, Pr, Nd) or a mixture of them (mischmetal [Mm]) to reduce costs and at the same time obtain better cyclic behavior. Substitutions of Ni with Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, and Al can reduce the plateau pressure, improve the release rate, and improve stability in cyclic operation. In this regard, a linear relationship was observed between the volume of the unit cell and the logarithm of the plateau pressure. Finally, AB₂ hydrides can instead have three different crystalline shapes: cubic and hexagonal with a-b-a-b or a-b-a-c-a-b-a-c packing sequence. As with AB₅, as the volume of the unit cell increases, the plateau pressure is reduced.

Heat Transfer

Given the intrinsic link between mass and heat exchange in these processes, it is noteworthy that the conductivities of hydride pellets are typically low. In order to address the issue of low conductivity that is inherent to hydrides, a number of potential solutions have been the subject of investigation.

- The use of coatings of high conductivity and ductility metals has often been explored, with the potential of copper being a particularly promising material. However, it appears that this approach may not be the optimal, as the desired increases in conductivity are only moderate and achieved with the use of significant quantities of material. Moreover, the transport kinetics may be adversely affected, particularly in the case of complex hydrides.
- A variety of materials have been employed as additives in the production of highly conductive alloys, including copper, aluminium, lead and lead-tin alloys. However, following multiple cycles, separation and fracture of the alloy occurs, which results in a reduction in the heat exchange properties. The integration of aluminium structures sintered in solid fractions of 20% into LaNi₅ hydrides has been successfully achieved, resulting in a notable enhancement in conductivity. However, the temperatures and quantities of material necessary for the process preclude its application for complex hydrides. Several examples of highly conductive structures have been integrated into beds, including copper wire arrays and copper or aluminium foams. In the initial case,

the observed increase was relatively modest (approximately 15%). In the second instance, it is essential to evaluate the costs and complexity of integration, while striving to avoid the formation of significant empty spaces.

- The utilisation of expanded natural graphite fibres has been identified as a potentially advantageous avenue of research, given their documented conductivity, porosity, dispersibility and cost-effectiveness. ENG fibres are manufactured from natural graphite that has been subjected to high-temperature treatment with sulfuric acid, resulting in the expansion of the material to form thin sheets. The conduction properties are highly anisotropic, thus the actual improvement in performance is contingent upon the alignment of the fibres with respect to the direction of the heat exchange. Furthermore, due to the difficulty of correctly aligning all the fibres, it is anticipated that performance will be up to 50% worse on a larger scale.

In this regard, the suitability of a range of designs for heat exchangers has been assessed, with due consideration given to a number of chemical and physical properties, as well as thermodynamic and kinetic aspects. The primary challenge lies in the management of absorption heat, and the selection of the optimal solution is contingent upon the specific application. In reference to the hydride pressure vessel, the principal designs that have been subjected to evaluation are as follows:

- Vessels with internal fins are designed to have greater monolithic tank characteristics, with the thermal conductivity increase brought about by the fins being exploited. This approach facilitates the creation of more aesthetically pleasing designs for automotive applications, as they are more straight-forward. However, it can be challenging to contain the requisite volumes and weights.
- The structure of a vessel in cross flow or axial flow can be distributed according to the motion field, which may improve the heat exchange properties. However, this approach involves considerable complexity and a reduction in volumetric and gravimetric efficiency.
- In the case of internal flow vessels, monolithic designs may also be employed, albeit with a degree of complexity associated with the integration of the heat exchange circuit.
- Fluid beds represent a means of enhancing the efficiency of both heat and mass transfer. However, these designs often exhibit a high degree of bulkiness, which can lead to a reduction in overall storage efficiency.

A further innovative proposal is the integration of metal hydrides with metal-organic structures. The frameworks can be employed to confine on a nanometric scale the hydrides, with the objective of enhancing the kinetic and thermodynamic properties. In particular, integrating the two technologies in a proportional manner can increase the thermal conductivity of the bed while simultaneously ensuring structural integrity and reducing the segregation of the hydrogen released.

A variety of designs have been proposed for the heat exchanger, but due to the zero-dimensional approach selected and the considerable advanced computations otherwise required, simple yet common designs have been chosen. The initial layout comprises a tubular reactor, as referenced in Chibani, Bougriou, and Merouani (2018), Meng et al. (2012), and Patil and Ram Gopal (2013), while the second layout is a shell and tube reactor, as documented in Mazzucco and Rokni (2017). Alternative designs feature solid metal hydride beds with internal coils and shell and tube reactors with metal hydride beds surrounding all the tubes and a filter core for hydrogen, (Satya Sekhar et al., 2015).

A.2 Modeling

Modelling procedure accounts for:

- Sizing: the sizing of the system reflects the energy requirements (Eq. A.10) and influences the scale factor (a_x , Eq. A.11):

$$m_{H_2} = \frac{E_{system}}{\eta_{HHV}} \quad (A.10)$$

$$a_x = M_{sample} \frac{[MH]}{MW_{MH}} \frac{MW_{H_2}}{2} \quad (A.11)$$

where η and E_{system} are the efficiency and the energy output of the user application, m_{H_2} is the required amount [kg] of hydrogen to store, a_x is the concentration $[\frac{[H]}{[MH]}]$ conversion factor, and $[MH]$ is the number of atoms in the MH molecule before the hydrogen sorption.

- Geometry: to ground the design procedure to realistic configurations, data obtained from experimental set-ups have been used to define the reactor's geometry: assumptions about the different diameters have thus been made, while the number of tubes and their length depends on the sample's mass. The geometry of the reactor is also required to evaluate the heat exchanger's weight, as to define the constant term in the heat capacity of the system, Eq. A.12.

$$CT_0 = M_{sample}c_{sample} + M_{heatex}.c_{heatex}. \quad (A.12)$$

- Materials: for the heat exchanger material the chosen material was copper, but aluminium and stainless steel alloys such as SS316 could be deployed as well.
- Velocity: the external fluid velocity affects both the overall heat transfer coefficient (U) and (\dot{m}_f). If the selected fluid is water, it has to be kept in the range of 1.0-2.5 m/s to both avoid sedimentation³ and contain the frictional losses and the pressure drop. An estimation of the convective heat transfer fluid has been implemented using either McAdams (Eq. A.13) or Gnielinski's (Eq. A.14,A.15) relations for laminar and turbulent flows, with Re number related to $D_{hyd} = \frac{4A_{cross}}{P_{wet}}$.

$$Nu = 0.023Re^{0.8}Pr^{1/3} \left(\frac{\mu_f}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14} \quad (A.13)$$

$$f = (0.79 \log Re - 1.64)^{-2} \quad (A.14)$$

$$Nu = \frac{\frac{f}{8}(Re - 1000)Pr}{1 + 12.7 \left(\frac{f}{8} \right)^{0.5} (Pr^{2/3} - 1)} \quad (A.15)$$

Most studies either use an approximate value of the overall heat transfer coefficient (Eq. A.16) set as $U = 1000 \text{ W}/(\text{K m}^2)$ or the external fluid convective heat transfer coefficient. However, the low value of the conductive resistance of the bed has a non-negligible influence, contrary to the heat exchanger walls'. In this regard the bed's thermal conductivity was chosen accordingly to the state-of-the-art best deposition techniques, with $\lambda_{MH} \approx 1.0 \times 10^{-3} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kW}/(\text{K m})$. Enhancement of the thermal conductivity is key for the performance, thus values on the higher end of the range have been chosen, accordingly to the previous model developed.

$$U = \left(1/\alpha_f + \frac{\log \left(\frac{D_t}{D_{H_2}} \right) D_{wall} + D_t}{2\lambda_{MH}} \right)^{-1} \quad (A.16)$$

In tubular concentric reactors such as Fig. A.7, a layer of MH dust is held in a tube; at its centre lays a porous cylindrical filter, through which hydrogen is either fluxed or released. The MH tube is then located inside another tube hosting the external fluid required to stabilize the temperature of the bed.

³Lower values of 0.8 m/s can be acceptable if demi water is implemented.

FIGURE A.7: MH tubular reactor design scheme.

(A) The external fluid flows through the tubes with the hydride making up the bulk of the shell.
 (B) The external fluid flows through the shell with the hydride confined inside the tubes.

FIGURE A.8: Shell and tubes exchangers alternative layouts.

Shell and tubes reactors with the hydride powder allocated inside each tube and the external fluid flowing in the shell, that come in two main layout options (Fig. A.8):

1. A solid hydride bed with one hydrogen filter at its center and multiple tubes allotted on the section, each one hosting a fraction of external fluid (Fig. A.8a).
2. Many hydride hollow cylinders each one encased around its own hydrogen duct and surrounded by the external fluid (Fig. A.8b).

Although the initial layout options have been the subject of limited research (Kumar et al., 2019; Raju et al., 2019), it is evident that this configuration gives rise to concerns pertaining to the diffusion of hydrogen through the powder bed. A more logical configuration is the second option, which is a common layout and aligns with the distinct mechanism of heat transfer in LOHC systems. This configuration may prove advantageous, either alone or in conjunction with the previously exploited option. A preliminary design procedure has been initiated in accordance with the latest methodologies, as referenced in Kakac, Liu, and Pramuanjaroenkij (2002).

A few parameters have to be introduced to fully characterize a shell and tube heat exchanger:

- B : relative baffle space, usually expressed as percentage of the shell's diameter (D_s).
- PR : pitch (p_t) to tubes' outer diameter (d_o) ratio.
- F_t : temperature correction factor to account for the difference between the ideal and real flow's directions, resulting in $\alpha_{f,real} = \alpha_{f,ideal} F_t$.
- CTP : tube count calculation constant for one tube pass to account for the tubes' imperfect coverage of the diameter shell due to clearances;

- C_t : tubes' layout constant to determine the actual room occupied by a single tube in a specific configuration

To find out the amount of hydride tubes required the concentric tubes procedure can still be carried out with Eq. A.17, A.18, A.19.

$$V_{MH} = \frac{M_{MH}}{\rho_{MH}} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$A_{sec} = \frac{\pi(d_{o,hyd}^2 - d_{H_2}^2)}{4} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$N_{tubes} = \text{int} \left(\frac{V_{MH}}{A_{sec}L_0} \right) \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Other geometrical output data are the exchange area (A_{hex} , Eq. A.20), the shell diameter (D_s , Eq. A.21), and the equivalent diameter (D_e , Eq. A.22⁴):

$$A_{hex} = \pi \frac{d_{o,hyd} + d_o}{2} N_{tubes} L \quad (\text{A.20})$$

$$D_s = 0.637 \sqrt{\frac{C_t}{CTP} \left(\frac{A_{hex} PR^2 d_o}{L} \right)^{0.5}} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$D_e = 4 \frac{\frac{p_t^2 \sqrt{3}}{4} - \pi \frac{d_o^2}{8}}{\frac{\pi d_o}{2}} \quad (\text{A.22})$$

with the equivalent diameter being the key geometrical length used to evaluate the Nusselt number. The convective heat transfer coefficient on the shell side is to be derived through the Bell Delaware (BD) procedure, although alternative methods may be employed. This model will both evaluate the BD coefficient and the Kern convective heat transfer coefficient.

The actual (Eq. A.24) and the theoretical (Eq. A.23) cross flow available sections do not coincide, so design parameters are introduced (Eq. A.25).

$$A_{cross,th} = \pi \frac{D_s^2 - N_{tubes} d_o^2}{4} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

$$A_{cross} = \frac{D_s C B}{p_t} \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$C = p_t - d_o \quad (\text{A.25})$$

- With the Bell Delaware method the complex nature of the flow shell-side can be replicated through a series of correction factors⁵ applied to the ideal convective heat transfer coefficient (Eq. A.26, A.27, A.28) which turns into its actual value (Eq. A.29) through a series of corrections (J , Eq. A.30):

$$\alpha_{id} = j_i c_p \frac{\dot{m}_f}{A_{cross}} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p \mu} \right)^{2/3} \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_{water}} \right)^{0.14} \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$j_i = a_1 \left(\frac{1.33}{PR} \right)^a \text{Re}^{a_2} \quad (\text{A.27})$$

$$a = \frac{a_3}{1 + 0.14 \text{Re}^{a_4}} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$\alpha = \alpha_{id} \prod J_i \quad (\text{A.29})$$

$$\prod J_i = J_c J_l J_b J_s J_r \quad (\text{A.30})$$

where the following parameters have been introduced:

⁴This relation refers to a triangular tubes' disposition. This layout allows for a higher tubes' density for any given D_s , so its performances should be better than the ones given by a square composition (Mazzucco and Rokni, 2017).

⁵Unless otherwise specified, the properties refer to the shell side fluid.

- J_i : Colburn factor, each featuring a_i is a function of the tubes' layout disposition and the Re number;
- J_c : baffle cut and spacing correction factor, accounting for heat transfer in the window;
- J_l : baffle leakage correction factor;
- J_b : bundle bypass correction factor, due to clearances (CTP) and, if present, pass dividers;
- J_s : variable spacing at the inlet and outlet of the exchanger correction factor;
- J_r : low Reynolds correction factor.

An in depth evaluation of the J_i could be made if a more detailed analysis was to be carried out; a reasonable value for combined effect of these factors is $\prod J_i = 0.6$ Kakac, Liu, and Pramuanjaroenkij, 2002.

- Alternatively with the Kern method if $2.0 \times 10^3 < \text{Re} < 1.0 \times 10^6$, it is possible to evaluate α through the McAdams correlation as in Eq. A.31.

$$\text{Nu} = 0.36 \left(\frac{D_e \dot{m}_f}{A_{\text{cross}} \mu} \right)^{0.55} \text{Pr}^{1/3} \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_{\text{water}}} \right)^{0.14} \quad (\text{A.31})$$

Regardless of the chosen procedure, the overall heat transfer coefficient can be written as Eq. A.32, disregarding the effect of the tubes' walls and heat transfer through the hydrogen filter.

$$U = \left(\alpha^{-1} + \frac{d_o + d_{o,\text{hyd}}}{4} \frac{\log(d_{o,\text{hyd}}/d_{H_2})}{\lambda} \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{A.32})$$

A.2.1 Tubular reactors

Sorption

While regarded as a common layout, only a small handful of sources provide the whole set of information required to replicate the simulation; two datasets have been used to validate the model. In order to do so a different formulation of the Van't Hoff (Eq. A.3) equation was deployed. During the sorption phase Eq. A.33 is thus used.

$$p_{eq} = p_0 \exp \left(\frac{\Delta H_r}{R_u T} + \frac{\Delta S_r}{R_u} + \phi_h / 2 + (\phi_0 + \phi_s) \tan \left(\pi \left(\frac{X}{X_f} - 1/2 \right) \right) \right) \quad (\text{A.33})$$

For the tubular reactor two different sets of data were used to validate the proposed model:

1. While Mazzucco and Rokni published a few detailed articles on the design of MH coupled systems (Mazzucco and Rokni, 2017; Mazzucco and Rokni, 2015) these works do not rely on experimental data. The published simulation results were still used as a reference to test this model. Results provided were obtained choosing Dexcool refrigerant as a cooling fluid Mazzucco and Rokni, 2017 with an inlet temperature $T_{f,i} = 273$ K. The profiles illustrate a representative $\text{Ti}_{1.1}\text{CrMn}$ bed charging process, exhibiting a brief interval during which no chemical reaction occurs. This interval is necessary for compressing the hydrogen feed from p_0 to p_g . Although Mazzucco and Rokni (2017) and Mazzucco and Rokni (2015) provide a comprehensive analysis of the heat exchanger, it is not a sufficient basis for the design of a new heat exchanger. Additionally, the proposed geometry does not include the hydrogen duct in the analysis of conductive bed resistance. Furthermore, the selected hydrogen pressure of 300 bar is not representative of the potential real-world applications.
2. A model based on experimental data, as referenced in Patil and Ram Gopal (2013), was selected to serve as the second dataset. The fitting charging rate implemented by Patil

(A) Original concentration profile over time published by Mazzucco and Rokni.

(B) Original temperature profile over time published by Mazzucco and Rokni.

(C) Evaluated profiles for both temperature and hydrogen content.

FIGURE A.9: Comparison of simulated data with the here defined scripting routine and the reference (Mazzucco and Rokni, 2017).

and Ram Gopal (Eq. A.35) differs slightly from the one previously used (Eq. A.34), as cited in reference Gambini (1994). Initially, the sorption phase of the process was the focus of the simulation, while the subsequent section Sec. A.2.1 will address the desorption phase. Fig. A.10 illustrates that the model continues to yield satisfactory results even for the second reference case. Furthermore, the original experimental data were employed to validate the model, and a satisfactory degree of agreement was observed (see Fig. ??) as referenced in Muthukumar, Madhavakrishna, and Dewan (2007).

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) \log \frac{p_g}{p_{eq}} (X_{sat} - X) \quad (\text{A.34})$$

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = k_0 \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) \frac{p_g - p_{eq}}{p_{eq}} \frac{X - X_f}{X_0 - X_f} \quad (\text{A.35})$$

Having validated this model, a new simulation was run to provide enough hydrogen for a 5 kWh PEM with an average efficiency of $\eta = 0.45$. The following performance was obtained using the input data below (Tab. A.1); and led to the charging process described in Fig. A.12.

Parameter	Value
Geometry	
Length (L , [m])	1.0
Inner diameter (D_i , [m])	0.024
Copper density (ρ_{he} , [kg/m ³])	8933
Copper specific heat capacity (c_{he} , [kJ/(kg K)])	0.385
Wall thickness (t , [mm])	1.5
Hydrogen duct diameter (D_{H_2} , [mm])	9.0
External fluid	
Fluid	water
Velocity (v , [m/s])	1.75
Pressure (p , [Pa])	101 325
Inlet temperature ($T_{f,i}$, [K])	298.15
Hydride	
Enthalpy of formation (ΔH_f , [kJ/kmol])	-28 000
Entropy of formation (ΔS_f , [kJ/(kmol K)])	107.2
Plateau slope factor (ϕ_s , -)	0.35
Hysteresis factor (ϕ_h , -)	0.20
Plateau constant factor (ϕ_0 , -)	0.15
Activation energy (E_a , [kJ/kmol])	21 170
Kinetic constant (k , [1/s])	75
Molecular weight (M , [kg/kmol])	426
Number of atoms ([MH], -)	6
Gravimetric capacity ($w_{\%}$, [%])	1.36
Specific heat capacity (c , [kJ/(kg K)])	0.419
Enhanced thermal conductivity (λ , [kW/(m K)])	0.016
Density (ρ , [kg/m ³])	8400
Porosity (ϵ , -)	0.5
Set-up	
Gas pressure (p_g , [bar])	30
Gas temperature (T_g , [K])	298.15
Initial concentration (X_0 , -)	0.10
Initial temperature (T_0 , [K])	300.15
Final concentration ($\frac{X_f}{X_{sat}}$, -)	0.95

TABLE A.1: Input data for the copper tubular shaped sorption reactor.

(A) Original concentration profile over time published by Patil et. al. Patil and Ram Gopal, 2013.

(B) Original temperature profile over time published by Patil et. al. Patil and Ram Gopal, 2013.

(C) Evaluated profiles for both temperature and hydrogen content.

FIGURE A.10: Comparison of simulated data with the here defined scripting routine and the reference. The reference dataset is represented with the brown line.

FIGURE A.11: Model performances with experimental data simulation of $\text{MmNi}_{4.6}\text{Al}_{0.4}$ bed charging process. Here $p_{\text{H}_2} = 30$ bar, as this was the main scenario used to define the heat exchanger design.

FIGURE A.12: Concentration and temperature profiles over time.

Ext. fluid mass flow rate (\dot{m}_f , [kg/s])	30.42
Convective heat transfer coef. (α_f , [kW/(m ² K)])	7.502
Overall heat transfer coefficient (U , [kW/(m ² K)])	1.093
Effective length(L , [m])	1.001
Tubes number (N_t , -)	15
Bed mass(M_{tot} , [kg])	24.527
Available H ₂ stored (m_{H_2} , [kg])	0.2821

TABLE A.2: Output auxiliary information about the model.

Ext. fluid mass flow rate (\dot{m}_f , [kg/s])	32.45
Convective heat transfer coef. (α_f , [kW/(m ² K)])	6.645
Overall heat transfer coefficient (U , [kW/(m ² K)])	1.007
Effective length(L , [m])	0.998
Tubes number (N_t , -)	16
Bed mass(M_{tot} , [kg])	26.068
Available H ₂ stored (m_{H_2} , [kg])	0.2821

TABLE A.3: Output auxiliary information about the model having considered changed made in kinetic equations.

Data from Tab. A.1 were used to deduce the additional data in Tab. A.2.

This set-up is however unable to store enough energy to keep up with the chosen PEM requirements, as for the chosen pressure value saturation phenomena prevent it from reaching the targeted $X_f \approx 0.9$. Another issue that was raised during this simulation was that the sorption rate thus described seems to be dependent on the desired amount of stored hydrogen. So, for instance, if one were to stop the process at $X_f = 0.3$ it would require a different amount of time compared to the time requirements to reach the very same loading percentage if the final concentration was set at $X_f = 0.8$! The very same consideration can be made about (Eq. A.33), so while during the experimental set up $X_{sat} \approx X_f$ it was deemed appropriate to change both of them into Eq. A.36-A.37.

$$p_{eq} = p_0 \exp \left[\frac{\Delta H_r}{R_u T} + \frac{\Delta S_r}{R_u} + \frac{\phi_h}{2} + (\phi_0 + \phi_s) \tan \left(\pi \frac{X}{X_{sat}} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right] \quad (A.36)$$

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = k_0 \exp \frac{E_a}{R_u T} \frac{p_g - p_{eq}}{p_{eq}} \frac{X - X_{sat}}{X_0 - X_{sat}} \quad (A.37)$$

It could be argued that even the value of X_0 should be modified for the same reason. However, MH formation commences at $X \neq 0$, suggesting that the initial assumed value of X may be contingent on the underlying physics of the process. A simulation was conducted with X_0 differing from the initial value, $X_{t=0}$, which was set to zero. In light of the afore-mentioned considerations, a new simulation was conducted using identical input parameters, with the exception of the final concentration, which was reduced to $\frac{X_f}{X_{sat}} = 0.9$. This selection offers substantial kinetic advantages without the necessity of raising the feed pressure, albeit with a restricted expansion in size. The revised output parameters are presented in Tab. A.3. The length of the reactor is slightly reduced, but the installation of an additional tube is necessary. The water mass flow and the sample weight have both increased, albeit moderately, by approximately 2.0 kg/s and 1.5 kg, respectively.

As shown in Fig. A.13 the influence of X_0 is negligible in this range, and having a lower final concentration allows for a relatively decent charging time reduction. The temperature profile has a slightly higher peak but it is overall alike the previously found profile.

FIGURE A.13: Concentration and temperature profiles over time.

Desorption

Although a preliminary estimation of the system dimensions can be conducted without a comprehensive examination of the release phase, the latter's kinetics is of paramount significance. This is because each end-user application will necessitate a specific quantity of hydrogen flow as an energy input. While the deployment of an intermediate vessel could serve as a buffer, both the power density and the attainable dynamics would be adversely affected. Experimental results about $Ti_{1.1}CrMn$ can be found in the literature (Ramana, 2010), and are reported in Fig. A.14; this work was made by the same team who characterized the sorption phase, with a similarly shaped reactor. No information was found about \dot{m}_f so its value was set as constant throughout the two phases.

Ramana claim to use Eq. A.38:

$$p_{eq} = p_0 \exp \left[\frac{\Delta H_r}{R_u T} + \frac{\Delta S_r}{R_u} - \frac{\phi_h}{2} + (\phi_s - \phi_0) \tan \left(\pi \frac{X}{X_f} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right] \quad (A.38)$$

however, by using this formula, the system never reaches the desired X_f . This is due to the value of X_f itself, which, given the data is $X_f = 0.0$, thus resulting in $p_{eq} = NaN$; even setting the final concentration at the typical initial value during sorption as $X_f = 0.1$ (while the plateau on the provided plot hints at a deep discharge process) the release ends abruptly after just a few instants when $p_{eq} = p_g$. The same concern raised for the sorption case apply: it is not physically accurate to have the desired final concentration affect the properties of the hydride. Without enough data to develop a new equation, Eq. A.38 was modified in Eq. A.39.

$$p_{eq} = p_0 \exp \left(\frac{\Delta H_r}{R_u T} + \frac{\Delta S_r}{R_u} - \frac{\phi_h}{2} \right) \quad (A.39)$$

The omission of the concentration dependency results in the assumption of a constant equilibrium pressure (if temperature is maintained constant) throughout the entire phase. This approach neglects the actual slope of the plateau. It is evident that this assumption introduces a degree of uncertainty in the simulation results, given that the slope of the plateau is related to the crystal lattice. In general, steeper profiles are associated with an increased amount of crystallographic defects and atomic disorder (Parilla, 2014).

(A) Original concentration profile over time published by Ramana.

(B) Original temperature profile over time published by Ramana.

FIGURE A.14: Desorption experimental results given in Ramana (2010).

All things considered, a new run was made and its results agree with the given experimental data. Comparing Fig. A.15 with the provided reference in Fig. A.14, highlights a good match between the two, with an overall reaction time that is basically the same and a temperature profile that closely resembles the provided profiles, even though a lumped parameters approach was chosen and a simplified equation was used to evaluate the system's thermal capacity (Eq. A.12).

FIGURE A.15: Released hydrogen as mass percentage and temperature over time for $T_{f,i} = 313$ K.

With the same geometry established in Tab. A.1 used for the sorption phase, the release process can be simulated. This time $T_{f,i} = 313$ K thus the water density will be slightly lower resulting in \dot{m}_f going from 32.45 kg/s to 32.30 kg/s. The convective coefficient changes too increasing to 7.630 kW/(m² K) from its previous value of 6.645 kW/(m² K), but the overall heat transfer coefficient's increase is clearly less evident going from $U = 1.073$ kW/(m² K) to $U = 1.096$ kW/(m² K).

While this particular hydride is suitable to work at low temperature even during the release process, so much so that the actual initial temperature is 2.0 °C lower than the sorption phase, enabling intermittent operations tightly spaced to avoid reaching the thermal balance, a few parameters have changed from Tab. A.1 as shown in Tab. A.4, and the initial concentration is now set as the final sorption concentration.

Parameter	Value
External fluid	
Fluid	water
Velocity (v , [m/s])	1.75
Pressure (p , [Pa])	101 325
Inlet temperature ($T_{f,i}$, [K])	313.15
Hydride	
Enthalpy of formation (ΔH_f , [kJ/kmol])	-27 500
Entropy of formation (ΔS_f , [kJ/(kmol K)])	100.0
Plateau slope factor (ϕ_s , -)	-
Hysteresis factor (ϕ_h , -)	0.20
Plateau constant factor (ϕ_0 , -)	-
Activation energy (E_a , [kJ/kmol])	22 000

PR	1.25
B	0.2
F_t	0.875
CTP	0.93
C_t	0.87

TABLE A.5: Design parameters for the shell and tubes reactor layout.

Table A.4 – continued from previous page	
Parameter	Value
Kinetic constant (k , [1/s])	100
Molecular weight (M , [kg/kmol])	426
Number of atoms ([MH], -)	6
Gravimetric capacity ($w_{\%}$, [%])	1.36
Specific heat capacity (c , [kJ/(kg K)])	0.419
Enhanced thermal conductivity (λ , [kW/(m K)])	0.016
Density (ρ , [kg/m ³])	8400
Porosity (ϵ , -)	0.5
Set-up	
Gas pressure (p_g , [bar])	1.0
Initial concentration (X_0 , -)	0.862
Initial temperature (T_0 , [K])	298.15
Final concentration ($\frac{X_f}{X_{sat}}$, -)	0.90

TABLE A.4: Input data for the copper tubular shaped desorption reactor.

Since the input parameters are so similar it is only logical for the behavior of the two phases to be alike, Fig. A.16-A.13. The sorption phase is characterised by a higher rate of change, which can be attributed to the high driving forces that are present at the outset of the process. These forces give rise to a notable step increase in the concentration profile, as it is often observed in metal hydrides. Given the considerable quantity of hydrogen stored in a relatively short period of time, the supplied coolant flow is unable to maintain the temperature at a constant level due to the effect of ΔH_r . Consequently, the maximum ΔT recorded is greater than the temperature drop that characterises the release, which in turn follows a more gradual trend. The release time is of a similar order of magnitude to that of sorption, although a comprehensive analysis has provided a more detailed understanding of the underlying physics that govern these systems.

A.2.2 Shell and tubes

For the shell and tubes reactor the comparison was led assuming the following input data as constant regardless of the heat exchanger: $v, T_{fi}, d_{H_2}, t_{wall}, L_0, d_{o,hyd}$. As for the newly introduced parameters (Tab. A.5), these values have been chosen to reflect the standards (Kakac, Liu, and Pramuanjaroenkij, 2002). The higher efficiency provided by shell and tubes reactors comes from the lower mass flow, while the convective heat transfer coefficient is actually lower. Carrying out a new simulation for both the sorption and release phase, it is clear that moving from a concentric tubular reactor to a shell and tube layout results in different heat transfer performances as shown in Tab. A.6.

In the shell and tubes design, the cross-sectional area available for the external fluid flow is determined by selecting a few design parameters. Their value is derived from empirical evidence and can only be modified within a limited range. Similarly, the permitted fluid velocity and even the outer tube's inner diameter in the tubular concentric reactor are also constrained by the design parameters. If the values proposed in Mazzucco and Rokni (2017) are used, a much lower external fluid mass flow is provided influencing the outcome of the analysis. From both Fig. A.17 for sorption and Fig. A.18 for desorption, it is clear that the

FIGURE A.16: Bed temperature and hydrogen concentration over time for a 5 kWh tubular reactor.

	sorption		release	
	Shell and tubes	Tubular	Shell and tubes	Tubular
\dot{m}_f	9.15	32.45	9.10	32.30
α_f	3.240	6.645	3.538	7.630
U	0.882	1.073	0.905	1.010
$\varepsilon\%$	2.737	1.006	2.824	1.033

TABLE A.6: Different exchanger's parameters for both phases and reactors.

FIGURE A.17: Shell and tubes performances during sorption phase.

Charging	<i>PR</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>v</i>	\dot{m}_f	α	<i>U</i>	ϵ
HEX 1	-	-	1.75	32.45	6.645	1.073	1.006
HEX 2	1.25	0.2	1.75	9.146	3.24	0.882	2.737
HEX 3	1.4	0.4	1.75	32.93	2.924	0.853	0.743
HEX 4	1.5	0.3	2	31.36	2.986	0.859	0.785
Release	<i>PR</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>v</i>	\dot{m}_f	α	<i>U</i>	ϵ
HEX 1	-	-	1.75	32.3	7.63	1.096	1.033
HEX 2	1.25	0.2	1.75	9.1	3.538	0.905	2.824
HEX 3	1.4	0.4	1.75	32.77	3.188	0.877	0.768
HEX 4	1.5	0.3	2	31.21	3.245	0.882	0.811

TABLE A.7: Different exchanger's parameters with HEX1 being the concentric tubular reactor and HEX 2, 3, 4 shell and tubes reactors. The measure units are: m/s, kg/s, kW/(K m²) for *v*, \dot{m}_f and α and *U*.

shell and tube design (HEX 2) has no advantage over the tubular concentric design (HEX 1), since both the ΔT and the operation time get higher.

It is still possible to tweak the shell and tubes design parameters and/or the external fluid speed to raise the latter's mass flow in order to held a more meaningful comparison. Four layouts have thus been tested and defined with parameters in Tab. A.7.

While slight changes occur among HEX2, HEX3, HEX4 they are completely irrelevant when compared to HEX1. As it can be seen in Tab. A.7 higher mass flows result in lower NTU and effectiveness. Since the heat flow can be written as Eq. A.40:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \pm c_f \dot{m}_f (T_{f,i} - T) (1 - \exp(-NTU)) \quad (\text{A.40})$$

what really matters is the product $\dot{m}_f c_f (1 - \exp(-NTU))$ which is overall almost constant and around 23-25 % lower than HEX1's.

Sorption and desorption performances for all four exchangers are reported in Fig. A.19-A.20.

FIGURE A.18: Shell and tubes performances during desorption phase.

FIGURE A.19: Layout comparison for HEX1, HEX2, HEX3, HEX4 during sorption.

FIGURE A.20: Layout comparison for HEX1, HEX2, HEX3, HEX4 during desorption.

A.2.3 Pressure drop

For concentric tubular reactors the friction factor can be evaluated in a multitude of different ways⁶ (Prinsloo, Dirker, and Meyer, 2014). Eq. A.41 to Eq. A.45 have all been used and tested.

$$\text{Re}^* = \text{Re} \frac{(1 + a^2) \log(a) + (1 - a^2)}{(1 - a)^2 \log(a)} \quad (\text{A.41})$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f}_{\text{Gnielinski}}} = 1.8 \log_{10}(\text{Re}^*) - 1.5 \quad (\text{A.42})$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{f}_{\text{Jones\&Leung}}} = 2 \log_{10}(\text{Re} * \sqrt{f}) - 0.8 \quad (\text{A.43})$$

$$\frac{f_{\text{Kenada}}}{8} = \left[1.61 + \frac{1}{0.436} \log \left(\frac{\text{Re}}{\sqrt{8/f}} \right) - \frac{550}{\text{Re} \sqrt{f/8}} \right]^{-2} \quad (\text{A.44})$$

$$f_{\text{Blasius}} = 0.3164 \text{Re}^{-0.25} \quad (\text{A.45})$$

These equations yield similar results, with maximum relative differences of only about 6-7%, so an average value was chosen. The pressure drop in each tube with only one pass per tube in straight concentric smooth ducts can be roughly expressed as Eq. A.46.

$$\Delta p = \left(4f \frac{LN_p}{d_i} + 4N_p \right) \frac{\rho u^2}{2} \quad (\text{A.46})$$

with $N_p = 1$ and $d_i = D_{\text{hyd}}$.

⁶This time Re is defined with the hydraulic diameter and not the equivalent diameter, and it does not matter that the outer wall is assumed adiabatic.

charging	<i>HEX1</i>	<i>HEX2</i>	<i>HEX3</i>	<i>HEX4</i>
<i>f</i>	0.0225	0.1646	0.1566	0.1483
Δp	12.081	1.162	0.424	0.722
<i>P</i>	0.393	0.011	0.014	0.023
release	<i>HEX1</i>	<i>HEX2</i>	<i>HEX3</i>	<i>HEX4</i>
<i>f</i>	0.0210	0.1553	0.1477	0.1399
Δp	11.61	1.091	0.398	0.678
<i>P</i>	0.378	0.010	0.013	0.021

TABLE A.8: Pumping requirements for every HEX configuration.

For HEX2, HEX3 and HEX4 different equations have to be used. Kern (Kakac, Liu, and Pramuanjaroenkij, 2002) assessed the shell side pressure drop as Eq. A.47:

$$\Delta p = \frac{f \left(\dot{m}_f / A_{cross} \right)^2 (N_b + 1) D_s}{2\rho D_e (\mu / \mu_w)^{0.14}} \quad (\text{A.47})$$

with $N_b = L/B - 1$ number of baffles and the friction factor f (Eq. A.48):

$$f = \exp(0.576 - 0.19 \log(\text{Re}_{D_e})) \quad (\text{A.48})$$

Results are thus summarised in Tab. A.8. Pressure drop and friction factor, Δp in bar, pumping power P in kW. Despite having better kinetics performances of concentric tubular reactors, the required pumping power is way higher than shell and tubes'.

Appendix B

LOHCs properties

This section provides a more technical description of the test procedures used to model the kinetic saturation of LOHCs and their thermophysical properties. Note that the lack of experimental data prevent an in depth validation of the found values. The first section details the process of developing a reliable procedure to assess the final LOHC concentration induced by chemical equilibrium, and has been omitted by Chapter 3 to return a cleaner description, thus omitting the preliminary tests made before developing an effective relation. Finally, the thermophysical properties have been modelled with a general approach and used throughout the full text.

B.1 Saturation

To approach the problem of thermodynamic equilibrium presented in Chapter 3, multiple intermediate steps have been taken. Through the introduction of the reaction coordinate (ζ) and its definition, the issue can be tackled starting from a schematization gradually approaching the real physics of the phenomenon. The following cases were therefore progressively evaluated:

- Homogeneous system in the gaseous phase with pressure correction;
- Homogeneous system with pressure correction with activity of the liquid components approximately unitary.

Finally, an alternative approach to the problem is reported to take into account the physical state of the reagents. Given the reaction:

and defined the excess hydrogen e as Eq. B.1:

$$e = \frac{n_{ce\text{H}_2}^0 - n_{ce\text{H}_2, \text{stech}}^0}{n_{ce\text{H}_2, \text{stech}}^0} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

given the initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\text{H}_2}^0 &= 1 \\ n_{0\text{H-NEC}}^0 &= \frac{n_0}{6} \\ n_{12\text{H-NEC}}^0 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

if $n_0 < 1$ the system foresees an excess of hydrogen, otherwise if $n_0 > 1$ there is a hydrogen deficiency. Overall, the hydrogen available to the system is in excess since a pressure of 60 bar is maintained on the system, although the reaction occurs in the liquid phase where dissolved hydrogen is limited.

The number of moles is therefore defined as a function of the degree of progress of the reaction as Eqs. B.2, B.3, B.4 for hydrogen, 0H-NEC, and 12H-NEC respectively; as such the

total number of moles can be expressed as Eq. B.5.

$$n_{\text{H}_2} = 1 - \zeta \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$n_{0\text{H-NEC}} = \frac{n_0 - \zeta}{6} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$n_{12\text{H-NEC}} = \frac{\zeta}{6} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$n_{\text{tot}} = 1 + \frac{n_0}{6} - \zeta \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The degree of hydrogenation for $n_0 \leq 1$ ¹ can be rewritten in terms of ζ as Eq. B.6.

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{n_{12\text{H-NEC}}}{n_{0\text{H-NEC}} + n_{12\text{H-NEC}}} = \frac{\zeta}{n_0} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

If instead hydrogen is the limiting agent, then the maximum possible hydrogenation becomes linked to the number of moles of hydrogen available and Eq. B.7 holds true.

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{n_{12\text{H-NEC}}}{n_{\text{H}_2}^0} = \frac{\zeta}{1} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Consequently, a more general formula is derived as Eq. B.8.

$$\text{DoH} = \frac{\zeta}{\min[n_0; 1]} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Referring to the concentrations, the molar concentrations (χ) on the totality of moles, regardless of the fact that the LOHC is not in the gaseous state, turn Eqs. B.2, B.3, B.4 into Eq. B.9, B.10, B.11.

$$\chi_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{1 - \zeta}{1 + \frac{n_0}{6} - \zeta} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\chi_{0\text{H-NEC}} = \frac{\frac{n_0 - \zeta}{6}}{1 + \frac{n_0}{6} - \zeta} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$\chi_{12\text{H-NEC}} = \frac{\frac{\zeta}{6}}{1 + \frac{n_0}{6} - \zeta} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

With K_{eq} evaluated from ΔG_f^0 data, Eq. B.12 is derived, where p is the pressure of the system, which in this case sees the total pressure coinciding with the hydrogen pressure maintained on the reactor and equal to 60 bar (Wan et al., 2012).

$$K_{eq} = \frac{\chi_{12\text{H-NEC}}^{1/6}}{\chi_{\text{H}_2} \left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right) \chi_{0\text{H-NEC}}^{1/6}} = \frac{\zeta^{1/6} \left(1 + \frac{n_0}{6} - \zeta\right)}{(1 - \zeta) \left(\frac{p}{p_0}\right) (n_0 - \zeta)^{1/6}} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

For different values of e the trends described in Fig. B.1 are therefore obtained. Although overall there is an excess of hydrogen, it is clear that the curves that best approximate the behavior are those for lack of hydrogen, in agreement with the consideration that the reaction takes place in the liquid phase for reduced hydrogen concentrations.

Taking into account the fact that in reality the activity of the liquid phases is approximately unitary, the equilibrium is rewritten as a function of the hydrogen pressure alone, calculated as a partial pressure on all the moles that make up the system. In essence, Eq. B.12 is a rewriting of the constant as a function of the partial pressure of hydrogen alone, imagining an equivalent system in which each component is in the gaseous phase. In fact, the pressure of hydrogen in the gaseous phase is the same for all simulations, and would not return any information with respect to final conversions (and therefore values of the equilibrium constant) which vary with temperature. From a phenomenological point of view, since

¹So that the reaction is either stoichiometric or in excess of hydrogen.

FIGURE B.1: Saturation effect during hydrogenation reactions under the afore-mentioned hypothesis.

FIGURE B.2: Saturation effect during hydrogenation reactions under newly defined hypothesis.

the reaction occurs on the submerged catalyst, it is clear that there must be a dilution effect linked to the liquid phase and Eq. B.12 turns into Eq. B.13.

$$K_{eq} = \frac{1}{\chi_{H_2} \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right)} = \frac{1 + \frac{n_0}{6} - \zeta}{(1 - \zeta) \frac{p}{p_0}} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

Fig. B.2 can thus be plotted. There is an excellent representation of the data provided, however the model does not return physically sensible values across the entire temperature range, and instead of gradually going to zero as in Fig. B.1 there is a discontinuity.

An alternative to this approach could come from defining the concentration of hydrogen dissolved in solution using Henry's law as a first approximation. This approach, whose details are reported below, leads however to poor results when compared to the reaction coordinate-based approach. Fig. B.3 shows the trend of the concentration of dissolved hydrogen ($[\%_{\text{mol}}]$) in equilibrium with the solution.

If the concentration of dissolved hydrogen (y_{H_2}) could be expressed in terms of the pressure exerted in solution (p_{H_2}), the y_{H_2} value could be obtained from the equilibrium constant. Through the concentration it would then be possible to obtain the degree hydrogenation at saturation, assuming it falls between the two curves shown in Fig. B.3. However, this approach presents two vulnerabilities:

- The relationship between y_{H_2} and p_{H_2} is not known.
- Rewriting the constant, neglecting the effect of the activity for the liquid phases, as Eq. B.14:

$$K_{eq} = \left(\frac{p_{H_2}}{p_0} \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{B.14})$$

FIGURE B.3: Henry constant for 0H-NEC (blue line) and 12H-NEC (orange line) with respect to temperature.

since the constant decreases as the temperature increases (exothermic reaction), the partial pressure should increase (Fig. B.4) and with it, reasonably, the concentration of dissolved hydrogen. This, however, is in disagreement with the data reported in Fig. B.3 where, beyond the general reduction in solubility, the dehydrogenated form can dissolve less hydrogen. This means that for higher temperatures, for which the hydrogenated fraction of the liquid begins to reduce, the solubility of hydrogen decreases and the concentration should also decrease.

- Looking at Fig. B.3 a further issue derives from the values themselves assumed by the inverse of the constant. If it is true that this is a dimensionless quantity, with $p_0 = 1$ bar in Eq. B.14, it is clear that the values in the ordinate can be read as the values of p_{H_2} in bar!

The only theoretical approach to LOHC equilibrium found in literature comes from Shin et al. (2018), and the thermodynamic equilibrium state (X_e) is defined starting from the reaction constant K_{eq} as Eq. B.15.

$$X_e = \frac{K_{eq}(T)}{1 + K_{eq}(T)} \quad (\text{B.15})$$

No explanation is provided regarding the formula, nor are there any corrections with respect to the pressure to take into account the fact that in reality $X_e(p, T)$. The parameter X_e indicates the conversion of the reactants at equilibrium. In order to then readapt the calculation to the case study, a bibliographic reference was searched for (Fogler, 2016).

In particular, the conversion X in the reaction can be defined in a manner not dissimilar to the reaction coordinate. Given the reaction:

FIGURE B.4: Trend of the inverse of the equilibrium constant, and therefore of the hydrogen pressure, with respect to the temperature.

The X conversion can be defined as Eq. B.17, knowing that the moles of reactants follow Eq. B.16.

$$n_A = n_{A,0} - n_{A,0}X = n_{A,0}(1 - X) \quad (\text{B.16})$$

$$X = \frac{n_{A,reacted}}{n_{A,fed}} \quad (\text{B.17})$$

so the remaining $n_i(X)$ can be written in a similar way. By introducing r as the derivative of the number of moles of a certain reagent over time, in an equilibrium reaction the net rate (Eq. B.18) is:

$$r = r_{direct} - r_{reverse}. \quad (\text{B.18})$$

At equilibrium the forward and reverse reactions proceed at the same rate and therefore $r = 0$. By rewriting the different r_i for the two forward and reverse reactions as a function of a parameter k and the functional dependence $f(C)$ ², having imposed the equilibrium, and writing the concentrations in terms of conversion, the value found coincides precisely with X_e . In the final reaction:

$$0 = k_{forward} \left(f_{forward}(X) - \frac{f_{inverse}(X)}{K} \right)$$

First of all, what was reported by Shin et al. was reproduced: as it was defined, it was deduced that the reference Gibbs free energy variation was normalized per mole of LOHC, therefore the value of ΔG_f^0 was multiplied by the number of moles of hydrogen involved in the complete hydrogenation reaction and the sign was changed (dehydrogenation).

In Fig. B.5 published data are compared with the simulation results. No reference to pressure can be found, however typically the discharge occurs at 1 bar so any possible correction would be unitary. The dashed orange curve refers to the formula used in the article, the experimental data are those provided for the NEC at the pressure of 1 bar (Kiermaier et al., 2021).

Shin et al. provide three different isomers and slightly different configurations that correspond to the various curves he reports. There is a good correspondence with the data provided and those reproduced but not with the experimental data. A further functional form is also introduced and compared to the one proposed, as in reality these are not first order reactions.

However, it is clear that this approach generates critical issues:

1. First of all, there is not such a good correlation with the experimental data.
2. In this way K_{eq} is no longer dimensionless so a correction factor should appear with the constant to correct the ratio between the two r ; what this is, however, is unclear.
3. In reality the dependence $f(C)$ found for the hydrogenation rate is of the type $f(C) = C_{lim} - C$ with C subtending the DoH, i.e. $f(X(r = 0)) = X_{eq} - X_{eq}$ but this is an absurd.

In any case, imagining replacing $f(C)_{hyd} = \text{DoDH}$ with the DoH which by definition corresponds to X , so $\text{DoDH} = 1 - X$ and neglecting the other issued, Eq. B.19 is derived.

$$0 = \text{DoDH} - \frac{\text{DoH}^2}{K_{eq}} = K_{eq}(1 - X_e) - X_e^2 \quad (\text{B.19})$$

Eq. B.19 however does not feature any pressure dependence. Taking into account how the previous methods produced correction factors of the type $K_{eq} \cdot p^n$, the equation was revised as Eq. B.20:

$$(1 - X_e)K_{eq}p^n - X_e^2 = 0 \quad (\text{B.20})$$

with n which as it is written the reaction should satisfy $n = 6$, however all the integer values included in the range 0-6 have been evaluated (Fig. B.6).

²In order not to generate confusion in this paragraph X refers to the conversion, while for the concentrations the C notation is used.

(B) Simulated data trends.

FIGURE B.5: Comparison with simulated and published data found in the literature.

FIGURE B.6: Saturation as a function of T and the reaction order.

Trends obtainable with the method proposed do not lead to the dimensional problem illustrated above even if it is conceptually less correct; on the other hand, however, the results are not so different. In conclusion, from Fig. B.6 it is evident that the trends most similar to the experimental data are obtained for the coefficient $n = 4$; however the results are not good enough to justify the plethora of critical issues introduced.

The amount of data available to evaluate the goodness of the model is extremely limited, therefore making the process relatively critical. Both proposed models have pros and cons. The first model presented returns physically reliable values for each temperature value; the second reports a slightly better correspondence with the data and provides an estimate of K_{eq} more similar to that appropriate for heterogeneous systems, but at the expense of a discontinuity. A further approach could be based on the definition of the concentration of hydrogen dissolved in solution, for example through Henry's law. However, the connection between this step and the rewriting of the DoH_{lim} is unclear.

B.2 Thermophysical properties

To compensate for the limited availability of experimental data available on the thermophysical properties of different carriers, an analytical procedure was introduced to estimate the trends in density, viscosity, conductivity and specific heat. In addition to the formulas needed to define the properties of the different substances, equations are needed to describe their behavior in a mixture: unless $DoH(t) = 0.0$ or $DoH(t) = num1.0$, conditions that never occur during operation, LOHC systems work with mixtures. In accordance with the simplified treatment intrinsically introduced by describing the chemical kinetics as a function of the DoH, and not of the concentration of the different species, the carrier is then seen as a mixture of $LOHC^+$ and $LOHC^-$.

The equations reported were taken from the literature (Green and Perry, 2008) and their application requires estimating the value of the descriptive parameters starting from the molecular structure of the species. By identifying the different groups into which this can be broken down, tables available in the literature allow the estimation of the parameters x_1, \dots, x_n to be used in relationships that allow the trend of the different property in a form like:

$$X_j(T) = X_j(x_{j,1}, \dots, x_{j,n}, T)$$

and where the different factors $x_{j,1}, \dots, x_{j,n}$ are calculated as a function of the structure as follows:

$$x_{j,i=1, \dots, n} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_g} x_{j,i,k} \cdot n_{j,k}$$

therefore having identified and counted the n_g functional groups, so each k group ($-CH_3$, $=CH - r, \dots$) is present n_k times in the molecule of the species j .

At this point, knowing the composition of the mixture, it is necessary to trace from the properties of the different components in the pure state (X_j) to the actual characteristic value of the mixture X_m with formulas of the type:

$$X_m(T) = X_m(X_1(T), X_2(T), \chi_i)$$

where χ_1 represents the concentration of one of the two species³ typically expressed as mass concentration; in this case it was chosen to use χ_1 referring to the hydrogenated species as reference.

³If the different steps in which the reaction proceeds were considered as distinct reactions, there would be m species and therefore it would be necessary to consider the parameters $\chi_1, \dots, \chi_{m-1}$. In the case of NEC the species that could be added would likely be 4H-NEC and 8H-NEC.

Taking into account the definition of DoH and introducing the ratio between the molecular weights (MW_{factor}) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DoH} &= \frac{n_1}{n_1 + n_2} \\ MW_{factor} &= \frac{MW_2}{MW_1} \end{aligned}$$

where the species 1 is the totally hydrogenated one, and the 2 is the totally de-hydrogenated one, the estimate of the mass concentration occurs via Eq. B.21 starting from the degree of hydrogenation.

$$\chi_1 = 1 - \frac{MW_{factor}}{1 + \frac{\text{DoH}}{1 - \text{DoH}}} \quad (\text{B.21})$$

The density of the mixture is calculated according to a different logic, dividing the total mass of the mixture by the volume occupied by the individual species (Eq. B.22).

$$\rho_m(T) = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{\frac{m_1}{\rho_1(T)} + \frac{m_2}{\rho_2(T)}} \quad (\text{B.22})$$

The density values of the two components of the mixture are calculated using the Rackett method, as expressed in Eq. B.23-B.24:

$$q = 1 + (1 - T_r)^{2/7} \quad (\text{B.23})$$

$$\rho = \frac{R_u T_c}{p_c} \cdot Z_c^{-q} MW \quad (\text{B.24})$$

and where the reduced temperature T_r is the ratio between the LOHC temperature and the critical temperature, obtained on the basis of the molecular structure as reported in Eq. B.25-B.30 to define the boiling temperature at normal pressure, the temperature, the pressure and the critical volume, and the compressibility factor according to the Joback method.

$$T_r = \frac{T}{T_c} \quad (\text{B.25})$$

$$T_b = 198.2 + \sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{T_b,k} \cdot n_k \quad (\text{B.26})$$

$$T_c = \frac{T_b}{0.584 + 0.965 \sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{T_c,k} \cdot n_k - (\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{T_c,k} \cdot n_k)^2} \quad (\text{B.27})$$

$$p_c = (0.113 + 0.0032 n_{atoms} - \sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{p_c,k} \cdot n_k)^{-2} \quad (\text{B.28})$$

$$V_c = 17.5 + \sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{V_c,k} \cdot n_k \quad (\text{B.29})$$

$$Z_c = \frac{p_c V_c MW}{RT_c} \quad (\text{B.30})$$

Thermal conductivity is obtained through the formula identified by Gharagheizi (Eq. B.37) as a function of the molecular weight, the previously defined boiling temperature, and the acentricity factor ω , a measure of non-sphericity of the molecules and associated with the shape of the vapor curve and can be obtained with the Edmister formula (Eq. B.31⁴) with

⁴The pressure must be inserted in atm, unit in which it is moreover also defined in Eq. B.28, although where not specified it must be reported in the SI units of measurement.

respect to $\theta = T_b/T_c$.

$$\omega = \frac{3}{7} \frac{\theta}{\theta - 1} \log(0.986923p_c) - 1 \quad (\text{B.31})$$

$$A_\lambda = 16.0407MW + 2T_b - 27.9074 \quad (\text{B.32})$$

$$B_\lambda = 3.8588MW^8(1.0045A_\lambda + 6.5152MW - 8.9756) \quad (\text{B.33})$$

$$C_\lambda = 1.908 \left(T_b + 1.009 \left(\frac{A_\lambda}{MW} \right)^2 \right) \quad (\text{B.34})$$

$$D_\lambda = 3.9287 \left(\frac{MW}{A_\lambda} \right)^4 \quad (\text{B.35})$$

$$E_\lambda = \left(\frac{B_\lambda}{A_\lambda} \right)^8 \quad (\text{B.36})$$

$$\lambda(T) = (10\omega + 2p_c + 4 + C_\lambda + D_\lambda + E_\lambda) \cdot T - 2 \quad (\text{B.37})$$

From the two values of λ found the characteristic value of the mixture as indicated by Vredeveld (Eq. B.38) using the mass fractions are found.

$$\lambda_m = \left(\sum_{j=1}^2 \chi_j \lambda_j^{-2} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (\text{B.38})$$

Under the name of Joback method, the properties of dynamic viscosity (Eq. B.39-B.41) and specific heat (Eq. B.42) can be evaluated -B.46)⁵.

$$A_\mu = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{\mu,k} n_k \right) - 597.82 \quad (\text{B.39})$$

$$B_\mu = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} b_{\mu,k} n_k \right) - 11.202 \quad (\text{B.40})$$

$$\mu(T) = MW \exp \left(\frac{A_\mu}{T} + B_\mu \right) \quad (\text{B.41})$$

$$A_c = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} a_{c,k} n_k \right) - 37.93 \quad (\text{B.42})$$

$$B_c = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} b_{c,k} n_k \right) + 0.21 \quad (\text{B.43})$$

$$C_c = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} c_{c,k} n_k \right) - 3.91 \times 10^{-4} \quad (\text{B.44})$$

$$D_c = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_g} d_{c,k} n_k \right) + 2.06 \times 10^{-7} \quad (\text{B.45})$$

$$c = A_c + B_c T + C_c T^2 + D_c T^3 \quad (\text{B.46})$$

For mixtures of organic liquids the specific heat c_m can be calculated as the weighted average with respect to the mass concentration (Eq. B.47) while for the viscosity the Gambill method can be used (Eq. B.48), defined for the kinematic viscosity but taking into account that $\mu =$

⁵The relations are presented here so as to return μ in Pa s and c in J/kg/K.

$\nu\rho$.

$$c_m = \sum_{j=1}^2 \chi_j c_j \quad (\text{B.47})$$

$$\nu_m^{1/3} = \sum_{j=1}^2 \chi_j \nu_j^{1/3} \quad (\text{B.48})$$

In the first simulations of the routines presented, the formulas illustrated in this section were implemented as shown above. However, their use has proven to be dramatically costly, significantly increasing the computation time⁶. However, by evaluating the trend of the thermo-physical properties defined in a temperature range of with a moderate variation in temperature, a very limited variability is observed. In reality, according to simulations results explained in Chapter 5, the temperature of the mixture could even be more or less constant during operation. Consequently, simplified relations have been introduced to estimate the trend of the required properties as a function of the composition alone, thus having a more marked influence than the temperature on the actual calculated value⁷. The different equations obtained allow the values otherwise obtained to be faithfully replicated while ensuring short calculation times. In particular, the formulas used are Eqs. B.49-B.50-B.51-B.52 valid only for the NEC, although similar results can be immediately replicated for any other carrier.

$$\mu_m(\chi_i) = a_\mu \exp(b_\mu \cdot \chi_i) \quad (\text{B.49})$$

$$\rho_m(\chi_i) = a_\rho \cdot \chi_i^2 + b_\rho \cdot \chi_i + c_\rho \quad (\text{B.50})$$

$$\lambda_m(\chi_i) = a_\lambda \cdot \chi_i + b_\lambda \quad (\text{B.51})$$

$$c_m(\chi_i) = a_c \cdot \chi_i + b_c \quad (\text{B.52})$$

B.2.1 Nusselt number

In the flow rate control, the variation of v_f carried out determines a secondary effect by acting on the convective exchange coefficient between the external fluid and the pipe wall. In fact, taking the relation that can be written on the single element to determine the exchanged heat, the efficiency term ε is a function of the global exchange coefficient (U), the exchange (A_{hex}), and the minimum thermal capacity through the number of transport units (NTU), Eq. B.53-B.54.

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp(-\text{NTU}) \quad (\text{B.53})$$

$$\text{NTU} = \frac{UA_{hex}}{\dot{m}_f c_f} \quad (\text{B.54})$$

Note that in Eq. B.54 the minimum heat capacity is that of the external fluid, taking into account the presence of the chemical reaction taking place in the LOHC. At this point the global heat transfer coefficient can be defined with Eq. B.55, where the convective coefficient α_f appears.

$$U = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_f} + \frac{r_{out} \log(r_{out}/r_{in})}{\lambda} + \frac{r_{out}}{r_{in}} \frac{1}{\alpha_L} \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{B.55})$$

The value of α_f can be estimated depending on the Reynolds number Re_f . In particular, in a configuration with concentric tubes in laminar and turbulent regime, the aforementioned Nusselt determination applies for the latter, while for low Re_f reference was made to data tabulated as a function of the ratio r_{in}/r_{out} as reported in Tab. B.1.

⁶This is particularly true for estimating different species densities.

⁷On the other hand, the variations expected in the exercise with $\text{DoH} \in [0.20; 0.95]$ predict a deviation from the average value of up to 65 %.

r_{in}/r_{out}	Nu_i	Nu_o
0.00	-	3.66
0.05	17.46	4.06
0.10	11.56	4.11
0.25	7.37	4.23
0.50	5.74	4.43
1.00	4.86	4.86

TABLE B.1: Nusselt number for laminar flows in an annulus with one surface isothermal and the other adiabatic.

In this case the Nusselt number that describes the case in question is Nu_o ; to improve the accuracy of the Nusselt Petukhov and Roizen introduced correction factors F as a function of the ratio between diameters, defined as Eq. B.56, (Petukhov and Roizen, 1964).

$$F = 0.86 \left(\frac{r_{in}}{r_{out}} \right)^{-0.16} \quad (\text{B.56})$$

In order to avoid the system containing discontinuities when a control of the input velocity of the external fluid is implemented, so that the system remains normally integrable via Simulink, a fitting relation of the type $Nu_o(r_{in}/r_{out})$ and a single polynomial function was sought to describe the Nusselt number as a function of the Reynolds number.

Appendix C

LOHCs modeling

This section provides a brief overview of the alternative kinetic models that could have been used to describe the LOHC behavior, scraped from Chapter 3, and a more technical description of the developed 0D models used for Chapter 4 and Chapter 5. Comparison with the equivalent one-dimensional simulations are run to quantify the error induced by the lumped parameter approach. Evaluation of the Biot number suggests that a one-dimensional model should be needed, however, the presence of an inner heat source and the induced feedback between temperature and reaction rate, leads to better 0D performance than expected.

C.1 Kinetics

C.1.1 Different Kinetic Models

While most research groups make use of similar equations, there are alternative modeling solutions than the one described in Chapter 3, which resembles the MH kinetic modelling described in the Appendix A (Xie et al., 2022).

The Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method: with the knowledge of a given heating rate (β in K/min), the following relation holds true:

$$\ln(\beta) = \ln\left(\frac{AE_a}{R_u G(\alpha)}\right) - 2.315 - 0.4567 \frac{E_a}{R_u T} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

with Eq. C.1 from Flynn and Wall (1966), where α is the conversion degree, and the function G is the integral kinetic function. The model assumes constant apparent activation energy as long as the heating rate is constant and the process is isothermal. However this model returns poor results when used to describe multi-step reactions with a significant difference in activation energy between steps (NEO, 2024).

Vyazovkin method: this is a model-free kinetic integration method, which returns the equivalent conversion for a temperature function under the same conversion rate with $t_{\alpha,t}$ as the time required to reach a given conversion rate, Eq. C.2.

$$\ln(t_{\alpha,t}) = \ln\left(\frac{A}{G(\alpha)}\right) - \frac{E_a}{R_u T} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

The biggest advantage of the Vyazovkin's isoconversional method is the assumption of the stability of the kinetic function, so that G is actually a constant. This simplification has led to a rise in popularity of this model, which has established itself among the standard approaches to solid-state dissociation kinetics (Mianowski, Sciazko, and Radko, 2021). However, the model features a major drawback which is the vulnerability to numeric instabilities (Sbirrazzuoli, 2020).

Kissinger method: this method is actually similar to the one mostly used in the literature (Gambini et al., 2022; Dennis et al., 2021), as it is based on the Arrhenius equation, but

FIGURE C.1: Dehydrogenation pathways of 12H-NEC: 12H-NEC to 8H-NEC, 8H-NEC to 4H-NEC, and 4H-NEC to 0H-NEC.

without pressure dependence (Xie et al., 2022), Eq. C.5:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$\left[\frac{E_a \beta}{R_u T^2} + A f'(\alpha_m) \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right)\right] \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)_m = 0 \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_m^2}\right) = \ln(-\text{frac}AR_uE_a) - \frac{E_a}{R_u T_m} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

where going from the first to the third and final equation implies the hypothesis of: $\frac{d^2\alpha}{dt^2} = 0$, as the equation is evaluated at the peak temperature corresponding to maximum transition (subscript m); afterwards, Kissinger assumes that the differential form of reaction mechanism function $f(\alpha)$ when derived is independent of β and at maximum transition is approximately equal to unitary Xie et al., 2022.

Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) method: a modified version of the previously shown method relies on the Arrhenius equation using a differential method and is widely used in the literature whenever no pressure dependence is considered (Peters et al., 2019). Modeling the conversion rate as Eq. C.6, relation to the heating rate is given as Eq. C.7.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{R_u T}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (\text{C.6})$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_m^2}\right) = \ln(-\text{frac}AE_aG(\alpha)) - \frac{E_a}{R_u T_m} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

Starink method: lastly, the KAS model can be slightly adjusted into Eq. C.8:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_m^{1.8}}\right) = C - 1.0037 \frac{E_a}{R_u T_m} \quad (\text{C.8})$$

where the introduced constants have been found by Starink by analysing hydrogen desorption under linear heating (Starink, 2018).

C.1.2 Intermediate Reactions

While great accuracy can be achieved under the assumption of an equivalent reaction between the fully hydrogenated and dehydrogenated compounds, more detailed studies have been published. A multi-step approach is tested in Chapter 10. Modeling the reaction into three stages (Yang et al., 2014), NEC compounds are either 0H, 4H, 8H or 12H, Fig. C.1.

Through in-situ analysis on the composition of the liquid samples, 8H and 4H-NEC were found to be the only intermediates, regardless of the catalyst selected. Additionally, it has been reported that the last stage is likely to be the limiting step as 4H-NEC appeared kinetically stable over some catalysts, and became the dominant component in the final product distribution. Overall, the reaction rate decreases significantly with the reaction stage for noble catalysts (Yang et al., 2014). Similar results had already been found by the same researchers (Dong et al., 2016) where dehydrogenation over a 5%_m Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst returned activation energies of 56.3, 59.2, 73.1 kJ/mol going from the first to the third stage.

FIGURE C.2: General layout of a shell and tubes reactor for LOHCs systems.

In a different fashion, Kiermaier et al. have tracked the concentration of 6H-NEC as well as the previously mentioned compounds under reduced pressure. According to Yang et al. the latter species concentration resulted to be extremely low under every thermodynamic condition and catalyst choice.

Interestingly enough, it appears that the bottleneck for dehydrogenation at increased pressure levels is mainly due to the last stage, as looking at the figures reported in Kiermaier et al. (2021), shows that only the 4H-NEC (and 0H-NEC) features major changes as the pressure varies.

C.2 Reactors

C.2.1 Shell and Tubes design: 0D-model

The proposed reactor design consists of a shell and tube exchanger made out of stainless steel (Peters et al., 2015) in which the LOHC flows through circular ducts filled with a heterogeneous catalyst, but half of the section is left empty to allow for easy hydrogen transfer (Peters et al., 2019). The ducts are submerged in the external fluid, which flows through the shell, to account for the reaction heat either released or sunk. The broad architecture of the reactor can be found in Fig. C.2.

Simulations were held with two different heat exchangers: the system sizing and the main parameters are summed up in Tab. C.1; the two set-ups are described in Tab. C.2.

	E	kWh	5
	η	%	45
	M_{H_2}	g	282
	w_{max}	%	5.8
	DoH_{max}	%	95
	DoH_{min}	%	20
	M_{LOHC}	kg	6.48
	ΔH_r	kJ/kmol	50600
<i>hydrogenation</i>	reaction	order	1
	k_0	1/min	30.33
	E_a	kJ/kmol	28074
	b	1/bar	0.038
	T_i	K	433
	$T_{f,i}$	K	433
	p	bar	60
<i>dehydrogenation</i>	reaction	order	2
	k_0	1/min	8.26×10^{11}
	E_a	kJ/kmol	121000
	b	1/bar	0
	T_i	K	473.15
	$T_{f,i}$	K	473.15
	p	bar	1

TABLE C.1: Input parameters to lead the simulation.

<i>geometry</i>	d_t mm	$pitch/d_t$	$buffle/D_s$	N_t	L m	D_s mm	M_{he} kg
HEX 1	8.0	1.4	0.45	8	16.90	34.6	65.2
HEX 2	5.0	1.4	0.20	21	17.02	35.0	108.0
<i>hydrogenation</i>	v_f m/s	G_f kg/s	$C_{T,f} \cdot eff$ kW/K	h_f kW/(m ² K)	h_l kW/(m ² K)	U kW/(m ² K)	P W
HEX 1	1.75	0.2313	0.4828	1.613	2.920	0.952	102.3
HEX 2	0.50	0.030	0.063	0.906	2.978	0.622	5.7
<i>dehydrogenation</i>	v_f m/s	G_f kg/s	$C_{T,f} \cdot eff$ kW/K	h_f kW/(m ² K)	h_l kW/(m ² K)	U kW/(m ² K)	P W
HEX 1	1.75	0.2232	0.493	1.614	1.821	0.795	102.1
HEX 2	0.50	0.029	0.064	0.907	1.795	0.550	5.3

TABLE C.2: Main heat exchangers input and output data.

(A) DoH and hydrogen mass flow trends (hyd.).

This set of input parameters leads to different amounts of heat transferable under the same temperature difference, with HEX1 having better performances than HEX2. On the other hand, the higher external fluid mass flow leads to a higher pumping power P needed. Lastly, due to the higher amount of tubes N_t , HEX2 results in a heavier design.

Pressure losses and heat transfer coefficients are evaluated through the Ergun and Whitaker equations for flows through porous beds for the LOHC, and the Bell Delaware and Gnielinski methods for the shell side fluid (*Dowtherm Q*) (Kakac, Liu, and Pramuanjaroenkij, 2002). The two set-ups were chosen to provide alternative designs characterized by a different external fluid mass flow \dot{m}_f and overall heat transfer coefficient U and simulations were run using an explicit third-order Runge-Kutta solver, using an adaptive step size because of the varying magnitude of the gradients expected. Equations presented in Chapter. 4 still hold true as a 0D approach has been chosen.

Despite being quantitatively different and requiring dissimilar operating times, both the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation phase follow a similar behaviour.

Figs. C.3a-C.3c showcase how DoH changes over time: at the beginning of the processes, high gradients take place and significant quantities of hydrogen are reacting. While initial rates of change in the profiles of the reaction are characterized by steep gradients, the rate of change subsequently slows down until saturation is reached at the conclusion of the reaction. The rate of increase in the degree of hydrogenation is faster than that of the degree of dehydrogenation, as would be expected from the experimental data. Furthermore, the saturation phase is considerably more limited due to the different kinetic law. The reacting hydrogen mass flow is directly proportional to the first derivative of the DoH. Consequently, an initial peak is to be expected, but this immediately and steadily drops as the reaction proceeds. This trend is consistent across both phases, although the faster kinetics results in a higher mass of hydrogen (m_{H_2}) during the hydrogenation stage.

Figs. C.3b-C.3d portray the LOHC temperature and the amount of heat transferred between the LOHC and the external fluid. The latter was normalized with respect to the total amount of energy based on hydrogen's higher heating value: this ratio was defined to contextualize the amount of energy exchanged. The process begins with the LOHC and the external fluid in equilibrium at $T_i = T_{f,i}$, and as the reaction takes place due to the reaction heat involved, a temperature peak (hydrogenation) or a temperature drop (dehydrogenation) is registered. This allows for finite heat transfer between the two fluids to restore thermal balance. As lower amounts of hydrogen react and the LOHC temperature approaches T_i , Q/E trends go through saturation. The total amount of heat transferred is almost the same between the two phases if the heat transfer is effective enough, though the exchange takes place over different time periods. This final value is related to the total reaction heat

(B) Normalized heat transferred and LOHC temperature trends (hyd.).

(C) DoH and hydrogen mass flow trends (deh.).

(D) Normalized heat transferred and LOHC temperature trends (deh.).

FIGURE C.3: Main parameters trends over time for both phases. Reaction progress (Fig. C.3a - C.3c) and heat normalization with respect to the amount of available hydrogen (Fig. C.3b - C.3d).

released or sunk, with an offset due to a finite temperature variation in the LOHC itself and the hydrogen enthalpy flows.

While no explicit data on the reacting hydrogen mass flow trend is typically provided for laboratory tests, the available data on DoH trends suggest that the mass flow profiles may be steeper (Kiermaier et al., 2021). The afore-mentioned discrepancies are less discernible during the hydrogenation phase, due to the influence of the Arrhenius term correction, which limits the impact of temperature on the kinetic rate. At elevated temperatures, the thermodynamic equilibrium shifts towards the reactants (exothermic reaction), which creates a discrepancy with the constant temperature system. Nevertheless, the temperature differential observed for the proposed configurations remains constrained, settling to values too low to induce a notable discrepancy prior to the system attaining elevated levels of hydrogen mass flow. For this reason, there is minimal discernible difference in Fig. C.3a, despite the second set-up resulting in a markedly elevated temperature peak and consistently higher overall temperatures due to the exchanger's reduced capacity to remove heat. Fig. C.3b illustrates that the discrepancy between the two heat profiles diminishes only slightly as the first set-up reaches equilibrium. Given that both operating times and the hydrogen mass flow are largely similar, it is evident that heat transfer cannot be employed as a control strategy unless significantly greater temperature peaks are anticipated. However, it is imperative to consider the thermal stability of the carrier, the catalyst, and all other miscellaneous components. Furthermore, only minimal divergence from the baseline behaviour could be achieved. Trends in Fig. C.3 are all related. If the system was held at constant temperature, there would have been a greater amount of heat to manage (about the overall reaction heat) and a shorter reaction time would be required to release hydrogen.

Fig. C.3c highlights how the second set-up still has not reached the discharged state after 130 min: consequently the reacting hydrogen mass flow is lower until, due to the carrier nearing the discharged state, the reaction hosted by the first set-up slows down at a faster rate than the one characterizing the second set-up. Overall, more constant trends can be achieved with slower release processes. This is caused by the greater temperature drop (Fig. C.3d) and its effect on the kinetic rate. In contrast to the observations made during the hydrogenation process, the discrepancy is limited in the second set-up despite a lower amount of heat transferred due to the less evident difference between the two temperature trends. This is a consequence of the reaction's intrinsic slower kinetic. Given that a slower

kinetics is to be anticipated, the reduced efficiency and thermal capacity of the second set-up exert a lower influence on the process. With regard to heat recovery, the hydrogenation steps sees the LOHC system release heat, and both the set-ups offer either a greater quantity of heat to be recovered (1) or a higher quality (temperature) heat (2). Conversely, dehydrogenation requires a heat source to feed the system. This indicates that a smaller quantity of heat is preferable, with the quality remaining consistent across the two configurations as it depends on the design reaction temperature (i.e. for a given system size, it is indicative of the power output). However, the Q/E profiles do not diverge as much as anticipated during the hydrogenation process, and temperature fluctuations are generally less pronounced.

It can be reasonably deduced that due to a more significant impact on the reactor's functionality, the dehydrogenation phase may be of greater importance in the design of shared reactors. In this instance, the heat transfer can only effectively accommodate minor to moderate fluctuations in the released hydrogen. The induced temperature variations do not present a challenge to the system resistance, as the temperature will typically decline under normal operational conditions. It is therefore necessary to take into account the consequent increase in reaction time in determining the size requirements. Furthermore, heat transfer can be employed as a control parameter following preliminary sizing for load modulation. The most immediate procedure entails modifying the speed of the external fluid. Should the mass flow rate and the friction coefficient be increased, enhanced heat transfer is to be expected. However, the pumping requirements must also be taken into account. Analysis of the different control strategies is provided in Chapter 6. In conclusion, the optimal reactor design for the two phases depends on many factors, including heat management, pumping requirements, sizing, and costs. Nevertheless, if the same reactor is anticipated to accommodate both phases, it is essential to take thermo-chemical performance into account when evaluating the optimal design.

C.2.2 Batch Reactors: 0D-1D Comparison

The viability of the lumped parameter approach for metal hydride systems has long been proven (Gambini, 1994), see Appendix A. However, the different nature of the LOHC reactions lead to the necessity to test if the 0D approach can effectively return good performances, when compared to one-dimensional models. The following procedure was followed to quantify the difference between the two modelling assumptions:

1. Both the 0D and the 1D simulations were run.
2. The total hydrogen mass released was used to define the equivalent 0-dimensional $D\bar{0}H(t)$.
3. From $D\bar{0}H(t)$ profiles, the equivalent instantaneous release is evaluated;
4. With information on both the $D\bar{0}H(t)$ and its gradient, a 0D temperature profile is defined.

If the 0D model was to adhere to this particular trend, the two runs would yield identical results meaning that by choosing the 0D model no global error would be introduced. The release profiles displayed in Chapter 5 exhibit notable discrepancies when the averaged temperature is employed to assess the system's kinetics. This is particularly evident when the temperature decreases, as the reaction is hindered by the lower temperatures. However, while the definition of T_{ave} is supported by the conduction in a cylinder temperature profile, the system also features an inner heat source. Consequently, the actual temperature distribution differs from the predicted distribution, and the average temperature is not the optimal parameter to describe the system.

The 1D model is then compared to 0D results where kinetics is either ruled by the outer fraction of the LOHC ($T = T(r = R)$) or the innermost ($T = T(r = 0)$), evaluated through different thermal resistance definitions. While the latter test returns meager results, the former provides a much more significant matching. More specifically:

- Less hydrogen is released according to the 0D forecast. At first temperature plummets, but it soon is affected by the external fluid and a temperature raise ensues.

FIGURE C.4: One-dimensional temperature time-trend data colormap.

- Conversely, the 0D equivalent temperature profile features a slow and steady lowering. Its trend implies that while the outer regions of the fluid soon recover from the initial temperature drop, the innermost have a lower temperature, impacting the overall kinetic but in a less prominent way due to the different amount of stored hydrogen releasable. Additionally, while the averaged 0D temperature had these very regions release more hydrogen than they would thus increasing the gap between the two extremities of the reactor, this temperature profile intrinsically accounts for these different behaviours, thus the occurring $T(r = 0)$ is higher in the 1D model than in the 0D.
- While at first hydrogen release is more limited in the 0D model, it then immediately speeds up accordingly to its temperature profile.

The equivalent zero dimensional temperature required to match the 1D performances can be compared to the actual temperature distribution inside the batch reactor.

Radial distribution time-trend for temperature inside the 1D reactor presented in Chapter 5 is shown in Fig. C.4. It shows that very moderate temperature gradients occur inside the reactor due to the high thermal capacity and efficiency of the heat exchanger. Due to less favourable kinetics, the limited heat drain prevents temperature to drop as low as forecast by the 0D model. It would appear that the most effective method of characterising the system is through its external temperature. The actual temperature drop that is experienced moving from $r = R$ to $r = 0$ is somewhat compensated by slower kinetics and thus a reduced reaction heat being drained. Performances of the 0D approximation with respect to the one-dimensional approach are reported in Fig. C.5.

In spite of the different set temperature level, the afore-mentioned approximation seems to lead to overall solid performances in terms of consistency. This test was made as the choice of the T_{ave} definition is the consequence of heat transfer with the external fluid, and reaction heat (kinetics) balancing each other out. As such, a moderate influence of temperature over the fitting performances can be seen. This effect was still considered small enough in the operational temperature range for the approximation to be adequate.

While for the final DoH(t) a correction can be introduced (Eq. C.9):

$$\text{DoH}_{effective}(t) = a(T_0)\text{DoH}(t)^{b(T_0)} \quad (\text{C.9})$$

FIGURE C.5: One-dimensional release rate compared to the lumped parameter hydrogen release under different temperature conditions.

with a and b being generic polynomial functions of T ; this correction should be modified at high temperature and a different function should be used instead to grant the effective DoH. Nonetheless, this procedure is intrinsically obsolete and is incompatible with future implementations in complex systems as it would require different iterations to achieve convergence. The effect of this correction for different temperature levels is shown in Fig. C.6

As it can be seen moving from lower to higher temperature levels, the 0D temperature drop increases, while the equivalent 1D model follows a more monotonous trend. Errors thus increase significantly in the early to middle stages of the process as the initial temperature is raised from 450 K to 480 K. While all models showcase a definite improvement when the proposed correction is introduced, it is more effective in low temperature scenarios, with $\text{DoH}_{0,\text{equivalent}}$ getting lower than the actual 0.95 starting value in the high temperature runs. Regardless, due to the external temperature being the most reliable predictor for the system's behaviour, an interesting consideration can be made. As seen above, temperature in the outermost region of the LOHC is independent from the inner heat transfer mechanism.

Consequently, higher heat transfer coefficients in the liquid bulk should not influence the performance of the system¹; if that were the case, convection with a super-imposed velocity profile could be treated in the same way as conduction. To prove the validity of this point, different runs were made with higher conductivity values, and then compared in Fig. C.7. Fig. C.7 illustrates that initially, the impact of λ is essentially inconsequential. As the reaction rate declines, some differences emerge, although they remain relatively limited. It is noteworthy that the ten- and one-hundredfold enhancements in conductivity values do not indicate a discernible trend. This suggests that the disparate temperature distribution profiles exert a non-linear influence on the overall hydrogen release, attributable to the mutual interplay between mass and energy transfer. It is also important to note that higher conductivity values require smaller time steps, as indicated by the Fourier number. The $0D - T(r = R)$

¹This is not necessarily in contrast with the $k(\text{rpm})$ relation documented in the literature (Wan et al., 2012) due to the model disregard for mixing phenomena.

(A) One-dimensional temperature time-trend data compared to the corrected 0D date for 450 K initial temperature.

(B) One-dimensional temperature time-trend data compared to the corrected 0D date for 460 K initial temperature.

(c) One-dimensional temperature time-trend data compared to the corrected 0D date for 470 K initial temperature.

(D) One-dimensional temperature time-trend data compared to the corrected 0D date for 480 K initial temperature.

FIGURE C.6: Correction effect for different temperature set-points.

FIGURE C.7: Effect of different LOHC conductivity values over the release.

ruled profiles demonstrate a promising accordance with the 1D data, which was not immediately apparent from the resulting Biot number, which is approximately equal to 4390 when the effective λ_{LOHC} is considered. However, the introduction of an internal heat source introduces a mitigating effect on both mass and energy transfer.

A full analysis of the LOHC inner heat transfer mechanism seems to be unnecessary due to the low expected velocities in the bulk liquid and the limited influence of heat transfer inside the reactor over the effective trends. While $DoH(t)$ and $T(t)$ trends are quite similar, hydrogen mass flows are still different, thus implementation in complex systems should account for this discrepancy. However, the 0D model could still prove to be a useful tool since the 1D modelling procedure depends on the actual reactor scheme. On the other hand, no significant correction factor was found to breach the already mentioned gap between the two modelling procedure. As such, if a higher degree of accuracy is required, it is advised to implement the 1D model itself.

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